

Designing with Stories: Women's Retirement Transitions and the Co-creation of Supportive Interventions

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of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

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Dedication

In loving memory of my mum, Joyce Calder, who passed away on Christmas Day 2024.

This thesis is for you; with the hope it would make you proud.

Declaration

This is to certify that I am responsible for the work submitted in this thesis, that the original work is my own except as specified in acknowledgements or in footnotes, and that neither the thesis nor the original work contained therein has been submitted to this or any other institution for an academic award.

A rectangular area containing a handwritten signature in dark ink. The signature is written in a cursive style and reads "Laura Calder".

LAURA CALDER

1st November 2025

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Calder, L. *Extending Healthy Life Years: Exploring the Role of Physical Activity in Women's Transition to Retirement*. Qualitative Research in Sports and Exercise, 2024.

Calder, L. *Social Prescribing*. Scottish Social Prescribing Network, 2024.

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Abstract

Policy and public health often frame retirement as a single, uniform milestone, overlooking the diverse social, emotional, and material realities women encounter. This thesis investigates how women navigate the transition to retirement and examines how narrative, human-centred design, and co-production methods can generate more responsive forms of support. The study engaged women approaching and beyond state pension age, alongside community stakeholders, through narrative interviews, co-design workshops, and a story completion study. Dialogical narrative analysis provided a consistent interpretive lens across all phases.

Phase One interviews revealed retirement as both disruption and reorientation, highlighting care responsibilities, financial uncertainty, shifting identities, and evolving uses of time. Analysis produced narrative typologies that captured different ways women positioned retirement in their lives. In Phase Two, these typologies were refined and used to shape design framings, composite characters, and co-design workshops. The workshops generated three prototype interventions: a Retirement Café, a Buddy Scheme, and new approaches to physical activity. Phase Three tested the functionality of these prototypes through story completion, where participants imagined themselves within designed scenarios. This revealed the value of socially safe, emotionally affirming, and contextually relevant support, while also showing where ideas felt less plausible or difficult to imagine in real-life contexts.

Empirically, the thesis demonstrates how gendered life-course patterns and cumulative inequalities shape retirement, challenging one-size-fits-all models of ageing. Practically, it shows how narrative typologies, framings, and co-created prototypes can inform tailored interventions, offering foundations for policy, community, and public health strategies that reflect women's realities.

Methodologically, it advances dialogical and imaginative approaches that elicit unspoken needs and provide a way to test early-stage concepts when real-world piloting is not feasible. Collectively, these contributions reposition women's voices at the centre of retirement research and open new directions for designing interventions that address the complexities of later life.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AIHW	Australian Institute of Health and Welfare
CALD	Culturally and Linguistically Diverse
CAP	Critical Analytical Practices
CDC	Centre for Disease Control and Prevention
DHSC	Department of Health and Social Care
DNA	Dialogical Narrative Analysis
DWP	Department of Working Pensions
HCD	Human-Centred Design
HLE	Healthy Life Expectancy
HMW	How Might We (questions)
IRTS	International Research Training School
IT	Information Technology
ME	Myalgic encephalomyelitis
NASSM	North American Society for Sports Management
NCD	Non-Communicable Disease
NI	Narrative Inquiry
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
ONS	Office for National Statistics
PA	Physical Activity
SC	Story Completion
SDH	Social Determinants of Health
SLO	South Lanarkshire Organisation
SIMD	Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation
SP	State Pension
SPA	State Pension Age
TtR	Transition to Retirement
UK	United Kingdom
UWS	University of the West of Scotland
WHO	World Health Organisation
WHRN	Women's Health Research Network

Chapter One: Framing the Problem: Gender, Narrative, and the Transition to Retirement

1.0 Chapter Aim and Objective

This chapter introduces the problem of how women experience the transition to retirement and why current support options are often insufficient. It situates the issue within broader social, policy, and research frameworks, introduces my reflexive position as a researcher, and establishes the need for narrative-based approaches that better reflect the complexity of women's later life transitions. The chapter also acknowledges that my own personal and professional trajectory has shaped the direction of this study, an account that is set out in **Section 1.4**.

1.1 Introducing the Problem: Transition to Retirement as a Critical Life Stage

Public discourse and policy often frame retirement as a time of leisure, relaxation, and personal fulfilment. Promotional materials from pension providers, ageing charities, and government departments often depict retirement as a reward for years of labour, emphasising autonomy, travel, or hobbies (Age UK, 2023; Department for Work and Pensions [DWP], 2022). Yet such framings obscure the complex, often gendered, realities of retirement as experienced in everyday life.

Around one in 4.5 adults in the UK is currently above state pension age (22%), a proportion projected to rise to 28% by 2075 (Government Actuary's Department, 2024). In England, the number of people aged 65 and over is expected to increase by 3.3 million over the next two decades and by 6.5 million over the next forty years, with the population aged 80 and over more than doubling by 2065 (Office for National Statistics [ONS], 2023). Alongside this demographic expansion, financial precarity remains a pressing concern. Around 43% of the working-age population (14.6 million people) are undersaving for retirement, a proportion projected to increase to nearly half, and only 27% are on track to achieve a moderate standard of living in later life (DWP, 2022). Gendered inequalities are particularly evident: women in Generation X hold an average of £72,000 in private pension wealth compared with £135,000 for men and receive £3,000 less per year in private pension income (Pensions Policy Institute, 2022).

The material challenges of retirement are also shaped by disparities between overall lifespan and years lived in good health. According to the Global Burden of Disease Study (2024), people worldwide spend an average of 9.6 years in poor health, with women facing a healthspan–lifespan gap that is 2.4 years longer than men across 183 countries. National figures reflect a similar pattern. In England, healthy life expectancy (HLE) at birth is estimated at 61.9 years for women and 61.5 years for men, representing a decline of 1.9 years and 1.7 years respectively since the pre-pandemic period (2011–13) (Government Actuary’s Department, 2024). In Scotland, HLE at birth in 2021–2023 is 60.0 years for females and 59.6 years for males, continuing a downward trend observed since 2014–2016 (National Records of Scotland, 2024). Together, these trends indicate that women, despite living longer than men, are spending more years in poor health, which amplifies the financial, social, and care-related challenges embedded in the transition to retirement.

The transition to retirement (TtR) is more than a chronological or administrative shift tied to a specific age or pension milestone. It is a biographical, relational, and embodied process that intersects with identity, social connection, and the negotiation of past and future selves (Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020). This process involves changes to daily routines, reconfigured relationships, and a re-evaluation of purpose and direction in later life. For women, it is often complicated by gendered life trajectories, including care responsibilities, interrupted employment histories, and systemic inequities in pension entitlements (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Foster, 2021).

Much of the support offered to individuals approaching or entering retirement focuses on logistical or behavioural domains such as financial planning, lifestyle promotion, or volunteering (DWP, 2017; Moore, 2020). While valuable in some respects, such services typically adopt an individualised model of adjustment and assume a uniform retirement trajectory (Phillipson, 2019; Calasanti, 2020). This orientation is reinforced by policy documents such as the UK Government’s *Fuller Working Lives* strategy (DWP, 2017), which emphasises extending employment participation and preparing for retirement through economic self-sufficiency.

Such interventions frequently overlook the emotional, social, and identity-based dimensions of retirement (Grenier, 2012; Phillipson, 2019). They rarely account for the

multiple meanings retirement holds, particularly for women who may have followed unconventional career paths or whose sense of self is closely tied to relational or unpaid roles (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Foster, 2021). For instance, a woman whose identity is rooted in caregiving may struggle with cultural expectations to ‘enjoy’ retirement through leisure while still carrying ongoing family responsibilities (Hamblin and Ismail, 2021).

As Grenier (2022) argues, later life continues to be governed by scripts of ageing, or culturally imposed expectations that constrain how ageing is understood and experienced. These scripts often fail to accommodate diverse experiences and overlook the personal narratives people construct to make sense of change. Dominant storylines are further reinforced through interventions, services, and media portrayals of older adults as either active and productive or frail and dependent, leaving little space for complexity or ambiguity (Rozanova, 2010).

Furthermore, retirement as a cultural script often ignores the ongoing nature of identity work across the life course. Rather than a fixed stage, for many it is better understood as a fluid and transitional process. As Gilleard and Higgs (2011) observe, the boundaries between middle age and old age have become increasingly blurred, and the TtR is one of the points where this ambiguity comes into focus. Researchers such as Baars (2012) and Hydén (2013) emphasise that identity in later life is not fixed, but a story in motion, continually shaped through narrative. Retirement requires individuals to rework their life stories, integrating past roles, losses, hopes, and cultural expectations (Baars, 2012; Hydén, 2013; Phoenix and Sparkes, 2019). For many women, this process involves navigating tensions between visibility and invisibility, dependence and autonomy, caring for others and attending to their own needs. As such, the TtR becomes a site of identity negotiation, in which women actively interpret what it means to age on their own terms.

There is a growing need to rethink how retirement is understood and supported, moving away from milestones and metrics toward stories and self-understanding (Grenier, 2012; Phillipson, 2019; Frank, 2010). Narrative approaches provide a means of accessing the subjective experiences that traditional retirement models tend to overlook. This thesis responds to that need by exploring the TtR as a rich narrative

landscape (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000) and as a site for designing forms of support grounded in women's lived experience.

Unlike approaches that prioritise behavioural change, economic planning, or generic activity models, this study centres on how women themselves make sense of retirement and uses these narratives to inform more context-sensitive, relational, and resonant forms of support. Behavioural interventions often promote individual responsibility for 'successful' ageing, emphasising mindset, health, or resilience (Moore, 2020; Katz and Calasanti, 2015). Economic planning frameworks commonly assume stable work histories and continuous pension contributions, assumptions that do not reflect the realities of many women's lives (Phillipson, 2019; Foster and Heneghan, 2022). Similarly, participation-focused models such as volunteering or digital engagement are presented as universally beneficial, yet they can feel alienating or irrelevant for those managing care responsibilities, health challenges, or structural exclusion (Hamblin and Ismail, 2021; Age UK, 2020). By contrast, this thesis uses narrative methods to surface women's own meanings, tensions, and priorities, offering a foundation for support that recognises complexity rather than conformity.

1.2 Why Focus on Women?

Women approach retirement with a distinct set of life experiences and expectations. Feminist and life course perspectives show that many women's employment histories are fragmented or non-linear due to caregiving responsibilities, gendered patterns of employment, and the cumulative effects of part-time or low-paid work (Cory and Stirling, 2022; Foster, 2021). These patterns often result in reduced pension wealth and fewer opportunities for financial autonomy in later life (Cribb and Emmerson, 2020).

Beyond the material disparities, retirement can also challenge women's sense of self and relational identity (Price, 2020; Calasanti and Slevin, 2020). Women frequently carry the emotional and invisible labour within families and communities (Lewis, 2001). As a result, the shift out of paid work does not necessarily reduce responsibilities but may lead to a reconfiguration of their sense of self (Denton and Boos, 2007). Some women may experience a loss of structure and recognition, while others may embrace

retirement as a chance for reconnection, rest, or reinvention (Evans and Williams, 2020; Price, 2020).

Women's retirement transitions are shaped by gender as well as intersecting social positions, including race, class, disability, and sexuality (Calasanti, 2020; Phoenix and Pattynama, 2006). Hamblin and Ismail (2021) highlight how women from racially marginalised backgrounds may face compounded pension disadvantages due to structural labour market discrimination and insecure employment. Reports by Age UK (2020) document how disabled women often experience retirement as a continuation of longstanding exclusion from workplace structures and formal support systems. The DWP (2021) also acknowledges the cumulative impact of overlapping inequalities on financial and social outcomes in later life. The broader literature on intersectional ageing reinforces this view, emphasising that retirement must be understood in relation to how intersecting identities shape both opportunities and constraints in later life (Calasanti, 2020; Phillipson, 2013; Van Dyk and Lessenich, 2017).

While this study focuses on women's experiences of retirement, it does not assume a single or unified experience of being a woman. Women's transitions are shaped by the intersecting dynamics of gender, race, class, disability, sexuality, and migration history. For instance, racially marginalised women may face cumulative disadvantage due to long-term underemployment and pension exclusion (Foster and Heneghan, 2022), while disabled women may encounter institutional barriers that blur the lines between working life and retirement (Wilkinson and Craig, 2019). Working-class women are more likely to enter retirement with health conditions and fewer financial resources, shaping how they narrate choice, care, and constraint (Reynolds et al., 2021). These overlapping social identities shape access to pensions and services, as well as the meanings retirement holds, the identities available to occupy, and the types of support that feel relevant (Calasanti, 2020; Phoenix and Pattynama, 2006). Rather than claiming to represent all women, this study focuses on the specific stories shared by participants, recognising both diversity and shared challenges within current retirement frameworks.

While this thesis does not adopt a feminist theoretical framework, it is informed by feminist perspectives that emphasise how gendered power relations, structural

inequalities, and life-course disruptions shape women's later-life experiences. Feminist gerontology and critical ageing research have long argued that retirement cannot be understood as a neutral or universal transition but must be situated within histories of paid and unpaid labour, caregiving, and cumulative disadvantage (Calasanti, 2020; Katz and Calasanti, 2015). Acknowledging these feminist concerns strengthens the rationale for focusing explicitly on women, not as a homogeneous group, but as individuals whose retirement trajectories are patterned by enduring social and economic inequalities. Framing retirement in this way emphasises the urgency of developing support mechanisms that respond to women's lived realities, rather than relying on models grounded in masculine or uninterrupted employment pathways.

Retirement has often been characterised in the literature as a disruptive break in identity, sometimes described as a sudden loss of structure and purpose (Sargent et al., 2013; Wang and Shi, 2014). At the same time, other studies emphasise its potential to be experienced as liberating, opening space for autonomy and new forms of self-expression (Price and Nesteruk, 2019; Nimrod, 2007). These contrasting perspectives highlight that retirement is not a uniform process but a deeply individual and sometimes contradictory experience. However, there remains limited evidence on how such complexities are articulated by women in the Scottish context, representing a knowledge gap that this thesis addresses.

Existing retirement models often rely on assumptions of continuous employment and personal responsibility, reflecting gendered and historically masculine life-course norms that obscure structural inequalities and unpaid labour (Katz and Calasanti, 2015). The 'successful ageing' paradigm, with its emphasis on productivity, health, and independence, tends to marginalise those who age differently or resist these normative ideals (Katz and Calasanti, 2015; Grenier, 2012). Such frameworks frequently privilege masculine life courses and do little to account for interruptions, caregiving roles, or collective forms of identity (Foster, 2021; Estes, Carroll, and Mahakian, 2020). This omission influences how services are imagined, implemented, and evaluated in practice.

At the same time, there are elements of existing theory and practice that offer valuable foundations for this study. Life-course and continuity perspectives have emphasised

the importance of maintaining social roles and connections in later life, while health-promotion research has drawn attention to the benefits of purposeful activity and community participation (Barnett et al., 2012; Cattan et al., 2011). In particular, growing work around physical activity highlights retirement as a potential opportunity to support wellbeing, social contact, and identity continuity when suitable conditions and access routes are provided (Tulle and Phoenix, 2015; Barker, Britton, and Windle, 2021; Wanka, 2020). These insights inform the design focus of this thesis, which explores how such opportunities can be made more inclusive and resonant for women whose pathways to retirement are diverse and often precarious.

There remains a gap in both research and practice when it comes to listening carefully to how women themselves narrate and make sense of retirement. This study addresses that gap by placing women's voices at the centre, exploring how they articulate *their* needs, reflect on *their* experiences, and respond to proposed support mechanisms. The research is situated in the UK, with a particular focus on the narratives of Scottish women, whose accounts form the basis of early typology development and inform the broader design and analysis of this work. By doing so, the research aims to challenge reductive models and co-create more resonant and responsive forms of support for women in the TtR.

While some recent work has begun to acknowledge the relevance of intersectionality in later life, it remains limited in many areas of retirement policy and practice. As Foster and Heneghan (2022) note, mainstream retirement planning tools often overlook the cumulative effects of low-paid, informal, or interrupted employment, especially where these intersect with caregiving roles, cultural norms, or racialised experiences. Although financial advice is typically presented in neutral terms, it often reflects assumptions of stable income and continuous pension contributions (Vickerstaff, 2010; Moore, 2020). These underlying assumptions can unintentionally narrow the reach and resonance of support offered, highlighting the value of more contextually grounded and narrative informed approaches (Grenier and Phillipson, 2022; Calasanti, 2020). These reflections help clarify why retirement cannot be understood (or supported) through generalised models alone. A more attentive approach is needed:

one that listens to how people narrate their transitions, make meaning from change, and articulate what forms of support feel possible, desirable, or out of reach.

1.3 Implications for Practice

The failure to centre women's lived experiences in retirement support has significant consequences. Models that prioritise financial management, lifestyle adjustment, or resilience tend to produce interventions that feel standardised and disconnected from everyday realities (Phillipson, 2019; Moore, 2020). As a result, many women encounter support that does little to address the relational, emotional, and identity-based aspects of their transition. For practice, this highlights the need for approaches that respond to material concerns while also creating space for narrative, self-understanding, and complexity in later life.

In practice, many of these interventions are shaped by dominant policy discourses such as 'active ageing'¹, which encourage older adults to remain productive, healthy, and socially engaged. While such goals hold value, they risk becoming limiting when applied too narrowly. Activity-based programmes that promote volunteering, exercise, or digital learning can feel misaligned with women's daily realities, particularly for those managing ongoing care responsibilities, financial constraints, or health challenges (Martinson and Minkler, 2006; Van Dyk and Lessenich, 2017). When support is framed primarily around staying active or independent, it risks reinforcing exclusion by failing to recognise diverse forms of contribution, dependence, or interdependence (Estes, Biggs, and Phillipson, 2003).

The policy emphasis on independence deserves critical reflection. While often positioned as empowering, it can marginalise those whose later lives involve reciprocal care, collective support, or changing needs. As Fine and Glendinning (2005) argue, the political ideal of independence risks framing dependency as failure rather than a normal and relational part of ageing. This can be particularly alienating for women whose lives have involved sustained caregiving or collaborative decision making.

¹ Active ageing is a policy concept developed by the World Health Organisation to promote continued participation in social, economic, cultural, and civic life as people age (WHO, 2002). While intended to support wellbeing, the term has been critiqued for reinforcing neoliberal ideals of productivity and independence, often marginalising those unable or unwilling to age in such ways (Martin et al., 2015; Van Dyk and Lessenich, 2017).

Narrative approaches offer an alternative by legitimising diverse ways of being in later life, including those that resist individualist ideals (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000; Riessman, 2008).

Pre-retirement planning seminars, typically offered by employers, further illustrate these limitations. These sessions often focus on pensions, legal issues, and post-work options, with little attention to identity, relationships, or emotional preparedness. For women whose careers have been shaped by caregiving or precarity, such seminars can feel abstract or exclusionary, reinforcing assumptions about linear employment and individual control (Vickerstaff and Cox, 2005; Calasanti, 2020). Similarly, digital inclusion initiatives are often promoted as tools for enhancing engagement and access, yet they frequently overlook the emotional, relational, and cultural barriers women may face such as digital fatigue, low confidence, or past exclusion from technology driven spaces (Age UK, 2020; Foster and Heneghan, 2022).

Many retirement interventions continue to rely on outdated assumptions, framing ageing through individual responsibility, biomedical ideals, and gender-neutral policy design (Calasanti, 2020; Grenier and Phillipson, 2022; Estes, Biggs and Phillipson, 2003). Despite policy commitments to fairness and person-centred practice (Scottish Government, 2021), most interventions still privilege measurable outcomes over lived meaning and structural equity (Grenier and Phillipson, 2022). This often alienates those who cannot conform to dominant ideals of ageing, such as uninterrupted work histories or financial independence. These gaps highlight the need to reframe retirement support through narrative approaches that privilege lived experience over prescriptive models.

In this study, I argue that more meaningful and effective interventions must begin with an understanding of how women narrate their own transitions. Narratives do not simply reflect experience; they shape how people interpret, justify, and respond to change (Frank, 2010). This narrative orientation opens up new ways to support women whose retirement journeys do not align with dominant ideals or policy assumptions.

Storytelling accommodates complexity, ambiguity, and contradiction, offering a way to surface what matters to individuals beyond standardised categories or outcome measures (Riessman, 2008). It enables a different mode of engagement: one that is

dialogic, generative, and reflective (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000). Within this study, narrative methods were used both to generate insight and to collaboratively test and refine potential forms of support with participants. In doing so, the research offers both a methodological contribution and a practical pathway toward more responsive and relational approaches to retirement.

1.4 Reflexive Positioning: Researcher as Narrator

I entered this research as both observer and participant, shaped by my own life course, disciplinary training, and social position. As a woman engaged in academic inquiry into ageing and retirement, I bring personal understandings formed by gendered expectations, cultural narratives, and institutional pressures. These experiences inevitably inform how I see, interpret, and represent the stories of others.

This project was undertaken as part of a funded doctoral studentship, which provided both the opportunity and the responsibility to pursue research of social value. For me, the studentship carried particular meaning. I did not arrive at doctoral study through a linear or privileged pathway. I grew up in a working-class background, and my adult life has continued to be shaped by economic precarity and constraint. I was diagnosed with Myalgic encephalomyelitis (ME) as a teenager, which has gone through periods of remission during adulthood. Alongside this, I have lived with a benign brain tumour since the age of twenty, an experience that introduced me early on to the realities of chronic health disruption. I am the mother of two differently abled young adults, and much of my pre-graduate life was shaped by caregiving, interrupted work, and illness. These circumstances meant that my education and career developed in uneven ways, pursued alongside responsibility and constraint. They also shaped how I understand privilege and oppression in relation to disability. My condition is often unseen, which affords me certain privileges in contexts where disability is not outwardly visible. At the same time, the hidden nature of impairment has meant repeatedly explaining and justifying my struggles when they are not obvious to others. This duality has sharpened my awareness of how narratives of health and ability are culturally policed, and how important it is to create space for diverse stories of disruption, resilience, and adaptation.

Alongside these personal experiences, I built a varied career: first as a nurse, later as a holistic therapist, and eventually as a postgraduate student completing a master's degree in public health. Each of these roles deepened my interest in health, wellbeing, and the social contexts that shape them, and each taught me different ways of listening to and supporting people in transition. Securing scholarships and funding made it possible for me to bring these strands together within doctoral research, and I am mindful that my position within higher education is built on persistence and opportunity rather than entitlement.

A serious neurological event during the PhD further reshaped how I understood disruption, recovery, and the fragility of assumed life courses. At the age of forty-four, I spent three weeks in a stroke ward during the COVID-19 pandemic, surrounded by women at least twice my age. Restrictions meant I could not see my family. My speech was muddled, I struggled to form sentences, and my memory was dulled in ways that I continue to live with. I experienced facial palsy, numbness down my right side, unsteady walking, and the loss of dexterity in my dominant hand. Gruelling headaches made concentration almost impossible. Although recovery has been partial, with lasting effects on communication and cognition, the experience gave me a deepened appreciation of how precarious and unpredictable life transitions can be. These events sharpened my awareness of how dominant scripts about ageing and retirement often overlook the realities of illness, fragility, and recovery. They also heightened my commitment to research that creates space for alternative stories to be told.

Illness has also shaped the way I engage with research and communicate ideas. Since the neurological event, I have found that I often think and express myself more clearly in writing than in speech. This does not represent a deficiency but a reminder that all narratives, including my own, are partial and situated. It has made me more attentive to the different ways women narrate disruption and transition, and to the importance of recognising varied forms of telling as valid.

My interest in the TtR did not emerge only from academic reading but from recognition of how invisible some life trajectories can become when they do not fit expected models. As a woman who has had to pause and reconfigure career ambitions due to illness and care, I understand that retirement cannot be reduced to a neat financial

calculation or a universal stage of life. Instead, it is experienced through the accumulation of earlier life events, interruptions, and turning points. This recognition made it meaningful to me that the stories of women with varied and uneven journeys should be listened to and valued.

The methodological implications of reflexivity, positionality, and narrative inquiry are taken up in greater detail in **Chapter Three**. Here, I simply note that my personal and professional trajectory shapes the questions I ask, the relationships I build, and the interpretations I make. This research is therefore inseparable from the story of how I came to do it.

1.5 Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is organised across seven chapters, each aligned with a distinct aim and objective, forming a coherent narrative about women's experiences during the TtR and the potential for more responsive forms of support. **Chapter One** introduces the central problem and sets out the conceptual, policy, and personal context for the study.

Chapter Two presents a discursive literature review that critically examines how retirement, ageing, gender, and intervention design are currently understood, identifying theoretical and empirical gaps; the research questions that guided this inquiry are introduced at the end of the chapter. **Chapter Three** outlines the study's methodological foundations and explains how narrative inquiry, human-centred design, and co-production were applied across the research phases. It also details the development of story completion as a methodological apparatus and the dialogical narrative framework used for analysis.

The empirical chapters follow the three phases of the study. **Chapter Four** focuses on Phase One, which incorporated narrative interviews and the first co-design workshop, generating a typology of women's retirement transitions (the hear/inspiration stage of human-centred design; IDEO, 2015). **Chapter Five** presents Phase Two, drawing on the outputs of Workshops Two and Three (ideation/create), where framings, composite stories, and three intervention prototypes were developed. **Chapter Six** reports Phase Three (implementation/deliver), presenting findings from the story completion activity and analysing how women engaged with the prototypes through narrative responses.

Chapter Seven brings together discussion and conclusion, offering a cross-phase synthesis, introducing a typology of narrative responses, and outlining the study's theoretical contributions, practical implications, limitations, and recommendations.

Each chapter builds on the last to centre women's voices and reimagine support during the TtR through a narrative and participatory lens. The thesis is deliberately structured to parallel the stages of human-centred design (hear, create, deliver) so that the organisation of the chapters reflects the iterative process through which insights and interventions were developed. This design contributes to both methodological innovation and practical understanding of how narrative inquiry can inform support for women in later life.

Chapter Two: Literature Review - Mapping Women's Retirement Transitions

2.0 Chapter Aim and Objective

This chapter examines existing research on retirement transitions, with a focus on how women experience, describe, and navigate this life stage. It identifies critical gaps in theory, practice, and intervention design, particularly where dominant models and policies fail to account for the emotional, relational, and narrative dimensions of women's lives. The chapter synthesises academic and policy literature on retirement and ageing, with attention to how the TtR is conceptualised, framed, and supported. It evaluates dominant retirement models in relation to women's lived experiences, considers how gendered life course patterns shape retirement pathways, and critiques existing interventions for their lack of emotional and narrative relevance. The chapter also explores the value of narrative, co-production, and Human-Centred Design approaches to ageing and retirement and identifies key gaps in the literature that inform the research questions, aims, and objectives of the thesis.

2.1 Introduction

Retirement is often presented as a predictable life milestone, framed in public discourse as a time of rest, leisure, and self-fulfilment. These images of freedom from work and the rewards of careful planning are widely reflected in media, policy, and workplace narratives (Atchley, 1982; (DWP, 2017; Age UK, 2023). Yet these portrayals overlook the layered, relational, and often gendered realities of how retirement is experienced, particularly by women (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Price, 2020).

I begin this chapter by challenging these dominant framings. Rather than viewing retirement as a discrete event or a linear adjustment process, I approach the TtR as a complex life stage shaped by identity, caregiving responsibilities, structural inequality, and cultural narratives (Grenier, 2012; Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020). I then critically review how the TtR has been theorised and supported, with attention to who is included and who is excluded in these accounts (Calasanti and Slevin, 2001; Phoenix and Pattynama, 2006).

In doing so, the chapter takes an interpretive and layered approach. It traces the assumptions underpinning dominant retirement models, identifies conceptual limitations, and highlights silences and exclusions within existing frameworks (Harding, 1991; Holstein and Minkler, 2007; Calasanti and Slevin, 2020). It draws on narrative and critical traditions to understand retirement as both a behavioural shift and a storied process through which women make sense of change, negotiate meaning, and express emotional and social complexity (Riessman, 2008; Phoenix, 2013; McPhillips, 2023). Guided by narrative inquiry (NI)², the review attends to what is said in the literature and to what remains unspoken, including contradictions, ambivalence, and emotional concerns that are rarely acknowledged in policy frameworks (Mazzei, 2009; Ahmed, 2010; Price, 2020). Being guided by NI means reading the literature as a collection of stories about how retirement is understood, rather than as an objective accumulation of evidence.

In engaging with this body of work, I became attentive to the contrast between abstract models of retirement and the more layered, emotional accounts I was already encountering in early narrative data. This awareness shaped how I approached the review, leading me to consider what was silenced and what was made visible in the literature. Although the review is presented here before the empirical chapters, the process was iterative: early engagement with participants' narratives informed which bodies of literature I prioritised, while the review itself helped refine the analytic focus and conceptual framing that developed across subsequent phases.

Throughout the chapter, emphasis is placed on the intersection of gender, narrative, and social positioning. Women's retirement transitions shaped by fragmented work histories, ongoing caregiving, and structural disadvantage, require conceptual frameworks that go beyond productivity and autonomy to engage with care, identity, and connection (Ginn and Arber, 1999; Calasanti, 2020; Bowlby et al., 2010). These concerns underpin the direction I take in the thesis and inform my rationale for using

² Narrative inquiry (NI) is an interpretive research approach that explores how people make sense of experience through story. It focuses on language, temporality, and social context, and is often used to investigate identity, meaning, and change (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000; Riessman, 2008).

participatory and narrative methods in the chapters that follow (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000; Sanders and Stappers, 2008).

2.2 Conceptualising the TtR: Definitions and Key Concepts

The TtR is frequently represented in research and policy as a discrete, age-bound event, typically linked to the cessation of paid employment and the beginning of a new life stage defined by leisure, autonomy, or freedom (Atchley, 1982; Phillipson, 2013). In the UK, the state pension age is currently 66 for both men and women, with further increases planned (DWP, 2023). However, the average age at which women retire is slightly lower, at around 64.3 years (ONS, 2022). While providing an administrative benchmark, these figures obscure the diverse and complex experiences which are shaped by gender, class, health, and relational factors (Grenier, 2012; Phillipson, 2013; Calasanti and Slevin, 2020).

Grenier (2012) argues that the stories people tell about retirement are central to how they make sense of ageing. These stories often challenge normative ideals of independence, productivity, or closure. Retirement is increasingly conceptualised as a liminal space: a transitional phase situated between the cessation of paid work and the onset of recognised old age (Gilleard and Higgs, 2011; Grenier, 2012). This in-between stage may involve the loss of familiar roles without the full establishment of new ones, generating uncertainty and disorientation, especially among those whose identities have been shaped by work or caregiving (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Price, 2020). Narrative approaches help illuminate how individuals navigate these shifts and construct new meanings (Moffatt and Heaven, 2017).

Women's experiences of retirement are often under-theorised, with many models assuming linear employment histories that overlook the constraints, caregiving roles, or employment interruptions that shape women's later life transitions (Foster, 2021; Katz and Calasanti, 2015).

Some women may never formally retire, especially if they exit precarious or informal work without institutional recognition or support (Cribb and Emmerson, 2020). Cultural narratives of ageing seldom accommodate the layered realities of care, constraint, or cumulative disadvantage (Price, 2020). Even when the literature recognises that

retirement is complex, it often stays at an abstract level, describing it as heterogeneous without exploring how individuals actually tell stories about the transition or make sense of it in their lives (Grenier, 2012; Riessman, 2008). In this thesis, I approach the TtR as a storied process shaped by cultural resources and life constraints. As Riessman (2008) and Phoenix and Pattynama (2006) argue, stories are the means through which people perform identity work, making retirement a dynamic site of ongoing negotiation.

Adopting a narrative framing of retirement opens space to consider how cultural, structural, and emotional dimensions intersect in later life. This chapter builds on such framing, engaging with broader public health discourses that shape ageing policies and assumptions. The Marmot Review (2010, 2020) and national Scottish data (Walsh et al., 2022) highlight how income, housing, education, and employment shape health outcomes in retirement. Global frameworks, including the WHO's World Report on Ageing and Health (2015), increasingly emphasise emotional and social wellbeing alongside physical health and financial planning.

Yet despite this recognition, dominant retirement models still centre behavioural change, individual responsibility, and financial preparation, often sidelining the relational and emotional dynamics that shape how retirement is actually lived (Grenier and Phillipson, 2022; Foster and Walker, 2015). Women's accounts repeatedly point to the significance of care, identity, and emotional work, realities that current public health agendas often overlook. Some researchers, particularly within feminist and critical gerontology, argue for a reframing of later life that values meaning, connection, and care alongside health and productivity (Holstein and Minkler, 2007; Bowlby et al., 2010; Calasanti and Slevin, 2020). This critical gerontological position informs the thesis's central argument: that emotional and social wellbeing must be understood as central to how women navigate retirement. While these perspectives highlight the complexity of retirement as a lived and narrated transition, feminist gerontological scholarship further demonstrates how such experiences are structured by gendered power relations across the life course.

2.3. Feminist Gerontology, Power, and the Gendered Life Course

Feminist gerontology and feminist political economy provide a critical context for understanding why women's retirement experiences have been marginal within dominant ageing and retirement frameworks. These traditions challenge individualised accounts of later-life transitions by drawing attention to gendered power relations, unpaid care work, and the cumulative effects of labour market inequality across the life course (Estes, 2001; Ginn and Arber, 1999; Calasanti and Slevin, 2001). Katz and Calasanti (2015) critique 'successful ageing' and related retirement frameworks for privileging historically masculine norms of continuous employment, productivity, and independence, thereby obscuring the realities of women whose working lives are shaped by caregiving, part-time work, and structural constraint. Feminist gerontology conceptualises the life course as cumulative. Structural inequalities are therefore understood to become material in later life (Price, 2020). This perspective contrasts with mainstream retirement models, treating gender as a structural relation rather than an individual characteristic and locating later-life outcomes within the political economy of work, care, and welfare provision (Calasanti and Slevin, 2001; Ginn and Arber, 1999). In practice, women's retirement trajectories are shaped by interrupted employment, part-time work, lower lifetime earnings, and extended periods of unpaid caregiving, all of which contribute to reduced pension security and constrained choices in later life (Loretto and Vickerstaff, 2015; Foster, 2021). These material conditions reflect gendered divisions of labour and policy frameworks that have historically prioritised paid employment over caregiving. Retirement therefore needs to be understood as a gendered and historically situated process rather than a universal life stage (Price, 2020).

Critical feminist scholars have also drawn attention to the relational and embodied dimensions of later life. Experiences of health, energy, mobility, and confidence are shaped by lifelong access to resources, working conditions, and caring responsibilities (Twigg and Martin, 2015; Calasanti, 2020). This challenges models of retirement that frame later life primarily in terms of individual behaviour or lifestyle choice, instead emphasising how opportunities for participation are structured by class, gender, and health across time. It also highlights how cultural narratives of "active" or "successful"

ageing can reproduce exclusion by privileging independence, productivity, and self-management as markers of value.

Intersectional feminist perspectives further complicate any singular account of women's retirement. Differences in ethnicity, class, disability, sexuality, and migration history shape access to pensions, health resources, and supportive social networks, producing diverse retirement pathways and meanings (Phoenix and Pattynama, 2006; Calasanti, 2020). Recognising these intersecting dynamics is essential for understanding why some women experience retirement as a period of opportunity while others encounter ongoing precarity or constraint.

Feminist theory has also problematised the idea of stable or universal identities. Butler (1990) conceptualises gender as produced through repeated social practices rather than as a fixed attribute, highlighting how normative expectations shape the identities available across the life course. Haraway's (1988) concept of situated knowledge similarly challenges claims to universal or detached perspectives, emphasising that knowledge is always produced from specific social positions. These ideas inform the present study by underpinning an approach that treats women's retirement narratives as diverse, partial, and contextually located rather than representative of a single category of "woman". They also underpin the use of participatory and narrative methods, which emphasise situated experience and co-produced meaning rather than assuming universal or decontextualised accounts. This emphasis on situated knowledge and the legitimacy of lived experience further supports the use of co-production, which seeks to redistribute expertise and involve participants as contributors to knowledge rather than as subjects of research (Beresford, 2019).

In this thesis, these feminist concepts are used as sensitising rather than structuring frameworks. They inform how women's narratives are read in relation to cumulative inequality, care, embodiment, and culturally normative expectations of activity and independence. This orientation shapes analytic attention to constraint, ambivalence, relational responsibility, and negotiated participation across **Chapters Four to Seven**.

These theoretical insights inform the rationale for the present study in three ways. First, they establish retirement as a gendered and relational process rather than a uniform

life stage. Second, they highlight the limitations of policy and intervention models that assume linear employment histories and individual responsibility for wellbeing. Third, they emphasise the need for approaches that attend to women's lived experiences, narrative meanings, and socially situated forms of knowledge.

Feminist gerontological perspectives therefore shape the identification of the research problem, the focus on situated narratives, and the participatory design of the study. They locate retirement within gendered power relations that shape access to resources, recognition, and participation across the life course. This orientation informs the narrative and co-design approach developed in **Chapter Three** and the interpretation of women's accounts in later chapters.

2.4 Dominant Models of Retirement

Much of the academic and policy literature on retirement has been shaped by a set of foundational theories that attempt to explain how individuals move out of paid work and adapt to life beyond employment (Atchley, 1982; Wang and Shultz, 2010). These theories offer useful conceptual tools, but they often rely on assumptions about stability, independence, and linear progress that do not reflect the complex realities of many women's lives. **Table 1** summarises five of the most commonly cited models, outlining their core features and highlighting key critiques, particularly in relation to gendered and relational aspects of the TtR.

Table 1: Summary of Dominant Retirement Models and Their Critiques

Model	Key Features	Critiques (Especially Women)	Key Reference
Atchley's Stage Model	Retirement as a predictable psychological sequence (e.g. honeymoon, disenchantment, reorientation).	Assumes a linear, complete withdrawal from work; overlooks ambiguous transitions shaped by ongoing care responsibilities common in women's lives.	Atchley (1982); Calasanti and Slevin (2020); Lain and Vickerstaff (2020)
Role Theory	Loss of work identity prompts search for substitute roles (e.g. volunteering, caregiving).	Centres paid employment as primary identity; marginalises relational or unpaid roles.	Wang and Shultz (2010); Calasanti and King (2015); Foster (2021)
Continuity Theory	Individuals seek coherence between past and present identities and routines.	Presumes predictable life paths; less applicable to interrupted, care influenced life courses.	Atchley (1999); Grenier (2012); Price (2020)
Life Course Perspective	Interplay between biography, timing, and social structures; emphasises cumulative (dis)advantage.	Over-emphasises individual adaptability; fails to address unequal access or systemic barriers.	Settersten and Gannon (2019); Lain and Vickerstaff (2020); Price (2020)
Resource Based Models	Retirement quality depends on personal, social, financial, and psychological resources.	Over-emphasises individual adaptability; fails to address unequal access or systemic barriers.	Wang et al. (2011); Calasanti and Slevin (2020); Grenier (2012)

One of the most enduring frameworks is Atchley's (1982) stage model of retirement adjustment, which conceptualises retirement as a linear psychological journey through phases: honeymoon, disenchantment, reorientation, stability, and termination. While this model offered a structured entry point into retirement research, it implies a predictable progression and assumes a complete exit from the workforce and eventual equilibrium. These assumptions often do not reflect the realities of women navigating care responsibilities, phased retirement, or intermittent work, where transitions are often prolonged or ambiguous (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020).

Role theory offers another dominant conceptual lens. It views retirement as a form of role exit and subsequent role acquisition, where psychological wellbeing depends on replacing the worker identity with new roles such as caregiving, volunteering, or leisure (Wang and Shultz, 2010; van Solinge and Henkens, 2008). Although this highlights the importance of identity and social participation, it centres paid work as the primary

source of identity and marginalises unpaid or relational roles that may be more significant in women's lives. It also aligns with discourses of active ageing and neoliberal ideals³ of self-management, portraying productivity as a benchmark for successful retirement (Calasanti and King, 2015; Foster, 2021).

In contrast, continuity theory (Atchley, 1999) proposes that individuals seek coherence between past and present by maintaining familiar patterns, relationships, and preferences across the retirement transition. This model recognises variation and respects personal history but assumes stable life trajectories. For women whose lives have been shaped by disruption, inequality, or caregiving, continuity may be unavailable, or even undesirable.

The life course perspective offers a broader structural framing by examining how biography, timing, and social institutions (such as work, family, and welfare systems) interact to shape retirement trajectories (Settersten and Gannon, 2019; Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020). It introduces useful concepts such as cumulative advantage/disadvantage and institutional timing, which help explain gendered disparities in retirement outcomes. For example, women who have experienced interrupted careers, wage gaps, or long-term unpaid care are more likely to reach retirement with reduced financial and social resources (Ginn and Arber, 1999; Price, 2020). However, while life course theory adds structural insight, it is often applied abstractly and fails to engage with the interpretive and emotional work involved in navigating later life (Grenier, 2012; Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020).

More recent resource-based and dynamic process models shift the focus from linear stages to the interplay of personal, social, and psychological resources (Wang et al., 2011). These models acknowledge variation in retirement experiences, such as the role of social support or financial security in buffering stress. However, they tend to emphasise individual adjustment, with success defined in terms of measurable outcomes like productivity or continuity, rather than how people interpret, narrate, or

³ Neoliberal ideas refer to policy and cultural frameworks that emphasise individual responsibility, self-management, and market-based solutions, often at the expense of structural or collective considerations (Brown, 2015; Davies, 2016). In the context of ageing and retirement, these ideas shape expectations around autonomy, productivity, and personal health maintenance.

resist retirement within context (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Grenier, 2012). This framing rests on normative assumptions: that retirement is a single, definable transition; that identity is rooted in paid work; that adaptation is necessary; and that continued productivity defines a good later life (Estes, Biggs and Phillipson, 2003; Grenier, 2012). Such assumptions risk marginalising those whose experiences fall outside these frameworks, particularly women managing ongoing care, health challenges, or economic precarity (Calasanti, 2020; Price, 2020).

These models also tend to prioritise action over meaning, focusing on what people do in retirement rather than how they make sense of it. Emotional nuance, relational identity, and ambivalence are often overlooked, despite being common features of women's narratives (Phoenix and Tulle, 2017; McPhillips, 2023). The frameworks leave little room for contradiction, such as experiencing both relief and loss, or for resistance to dominant ideals of retirement.

2.5 Gender and the Life Course: Women's Pathways to Retirement

While the life course perspective provides a vital structural lens, it often overlooks how gendered pathways uniquely shape women's experiences of retirement (Calasanti and Slevin, 2001; Loretto and Vickerstaff, 2013). For many women, retirement is a phase closely interwoven with ongoing caregiving, financial precarity, and shifting responsibilities, complexities that are only partially acknowledged in mainstream retirement frameworks (Ginn and Arber, 1999; Phillipson, 2013; Price, 2020).

Unlike men, who are more likely to follow continuous, full-time careers into retirement, many women experience a fragmented sequence of part-time jobs, career breaks for childrearing or eldercare, and precarious or informal employment (Loretto and Vickerstaff, 2013; Kojola and Moen, 2016). These patterns result in lower pension entitlements, reduced access to retirement benefits, and fewer financial buffers in later life (Cribb and Emmerson, 2020; Principi et al., 2020). However, Principi et al. (2020) also highlight the role of social networks and community engagement as essential resources for navigating these challenges, though such supports are not always equitably distributed.

Caregiving plays a cumulative role in shaping women's later life options. Ferraro, Shippee, and Schafer (2009, p. 61) describe caregiving as "both a feminist and life course issue, rooted in cumulative disadvantage." This framing makes visible how unpaid care responsibilities are carried across decades, often intensifying around retirement and continuing into later life (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020). Rather than signifying rest or leisure, retirement often involves a reorientation into new or intensified care roles.

Women may delay drawing pensions to support family members or exit work earlier than planned due to illness or caregiving obligations (Phillipson, 2013; Price, 2020). These realities often conflict with dominant cultural ideals of 'ageing well' or achieving a fulfilling 'third age'⁴ (Katz and Calasanti, 2015). The result is a narrative misalignment that shapes how women understand and express their experiences of later life.

Retirement stories often reflect these tensions, conveying resilience alongside ambivalence, guilt, fatigue, or subtle resistance to social expectations (Moffatt and Heaven, 2017; Price, 2020). These narratives challenge idealised framings of retirement as a time of liberation and instead reveal ongoing negotiations of care, identity, and constrained autonomy. As Jordan (2025, p. 15) writes, "The women's movement touched me like no other social change movement had. Feeling 'over the hill'... are both personal and political problems." Attending to such stories requires narrative approaches that centre complexity, rather than viewing retirement as a problem to be managed or a lifestyle to be optimised (Riessman, 2008; Price and Nesteruk, 2015).

In this context, retirement can be understood as both the end of paid employment and the continuation of emotional labour and social reproduction. UK policy remains largely structured around formal work trajectories, yet women aged 45 to 64 are the most likely group to be providing unpaid care to elderly parents, partners, or grandchildren, contributing an estimated £132 billion in unpaid care annually (Carers UK, 2023; Finch

⁴ The "third age" is a sociological concept that frames retirement as a time of leisure, self-fulfilment, and cultural participation, typically contrasted with the dependency of the "fourth age" (Laslett, 1989; Katz and Calasanti, 2015).

and Groves, 2020). This work is often invisible in retirement planning and support frameworks, despite its social and economic significance (Bennett, 2022).

The Joseph Rowntree Foundation (2022) notes that these responsibilities contribute directly to later life poverty among women, reinforcing cumulative disadvantage. Many are forced to access their pensions early, rely on savings, or enter retirement without financial independence. These patterns are particularly pronounced among low-income households and ethnic minority women, where limited access to formal care services intersects with structural inequalities and entrenched gender norms (Byles, 2013; Price, 2020; Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020). These experiences are further shaped by intersectional factors such as race, class, disability, and migration, which compound inequalities across the life course (Crenshaw, 1991; Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020).

Few prevailing accounts recognise the ongoing demands of unpaid labour or its emotional, physical, and social consequences (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Holstein and Minkler, 2007). As outlined earlier, prevailing narratives of success, choice, or fulfilment in retirement leave little space for such realities, positioning women's experiences at the margins. The lack of recognition for care work perpetuates inequalities that shape both financial outcomes and the ways ageing is experienced, narrated, and made meaningful (Baker et al., 2020). This critique informs the thesis's argument for more relational, narrative, and context-sensitive understandings of later life transitions. The following section continues this analysis by exploring how cultural narratives of retirement shape which stories are available to women, and which remain unheard.

2.6 Retirement and Cultural Narratives

As discussed in the previous sections, structural models of retirement often rest on gendered assumptions that exclude women's experiences. Beyond these frameworks, retirement is also shaped by cultural narratives, shared stories, values, and expectations surrounding ageing, work, and later life. These narratives offer frameworks through which individuals interpret and make sense of retirement, yet they often carry assumptions that exclude or marginalise diverse experiences (Phoenix, Smith, and Sparkes, 2010; Holstein and Minkler, 2007; Phillipson, 2013; Price, 2020).

Early accounts often idealised retirement as a ‘golden age’⁵ of freedom and reward after decades of work (Atchley, 1982; Johnson, 2005). These narratives were built around assumptions of continuous, stable employment and financial security, assumptions that reflected male and middle-class experience more than women’s. For those with interrupted careers or long periods of caregiving, such expectations were rarely achievable (Calasanti and Slevin, 2001; Phillipson, 2013; Price, 2010).

Recent research challenges the notion of a singular retirement narrative, emphasising instead that stories of later life are multiple, fluid, and deeply shaped by gender (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Wanka, 2020; Phoenix, 2013). Dubberley (2014) shows how cultural expectations around femininity and care influence women’s accounts of retirement, with many continuing to juggle responsibilities rather than withdrawing from them. Kubicek (2011) similarly highlights the shifting and unfinished nature of retirement as an ongoing process of role negotiation. Price (2010) critiques dominant retirement narratives for silencing the emotional complexity, contradictions, and resistance often found in women’s experiences.

Cultural narratives shape which stories are considered acceptable, credible, or worthy of telling (Phoenix and Pattynama, 2006; Hydén, 2018; Riessman, 2008). Recent feminist and critical gerontological research highlight the concept of *narrative availability*, referring to the culturally recognisable storylines through which people interpret and communicate later life experiences (McPhillips, 2023; Calasanti and King, 2015).

When dominant stories prioritise autonomy, optimism, and reinvention, more ambivalent or care-laden experiences may become difficult to voice without embarrassment or self-blame (Ahmed, 2010; Twigg, 2004). For example, narratives of positive ageing often obscure feelings of grief, exhaustion, or stagnation, which emerge as central themes in many women’s accounts (Price, 2020).

⁵ Golden age refers to an idealised narrative of retirement as a time of rest, reward, and self-fulfilment following a lifetime of work. It is often rooted in post-war welfare imaginaries and assumes continuous employment, financial stability, and personal autonomy - conditions that do not reflect many women’s retirement experiences (Katz, 2000; Phillipson, 2013; Price, 2020).

Cultural narratives also shape how policies and interventions are imagined. When retirement is framed primarily as an opportunity for reinvention and personal fulfilment, support efforts tend to emphasise behaviour change, lifestyle enhancement, and individual responsibility (Baker et al., 2020; Foster and Walker, 2015; Greenhalgh and Papoutsi, 2018). Such assumptions can marginalise those who experience retirement as constrained, care-bound, or emotionally ambivalent (Calasanti and King, 2015; Price, 2020; Twigg, 2013). As Phillipson (2013, p. 45) notes, “retirement policy often reflects a male-centric, idealised notion of withdrawal that marginalises the experiences of women and other disadvantaged groups.”

Narratives of retirement are shaped by intersecting factors such as class, ethnicity, health, and migration status (Crenshaw, 1991; Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020). Zhu (2016) illustrates how cultural and ethnic diversity influences how later life is interpreted, including how retirement is narrated, postponed, or resisted. These differences challenge the universality of retirement scripts and highlight the need for more inclusive and culturally responsive support frameworks (Phoenix, Smith, and Sparkes, 2010).

Understanding retirement as a culturally mediated and narratively constructed process shifts attention from fixed life stages to ongoing meaning making (Riessman, 2008). It invites greater sensitivity to identity, story, and emotion in later life transitions. This perspective informs the thesis’s methodological approach, which draws on NI to explore how women navigate, resist, and reframe dominant expectations of retirement. Where earlier critiques highlight structural inequalities in women’s retirement trajectories, a cultural perspective makes visible how stories of ageing are socially circulated and unevenly available. This distinction is central to the thesis, which uses NI to examine how women negotiate and resist these available scripts in practice.

These cultural narratives shape both personal stories and the design of retirement interventions, influencing what kinds of support are considered necessary or possible. Retirement interventions typically focus on four key domains: financial preparation, health promotion, social inclusion, and personal development, each addressing distinct but overlapping aspects of the TtR. Together, these domains provide a useful analytic framework, following Wang et al. (2011) and Baker et al. (2020), for understanding the scope and limitations of existing support. In the sections that follow,

I use this domain-based framework to critically examine current retirement interventions, highlighting how many continue to be shaped by narrow assumptions embedded in dominant narratives. A more inclusive, relational, and story-aware approach is needed, one that reflects the complexity of lived experience and broadens the possibilities for support, recognition, and resonance.

2.7 Financial Preparation and Economic Security

Financial security is fundamental to retirement readiness and greatly influences wellbeing in later life (Smeaton, 2016; Walsh, 2019). In the UK, retirement programmes often prioritise pension planning, budgeting skills, and access to financial advice (van den Hoonaard, 2015). While these are essential components, prevailing interventions frequently rest on assumptions of continuous, full-time employment and individual autonomy that do not fully capture the realities faced by many women (Cribb and Emmerson, 2020; Calasanti and Slevin, 2020).

Women's employment histories often involve fragmentation, with career breaks for childrearing or caregiving and employment in precarious or part-time roles, limiting pension accumulation and financial preparedness (Byles, 2013; Dionigi, 2015). These structural inequalities intersect with personal financial insecurity, producing complex emotional burdens, including anxiety, embarrassment, and uncertainty, that traditional financial literacy programmes inadequately address (Muratore, 2015; Henning, 2021; Cherry, 2023).

Financial literacy initiatives tend to adopt a rational actor model⁶, presuming individuals make informed, autonomous decisions (Zantinge, 2013; van Solinge, 2021). This framing overlooks relational and systemic factors shaping financial behaviour, such as household dynamics, cultural norms, and cumulative disadvantage. Consequently, many women face barriers in accumulating resources and confidently managing them within often challenging social contexts (Lusardi and Mitchell, 2014; Miller et al., 2015; Perry, 2017).

⁶ The *rational actor model* assumes individuals make decisions based on logical evaluation of available information, acting independently to maximise personal benefit. This model underpins many economic and behavioural theories but has been critiqued for overlooking how decisions are influenced by social relationships, cultural norms, emotions, and structural constraints (Zantinge, 2013; van Solinge, 2021).

Programmes that focus on individual responsibility risk reinforcing inequality by overlooking broader structural issues like the gender pay gap, caregiving penalties, and limited pension access (Smeaton, 2016; Foster and Heneghan, 2022). This deficit-focused approach can reinforce feelings of failure or inadequacy among women who struggle to meet these standards (Ahmed, 2010).

There is a growing call for financial interventions to integrate emotional support and relational awareness, fostering financial self-efficacy and resilience (Financial Planning Association, 2021; Rodríguez-Monforte et al., 2019). Co-designed, culturally sensitive programmes that acknowledge diverse employment trajectories and caregiving responsibilities hold promise for creating more equitable and effective financial preparedness support (Lusardi and Mitchell, 2014; Miller et al., 2015; Perry, 2017).

Understanding financial preparation as a deeply relational and emotional process aligns with critiques that call for moving beyond individualised models toward more holistic, context-sensitive frameworks (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Cribb and Emmerson, 2020). These perspectives emphasise the importance of designing retirement support that resonates with women's lived experiences and fosters wellbeing in later life.

2.8 Health Promotion and Physical Activity

Physical activity (PA) is widely recognised as a cornerstone of healthy ageing, with substantial evidence linking regular exercise to improved physical function, mental health, and quality of life among older adults (Bull et al., 2020; WHO, 2020). UK health policy promotes a healthy ageing agenda, framing PA as a key behaviour for achieving independence and reducing the burden on health and social care systems. Chief Medical Officers recommend at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity activity per week for adults over 65 (Department of Health and Social Care [DHSC], 2019).

However, such targets are rarely met. Only 15% of adults aged 65–74 achieve these levels, with participation rates dropping sharply among women over 75 (Health Survey for England, 2020).

Retirement is often framed within health promotion policy as a period when individuals can enhance wellbeing and PA due to increased discretionary time (Barnett et al.,

2012). Yet women's opportunities to do so are often constrained by continuing caregiving, financial strain, or health concerns that limit access to such initiatives (Wanka, 2020; Barker, Britton, and Windle, 2021). These intersecting factors illustrate how assumptions about time, freedom, and personal responsibility may not align with the lived realities of women in the TtR.

Public health and ageing policies often frame PA through a lens of individual responsibility and behavioural change, echoing neoliberal ideals⁷ of self-optimisation and productivity in later life (Calasanti and King, 2015; Foster and Walker, 2015). For example, the UK government's *Healthy Lives, Healthy People* strategy (HM Government, 2010) encourages older adults to stay active through structured programmes, yet these often fail to account for unequal access, cultural fit, or emotional readiness. The emphasis on lifestyle change and self-care can unintentionally blame those who cannot participate due to chronic illness, caring duties, or environmental barriers such as unsafe neighbourhoods or inadequate transport (Marmot Review, 2010; WHO, 2021).

Intersectional approaches, which examine how overlapping systems of identity and power such as gender, race, class, disability, and age, shape lived experience, are crucial for understanding the diverse barriers women face during the TtR (Crenshaw, 1991; Calasanti, 2020; Wanka, 2020). For example, migrant women may encounter language barriers, cultural discomfort in mixed-gender settings, or mistrust of public health institutions (Zhu, 2016; Williams et al., 2019). Disabled women may find that mainstream PA programmes are physically inaccessible, poorly adapted to their needs, or stigmatising (Barker, Britton, and Windle, 2021). Such dynamics are frequently overlooked in generalised policy targets and health promotion interventions, which often assume a universal retirement experience (Holstein and Minkler, 2007; Katz and Calasanti, 2015).

⁷ Neoliberalism refers here to a dominant policy orientation that emphasises individual responsibility, market-based solutions, and self-management, often at the expense of collective welfare or structural analysis. In ageing and health promotion, neoliberal logics typically frame successful ageing as a personal choice and moral obligation, positioning older adults as autonomous agents responsible for managing risk and optimising their own wellbeing (Katz, 2000; Ayo, 2012; Calasanti and King, 2015).

International comparisons offer instructive contrasts. In Sweden, for example, municipal level senior health coordinators support older adults in tailoring physical and social activities to their needs, acknowledging both relational and cultural dimensions (Trydegård, 2012). In Australia, the Active Ageing framework includes culturally specific programmes for Indigenous women and CALD (culturally and linguistically diverse) communities, recognising historical trauma and social marginalisation (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare [AIHW], 2021). These models suggest that embedded, localised, and co-designed programmes are more likely to engage diverse older women than standardised, behaviourist models.

Evidence supports socially embedded, peer-supported activities that focus on pleasure, flexibility, and inclusion rather than discipline or self-monitoring. Walking groups, dancing, water aerobics, and yoga classes that incorporate music, conversation, or cultural practices have demonstrated high uptake and retention, particularly when hosted in familiar, non-clinical settings (Gardner et al., 2017; Netz et al., 2019). The emotional and social rewards of such programmes including laughter, companionship, and shared identity may be more motivating than health outcomes alone (Taylor et al., 2015).

Some researchers advocate for narrative-based approaches to PA promotion, recognising that the ways in which women narrate their bodies, ageing, and movement significantly shape their willingness and capacity to engage. Dionigi (2015) and Phoenix and Tulle (2017) show that older women often describe PA as a meaningful practice that supports self-worth, independence, and connection, rather than as a duty or medicalised obligation. This narrative framing creates opportunities for designing interventions that acknowledge the symbolic, emotional, and identity related dimensions of movement, moving beyond a purely instrumental or behavioural health model.

Existing PA policies and interventions often reproduce narrow assumptions about ageing bodies and overlook the lived, relational, and emotional realities of women in the TtR (Calasanti and King, 2015; Phoenix and Tulle, 2017; Wanka, 2020). Despite increasing policy attention to PA in later life, frameworks such as the UK Chief Medical Officers' guidelines (DHSC, 2019) and the World Health Organisation's Global Action

Plan on Physical Activity (WHO, 2018) continue to emphasise behavioural change and individual responsibility, with limited attention to gender, cultural context, or emotional wellbeing. Effective support must be co-designed, culturally relevant, and responsive to story, identity, and care. This thesis builds on these critiques by exploring how women narrate PA within their retirement transitions and by developing interventions that embed PA within social and narrative support structures.

2.9 Social Inclusion and Relational Support

Social connection is a critical determinant of health and wellbeing in later life, with social isolation and loneliness linked to increased risks of depression, cognitive decline, and premature mortality (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015; Campaign to End Loneliness, 2022). These issues disproportionately affect older women due to intersecting factors including longer life expectancy, widowhood, caregiving responsibilities, and economic disadvantage (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Arber and Ginn, 2021; Foster and Heneghan, 2022). As women transition into retirement, the loss of routine workplace interactions can coincide with intensified care obligations or the dispersal of family and social networks creating conditions for social disconnection.

Although a range of community-based programmes exist such as friendship clubs, walking groups, or intergenerational activities, participation is shaped by accessibility, cultural relevance, and personal readiness. Research shows that women facing health challenges, income insecurity, or social stigma may feel alienated from formal support schemes (Bjornsdottir, 2012; Wanka, 2020). These women are often the least likely to be reached by mainstream initiatives, despite being most at risk of loneliness (Goll et al., 2015).

Recent research has shown that barriers to social inclusion are often psychosocial and narrative, shaped by emotional vulnerability, identity negotiation, and cultural discomfort (Goll et al., 2015; McPhillips, 2023; Victor and Bowling, 2012). Fears of rejection, uncertainty about social roles, and perceived threats to identity are frequently cited as reasons older adults withdraw or hesitate to engage with new groups (Donovan et al., 2017; Goll et al., 2015). Among women from minoritised ethnic or cultural backgrounds, discomfort may arise in predominantly white or middle-class

spaces, or in activities that do not reflect their cultural or spiritual values (Zhu, 2016; Williams et al., 2019). These findings highlight the need for inclusive, culturally grounded interventions that build trust and reflect the diversity of later life experiences.

Government strategies often frame loneliness as a public health challenge. For instance, the UK Government's Loneliness Strategy (Department for Digital, Culture, Media, and Sport, 2018) promotes social prescribing and community infrastructure, but critics argue it places too much emphasis on individual behaviour and not enough on structural inequalities that limit access and participation (Mahoney and Roberts, 2021). Similarly, the WHO's Decade of Healthy Ageing 2021–2030 prioritises social inclusion, but implementation often lacks gender-sensitive and intersectional specificity (WHO, 2020).

Relational approaches rooted in NI offer a more nuanced understanding of social participation. Rather than treating loneliness as a condition to be fixed, these approaches explore how women story their relationships, roles, and identities during the TtR. Price and Nesteruk (2015) and McPhillips (2023) show that women's narratives often express ambivalence, grief, or resistance in relation to social expectations. For some, traditional forms of inclusion such as structured clubs or volunteering, may feel misaligned to their needs or past experiences. Informal, low-pressure environments that foster continuity, belonging, and shared meaning are often more effective (Muratore and Earl, 2014; Victor and Bowling, 2012).

Programmes that integrate storytelling, peer co-facilitation, and participatory design can help uncover unmet social needs and foster environments of recognition and resonance (Frank, 2010; Phoenix and Sparkes, 2009). When older women are actively involved in shaping interventions that reflect their lived realities, often marked by caregiving, migration, loss, or discrimination, social support becomes more meaningful, accessible, and empowering (Beresford, 2019; Greenhalgh et al., 2016; Sanders and Stappers, 2008). Such approaches also create space to resist normative ideals of ageing, allowing women to articulate complex emotions without embarrassment or having those emotions framed as signs of dysfunction (Calasanti and King, 2015; McPhillips, 2023).

Addressing social inclusion in retirement calls for a shift from service provision alone to approaches that are relational, intersectional, and narrative-aware (Calasanti and Slevin, 2020; Beresford, 2019). Such approaches recognise the emotional and social dimensions of later life and attend to how identity, care, and connection are negotiated through everyday experiences. This thesis adopts this perspective by exploring how women narrate connection and disconnection, and by designing interventions that prioritise continuity, recognition, and cultural relevance over standard measures of participation.

2.10 Information, Personal Development, and Lifelong Learning

The TtR is frequently framed as an opportunity for renewal and self-development, with lifelong learning and personal growth initiatives positioned as ways to maintain purpose, wellbeing, and cognitive health in later life (Gouthro, 2011; WHO, 2015). Access to meaningful learning opportunities can support identity reconstruction, expand social networks, and facilitate continued social participation during this period of life change (van den Hoonaard, 2015; Byles, 2013).

However, such programmes often remain marginal within broader retirement support strategies. Funding is frequently limited, delivery inconsistent, and access shaped by intersecting barriers including gender, income, health status, and caregiving responsibilities (Henning, 2021; Zantinge, 2013). Women in lower-income households, minoritised ethnic communities, or rural areas may encounter structural and cultural exclusion from adult education and development opportunities, particularly when programmes assume a narrow profile of the motivated retiree with time, autonomy, and confidence (Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020; Foster and Heneghan, 2022).

Even where such programmes are accessible, their design often reflects dominant cultural assumptions about ageing and productivity. Much like health promotion and financial planning interventions, they frequently emphasise self-improvement, goal-setting, and individual responsibility (Calasanti and King, 2015; Phoenix et al., 2010). This framing aligns with active ageing discourses that prioritise visible achievement and personal optimisation, but it risks excluding those navigating ambivalence, fatigue, grief, or shifting priorities in later life (Ahmed, 2010; Price, 2020). The emotional and

narrative aspects of this transition are often overlooked, making these initiatives less relevant for women whose experiences differ from positive or self-directed ageing narratives.

Critiques from feminist gerontology and critical public health research highlight the significance of recognising later life as a period defined by productivity, as well as by opportunities for reflection, reorientation, and relational engagement (Calasanti, 2020; Holstein and Minkler, 2007). Within this perspective, personal development moves beyond self-improvement, focusing instead on the ongoing process of making sense of change on emotional, social, and narrative levels.

Scholarship on cognitive health adds further nuance to understandings of retirement and ageing. Ritchie et al. (2020) use the capability approach to examine employability among people with dementia, arguing that wellbeing in later life depends on maintaining opportunities for contribution and purpose. Their subsequent work (Ritchie, Lebec and Allen, 2025) highlights how early cognitive changes can precipitate withdrawal from employment, often before conventional retirement age. Such evidence challenges linear models of retirement and supports a relational view of ageing as shaped by health, identity, and structural context.

2.11 Narrative and Emotional Support Gaps

Narrative approaches to learning and transition support acknowledge that women may need space to grieve the loss of past roles, articulate uncertainty, and reconstruct identity through shared storytelling and peer exchange (Riessman, 2008; McPhillips, 2023). For example, storytelling groups, arts-based reflection sessions, or participatory journaling have been shown to support emotional processing and foster solidarity in later-life transitions (Henning, 2021; Dionigi, 2015).

Despite growing evidence of their value, narrative and emotionally resonant approaches remain largely absent from mainstream retirement programmes. Much of the existing literature focuses on small-scale, time-limited projects, often within health or community settings, and evidence of long-term impact is limited (Henning, 2021; Greenhalgh and Papoutsis, 2018). They can also be resource intensive, requiring skilled facilitation and sustained engagement, which makes integration into mainstream

provision challenging. Furthermore, while they prioritise voice and inclusion, critiques suggest that participatory initiatives may reproduce inequalities if not carefully designed (Beresford, 2019; Akama and Light, 2019). This thesis responds to such limitations by adapting narrative and co-design methods in ways that are sensitive to women's diverse retirement experiences and attentive to sustainability, inclusivity, and resonance.

At the same time, many interventions continue to prioritise structured, outcome-oriented activities such as digital literacy training, CV building, or volunteering preparation over participant-led reflection, relational support, or identity work (Henning, 2021; Calasanti and King, 2015; Greenhalgh et al., 2016). These externally defined goals can be poorly aligned with women's priorities during the TtR, leaving some participants feeling alienated or inadequately supported by initiatives that fail to reflect their lived realities (Price, 2020; Wanka, 2020).

Participatory models that engage women in co-designing learning and development opportunities offer a more equitable and resonant alternative (Sanders and Stappers, 2008; Beresford, 2019). Such programmes are grounded in women's own narratives, creating space for emotional expression, relational reflection, and culturally specific experience. In doing so, they move away from deficit framing toward a strengths-based ethos that honours diversity in how women experience and interpret later life (Beresford, 2019; Holstein and Minkler, 2007; Phoenix et al., 2010).

Although narrative identity theory and feminist gerontology have long highlighted the importance of meaning making and emotional work in later life, these dimensions are often neglected in mainstream retirement support frameworks (Riessman, 2008; Holstein and Minkler, 2007; Phoenix, 2013). Many interventions continue to prioritise measurable outcomes such as financial security, digital skills, or physical health over the relational and narrative processes through which women make sense of change, loss, and new possibilities (Henning, 2021; Price, 2020). The emotional labour of dealing with uncertainty, grief, or the ongoing demand of caregiving remains largely overlooked in formal retirement support programmes (Hochschild, 1983; Calasanti and Slevin, 2020). A narrative perspective highlights how such experiences are expressed in women's stories, offering insights that conventional frameworks miss. In reviewing this

gap, I found myself questioning how far existing interventions acknowledge the emotional labour women had already described in their stories during Phase One. These insights point to the need for conceptual frameworks that recognise retirement as both structurally constrained and narratively negotiated, a gap addressed in the following section.

Where narrative or emotional support is included, it is often informal, emerging in side conversations or peer discussions rather than being intentionally built into programme design (Barker et al., 2021; Moore, 2022). This reflects a wider pattern in ageing and health policy, where emotional experience is treated as private or secondary rather than as central to navigating later-life transitions. Failing to embed emotional and relational dimensions into formal support reinforces models of retirement that emphasise autonomy and self-management while overlooking the complexity of women's experiences at this stage of life (Formosa, 2012; Lain and Vickerstaff, 2020).

Evidence from narrative research suggests that structured opportunities for storytelling, group reflection, and co-created dialogue can support emotional processing, foster social connection, and help women articulate new meanings in retirement (Henning, 2021; Phoenix and Tulle, 2017; Frank, 2010). These approaches recognise that expressing emotion is a key part of how people think, make decisions, and adapt to change. When women are supported in telling complex, even contradictory stories, they can take ownership over how their transitions are understood, represented, and supported in practice.

2.12 Co-Production and Participatory Approaches

Participatory design approaches offer a practical way to embed narrative and emotional support within retirement interventions. Co-design methodologies create space for shared reflection and for women to shape the language, format, and ethos of support in ways that feel relevant and affirming (Sanders and Stappers, 2008; Beresford, 2019; Akama and Light, 2019). Rather than framing grief or ambivalence as problems to be solved, these methods recognise them as valid aspects of the retirement process, fostering more responsive, inclusive, and sustainable forms of support. While participatory and co-production approaches share a commitment to collaboration, this

study distinguishes between them. Participatory design guided the creative, exploratory aspects of the workshops, whereas co-production referred to shared decision making and mutual ownership of the research process (see **Chapter Three, Section 3.5**).

These participatory principles also align with Human-Centred Design, which emphasises iterative engagement with users' experiences, meanings, and contexts in the development of interventions.

While widely celebrated for their inclusivity and responsiveness, participatory approaches can be uneven in practice, with outcomes dependent on facilitation quality and participant dynamics (Beresford, 2019; Akama and Light, 2019). Questions also remain about scalability and sustainability, as many co-design projects are small-scale and time-limited (Greenhalgh and Papoutsis, 2018). Others caution that participatory methods can unintentionally reproduce inequalities if power relations are not explicitly addressed (Cornwall, 2008; Beresford, 2019). These limitations underline the need for continued adaptation. This thesis builds on those debates by using participatory design as both a methodological commitment and a site of experimentation, exploring how such approaches might be reconfigured to better support women during the TtR.

The neglect of narrative and emotional dimensions in retirement support is not only a theoretical concern but also a structural and cultural one. This thesis places narrative methods and emotional resonance at the centre of its research design, extending participatory traditions (Riessman, 2008; Sanders and Stappers, 2008). Through story-based, co-created approaches, it explores how support during the TtR can be reimagined to reflect the experiences, needs, and values of women in later life. These considerations connect directly with wider debates on co-production, outlined below.

Co-production has become an influential concept across health, social care, and ageing research, emphasising the active involvement of those most affected in shaping policies, services, and interventions (Beresford, 2019; Needham and Carr, 2009). It challenges top-down models by advocating collaboration, mutual learning, and the redistribution of expertise between professionals and participants. Within ageing and retirement studies, co-production is often framed as a means of ensuring relevance, legitimacy, and responsiveness in support provision (Greenhalgh et al., 2016; Cornwall, 2008).

While co-production is often celebrated for its inclusivity, researchers caution that its application can be uneven. Some initiatives involve participants in a consultative capacity without substantial influence over outcomes, while others struggle to maintain engagement beyond short-term projects (Farr, 2018; Oliver et al., 2019). Questions of power, representation, and scalability remain central in ageing research, where structural inequalities shape whose voices are heard and valued (Needham, 2021; Renedo and Marston, 2015). These debates highlight both the promise and fragility of co-production, emphasising the need to adapt participatory approaches with sensitivity to context.

Nevertheless, evidence suggests that when carefully implemented, co-production can foster ownership, trust, and meaningful outcomes by embedding participants lived experiences at the centre of design and delivery (Beresford, 2019; Greenhalgh et al., 2016). For women navigating the TtR, co-produced approaches hold value by creating space for the emotional and narrative dimensions of later life that standardised programmes often neglect. This thesis draws on such insights by treating co-production as both a methodological commitment and a theoretical stance. It acknowledges the opportunities and limitations of co-production while exploring how story-based and participatory methods might be adapted to support women's diverse and complex retirement transitions. Alongside co-production, Human-Centred Design has become another important approach shaping research and practice in ageing.

2.13 Human Centred Design

Human-Centred Design (HCD) has gained prominence in health, ageing, and social care research as a way of involving those most affected in shaping services and interventions. IDEO (2015, p. 9) defines HCD as “a creative approach to problem-solving that starts with the people you’re designing for and ends with new solutions that are tailor-made to suit their needs.” In academic terms, Sanders and Stappers (2012) describe HCD as a process that empowers people to inform, shape, and make design outcomes in collaboration with designers. Within ageing research, HCD is valued for its capacity to surface tacit knowledge, foster imaginative engagement, and generate contextually relevant forms of support (Bazzano et al., 2017). These features make it a

potentially useful framework for engaging with the complexity of retirement, where conventional interventions often fail to capture the nuances of lived experience.

Despite these strengths, HCD has also attracted critique. Some argue that it is sometimes reduced to a set of techniques or a “toolkit,” detached from the relational and political commitments needed for meaningful change (Bazzano et al., 2017; Robertson and Simonsen, 2012). Others point to risks of superficial inclusion, where participation is invited but decision-making power remains unevenly distributed (Domecq et al., 2014; Light and Akama, 2014). Questions have also been raised about scalability and sustainability, as many HCD projects operate on a small scale and struggle to embed long-term change in complex social systems (Greenhalgh et al., 2016; Jégou and Manzini, 2008).

In the context of the TtR, HCD offers both opportunities and challenges. Its emphasis on empathy and collaboration aligns with the need for retirement interventions that reflect diverse experiences and priorities. Yet its limitations emphasise the importance of applying participatory and narrative approaches with sensitivity to context, inclusivity, and sustainability. This thesis builds on those insights by situating HCD alongside co-production and NI, using it as a conceptual and practical resource for reimagining support with women in retirement. While HCD offers valuable principles, its limitations highlight the importance of also considering how narrative and emotional dimensions are addressed, a focus of the following section.

2.14 Conceptual and Theoretical Gaps

Although retirement has been studied extensively, many theoretical models continue to reflect narrow or standardised assumptions about life transitions. Early frameworks such as role theory and stage-based models focus on identity loss, psychological adjustment, or planned withdrawal from paid work (Atchley, 1982; Wang and Shultz, 2010). Later developments, including continuity theory and resource-based models, highlight adaptation, self-efficacy, and the maintenance of stable routines (Atchley, 1999; Wang et al., 2011). These theories offer valuable starting points but tend to centre on individual-level change, often overlooking the broader social, emotional, and narrative contexts in which retirement takes place.

One key limitation of these models is their focus on consistency and control. For example, continuity theory assumes that people seek to maintain familiar roles and patterns into later life. Likewise, behavioural and resource-based models often suggest that successful retirement depends on preparation, resilience, and adaptability. These ideas align with broader discourses of self-reliance and health promotion, but they do not always account for the structural inequalities that shape how retirement is experienced (Walker, 2002; Foster and Walker, 2015).

A related issue is the tendency of mainstream theory to treat emotion as secondary. While psychological models may acknowledge stress or wellbeing as variables, they rarely explore how emotions function within the lived experience of transition. This is particularly significant for women, whose retirement journeys may involve emotional work related to loss, identity shifts, or relational change (Henning, 2021; McPhillips, 2023).

Another gap concerns the role of meaning making. Despite the growing influence of narrative research in health and education, retirement theory still tends to rely on quantitative measures of success such as income, activity levels, or psychological adjustment, rather than exploring how people make sense of this life stage. Yet research shows that storytelling is central to how individuals process change, negotiate identity, and build connection with others (Riessman, 2008; Frank, 2010; Phoenix, 2013). These processes are not just expressive; they are formative. They shape how retirement is lived, shared, and supported. Overlooking this aspect limits the capacity of interventions to meet people where they are and to reflect the values and challenges that matter most to them.

In recent years, a growing body of research has called for more relational, narrative, and context-sensitive approaches to later life. This includes work in critical gerontology (Calasanti and King, 2020; Grenier et al., 2022), participatory health research (Greenhalgh et al., 2016; Bissell et al., 2021), and adult education (Milana and Webb, 2018). This growing body of work signals a shift away from standardised, behaviour-focused models and toward approaches that recognise the complexity of later life (Formosa, 2012; Phoenix et al., 2010). By framing retirement as a process shaped by emotion, social context, and narrative meaning making, these perspectives help

explain why many current interventions fail to resonate with those they aim to support (Henning, 2021; Greenhalgh et al., 2016). This thesis contributes to that shift by drawing on research traditions that attend to story, reflection, and relational context, and by exploring how these elements can inform more relevant and acceptable forms of support for women in the TtR.

International examples support this shift. In Canada, initiatives such as the AGE-WELL programme and participatory ageing labs have tested co-designed interventions that reflect local contexts and older adults lived expertise (Chaudhury et al., 2021). In Australia, place-based programmes for older women from culturally and linguistically diverse backgrounds have embedded storytelling into service design to improve accessibility and relevance (AIHW, 2021). These developments suggest that it is possible and necessary to move beyond deficit-oriented models and instead build supports that reflect social connection, cultural meaning, and emotional reality.

Despite these innovations, gaps remain. Few theoretical models offer a framework for understanding retirement as a narrative process shaped by social structures, cultural expectations, and emotional complexity. Terms such as ‘successful ageing’ and ‘healthy retirement’ continue to dominate policy discourse, often linked to individual responsibility and performance (Katz and Calasanti, 2015; Foster and Heneghan, 2022). These framings may marginalise or render invisible those who experience retirement as constrained by structural factors, emotionally disorienting, or unresolved in terms of identity, purpose, or financial security (Grenier, 2012; Wanka, 2019). As a result, support programmes may feel irrelevant or alienating to the people they are intended to serve (Barker et al., 2021; Wanka, 2020).

More than twenty years on, Walker’s (2002) critique remains highly relevant. Many of the concerns he raised (particularly the failure to address structural inequality and the marginalisation of social and emotional dimensions) continue to shape the design of contemporary retirement models and interventions. His work highlighted the risk of reducing later life to individual behaviour change and the need to embed ageing policy within broader frameworks of social justice and lived experience.

This thesis responds to these gaps by exploring how women describe and interpret their experiences of the TtR and by examining how co-created, story-based methods can be used to develop and reflect on potential support options. Rather than imposing external categories, the research begins with the stories women choose to tell, which include contradiction, emotion, care, and resistance. Retirement is treated as an evolving process, understood through shared language, reflection, and connection, rather than as a fixed event or standardised outcome. In doing so, the study addresses what is missing in conventional theory and establishes a foundation for designing more inclusive and meaningful forms of support. **Table 2** summarises the key assumptions in dominant retirement models, the critiques discussed throughout this chapter, and the ways in which the thesis responds conceptually and methodologically.

Table 2: Critiquing Retirement Models and Positioning the Thesis

Model or Assumption	Critique (from literature)	This Thesis Responds By...
Retirement as a linear stage of life	Overlooks variation, emotion, and discontinuity (Wanka, 2020; Grenier, 2012)	Treats TtR as a meaning making process shaped by story and social context
Behavioural/individual focus	Neglects social structures and emotional needs (Walker, 2002; Henning, 2021)	Uses narrative inquiry and co-design to centre lived experience
Successful ageing and productivity narratives	Reinforce exclusion and unrealistic ideals (Katz and Calasanti, 2015; Price, 2020)	Engages with ambivalence, contradiction, and relational priorities
Standardised support interventions	Often feel irrelevant or misaligned (Greenhalgh et al., 2016; Dionigi, 2015)	Co-develops support options grounded in story, emotion, and collaboration

Viewed collectively, these theoretical, cultural, and methodological gaps highlight the need for an integrated approach that addresses structural inequalities while recognising the relational, emotional, and narrative dimensions of retirement. This forms the foundation for the present study, which is guided by the following research questions, aims, and objectives.

2.15 Research Questions, Aims, and Objectives

Building on the critical review presented in this chapter, this thesis is guided by the following research questions:

- 1. How do women narrate their expectations and experiences during the TtR?**

2. **What types of support feel helpful, acceptable, or misaligned to women at this stage of life?**
3. **How can creative narrative methods (like story completion and co-design) be used to explore and test interventions?**

These questions respond directly to the limitations identified across the retirement literature. Much of the existing research focuses on behavioural outcomes, psychological adjustment, or resource-based models, often overlooking the emotional and relational complexity that shapes how retirement is experienced. This study takes a different approach, beginning with women's own accounts and placing value on the stories they tell about this transition. The research questions are designed to explore what matters to women and to examine how support can be reimagined through participatory and story-based methods.

Thesis Aims

- To explore how women understand and navigate the TtR, with attention to its social, emotional, and narrative dimensions.
- To co-design potential support options with women using participatory, human-centred methods⁸.
- To test the narrative functionality and emotional relevance of these support prototypes through story-based approaches.

Thesis Objectives (by research phase)

- **Phase One:** Explore retirement narratives through early story data (interviews and a workshop), with attention to emotional themes, relational dynamics, and identity work.
- **Phase Two:** Co-design prototype interventions that reflect women's expressed needs, priorities, and constraints.

⁸ Human-centred methods focus on designing support, services, or interventions in collaboration with the people who will use them. Rooted in design research, these approaches emphasise empathy, contextual understanding, and iterative development based on lived experience (IDEO, 2015; Sanders and Stappers, 2008).

- **Phase Three:** Test the resonance and relevance of these prototypes using story completion activities, analysing responses to assess potential acceptability, meaning, and application.

These aims and objectives reflect a broader commitment to developing support for the TtR that is responsive, meaningful, and grounded in the lived experiences of women. They also reflect a methodological interest in how story and collaboration can be used to generate insight and to shape more relevant forms of support.

These three phases form the foundation of the study's overall design: exploring existing narratives (Phase One), co-designing support ideas with women (Phase Two), and examining their resonance through story completion methods (Phase Three). This layered structure reflects a commitment to understanding and addressing the TtR through reflection, collaboration, and imaginative engagement, and it is elaborated in the methodological discussion that follows in Chapter Three.

2.16 Transition to Chapter Three

This chapter has reviewed how women's retirement transitions are framed in research, policy, and practice, highlighting the limitations of dominant models and the gaps around emotional, relational, and narrative dimensions. It has also examined the potential contributions and limitations of participatory approaches, including co-production and HCD, alongside the need for narrative perspectives that attend to meaning, emotion, and identity. Collectively, these insights point to the need for approaches that are more context-sensitive, inclusive, and responsive to women's diverse experiences. The next chapter outlines the methodological design of the thesis, explaining how NI, co-production, and participatory approaches were applied to explore these issues in practice.

As I worked through the literature, I became aware of a clear disconnect between dominant frameworks and the stories I was already beginning to hear in early data. This gap felt theoretical, but also emotional and practical. Reading debates on narrative identity, emotion, co-production, and HCD made me realise how often retirement models fail to reflect women's lived realities. These insights led me to centre narrative methods and participatory design in the study. **Chapter Three** develops this by setting

out the methodological design and showing how these approaches were applied in practice.

Chapter Three: Methodology - Narrative, Co-Production, and Design Approaches

3.0 Introduction: Producing Situated Knowledge Through Narrative and Design

As discussed in **Chapter Two**, dominant approaches to retirement often privilege measurement, prediction, and generalisation, reducing retirement to a discrete event (Atchley, 1976; Beehr, 1986; Wang, Henkens, and van Solinge, 2011). Such models tend to assume stable employment and financial independence, overlooking the diverse, storied ways women navigate the TtR (Price, 2000; Moen and Sweet, 2004; Calasanti, 2007). These framings risk enacting epistemic injustice (Fricker, 2007; Carel and Kidd, 2014) by silencing experiences shaped by interrupted careers, caregiving responsibilities, or precarity.

This chapter responds to those gaps by outlining the methodological foundations of the study. Narrative Inquiry (NI) provides a way of exploring how retirement is narrated and understood, while co-production establishes a collaborative ethos for designing and exploring support. Human-Centred Design (HCD) is introduced as a nested set of practices within this co-productive orientation, offering practical tools for creative, participatory exploration. Dialogical Narrative Analysis (DNA) was applied across all three phases, with story completion (SC) introduced in Phase Three to examine the resonance of prototype ideas.

The chapter begins with my philosophical positioning, clarifying the ontological and epistemological commitments underpinning the study. It then outlines the methodological framework, including NI, co-production, and HCD, before turning to the analytic tools of DNA and SC. The design of each phase is described in detail, including recruitment procedures, participant demographics, and the rationale for key methodological decisions such as moving from in-person prototype exploration to SC. Ethical considerations, rigour, and reflexivity are then addressed to show how credibility and care were sustained. In this way, **Chapter Three** provides the foundation for the empirical chapters that follow.

3.1 Philosophical Commitments

Ontology and epistemology

I take a relativist ontological stance and a social constructionist epistemology. Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 110) describe relativism as the position where “realities are multiple, socially constructed, and mind-dependent.” Social constructionism builds on this by treating knowledge as actively produced through language, culture, and interaction (Crotty, 1998; Burr, 2015). From this perspective, retirement can be understood as a socially constructed process, narrated and experienced in diverse ways depending on gender, class, work history, health, and cultural expectations. Mainstream retirement research often privileges measurable outcomes and normative ideals such as independence, planning, and productivity (Wang and Shi, 2014; Lain et al., 2019). Such framings risk enacting epistemic injustice by marginalising the voices of those whose lives do not align with these models. This includes many women whose retirement transitions are shaped by caregiving histories, interrupted employment, or precarious financial security (Foster and Heneghan, 2018). These concerns also resonate with feminist critiques of knowledge production, which have long highlighted how gendered power relations shape whose experiences are recognised as legitimate and whose are rendered marginal within research and policy frameworks that are often presented as neutral (Calasanti and Slevin, 2001; Harding, 1991). While this study does not adopt a feminist epistemological framework, feminist scholarship informs my attention to power, voice, and exclusion within dominant models of retirement research and policy.

A constructionist methodology therefore offers an alternative to mainstream outcome-driven paradigms by creating space for diverse stories, valuing contradiction and ambiguity, and legitimising forms of knowledge that are experiential, emotional, and relational (Riessman, 2008; Smith and Sparkes, 2009). Given that this study combines approaches rarely brought together in a single project (NI, DNA, co-production, HCD, and SC) it was important to document design decisions in detail. Transparency does not imply replicability in a conventional sense, but it provides a traceable account (Riessman, 2008; Tracy, 2010) that enables readers to see how methodological choices were made and to evaluate their coherence.

Humanist and experiential orientation

The study's constructionist and narrative methodology also reflects a humanist and experiential orientation, treating participants' stories as meaningful accounts of lived experience rather than data points to be abstracted (Bochner and Ellis, 2016; Smith and Sparkes, 2009). Humanist approaches emphasise respect for participants' perspectives and acknowledge the emotional and identity-related dimensions of retirement (Todres and Galvin, 2010a). An experiential orientation prioritises understanding how retirement is felt and narrated, ensuring that the study remains grounded in lived realities while exploring possibilities for practice.

Narrative inquiry, co-production, and human-centred design

Within this philosophical foundation, I use NI as the overarching methodological frame. NI treats stories as dynamic acts of meaning-making, shaped by cultural resources and social interaction rather than as containers of fact (Riessman, 2008; Frank, 2010). This orientation supports exploration of how women articulate retirement transitions in ways that reveal identity, emotion, and social positioning. To align inquiry with practice, I also adopt a co-production ethos, treating participants as collaborators in shaping knowledge and potential support options. Co-production extends constructionist commitments by embedding collaboration into the research process, resisting extractive modes of knowledge production, and valuing diverse contributions as legitimate forms of expertise (Beresford, 2019). Within this co-productive orientation, HCD operates as an integrated component rather than as an independent methodology. Its design practices, including persona building, values mapping, and speculative scenario work, offer structured approaches for supporting creative, participatory exploration (Sanders and Stappers, 2012; Bazzano et al. 2017; Light and Akama, 2019). These practices were used to open up possibilities rather than impose solutions, supporting participants to imagine, critique, and refine what retirement support might feel like in their own terms.

NI and co-production constitute the primary methodological framework of the study, with HCD serving as a set of practices that enact co-creative inquiry. This methodological combination reflects my commitment to producing knowledge that is

situated, dialogical, and relevant to practice, while also addressing the epistemic limitations of dominant paradigms. Each of these methodological approaches will be discussed in greater depth throughout the remainder of this chapter.

3.2 Narrative Inquiry (NI)

NI begins from the premise that humans make sense of experience through stories. Clandinin and Connelly (2000, p. 20) describe it as “the study of experience as story,” where stories are seen as the fundamental way people organise and communicate their lives. Stories are more than accounts of what happened; they are acts of meaning-making that draw on cultural resources, respond to audiences, and position narrators in relation to wider social narratives (Bamberg, 2004; Smith and McGannon, 2018). In this study, I use the term narrative positioning to refer to how participants located themselves and others within cultural storylines about retirement, ageing, and identity. This analytic lens informed interpretation across all phases of the research. Narrative approaches have also been used extensively in ageing research to explore how people construct and communicate their experiences of later life transitions (Marshall and Katz, 2018).

In practice, I applied NI across all three phases of the research. In Phase One (**Chapter Four**), it guided the generation of rich personal accounts through interviews and workshop discussion. In Phase Two (**Chapter Five**), it shaped the development of composite stories and framings, which became tools for collaborative design. In Phase Three (**Chapter Six**), NI principles underpinned the use of SC, where participants’ imaginative responses created new narrative material for analysis. Across these phases, NI supported a dialogical understanding of stories as always in conversation with other stories, both personal and cultural (Frank, 2012). Using NI in this way allowed me to treat participants as narrators and interpreters of their own transitions, rather than as data sources (Chase, 2011). This orientation resonates with the study’s co-productive commitments, positioning stories as co-constructed and recognising participants’ expertise in shaping inquiry and intervention design. This narrative orientation also aligns with feminist research traditions that prioritise voice, lived experience, and the social contexts through which stories are produced and interpreted

(Harding, 1991; Haraway, 1988), particularly in relation to recognising participants as knowledge holders rather than research subjects.

3.3 Co-Production

Co-production refers to research processes in which participants and researchers share responsibility for generating knowledge. In ageing research, co-production has been used to promote meaningful collaboration with older adults and challenge traditional hierarchies of expertise (Beresford, 2019; Fudge et al., 2008; Greenhalgh et al., 2019). According to Beresford (2019, p. 67), co-production involves “collaborative relationships that aim to value various forms of knowledge and minimise hierarchical distinctions.” In this study, the term is used to describe both a guiding approach and a collection of practices. The word "participants" is used when describing women who took part in Phase One interviews and Phase Three SC activities, while "co-producers" refers to those involved in workshops during Phases One and Two to indicate the collaborative nature of these sessions. Participants were considered co-producers, with their lived experiences recognised as contributing expertise and their input influencing both the knowledge produced and the direction of the research.

Co-production is often discussed alongside related concepts such as co-design and co-creation. While these terms are sometimes used interchangeably, I treat them as connected but distinct. *Co-production* is the broadest orientation, emphasising shared decision-making, reciprocity, and redistribution of power in research (Greenhalgh et al., 2019). *Co-design* refers to collaborative processes of developing interventions or services, often drawing on design-led methods to support creative exploration (Akama and Light, 2019). *Co-creation* highlights joint knowledge-building that extends beyond specific outputs and may include cultural or relational change (Palmer et al., 2019). This project drew on elements of all three, but I use co-production as the overarching term because it most clearly reflects my methodological stance and commitment to collaboration across all phases.

In practice, co-production shaped the study at multiple levels. Participants and co-producers contributed to data generation, to the development of typologies in Phase One, to the construction of framings in Phase Two, and to the creation and critique of

prototypes. Across the study, workshops (Workshop One in Phase One; Workshops Two and Three in Phase Two) were structured to encourage discussion, critical reflection, and imaginative thinking, consistent with the co-production ethos underpinning the research. Activities were designed to enable participants to shape both the process and the outcomes, and this ethos also guided my analytic decisions, where interpretations were regarded as provisional until tested through collaborative dialogue. The distinctions between co-production, co-design, and co-creation as they apply in this study are summarised in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Relationship between Co-Production, Co-Design, and Co-Creation

Term	Focus	Emphasis in this study	Key References
Co-production	Shared responsibility for knowledge-making and decision-making	Overarching ethos guiding all phases	Beresford (2019); Greenhalgh et al. (2019)
Co-design	Collaborative development of interventions and services	Workshop activities: framings, prototypes	Akama and Light (2019)
Co-creation	Joint knowledge-building beyond outputs, often cultural/relational	Emerged through composite narratives and shared reflections	Palmer et al. (2019)

Co-production provided a methodological and ethical orientation aligned with my constructionist stance and the principles of NI. Within this frame, participants were positioned as narrators and co-producers rather than subjects, and HCD offered a set of practices for facilitating collaboration (outlined in **Section 3.4** and revisited in **Chapter Five**).

3.4 Human-Centred Design and Design Thinking Framework

HCD refers to design approaches that prioritise the needs, values, and perspectives of the people most affected by an intervention. Sanders and Stappers (2012, p. 22) describe it as “a process that starts with the people you are designing for and ends with new solutions that are tailor-made to suit their needs.” In this study, I use HCD as a set of practical methods nested within co-production, rather than as a standalone

methodology. Its value lies in providing tools for creative, participatory exploration, consistent with my constructionist stance and co-productive ethos.

HCD encompasses a broad range of practices that help participants articulate and explore possibilities (IDEO, 2015). In this study, these included persona building, values mapping, speculative scenarios, and the use of visual prompts (see **Appendix J-L**).

Such activities supported co-producers to express concerns and aspirations in ways that moved beyond individual stories and opened collective imagining. As Bazzano et al. (2017) argue, HCD offers structured, yet flexible means of eliciting lived experience and translating it into design possibilities, while Light and Akama (2019) emphasise its potential to redistribute design authority by foregrounding relational and situated knowledge. Similarly, research on cognitive health and employability (Ritchie, Egdell and Tolson, 2020) demonstrates how design and participation frameworks can uphold identity and purpose when people experience cognitive or social change, reinforcing the value of inclusive, relational approaches to design.

My use of HCD was informed by IDEO's (2015) Hear–Create–Deliver framework, which I treated as a starting point rather than a prescriptive template⁹. Rather than applying it in a linear way, I reinterpreted *Hear* as listening to stories within wider cultural narratives, *Create* as collaborative imagining through framings, composites, and prototyping, and *Deliver* as exploring resonance through SC. Embedding HCD within co-production ensured it was not treated as a technical fix or a means of extracting participant ideas. Instead, it offered a structured yet flexible process for collaborative inquiry. This acted as a bridge between NI and design practice, translating stories into prototype ideas while keeping participants' voices central.

While HCD offered clear methodological benefits, its use also required careful reflexive handling. One strength of HCD in this study was its capacity to support collective sense-making and imaginative exploration, a function widely associated with human-centred and participatory design approaches that emphasise iterative, user-led problem framing and prototyping (Sanders and Stappers, 2012; Brown, 2009; Bazzano

⁹ Prior to this study, I completed a three-month design thinking course with IDEO.org, which provided practical grounding in the methods later adapted for the research (see **Appendix T** for certification).

et al., 2017), particularly at points where participants were invited to move beyond reflecting on past experience and towards articulating possible futures. Design activities created shared reference points that surfaced tacit assumptions, emotional responses, and practical concerns, enabling participants to engage with abstract ideas in concrete ways. This was especially valuable in the co-design workshops, where HCD tools helped bridge narrative insight and intervention development without reducing participants' accounts to predefined categories or outcomes.

At the same time, HCD carries limitations that are important to acknowledge. Design-oriented practices can implicitly privilege solution-building, progress, or innovation, which risks narrowing discussion and constraining more ambivalent, resistant, or unresolved narratives. In a study focused on transition, uncertainty, and negotiation, there was a risk that design activities could create pressure to move towards clarity or resolution prematurely. To mitigate this, HCD was used lightly and flexibly, with participants encouraged to adapt, resist, or reinterpret activities rather than complete them as intended. Emphasis was placed on dialogue and reflection rather than on producing polished design outputs.

This experience suggests that HCD is most appropriate in qualitative and participatory research when it is positioned as a set of supportive practices rather than a prescriptive framework. Its strengths lie in enabling collaborative imagination, supporting translation between narrative data and intervention concepts, and creating artefacts that can travel across research phases. However, its use requires attentiveness to power dynamics, pacing, and emotional labour, particularly when working with groups navigating complex life transitions. Future studies adopting HCD within narrative or co-produced designs should prioritise flexibility, reflexivity, and participant-led adaptation to ensure that creative practices remain aligned with interpretive and relational research commitments.

Used reflexively, HCD functioned as a method for generating and translating narrative knowledge rather than producing design outputs alone, supporting the study's wider aim of making women's retirement experiences visible within intervention development processes. In this sense, the use of HCD aligns with feminist qualitative traditions that

emphasise relational knowledge production, attentiveness to power, and the value of lived and embodied experience as sources of expertise (Haraway, 1988; Fullagar, 2017b). In this study, HCD practices supported participants to articulate meanings and possibilities in their own terms, rather than positioning design as a process of extracting user insight for pre-defined solutions. This was particularly important in a study concerned with gendered life-course experience, where design processes risk reproducing dominant assumptions about whose knowledge counts unless used reflexively.

3.4.1 Framings, Composites, and Prototyping in Narrative Design

Adapting HCD for this study required introducing methodological concepts less familiar in social science research, namely framings, composite characters, and prototyping. These tools helped to translate narrative insights into collaborative design activities and to keep the process accountable to participants' experiences.

Framings, derived from Phase One typologies (see **Chapter Four**), are design devices that shape how a problem is approached by highlighting certain perspectives while leaving others in the background (Dorst, 2015). In narrative terms, a framing functions like a lens: it makes particular values, constraints, or possibilities more visible (Dorst, 2015; Schön, 1983). In Phase Two workshops, framings provided structured entry points for collaborative discussion, enabling participants to situate themselves in relation to different ways of seeing retirement and to test how potential support might resonate.

Composite characters, developed in Phase Two (see **Chapter Five**), drew together elements from multiple narratives into a single, situated figure. Rather than representing any one participant, they offered composite representations of recurring themes, dilemmas, or identities (Carless and Douglas, 2013). Composites allowed participants to engage imaginatively with recognisable yet non-identifiable figures during co-design, providing a safe way to surface tensions and possibilities while maintaining confidentiality and preserving the richness of lived accounts.

Prototyping, also developed in Phase Two (see **Chapter Five**), involved creating preliminary versions of an idea to explore how it might work in practice (Brown, 2009). In

this study, prototypes were narrative and conceptual rather than technical. Three were produced, each embodying insights generated through earlier phases. Prototyping served as a way of exploring ideas with participants and as a means for imagining how support could be experienced in everyday life. Collectively, the framings, composites, and prototyping demonstrate how NI was translated into design practice. Their application in the co-design workshops is elaborated in **Chapter Five**.

3.5 Dialogical Narrative Analysis (DNA)

DNA is not a prescriptive method but an orientation to studying stories in relation to other stories (Smith, 2016). It builds on the premise that stories are told in dialogue with other stories, cultural narratives, and audiences (Frank, 2010). This emphasis shifts attention from treating stories as factual records to understanding them as contextual performances, shaped through relationships and circumstances (Gubrium and Holstein, 2009; De Fina and Georgakopoulou, 2015).

Carless and Douglas (2013) extend this view by emphasising that stories describe lives while also actively participating in their ongoing construction. Bochner and Ellis (2016, p. 59) argue further that “stories are both the object and the method of inquiry, a way of knowing and a way of showing.” These perspectives align with DNA’s concern for what stories do as well as what they say, and for how meaning is produced through the act of telling (Frank, 2010; 2012). In this study, a story is understood as any act of meaning-making through which experience is temporally and emotionally organised (Bamberg and Georgakopoulou, 2008; Georgakopoulou, 2015). Whether conveyed through an extended account or a short narrative fragment, each story contributes to the dialogical field of how retirement is imagined, told, and shared (Phoenix and Sparkes, 2009).

In the early stages of the study, my approach was most strongly influenced by Frank’s (2010, 2012) articulation of DNA. As the study developed, I drew increasingly on exemplars from the field, including Smith and Sparkes (2009, 2012), Phoenix (2013, 2017), Caddick and Smith (2014), and Monforte (2018, 2020), who have demonstrated how DNA can be adapted to examine stories of identity, ageing, health, and transition. These works informed my attention to narrative resources, positioning, and resonance, and supported me in tailoring DNA to the context of women’s retirement. The analysis

presented in later chapters reflects a fusion of Frank's (2010;2012) principles with more recent applications of DNA.

The distinctiveness of DNA lies in the way it addresses both the *what* and the *how* of stories. The *whats* concern the kinds of narratives people draw on: what cultural resources are mobilised, what identities are claimed or resisted, what assumptions are reinforced or unsettled (Smith and Sparkes, 2009; Phoenix, 2013). The *hows* refer to the ways stories are told: their tone, rhythm, structure, contradictions, and silences, as well as the positioning of narrators in relation to audiences (Smith and Sparkes, 2012). These concerns distinguish DNA from approaches that emphasise classification and coding. Instead, DNA treats stories as dialogical and performative, always told in relation to other stories and to cultural contexts that make some forms of expression easier to tell than others (Frank, 2010; Phoenix, 2013).

The questions that guided my use of DNA included:

- **Circulation:** How do stories travel across contexts and phases of the study, and how do they shift when retold?
- **Resources:** What cultural, emotional, and relational resources do narrators draw upon in constructing their accounts?
- **Positioning:** How do narrators position themselves in relation to others, to cultural narratives, and to imagined audiences?
- **Identity work:** What versions of self are produced or resisted in the telling of stories?
- **Resonance:** How do stories connect with or challenge other stories in the study, and what possibilities for meaning or action emerge from these connections?

DNA shaped each phase of the research in distinct but connected ways. In Phase One it guided the analysis of interviews and workshop narratives that informed the construction of typologies that are presented in detail in **Chapter Four**. In Phase Two (**Chapter Five**), it supported the interpretation of stories generated through framings and prototype development, helping to surface the cultural tensions embedded in participants' accounts. In Phase Three (**Chapter Six**), DNA was applied to SC

responses to examine how participants tested and reshaped the prototype ideas, and to consider how participants engaged with and responded to the prototype ideas, particularly whether these ideas resonated with them or not. Resonance here refers to the extent to which a story or idea connects meaningfully with others (see **Chapter Seven** for fuller discussion).

As DNA is not a fixed procedure (Frank, 2012; Smith and Sparkes, 2009; Phoenix, 2013), transparency was particularly important. I documented interpretive decisions through analytic memos, reflexive journaling, and iterative discussions with supervisors, in line with wider calls for qualitative researchers to make analytic processes visible and accountable (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). Examples of how DNA questions were applied are presented in the relevant findings chapters, with further documentation provided in the appendices (see **Appendix N** for analytic memos and coding extracts).

3.5.1 Narrative Typologies as Analytic Devices

One analytic outcome of applying DNA in this study was the development of narrative typologies. Typologies are not intended to categorise individuals or to fix experience into static groups, but rather to illuminate patterned ways of narrating a life transition (Frank, 2010). Within this thesis, they function as analytic devices that condense complexity into recognisable story forms while remaining open to overlap, contradiction, and change (Frank, 2010; Smith and Sparkes, 2009; Phoenix, 2013).

Constructing typologies was an inductive process (Kluge, 2000; Joffe, 2012; Monforte, 2018) that served two purposes. First, it provided a way of making sense of recurring narrative positions identified in Phase One interviews, such as whether retirement was described as anticipated, resisted, or reimagined. Second, it created usable resources for subsequent phases of the research. In this way, typologies supported both analytic interpretation and practical design work, providing a foundation for developing design framings and composite characters in Phase Two. They also offered a basis for examining resonance and divergence in the imaginative responses generated through SC in Phase Three, while serving as a means of moving beyond individual accounts toward forms that could inform both understanding and practice. This approach also resonates with Sparkes and Smith's (2014) argument that qualitative representations

should be both rigorous and meaningful for their audiences. The typologies are presented in detail in **Chapter Four**, where their content and implications are explored through participants' stories.

3.6 Story Completion

Building on DNA's interpretive orientation, SC offered a creative way of generating new narrative material for this study. It is a qualitative method that invites participants to complete a story stem or prompt, generating short narratives in response. Braun and Clarke (2013, p. 15) describe SC as "a way of accessing participants' implicit assumptions, cultural meanings, and imaginative possibilities without directly asking them to account for themselves." Responses are fictional but culturally meaningful, offering insights into shared discourses, expectations, and possibilities. Its implementation is covered in **Chapter Six**.

SC can be adapted in different ways depending on the research purpose. Story stems may be written in the first person, encouraging autobiographical reflection, or in the third person, allowing for imaginative distance (Clarke et al. 2019). Instructions can invite participants to write freely, or to address specific prompts, with each choice shaping what kind of stories are produced. These design decisions highlight the flexibility of SC but also underline the importance of providing clear instructions and considering how participants will interpret the task (Gravett, 2019).

For this study, SC was selected because it aligned with my narrative and dialogical commitments. Rather than treating SC responses as insights into private thoughts or hidden truths, I approached them as cultural texts that could be read in relation to wider narratives of ageing, gender, and retirement. This stance also reflects the humanist orientation outlined in **Section 3.1**, as it respects participants' autonomy by enabling them to decide the degree of distance or personal resonance they wished to bring to the task (Todres and Galvin, 2010b). It also resonates with the tradition of Creative Analytical Practices¹⁰ (CAP), where writing is understood as both a method of inquiry and a mode of meaning-making (Richardson, 2000; Bochner and Ellis, 2016).

¹⁰ Creative Analytical Practices (CAP) is a term introduced by Richardson (2000) to describe qualitative writing forms that blur the boundaries between social science and literature, using creative strategies such as narrative, poetry, or layered accounts to evoke and analyse lived experience.

Finally, SC offered a practical alternative to in-person prototype trials, which were constrained by cost, time, and project disruptions. This orientation supported the exploration of how imagined scenarios might surface possibilities, tensions, and assumptions that could be missed in direct questioning. The following section outlines how SC was operationalised in this study as a prototyping apparatus for Phase Three.

3.6.1 Story Completion as prototyping Apparatus

The aim of this section is to explicate how the prototype ideas generated in Phase Two were translated into a SC activity, creating the methodological apparatus through which their resonance and functionality could be explored in Phase Three. This section therefore extends the methodological framework outlined earlier in this chapter by detailing how co-designed concepts were operationalised within a narrative research activity.

The objective is to provide a reflexive account of the process through which the prototypes were developed into fictional story stems, piloted, refined, and implemented as a qualitative activity. This includes the design choices, the pilot study, and the recruitment and implementation processes. In doing so, I show how this study makes an original contribution by using SC to test co-designed intervention ideas. While SC has been used in psychology, education, and health research to explore normative beliefs and cultural frameworks (Kitzinger and Powell, 1995; Braun et al., 2019; Gravett, 2019), to my knowledge it has not previously been applied in this way. This section therefore makes visible the methodological craft involved in shaping the apparatus for Phase Three and situates it within the liminal space between design and analysis.

The purpose of this section is to document the development of SC as a methodological apparatus, clarifying how it was adapted to carry the study from design into narrative exploration. It explains the rationale for using SC in this way and outlines the steps involved in shaping the activity.

The end of Phase Two marked a turning point in the research process. According to the IDEO (2015) Hear–Create–Deliver model, the next stage after generating ideas is to

prototype and trial them in practice. In principle, this would have involved developing low-cost versions of the three concepts and exploring their feasibility with women approaching retirement. Prototyping is intended to expose strengths and weaknesses early, so that ideas can be refined before significant resources are committed and before services are implemented in real-world contexts (Sanders and Stappers, 2014; Steen et al., 2011).

In practice, this was not possible. Time and resources were constrained, and several unforeseen disruptions, including a university cyber incident, a period of ill health, and extended research travel, had already affected the project's timeline and capacity. These issues and their implications for recruitment and scheduling are discussed in **Chapter Four (Sections 4.8–4.10)** and revisited in **Chapter Five (Section 5.4)**. As a result, in-person prototyping activities were no longer feasible within the available timeframe, and alternative approaches to exploring the concepts were required.

These concerns had particular weight in this study. The prototypes had emerged from a collaborative process, and to produce superficial versions would have risked diluting participants' ideas or signalling that their contributions were expendable. For me, this raised practical as well as ethical questions about the quality and integrity of the research relationship. Brinkmann (2014) reminds us that qualitative inquiry demands attentiveness and care, which would have been undermined by creating interventions simply to meet procedural expectations of prototyping.

For these reasons, I sought an alternative that would remain faithful to the principles of co-production while making purposeful use of the data already generated. At this point, I revisited the design principles underpinning the study. HCD, as described by IDEO (2015), emphasises iterative refinement that is responsive to users' needs and contexts and encourages innovative ways of implementing ideas when standard routes are impractical. Within this framework, SC offered a way forward as a means of extending the prototypes into a narrative mode that was resource-sensitive, ethically defensible, and creatively open. To make the activity accessible and manageable within the project's timeframe, the SC tasks were distributed online using Microsoft Forms. This

enabled participants to complete the activity at their convenience and supported wider geographical reach.

3.6.2 Story Completion as Apparatus

The use of SC in this study extended beyond its more familiar applications in psychology, education, or health research. Here, SC functioned as the apparatus through which the prototype ideas developed in Phase Two could be explored without requiring their premature implementation. There is little precedent for using SC in this way, and the absence of established models required me to devise an approach that was both methodologically rigorous and practically feasible.

This apparatus was shaped by two considerations. First, the ethical and resource-related constraints described earlier meant that physical prototyping risked being tokenistic or unviable. Producing scaled-down or low-budget versions of the prototypes would not have done justice to the co-design process and could have undermined participants' trust in the project. Second, the ethos of HCD emphasises creating processes that allow participants to engage meaningfully with ideas, rather than producing outputs for appearance's sake (IDEO, 2015; Sanders and Stappers, 2012). Translating prototypes into story stems allowed these principles to be honoured. It enabled participants to encounter the ideas narratively, to imagine how they might work in practice, and to respond in ways situated in their own cultural and social contexts.

Positioning SC in this way also drew on my commitments to NI and co-design. NI approaches stories as relational, temporal, and culturally embedded (Clandinin, 2013), while co-design positions participants as active collaborators in shaping ideas (Akama and Light, 2019; Greenhalgh et al., 2019). Combining these traditions, the point was less about what participants wrote as content, and more about *what their stories did*. From a dialogical perspective, stories are actions rather than mirrors, shaping and reshaping the social worlds in which they circulate (Frank, 2010; Riessman, 2008). From a social constructionist standpoint, this means stories are not treated as access points to hidden truths but as situated practices through which cultural meanings are negotiated and sustained (Burr, 2015). SC, used in this way, did not seek to reveal hidden personal truths but to illuminate the relational and cultural work performed

through storytelling. This understanding aligns with recent arguments that qualitative practices should be recognised for what they enact rather than reduced to technical procedure (St. Pierre, 2021; Brinkmann, 2014; St. Pierre, 2025).

Taking this stance also involved a degree of methodological risk. With no precedent for using SC to test co-designed interventions, I had to work with the uncertainty of whether the stems would be able to carry the prototypes into narrative form. This demanded reflexive judgement, balancing the limitations of not producing material prototypes against the opportunity to create an alternative that could still respect participants' earlier contributions (Schön, 1983). The decision to repurpose SC was therefore both pragmatic and principled, informed by the need to avoid tokenistic practices while still extending the design process.

The contribution of this approach lies in showing how SC can operate as a prototyping device within co-design research, rather than solely as a tool for exploring beliefs or discourses. Rather than producing scaled-down prototypes, the apparatus generated narratives that revealed how interventions might be lived, resisted, or reshaped. Conventional prototype trials would likely have revealed pragmatic feedback such as logistical barriers, costs, or scheduling concerns. As Beggan and McGannon (2025) argue, understanding how interventions are lived, rather than focusing only on outcomes, is key to evaluating whether they work at all. In this study, the SC approach enabled such insight by revealing relational dynamics, affective tensions, and the cultural meanings that underpin participation (see also Gravett, 2021). This distinction is important because whereas traditional trials focus on functionality and outcomes, SC illuminated the interpretive and emotional work that shapes whether an intervention feels viable or meaningful in practice.

This orientation also aligned with the study's broader narrative commitments. Rather than relying solely on spoken dialogue, it extended dialogical work into written stories that positioned characters in relation to cultural expectations, emotional risks, and possibilities. Frank (2012, p. 147) describes this as "moral storytelling," where stories do not simply recount events but grapple with questions of value, meaning, and responsibility. In the context of retirement, this enabled exploration of how support

might be desired, resisted, feared, or reimagined, and what such responses revealed about women's experiences of ageing, identity, and belonging.

In doing so, SC opened a distinctive liminal space between design and analysis. It was neither a physical prototype trial nor a conventional narrative interview, but a hybrid practice that moved the study into its final phase. This constitutes a novel methodological contribution, as there is little precedent for using SC in this way to extend co-designed prototypes through narrative means. For me, this positioning felt both uncomfortable and generative. It meant relinquishing the security of established procedures and taking responsibility for crafting something new. The advantage of this orientation was threefold. It was resource-sensitive, ethically responsible, and creatively expansive. It respected the contributions of participants to the co-design process while producing narratives that illuminated both the potential and the limitations of the prototypes. This resonates with the HCD Hear–Create–Deliver cycle (IDEO, 2015), in which design processes evolve iteratively through multiple modes of exploration.

3.6.3 From Prototypes to Story Stems

Translating the prototypes into SC required careful consideration of how to frame each scenario. The aim was to provide enough orientation to signal the intended intervention while leaving sufficient openness for participants to imagine how events might unfold (see Braun, Clarke, and Gray, 2019; Gravett, 2022). This balance was central to the design of the stems. Providing too much detail risked closing down possibilities. Too little could leave participants unsure of what was being asked.

The process was guided by principles of NI, where stories are understood as situated and dialogical rather than fixed representations (Clandinin, 2013). Story stems needed to cue certain contexts such as retirement, social transition, or participation in a new activity without dictating the characters' decisions or the outcomes. By keeping the stems open, participants could work with them in ways that reflected their own cultural knowledge, expectations, and concerns. This approach reflects Bamberg's (2004) argument that prompts inevitably position characters within particular worlds, shaping how participants take them up and extend them. More recent discussions by Braun and

Clarke (2019), Clarke et al. (2019), and Gravett (2019) emphasise that stem design directly influences the kinds of narrative resources participants mobilise, reinforcing the need for careful attention to wording and framing.

One of the more practical challenges in writing the stems was deciding whether to adopt the first or third person. As discussed in **Chapter Three (Section 3.6)**, SC literature generally recommends the third person because it reduces pressure on participants to disclose personal experience (Braun, Clarke, and Gray, 2019). To ensure this was the right choice for my study, I drafted two versions of the same scenario, one in each voice, and compared them. The third-person version created a clearer sense of distance, which aligned with existing guidance while also reflecting my concern to safeguard participants' sense of safety and freedom. Similar considerations are evident in creative and arts-based research, where perspective is understood to shape how people engage with imaginative tasks (Lenette, 2022). This exercise confirmed that the third person was the more suitable choice for the aims of this study.

Characters were given names, not initials or generic labels, to enhance their believability. The pseudonyms were chosen as personally meaningful, drawn from women who had influenced my life. My intention was for the characters to feel recognisable without being generic. I took particular care to avoid names that might carry ethnic or cultural connotations, in order to minimise the risk of participants associating the characters with specific backgrounds or stereotypes. In narrative research, such decisions matter because characters become figures through which identities and cultural expectations are negotiated (Smith and Sparkes, 2016). This reflexive attention to naming helped create characters who were open enough to invite multiple readings while remaining anchored in a personal ethic of care. Each of the three prototypes was therefore reimagined as a short, open-ended story stem. The following subsections describe the stems in turn, showing how the intervention concepts were translated into narrative prompts.

3.6.3.1 Retirement Cafe

The Retirement Café prototype emerged from participants' emphasis on connection, belonging, and informal support during the TtR. In the workshops, women spoke about

the value of spaces that were welcoming but not stigmatised, where they could meet peers, share experiences, and access information in a relaxed environment. They also highlighted the importance of tailored resources, such as health and wellbeing advice, budgeting support, cooking low-cost nutritious meals, and information on finance or benefit entitlement. The co-producers and I envisaged the café as a targeted outlet that could deliver age-appropriate information relevant to women in the TtR and early retirement, while also offering a social environment that felt inviting and adaptable to different needs.

For this stem, I named the central character Katie, drawing on influential women in my own life. This reflexive gesture grounded the scenario in lived experience while still leaving the character open for participants to project their own interpretations. The story stem for the Retirement Café read as follows:

Katie is approaching her retirement. She has mixed feelings about this and is not sure what she will do once she has retired. She saw an advertisement in her local newspaper for a retirement café. The retirement café is a social and information service that has been set up for women like Katie, who are retiring. Katie went along in her lunch hour and ...

The stem offered just enough contextual information to make the idea recognisable, with a woman approaching retirement and a local café as a dedicated space for social support and information. Yet the encounter was deliberately left open-ended. Previous work with SC emphasises the importance of providing sufficient orientation to avoid confusion while still leaving scope for multiple interpretations (Moller et al., 2021; Williams, Lozano-Sufrategui and Tomasone, 2021; Pong, Roberts and Lum, 2024). In practice, participants could imagine Katie's experience as positive, negative, or ambivalent, depending on their own orientations and expectations. For example, a participant aligned with a Traditional orientation might view the café as unnecessary or unfamiliar, whereas someone with a Corporate or Circumstantial orientation might imagine it as a resource for networking or practical support. The open ending was therefore central in enabling different meanings to emerge, illuminating how women envisaged social connection and what forms of information they considered valuable in their imagined futures.

3.6.3.2 Buddy Scheme

The Buddy Scheme prototype was developed in response to women’s concerns about confidence, belonging, and the challenge of entering unfamiliar spaces after retirement. In the workshops, participants described how friendships often revolved around work and could diminish once employment ended, leaving them uncertain about how to rebuild social networks. Many said they would feel more able to join new groups or activities if they had someone to accompany them at the outset. The Buddy Scheme was designed to address this issue: a structured but informal support mechanism where women could be matched with a companion who would join them for initial visits to local activities, helping them to integrate more easily. By reducing the anxiety of “going it alone,” the scheme aimed to increase the likelihood that women would engage with new opportunities and sustain participation.

For this stem, I named the central character June. Placing her in a new location was a deliberate design choice intended to reflect the sense of isolation that can accompany retirement when established routines and relationships fall away. The choice of name reflected a reflexive awareness of how personal and cultural reference points can shape story design. While I drew on names familiar from my own social world, they were selected for their ordinariness rather than specificity, allowing participants to interpret and extend the characters in their own ways (Smith and Sparkes, 2016; Gravett, 2022). The Buddy Scheme story stem read as follows:

June has decided that the time is right for her to retire and has given her notice at work. She has always wanted to live by the sea and is moving to the coast. She is unfamiliar with the area and doesn’t know anyone. She has looked online and has found a retirement buddy scheme operating near her new home which supports women in their retirement transition. She gives them a call and ...

The stem provided a clear scenario in which a woman had retired, relocated, and faced the challenge of starting over in an unfamiliar setting. Yet it left the outcome open-ended, allowing participants to imagine how June’s experience with the scheme might unfold. The aim was to balance contextual grounding with narrative openness, in line with SC guidance that prompts should orient but not over-direct responses (Braun et

al., 2019; Gravett, 2022; Pong, Roberts and Lum, 2024). This openness created space for different orientations to come through. For example, a Conventional orientation might imagine June relying on familiar social structures, while a Circumstantial orientation might see the scheme as essential to navigating precarity or vulnerability.

The Buddy Scheme stem was therefore designed to elicit stories about confidence, belonging, and support in unfamiliar social environment. It also invited participants to imagine whether they would use such a service and what they might expect from it. This conditional focus was important, as it encouraged participants to narrate initial impressions while also considering the commitments, resources, and reassurances that might be necessary for sustained participation. In doing so, the stem echoed co-design principles by enabling participants to articulate the conditions under which such a service could be meaningful in their retirement transitions.

3.6.3.3 Reimagining Physical Activity

The PA prototype stem was developed to explore how women imagined exercise opportunities that were relevant, appealing, and feasible during the TtR. In the workshops, co-producers spoke about barriers to PA, including cost, confidence, lack of tailored provision, and discomfort in mixed or age-diverse classes. They also highlighted the potential of PA as a way to sustain health, build confidence, and form friendships beyond the workplace. The stem was therefore designed to capture both the health-related and social dimensions of PA, while leaving space for participants to narrate what would make such provision meaningful to them.

The character in this stem was named Betty. She was imagined as someone who was three months away from retirement and motivated both to improve her health and to establish new social connections. The story stem for the PA prototype read as follows:

Betty is retiring in three months. She is determined to reduce her weight and care for her health better. She would also like to make new friendships away from her work environment. She has seen an advert for an exercise class for women in the transition to retirement. She decides to go along to the exercise class and ...

The stem was deliberately left ambiguous so that participants could shape the scenario according to their own expectations and preferences. They could indicate the kind of

class they found appealing, the intensity or formality of the activity, and the kinds of support they felt would make participation possible. In this way, the stem invited participants to effectively “design” the class through narrative, offering insights into what they wanted PA provision to look like, what barriers they anticipated, and how such a service could be structured in practice. This approach reflects guidance that SC stems should provide sufficient orientation to be recognisable while leaving the outcome unresolved (Braun et al., 2019; Gravett, 2022; Williams et al. 2021).

The inclusion of a health dimension was also important, as it created space for participants to narrate what kinds of information, advice, or lifestyle support they felt were valuable during the retirement transition. The open ending allowed participants to position Betty’s experience in different ways, with some imagining the class as supportive and confidence-building, and others portraying it as intimidating or alienating. Such differences echo Gravett’s (2022) and Moller et al.’s (2021) observations that the design and framing of SC stems shape the kinds of cultural and emotional resources participants bring into play. In this way, the stem captured women’s imagined decisions about attending the class, their expectations of it, and their preferences for how it should be organised.

Collectively, the three stems translated the prototypes into narrative form, each capturing a distinct but interconnected aspect of the retirement transition. The Retirement Café addressed information and belonging, the Buddy Scheme emphasised confidence and support, and the PA prototype focused on health and social participation. At this stage, however, I could only speculate about how women might respond and engage with them. The stems were deliberately designed to be open enough to accommodate multiple interpretations, in line with SC guidance on balancing orientation and narrative freedom (Braun et al., 2019; Gravett, 2022). Yet the degree to which they would resonate, and the kinds of stories they might elicit, remained uncertain. This uncertainty underlined the need for piloting, both to refine the instructions and to test whether the stems effectively invited responses from women in the TtR. The next section outlines how the stems were piloted, the criteria for participation, and the practical steps taken to develop the instructions for the SC activity.

3.6.4 Pilot Study

Pilot studies are widely recommended in SC research because the quality of the data is shaped by the design of the stems and the clarity of the instructions (Braun et al., 2019; Gravett, 2022). Small-scale testing allows researchers to check whether prompts provide enough orientation to elicit sustained engagement while remaining open to multiple possibilities. It also ensures that instructions are comprehensible and do not inadvertently constrain participants' responses. Following this guidance, I conducted a pilot study to test the three stems and the accompanying instructions before proceeding to the main rollout of the SC activity.

The pilot was also consistent with the co-productive ethos underpinning the wider project. Hannah and Sheila, who had contributed to earlier phases, were invited to take part to sustain continuity and collaboration, while Flora, a participant from Phase One, also took part. Involving women who were already familiar with the study provided an opportunity to refine the activity with input from those whose perspectives had helped shape the prototypes. This reflexive loop reflected theoretical commitments to HCD and NI by treating participants as collaborators in the design of research materials, not only as data providers (Clandinin, 2013; Akama and Light, 2019).

Eligibility for the pilot study reflected the sampling criteria established in the ethics amendment (**Appendix M**), which focused on women in the TtR, defined as being within five years either side of retirement. This ensured that the stems were tested with the intended demographic and that the responses would be grounded in the perspectives of those navigating this life stage.

From my perspective as a researcher, the pilot served two important purposes. It offered reassurance that the stems were legible and resonant for women in the target group. It also gave me the chance to observe how participants approached the activity in practice, which helped me to anticipate issues of accessibility and engagement. Through this process, I realised that even small details such as wording choices in the instructions, or the order in which information was presented, could affect how participants felt about the task and how confident they were in responding. Participants

were asked to complete all three story stems, following a standardised set of instructions (see **Appendix O**).

These instructions reflected deliberate design choices. Asking for a minimum of ten lines encouraged narrative development, while suggesting ten minutes for each story helped avoid over-thinking while signalling that the activity should be given sustained attention. These decisions were informed by Gravett's (2019) account of SC as a flexible method that can encourage participants to surface the discourses they draw upon in meaning-making, provided the task is framed with sufficient orientation and time for engagement.

After completing the activity, participants were asked additional reflective questions about which story stem they felt most affinity with, which prototype they were most drawn to, whether they would use such a service, and why. This feedback was critical for evaluating the clarity of the instructions and the resonance of the stems.

The pilot demonstrated that the story stems themselves did not require alteration. They had been sufficiently crafted to elicit the kinds of responses I had intended, generating narrative material that was detailed, varied, and relevant to the prototypes. This was a strength of the process, as it indicated that the stems worked as designed and could carry forward into the main study without further adaptation. However, feedback also highlighted minor areas where the instructions could be clarified. While the stems provided sufficient depth and flexibility, the way the task was explained sometimes created confusion or unnecessary burden. These insights informed the revisions made before the full rollout of the SC activity.

The responses from the pilot were used solely to test clarity and resonance; they were not included in the analytic dataset presented in **Chapter Six**. However, in the interests of transparency and to demonstrate methodological rigour, the full pilot stories are included in **Appendix P**.

The pilot also became a source of reflexive learning. I had anticipated straightforward feedback on clarity and usability, yet the responses carried more emotional charge than expected. This reminded me that even fictional stories can stir affective responses, sharpening my awareness of the ethical responsibilities attached to asking

women to write into sensitive and transitional life experiences (Frank, 2010). Reading fictionalised accounts that touched on themes already familiar from earlier phases was also emotionally affecting for me as a researcher. It demonstrated that ethical responsibility in NI extends beyond formal procedures to the ongoing attentiveness of the researcher (Clandinin, 2013). In this way, the pilot functioned as a methodological rehearsal. It reassured me that the apparatus was viable while also prompting adjustments that reflected ethical judgement, practical care, and the relational ethos of the study.

3.6.5 Developing and Revising Instructions

The pilot study showed that while the fictional scenarios were resonant and emotionally plausible, the accompanying instructions required refinement. Participants reported confusion over terminology such as “story,” “scenario,” and “story stem,” uncertainty about how many stories they were expected to complete, and discomfort with the prescriptive requirements for time and length. These issues raised concerns about accessibility, especially for participants unfamiliar with narrative research.

The revisions therefore aimed to simplify language, standardise terminology, and reduce performance expectations, ensuring that the task remained clear and approachable while preserving its imaginative and open-ended character. These modifications aligned with recommendations that SC prompts and instructions should provide adequate orientation for participants while preserving opportunities for creative exploration (Braun et al., 2019; Gravett, 2022).

Table 4: Revisions to Story Completion Instructions Based on Pilot Feedback (Three-Story Version)

Original Wording (Pilot Version)	Revised Wording (Post-Pilot)	Rationale for Change
<i>“You are invited to complete three stories – by reading the opening sentences of each story and then writing what you think will happen next.”</i>	<i>“You are invited to complete three fictional stories. Each story begins with a few sentences about a woman approaching retirement. Your task is to imagine what happens next and write a short continuation.”</i>	Clarified fictionality and simplified task structure
Mixed use of “story,” “scenario,” and “story stem”	Standardised to “story”; explained “story stem” once in brackets	Reduced confusion, simplified task language
<i>“Write down whatever first comes to mind... please take at least ten minutes... at least ten lines.”</i>	Removed time and length instructions	Reduced pressure, addressed performance anxiety

Although these refinements were primarily textual, they had methodological significance. By clarifying expectations and reducing potential barriers, the revised instructions supported the relational and co-productive ethos of the project. Documenting these changes also contributes to the wider SC literature, where instructional language is rarely examined in detail (Williams et al., 2021). In this respect, **Table 4** provides a transparent record of how instructions were adapted responsively without compromising methodological rigour.

These refinements, while relatively minor, had meaningful implications for how participants encountered the SC activity. By simplifying language, clarifying expectations, and reducing performance pressure, the instructions created a more accessible and inclusive environment for women in the TtR, a group who may not always be familiar with academic or research-oriented tasks. This process of revision was not a technical afterthought but part of the apparatus itself. Instructions, like story stems, shape what stories can be told and how participants engage with them. Methods are not fixed tools but generative practices that evolve through iterative adjustments and relational responsiveness (Fox and Alldred, 2015; St. Pierre, 2021; Braun et al., 2019; Gravett, 2022). In this sense, revising the instructions exemplified

the methodological craft of SC, ensuring that the apparatus remained robust, sensitive, and aligned with the ethos of dialogical and co-productive inquiry.

3.6.6 Recruitment and Participants

Recruitment for the SC activity followed the strategy outlined in the ethics amendment (**Appendix M**), which specified women in the TtR as the target group. Eligibility criteria for participation in Phase Three were consistent with the sampling framework established for the study, focusing on women in the transition to retirement. The aim was to recruit a diverse sample of up to thirty women, with attention given to age, socio-economic background, and other contextual factors.

In line with the co-productive ethos underpinning the wider study, women who had taken part in earlier phases were also invited to continue their involvement. This offered continuity and reinforced the collaborative nature of the project. Recruitment therefore combined institutional support via SLO with more open-ended outreach, including targeted social media advertising (LinkedIn, X, and Facebook) and contact with community-based organisations and research groups such as the Women's Health Research Network (WHRN), the Scottish Women's Budget Group, the Carers Trust, and a community charity supporting older adults through social and learning activities. Recruitment materials were also distributed through PA classes, which were familiar and trusted settings for many women in the TtR. Snowball sampling further extended reach, inviting women who expressed interest to share the study information within their networks. These combined strategies were designed to ensure both a defined base and wider inclusion, reducing barriers to participation and supporting sample diversity in an online narrative context (Braun et al., 2019; Gravett, 2022; Williams et al., 2021).

Despite these multiple strategies, recruitment proved more challenging than anticipated. Initial uptake was slow, particularly under the first version of the instructions, which asked participants to complete all three story stems. Informal feedback suggested that this was perceived as too time-intensive and risked deterring potential participants. Some women also voiced anxieties about writing, worried about "getting it wrong" or lacking confidence in their creativity. These reactions revealed that

even when the task was framed as flexible and open-ended, underlying insecurities could affect willingness to take part.

These difficulties were at times disheartening. Having invested in building the prototypes and designing the apparatus, I felt the weight of responsibility to secure a sufficient dataset. At the same time, the challenges highlighted the realities of working with community-based participants whose time and energy are stretched. They reinforced the importance of flexibility and of ensuring that the activity remained accessible, realistic, and non-burdensome, consistent with the participatory ethos of the wider project. Reflexively, I also recognised that my own investment in the prototypes may have shaped the way I communicated about the study. I was conscious of the risk of presenting the activity as evaluative rather than exploratory and worked to guard against this in later recruitment materials.

The recruitment and participation strategy therefore built directly on lessons learned from Phases One and Two, particularly the importance of providing accessible entry points and of sustaining relational continuity where possible. This dual emphasis on inclusivity and continuity reflected the project's broader methodological commitments to HCD and NI. The recruitment flyer, which was updated alongside the revised SC instructions, is included in **Appendix O** for transparency.

3.6.7 Implementation and Response

Following the pilot refinements, the SC activity was launched with the three fictional story stems: Katie at the Retirement Café, June in the Buddy Scheme, and Betty attending an exercise class. At first, participants were asked to respond to all three stories, with instructions suggesting that each response should take around ten minutes and be a minimum of ten lines. Although this provided structure, it also placed a considerable time demand on participants, which became evident once the study was underway.

Early responses showed that many participants were taking close to an hour to complete the task. Uptake was also slower than anticipated, despite the multiple recruitment strategies described earlier. This prompted me to evaluate the “ask” being made of participants. The initial requirement to complete three full stories risked

detering further engagement. In consultation with my supervisory team, I therefore revised the instructions to reduce the requirement to one story. This was both a methodological and ethical adjustment. Methodologically, it ensured that responses remained focused and manageable for analysis. Ethically, it reduced the burden on participants, respected their time, and helped to preserve the collaborative spirit that underpinned the wider project. The change gave participants greater flexibility, lessened the sense of pressure, and encouraged them to select the scenario that resonated most with their own perspective.

3.6.8 Applying Dialogical Narrative Analysis to Story Completion

The analytic approach to the SC dataset drew on DNA, consistent with the wider methodological commitments of this study. DNA emphasises how stories are shaped through dialogue with cultural resources, social expectations, and imagined futures, rather than treating them as private accounts of individual psychology (Frank, 2010; Bamberg, 2020). This orientation was particularly suited to the SC data, which invited participants to construct fictional narratives that nevertheless drew heavily on their own experiences, emotions, and assumptions about the TtR.

I began with Frank's (2010, 2012) four central questions for dialogical narrative analysis: affiliation (who or what the story seeks to connect to), identity (how the narrator or character is positioned), circulation (how stories draw upon and travel through wider cultural discourses), and resources (what supports, materials, or meanings the story mobilises). These questions provided an initial scaffold for considering how stories functioned dialogically, both in terms of character positioning and cultural resonance.

As my analysis developed, I drew on extensions proposed by Smith and Sparkes (2009) and Smith and Monforte (2020), who emphasise the value of attending to the body and the function of stories. This broadened the framework to include how retirement transitions were narrated as embodied experiences (for example, through health, confidence, or appearance) and to consider what social or psychological work the stories were doing (such as normalising, resisting, or imagining alternatives). In this

sense, Smith and Monforte (2020) argue that stories are not only descriptive but also performative, as they affiliate, position, circulate, resource, embody, and function.

To operationalise these principles, I developed an analytic template in advance of coding the dataset (**Appendix Q**). The template provided a consistent yet flexible structure for reading each story dialogically, capturing how participants positioned characters, what cultural discourses they invoked, and what work the stories were doing.

Table 5. Dialogical Narrative Analysis Questions Applied in this Study

Framework	Question	Focus
Frank (2010, 2012)	Affiliation	Who or what the story seeks to connect to (communities, relationships, imagined groups).
	Identity	How the narrator or character is positioned within the story.
	Circulation	How the story draws upon, reworks, or travels through wider cultural discourses.
	Resources	What material, emotional, or symbolic supports the story mobilises.
Smith and Sparkes (2009); Smith and Monforte (2020)	Body	How embodiment is represented — what the story reveals about bodies, ageing, and lived experience.
	Function	What social or psychological work the story does (e.g., resisting, justifying, imagining alternatives).

A simplified version of the analytic template is shown below to illustrate how these questions were applied:

Table 6. Example of Analytic Template Applied to Story A4 (Retirement Café)

Story ID	A4
Prototype (Stem)	Retirement Café
Orientation	Circumstantial
Character Positioning	Katie positioned as hesitant, uncertain about fitting in
Affiliation	Aligns with imagined peer group at café
Identity	Retirement as uncertain, vulnerable
Circulation	Draws on discourse of exclusion in ageing
Resources	Community space, financial support
Body	Anxiety expressed through body (appearance, energy)
Function	Functions as warning about isolation
Analytic Memo	Highlights tension between desire for belonging and fear of exclusion

A full version of the analytic template, applied across all stories, is provided in

Appendix R.

This framework supported a layered, dialogical reading of each response. Stories were examined for their surface plots, as well as for how they affiliated with imagined communities, positioned characters within cultural discourses of ageing and retirement, and performed embodied and functional work. In this way, DNA was adapted to capture both resonance and resistance in relation to the prototypes. This analytic framework is used in the findings chapter (**Chapter Six**) to examine how the three prototypes were taken up narratively and what these responses reveal about women’s expectations of support in the TtR.

3.6.9 Conclusion and Transition

This section has traced how the prototype ideas from Phase Two were transformed into a narrative apparatus using SC. The process involved crafting, piloting, refining, and implementing fictional story stems that enabled participants to encounter the prototypes imaginatively. While recruitment was more challenging than expected, the adjustments ensured that participation remained accessible and ethically sound. The

final dataset, though modest in number, was rich in tone and variation, providing a strong foundation for DNA.

This phase also demonstrated that SC could function as a methodological bridge between design and analysis. It enabled prototypes to be tested narratively rather than materially, generating stories that performed, reshaped, and sometimes resisted the support concepts. In this way, the study extended the use of SC beyond its more established applications and positioned it as a creative mode of prototyping in contexts where identity, culture, and emotion are central.

The contribution lies both in demonstrating the adaptability of SC as a narrative method and in offering a practical model for researchers and practitioners working in resource-constrained or ethically sensitive contexts. Carefully designed prompts can surface affective and relational dimensions of support that might remain hidden in conventional prototyping, while imaginative engagement can generate richer insight than reduced or tokenistic interventions. Having outlined the methodological development and implementation of SC, the following section considers the ethical principles that guided this process, including issues of consent, accessibility, and relational responsibility in working with women in the TtR.

3.7 Ethics and Consent

Ethical practice in this study was guided by the principle that research involving stories and co-production requires attentiveness to relationships, care, and ongoing negotiation (Ellis, 2007; Guillemin and Gillam, 2004; Beresford, 2019). Rather than treating ethics as a set of procedural requirements completed at the outset, I approached it as an iterative process embedded across all phases of the project (Guillemin and Gillam, 2004; Tracy, 2010). This orientation also reflects the study's humanist commitments, where care and respect for participants were treated as integral to both ethical and methodological practice.

Ethical approval was obtained for each phase of the study, with documentation, consent procedures, and recruitment processes reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland School of Health and Life Sciences Academic Integrity and Ethics

Committee. To avoid duplication, fuller details of approvals, information sheets, and consent forms are provided in the phase-specific sections (3.10–3.12).

Consent was treated as an ongoing process rather than a one-time formality. Participants and co-producers were given detailed information sheets outlining the purpose of each phase, the voluntary nature of participation, and their right to withdraw at any time. Consent was revisited as the project evolved, enabling participants and co-producers to decide their level of involvement. This approach reflects ethical guidance for narrative and creative inquiry, where consent is understood as negotiated and situated (Sikes and Gale, 2006; Ellis, 2007).

Attention to ethics also extended to the use of narrative and creative methods. Asking women to share stories about retirement carried potential risks of discomfort, particularly around topics such as financial insecurity, health concerns, or social isolation. To mitigate these risks, workshops emphasised collective exploration rather than personal disclosure, and third-person story stems in Phase Three created imaginative distance. These strategies align with ethical guidance for narrative and arts-based methods, which emphasise minimising harm while enabling expression and meaning-making (Phoenix, Smith, and Sparkes, 2010; Lenette et al., 2022).

Pseudonyms were assigned to all participants, and identifying details were removed from transcripts.

From my social constructionist stance, I understood ethics as inseparable from methodological rigour. Ethical practice was not only about safeguarding participants but also about ensuring accountability in knowledge production. This involved attentiveness to power dynamics, reciprocity, and care throughout the project. Ethical integrity therefore supported the credibility of the study, as the findings needed to be both respectful of participants' stories and recognisable to them as fair representations of their experiences (Bochner and Ellis, 2016; Mauthner and Doucet, 2008). These ethical commitments shaped how the study was designed and conducted. A related concern is rigour, which here refers to the processes that make findings credible, transparent, and accountable within a co-produced, narrative framework. The following section addresses this in detail.

3.8 Rigour and Reflexivity

Rigour in qualitative research is often framed in terms of trustworthiness, encompassing credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). More recent frameworks emphasise ethical and relational dimensions of rigour, particularly in co-produced and NI research (Tracy, 2010; Smith and McGannon, 2018). In this study, rigour was enacted through attention to methodological coherence and relational practice.

Reflexivity was central to sustaining rigour. My positioning as researcher is outlined in **Chapter One (Section 1.4)**, and reflexive commentary continues throughout the thesis, where it is integrated into the empirical chapters and linked to methodological decision-making. These reflections address, for example, the influence of my professional background, the impact of illness and institutional disruption, and the relationships developed with co-producers. In this way, reflexivity was not confined to a single section but embedded across the thesis as a continuous practice.

In relation to rigour, my approach aligns with a relativist position rather than a criteria-based one (Smith and McGannon, 2017). Rather than applying fixed checklists or universal criteria, I focused on demonstrating methodological coherence, transparency, and reflexive accountability throughout the research process. Rigour was enacted through detailed documentation of research decisions, transparent presentation of data and interpretation, and iterative engagement with participants and co-producers. This approach recognises that qualitative knowledge is situated and partial, and that rigour emerges through the quality of the interpretive process rather than adherence to standardised procedures. I also engaged critically with evolving debates around rigour in qualitative research (Smith and Caddick, 2024), which call for researchers to move beyond procedural notions of trustworthiness and take a clear epistemological stance. My approach therefore sought to ensure credibility and transparency by linking methodological choices to epistemological commitments, while remaining reflexively attentive to the conditions under which knowledge was co-produced.

Rigour and reflexivity were therefore enacted in combination. By creating space for participants and co-producers to critique and refine emerging ideas, documenting how interpretations were developed, and remaining attentive to ethical responsibilities, I sought to ensure that findings were credible, transparent, and accountable. These practices helped to sustain trustworthiness across all phases, while recognising that knowledge produced through this study is partial, situated, and co-constructed.

3.9 Study Phases

This research was structured in three interconnected phases. Each phase was designed to address a specific objective while building on the insights and relationships developed in earlier stages. Collectively, the phases created a layered approach to understanding and supporting women in the TtR.

Table 7 provides an overview of how the study phases aligned with the stages of HCD, the methods and activities undertaken, and the narrative purposes they served. This alignment illustrates how design and narrative commitments were integrated across the project, while also signposting the structure that the following sections describe in greater detail. Phase One is reported in **Chapter Four**, Phase Two in **Chapter Five**, and Phase Three in **Chapter Six**.

Table 7: Alignment of Research Phases, Methods, and Narrative Purposes

HCD Stage	Research Phase	Methods and Activities	Narrative Purpose
Hear/ Inspiration	Phase One	Pilot interviews, narrative interviews, planning meeting, DNA, composite construction, typology development	To elicit lived experience, surface values, and explore complexity
Create/ Ideation	Phase Two	Co-design workshops using HCD practices, collaborative prototyping, DNA	To imagine and refine support options grounded in lived experience and narrative logic
Deliver/ Implementation	Phase Three	Pilot SC activity, main SC activity, DNA	To evaluate and test the resonance, feasibility, and emotional credibility of support ideas

As shown in **Table 7**, Phase One focused on eliciting lived experience and surfacing complexity through interviews and an initial workshop, supported by DNA and the development of typologies. Phase Two centred on ideation, where participants engaged in co-design workshops to imagine and refine support options through collaborative prototyping. Phase Three emphasised a form of implementation by exploring the resonance and feasibility of these ideas through SC activities. While this did not involve full real-world delivery, the use of imaginative scenarios provided a practical means of evaluating how prototypes might be experienced. The following sections expand on each phase in turn, with details of participants, recruitment, methodological decisions, and links to supporting appendices.

3.10 Phase One – Hear

Purpose and Orientation

Phase One established the empirical foundation of the study by eliciting women’s retirement narratives through interviews and an initial workshop. This stage corresponded to the Inspiration/Hear phase of HCD (IDEO, 2015), which emphasises

attentiveness to lived experience, listening, and the surfacing of complexity. The purpose was to generate a grounded understanding of how women narrated the TtR and to identify patterns, tensions, and resources that could inform later design activities. Although the aims and objectives for Phase One were presented in **Chapter Two**, they are restated here for continuity:

Phase One Objective: Explore retirement narratives through early story data (interviews and a workshop), with attention to emotional themes, relational dynamics, and identity work (**Chapter Two, Section 2.15**).

NI framed this phase. Narrative-led interviews were chosen because they encourage participants to tell their stories in their own terms and at their own pace (Riessman, 2008; Chase, 2011). Such interviews capture the contradictions, ambiguities, and shifts that characterise lived experience (Frank, 2010). From a social constructionist stance, stories were treated as cultural accounts rather than factual records, and analysis was understood as interpretive and context-dependent (Sparkes and Smith, 2014; Phoenix, 2013). DNA was applied to explore both the content of participants' accounts and the ways stories worked, including the positions taken up, the cultural resources drawn upon, and the identities constructed in telling.

Phase One was approved under Ethics Application 19467 (**Appendix A**). Participant information sheets and consent forms are provided in **Appendices B and C**. A sample of interview prompts, submitted as part of the ethics process, is included in **Appendix D**. These prompts were available during interviews but used flexibly and only if conversation lulled, ensuring participants shaped the narrative direction.

3.10.1 Pilot Study

Before launching Phase One interviews, a small pilot study was carried out to test the feasibility of narrative interviewing, transcription, and different formats (online and in-person). Three participants took part, recruited through convenience sampling within my university networks. Their demographic details are shown in **Table 8**.

The pilot was methodological rather than analytic. It was designed to test the clarity and feasibility of the interview process. Two women and one man participated. The man's response was used only to assess usability and was excluded from the main dataset,

which focused on women’s experiences. This approach is consistent with the purpose of piloting, which is to refine research design rather than generate findings (van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001; Kim, 2011).

The pilot confirmed that an open, narrative-led approach was suitable, and that prompts should be used only if conversation lullied. This stage also enabled me to test remote recording and transcription procedures in practice. Consent was obtained from all participants, and supporting materials (information sheets, consent forms, and pilot interview questions) are provided in **Appendices B–D**.

Table 8: Pilot Study Participants

Pseudonym	Age	Gender	Status	Employment	Marital/Partner status	Interview Format	Notes
Christine	60	Female	Retired	Caregiver	Married	Online	Continued in main study (Phase One)
Sharon	63	Female	Working	Part-time	Divorced	Online	Pilot only
Jeremy	56	Male	Retired	Retired	Partnered	In-person	Pilot only, excluded from main dataset

Christine met the eligibility criteria of the study and consented for her data to be included in the main study. She later took part in the planning meeting and the co-design workshops, providing continuity between the pilot and subsequent phases. Sharon and Jeremy did not continue beyond the pilot stage.

Reflexive Account of the Pilot Study

The pilot provided an early opportunity for me to reflect on my role as a researcher. My background as a health professional had trained me to listen actively and respond empathetically, yet in the pilot interviews I noticed moments when my instinct was to offer reassurance or advice rather than to leave space for participants’ unfolding stories. This highlighted the need to adjust; my task was to facilitate storytelling rather than intervene. Keeping a reflexive journal helped me monitor these tendencies and reminded me to shift from practitioner to researcher.

The pilot also revealed the practical and emotional demands of narrative interviewing. Conducting interviews online and in-person required me to manage technology while remaining present and responsive, and I noted differences in conversational rhythm between formats. Although I personally found in-person interviews more conducive to conversational flow, these reflections informed the decision to remain flexible about interview mode in the main study, prioritising participants' preferences.

The transcripts allowed me to experiment with DNA, paying attention to tone, structure, and positioning. This initial attempt was tentative but helped me to see how DNA could be applied in practice and how it differed from other qualitative approaches I had previously employed. The pilot also provided practice with NVivo for storing and organising narrative data. After training, I used the transcripts to trial coding and memo-writing, which built confidence in managing the larger dataset.

Finally, Christine's movement from the pilot into the main study and later into the co-design workshops illustrated the value of continuity and trust. Her willingness to re-engage suggested that the methods felt meaningful and non-extractive. This reinforced the ethical and relational appropriateness of the approach and aligned with the ethos of co-production, where participants are seen as collaborators whose ongoing involvement helps to shape the study (Beresford, 2019; Greenhalgh et al., 2016).

3.10.2 Main Study (Narrative Interviews)

Sampling and eligibility

Participants were Scottish women within approximately five years before or after retirement. Eligibility was defined in the first ethics application (Application 19467; **Appendix A**) as women in mid-to-later life with variation in employment status, family circumstances, and caregiving roles. A purposive sampling strategy was used to capture heterogeneity in the TtR, consistent with established qualitative guidance (Ritchie, Lewis and Elam, 2003; Patton, 2015). Men and non-binary participants were not included, consistent with the focus of the study.

Recruitment procedures

Recruitment for Phase One interviews was facilitated through a gatekeeper at a South Lanarkshire Organisation (SLO), who circulated the study invitation via institutional email following receipt of a formal recruitment letter (**Appendix E**). Interested women received an information sheet and consent form (**Appendices A-B**) before arranging an interview. Flexibility in interview mode (online, in-person, or telephone) was offered to support accessibility and participant preference.

Fifteen women were recruited in total, ranging in age from 59 to 67, with varied employment statuses, marital circumstances, and caregiving responsibilities. This variation reflected the study's aim to explore retirement as a socially situated and diverse process. In addition to demographic details, SIMD (Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation) scores¹¹ were recorded where possible. This provided a contextual indicator of the socioeconomic environments in which women lived, highlighting the diversity of backgrounds represented in the sample (Scottish Government, 2020). SIMD is an area-based measure and does not capture individual-level deprivation, so it was used here as a broad contextual marker rather than an analytic category (Walsh et al., 2016; Smith et al., 2018; McCartney et al., 2019). Including this measure helped situate participants' stories within wider social conditions while keeping the focus on narrative diversity.

Participant Overview

Table 9 provides an overview of the Phase One interview participants. Three women (Christine, Hannah, and Flora) remained engaged across multiple phases of the study, with Christine taking part in all three.

¹¹ The SIMD is the Scottish Government's official tool for identifying area-level deprivation, ranked from 1 (most deprived) to 10 (least deprived). It combines indicators such as income, employment, health, education, housing, crime, and access to services.

Table 9: Phase One Interview Participants

Pseudonym	Age	Employment/Retirement Status	Marital/Partner Status	SMID	Interview Format	Notes
Susan	n/d	Full-time	Single, Divorced	n/d	Online	n/d
Margaret	60	Part-time	Married	9	In-person	
Charlotte	67	Full-time	Married	7	In-person	
Frances	65	Full-time	Married	8	Online	
Lynda	67	Full-time	Divorced	8	Online	
Amanda	61	Part-time	Single	8	Online	
Hannah	64	Retired	Married	8	In-person	Involved in all three phases
Rachel	66	Retired	Married	9	Online	
Ann	59	Part-time	Married	4	Online	
Carly	61	Part-time	Single	4	Online	
Flora	59	Retired	Single, Divorced	4	Online	Involved Stages 1 and 3
Janice	62	Full-time	Partnered	8	Online	
Donna	65	Full-time	Single	1	Telephone	
Christine	60	Retired	Married	4	Online	Involved in phase 1 and 2
Sharon	63	Part-time	Widowed	n/d	Online	

Sample size justification

Qualitative research prioritises depth and richness of accounts over representativeness. Studies exploring narrative identity and life transitions often work with relatively small samples, since analysis involves detailed interpretive engagement (Riessman, 2008; Sparkes and Smith, 2014). A sample of 15 participants is consistent with this tradition and provided sufficient variation to explore both shared and divergent narrative resources while supporting in-depth DNA. The inclusion of SIMD scores (ranging from 1 to 9) further highlighted the heterogeneity of the sample by recognising variation in the socioeconomic contexts of participants' lives. Such diversity is desirable in narrative research because it allows for the exploration of multiple perspectives and enhances the richness and contextual depth of the analysis (Riessman, 2008; Tracy, 2010; Patton, 2015).

Transition to planning meeting

The interviews provided the empirical grounding for Phase One, surfacing early insights into women's retirement narratives. They also established relationships that were carried forward into the next stage. This planning meeting sought to bridge individual

accounts with collective exploration and shape the design of subsequent workshops in line with participant feedback.

3.10.3 Planning Meeting

Purpose and Orientation

The planning meeting acted as a bridge between Phase One interviews and the workshops. It remained within the Hear stage of HCD (IDEO, 2015), creating space for participants to shape design choices before structured co-design began. The meeting tested the feasibility of proposed activities, refined logistical arrangements, and ensured the emerging structure reflected participant preferences.

Recruitment and Eligibility

All women who had taken part in the Phase One interviews were invited to remain involved, consistent with the co-productive ethos of sustaining relationships rather than treating participants as one-off data sources (Beresford, 2019). Additional recruitment drew on local community networks and informal contacts. Four women attended: Hannah and Christine, both previously interviewed; Collette, who responded to an agency email; and Sheila, who joined through word of mouth.

This stage was covered under a second ethics application (Application 20105;

Appendix F). Information sheets and consent forms (**Appendices G–H**) were distributed in advance. The meeting was held online in the evening to maximise accessibility for women still in employment. Relevant materials have been included in **Appendix I** to provide transparency regarding the preparatory process.

Participant Overview

Demographic details of those attending the planning meeting are summarised in **Table 10**.

Table 10: Planning Meeting Participants

Pseudonym	Age	Employment/Retirement Status	Notes
Hannah	64	Retired	Involved across all 3 phases
Christine	60	Caregiver/Retired	Involved in phase 1 (pilot study and planning meeting) and phase 2
Sheila	n/d	Retired	Involved in all 3 Phases
Collette	73	Retired	Involved in Phase 1 and 2

Outcomes of the Planning Meeting

Feedback from participants directly shaped the design of the subsequent workshops. While the initial plan was to hold two three-hour sessions followed by a full-day workshop, participants explained that shorter sessions would be more manageable given health, caregiving, and work commitments. The design was therefore revised to three three-hour workshops. This responsiveness reflected both HCD principles of iteration and the co-productive commitment to structuring research around participants' needs (IDEO, 2015).

Reflexive Account

For me, this meeting marked the first time participants actively shaped the study's design rather than responding to pre-set structures. Their input deepened my understanding of co-production in practice: letting go of fixed plans and adapting to participant needs. My illness at the time (see **Section 1.4**) meant preparing for the possibility of not being able to facilitate alone, which required involving a colleague as backup. While this initially felt like a loss of control, it ultimately reinforced the ethos of shared responsibility that underpinned the project. The experience also deepened my appreciation of interdependence, care, and vulnerability, which were central to the study's focus. Experiencing fragility first-hand made me more sensitive to participants' reflections on uncertainty and adjustment during the TtR, and it reminded me that collaborative research depends on flexibility, trust, and mutual care.

Looking back, I would build greater flexibility into both recruitment and scheduling to accommodate participants' changing circumstances. Establishing stronger relationships with community gatekeepers earlier in the process might also have improved continuity and diversity within the sample. I would allocate more time for

iterative engagement between phases, allowing participants to rejoin at different points as their circumstances permitted. In practical terms, I would also plan for contingencies such as illness or unexpected disruptions by ensuring that co-facilitators or collaborators are briefed and ready to step in if needed. This would protect the collaborative ethos of the research while maintaining momentum through unforeseen challenges.

3.10.4 Workshop One (Phase One)

Participants and orientation

Workshop One concluded Phase One and remained within the Inspiration/Hear stage of HCD (IDEO, 2015). Its purpose was to deepen understanding of women's retirement experiences through collaborative discussion and early design-oriented activities. While the interviews had generated rich individual narratives, the workshop created a collective space where participants could share, compare, and reflect on experiences together. This provided both additional narrative data and insight into how women engaged with each other's stories in a group setting.

Recruitment and eligibility

Recruitment followed the procedures approved under the second ethics application (**Application 20105; Appendix F**). Women who had participated in interviews were invited to attend, and additional participants were recruited through community networks and informal contacts, consistent with the co-productive ethos of sustaining relationships and widening involvement. Information sheets and consent forms (**Appendices I – J**) were distributed in advance.

Participant overview

Three women took part in Workshop One. **Table 11** summarises their demographic details, recruitment routes, and involvement across phases. Age information was not disclosed by Jenny or Sheila. However, both participants met the study's eligibility criteria through other indicators. Sheila indicated during recruitment that she was recently retired, and Jenny identified herself as being in the TtR while working part-time. These disclosures confirmed that both women fell within the target demographic, even

though exact ages were not provided. Their inclusion is therefore consistent with the purposive sampling strategy adopted for this phase.

Table 11: Workshop One Participants

Pseudonym	Age	Employment/Retirement Status	Recruitment Route	Prior Involvement	Subsequent Involvement
Jenny	n/d	TtR, working part-time	IDEO design thinking module	n/d	n/d
Collette	73	Retired, voluntary work (ageing)	Agency email	Planning Meeting	Workshops Two and Three
Sheila	n/d	Retired, voluntary work	Word of mouth	Planning Meeting	One, Two and Three; Phase Three SC pilot

Workshop design and facilitation

Workshop One was held in person at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS), Lanarkshire Campus, and lasted three hours. As set out in the Phase Two ethics application, the session was audio- and video-recorded with prior consent, and participants received printed information sheets and signed consent forms before taking part. A risk assessment had been completed and shared as part of ethical approval. The session took place in a classroom, with participants and facilitators seated around a single table so that everyone could see each other and the slides. This arrangement helped foster a conversational atmosphere and enabled attention to non-verbal cues. Refreshments were available, and participants were free to move around the space as needed, which helped maintain comfort and ease.

Activities were adapted from IDEO’s (2015) design thinking resources, particularly the Inspiration and Ideation stages. The intention was to move from generating individual perspectives toward sharing and synthesising ideas collectively. Specific exercises included:

- **Values mapping**, where participants placed cards representing personal and social priorities (health, security, connection, freedom) on a large board and discussed their choices.

- **Persona building**, in which fictional retirement characters were created to explore diverse experiences and challenges.
- **Speculative scenarios**, where participants responded to *what if* prompts (imagining support services or community initiatives) to spark critical discussion and creativity.

These activities encouraged storying and imagination without requiring participants to disclose personal details they might not wish to share. They created a blend of narrative and design-based entry points into thinking about retirement transitions. Materials used in the workshop, including slides, activity sheets, and handouts, are included in **Appendix J**.

Facilitation and reflexivity

As disclosed in **Chapter One (Section 1.4)**, my illness at the time required careful preparation and adaptation. I facilitated the session, supported by Supervisor 1 and a colleague. My colleague took detailed notes to ensure the flow of discussion was captured, which provided an additional layer of documentation alongside the audio and video recordings. Reviewing the video allowed me to notice non-verbal cues and group dynamics that might have been missed in the audio alone, strengthening the accuracy of the record. Transcriptions were produced verbatim, ensuring that participants' words were captured in full and could be returned to during analysis.

While my colleague's support was practical, it also aligned with the collaborative ethos of the study, enabling richer attention to participant contributions and dynamics in the room. Reflexively, this stage reminded me that health and contingency are always part of the research process, and I recorded these reflections in my research journal.

Linking Data to Analysis

Narrative analysis began with an immersive engagement with the data through repeated listening to audio recordings, reading transcripts, and reviewing participant materials. This process of 'indwelling' (Frank, 2010) supported the identification of stories, which were understood as extended accounts through which participants made sense of experiences, identities, and imagined futures (Riessman, 2008; Caddick and Smith, 2014). Once stories were identified, I examined how they were structured

and positioned in relation to wider cultural narratives, attending to both what was said and how meaning was produced dialogically (Frank, 2010; Phoenix, 2013). My role as story analyst involved interpreting these narratives as ‘realist tales’ (Frank, 2010), aiming to provide credible and situated accounts while recognising my interpretive role in the co-construction of meaning.

Data from Workshop One included audio recordings, participant materials (maps, personas, written notes), and field observations. These were imported into NVivo for organisation and coding, with DNA applied as the interpretive lens to explore how stories, scenarios, and personas drew on cultural resources and positioned participants in relation to wider social narratives (Frank, 2010; Smith and Sparkes, 2008; Phoenix, 2013). **Section 3.6** details this analytic orientation, and **Appendix J** provides coding examples, interpretive templates, and selected design materials used in the workshop. These examples demonstrate how abstract ideas from Phase One were translated into discussion tools, illustrating the analytic chain from activity to interpretation. A completed IDEO (2015) Frame Your Design Challenge sheet is reproduced here (**Figure 1**), illustrating how participants articulated problems, reframed them as design questions, and generated possible solutions and constraints.

Although findings are presented in **Chapter Four**, it is important to note here that Workshop One bridged individual narratives and collective co-design. It demonstrated the feasibility of creative, narrative-informed design methods with women in the TtR and generated early insights that later shaped the typologies and framings developed in Phase Two.

Figure 1 – Frame Your Design Challenge¹²

¹² The “How Might We” (HMW) question format is widely used in HCD to reframe challenges in a generative way, turning problems into opportunities for exploration (IDEO, 2015).

Reflexive Note on Phase One

Phase One unfolded under conditions that were both productive and challenging. While the pilot and Workshop One provided a strong methodological foundation, the period was also marked by disruption, illness, and the practical difficulties of sustaining engagement in a small-scale, community-based project. The continued involvement of Sheila, Hannah, and Christine was particularly important during this stage. Each of them engaged more than once in Phase One, either by moving from interviews to the planning meeting and workshops or by carrying their involvement forward from the pilot study. This continuity reflected the trust and shared purpose that developed between us. Their willingness to return at different points highlighted the feasibility of sustaining engagement across multi-stage qualitative research and reminded me that co-production is built on relationships as much as on methods.

At the same time, my own health presented significant challenges. Within six months of finding myself in hospital, I faced moments when I nearly gave up on the project entirely. I struggled with memory lapses, muddled speech, and reduced fluency, which made it difficult to imagine returning to the clarity and coherence I once had. Facilitating sessions under these conditions required immense preparation and courage, and I often doubted whether I could continue. Yet I also recognised the privilege of being in this position, of being able to do this research at all, and to do it with women who were willing to share their experiences with such generosity.

Progressing with Phase One became a way of holding on to that sense of privilege and responsibility. I felt strongly that I needed to grasp every opportunity to move forward despite the setbacks. This was not about returning to who I was before but about evolving into a researcher who worked differently, with more humility, patience, and openness to others. My journal entries from this period record both the frustration of illness and the small victories of persistence: completing a session, finishing an analysis, or seeing participants respond with energy to an activity.

International travel during this period both enriched and complicated the research process. I spent five weeks in Canada, attending the International Research Training School (IRTS) at Western University and presenting at the North American Society for

Sport Management (NASSM) Conference in Montreal. Shortly afterwards, I participated in the European College of Sport Science (ECSS) Conference in Paris, where I undertook facilitator training. These experiences gave me valuable learning, international feedback, and professional development opportunities. They also created time lapses that made it harder to maintain continuity in recruitment and momentum between workshops.

Further disruption came from the cyber incident at the university, which had significant practical consequences for both recruitment and retention. Partner organisations and governing bodies who had initially committed to support the research were instructed to block email correspondence from my university as a precautionary measure against the perceived data threat. This severed communication channels at a crucial time and limited my ability to sustain networks of support. In addition, two transcripts from Phase One interviews (Carly and Sharon) were irretrievably lost during this incident, which meant that their accounts could not be included in subsequent analysis. These challenges made Phase One as much a test of resilience as of methodological design. They highlighted the embodied, situated nature of research: projects do not unfold in controlled conditions but within the contingencies of illness, institutional infrastructure, and the shifting possibilities of academic life. Phase One was therefore not only the methodological foundation for what followed but also the moment when I learned that progression, however fragile, was still possible.

3.11 Phase Two: Co-Design Workshops

Purpose and Orientation

Phase Two extended the study from exploring women's retirement narratives into the collaborative design of potential support options. The purpose of this phase was to co-produce ideas for interventions that reflected the lived experiences of women in the TtR. While Phase One was aligned with the Hear or Inspiration stage of the IDEO (2015) model, focused on listening to and understanding women's stories, Phase Two moved into the Create or Ideation stage. Here, the emphasis shifted toward collective creativity, exploring how narrative insights could be translated into tangible prototypes that addressed participants' priorities and resonated with their everyday contexts (IDEO, 2015).

Although the broader aims and objectives of the study were set out in **Chapter Two**, it is important to restate those specific to Phase Two for clarity:

- **Aim:** To co-design potential retirement support options with women in the TtR, using participatory and narrative-informed methods.
- **Objectives:**
 1. To use the retirement typologies and framings generated in Phase One as prompts for co-design.
 2. To facilitate workshops where participants could imagine, critique, and refine possible forms of support.
 3. To document how co-design processes shaped the development of prototype interventions.
 4. To assess the acceptability and feasibility of creative design methods with women in mid-to-later life.

These aims and objectives positioned Phase Two as a bridge between narrative exploration and prototype development. The phase was guided by a co-productive ethos, emphasising collaboration, reciprocity, and responsiveness to participants' ideas. As outlined in **Section 3.4**, HCD provided the practical framework for structuring the workshops, with selected activities adapted from IDEO (2015) to support ideation and iteration. Workshop materials, including slides, activity sheets, and prompts, are included in **Appendix K** (Workshop Two) and **Appendix L** (Workshop Three).

To situate Phase Two within the wider research design, **Figure 2** illustrates the Hear–Create–Deliver cycle, showing how insights from Phase One informed the workshops and how outcomes fed forward into Phase Three. The framework was used flexibly, with each phase influencing the next rather than following a rigid sequence.

Figure 2: Alignment of Research Phases with IDEO’s Hear–Create–Deliver Cycle

The following section turns to participants and recruitment for the co-design workshops, showing how Phase Two was enacted in practice.

Participants and Recruitment

All participants from Phase One were invited to join the co-design workshops. Retention proved challenging, as illness, international travel, and institutional disruption created a significant time lapse between phases (see **Section 1.4** and **Chapter Four** for detail). Recruitment was therefore reopened through local agencies, community groups, and word of mouth to strengthen participation.

As previously outlined (see **Section 3.10.4**), the cyber incident also created additional challenges for recruitment at this stage. Partner organisations and governing bodies who had initially expressed willingness to support the project were unable to sustain engagement due to the disruption, which particularly hindered recruitment for Workshops Two and Three, where broader stakeholder involvement had been planned.

Attendance also fluctuated due to conflicting schedules, caring responsibilities, and last-minute changes. These challenges sometimes required workshops to be rearranged several times. On other occasions, I had to make decisions about whether

to proceed with small numbers or to cancel sessions and risk losing momentum. These dilemmas are revisited reflexively later in this chapter (see **Section 3.14**).

Phase Two of the study was delivered through two workshops, each designed to build on the stories and themes from Phase One while also introducing participants to collaborative prototyping activities. As the two workshops were distinct in their structure, attendance, and outcomes, they are described separately in the following sections.

3.11.1 Workshop Two – Create

Purpose and orientation

Workshop Two marked a methodological shift from exploration to refinement. While Workshop One had encouraged divergence by surfacing a wide range of values, scenarios, and speculative ideas, this session moved toward convergence, examining whether emerging typologies and framings could be meaningfully developed into prototypes. Following IDEO's (2015) design cycle, the workshop sat firmly within the *Create* stage, while also drawing on Schön's (1983) notion of "problem framing"¹³ to encourage participants to interrogate assumptions about retirement transitions. This workshop therefore served a dual purpose: to examine whether participants recognised the narratives and framings generated so far as relatable, and to begin sketching concrete interventions that could be taken forward into prototype development.

Participants (co-producers)

Four participants (now co-producers) attended Workshop Two (see **Table 12**). Christine and Hannah returned from earlier phases, and Sheila continued her involvement from the planning meeting and Workshop One. Douglas was the only male co-producer to join the co-design workshops. While a male participant had been included in the pilot study, Douglas's involvement extended the exploration of the method's adaptability into the later, collaborative phase. Recruited via a local Money Advice Service within South Lanarkshire Council, Douglas brought a dual perspective: his professional experience of supporting people with financial difficulties and his own position as

¹³ Schön (1983) describes problem framing as the process by which practitioners define and structure the issues they are addressing, recognising that how a problem is framed shapes the range of possible solutions

someone approaching retirement. This enabled him to contribute both expertise and lived insight, broadening discussion beyond women’s accounts. HCD also emphasises the deliberate composition of design groups to include varied forms of knowledge and stakeholder perspectives, particularly those connected to service delivery or structural contexts that shape user experience (Sanders and Stappers, 2012; Akama and Light, 2019). Douglas’s inclusion was therefore a methodological decision aligned with HCD principles rather than a departure from the study’s focus on women. His professional role in financial advice provided insight into institutional processes that directly affect women’s retirement security, while his own transition towards retirement offered a comparative narrative position. In design terms, he functioned as a stakeholder participant whose perspective could inform feasibility and implementation considerations without displacing women’s experiential knowledge. Women’s narratives remained the primary design drivers, supported by the use of composite stories and typologies as anchoring devices throughout the session.

Table 12: Workshop Two Participants (co-designers)

Pseudonym	Age	Employment Status	Mode of Engagement	Mode of Participation	Notes
Christine	60	Retired / Caregiver	Agency email	Workshop 2	Continued from pilot study and Workshop One
Sheila	n/d	Retired	Word of mouth	Workshop 2	Attended planning meeting and Workshop One; later Phase Three SC pilot
Hannah	64	Retired, in TtR	Word of mouth	Workshop 2	Active in all three phases of the study.
Douglas	n/d	Full time, approaching the TtR	Agency email	Workshop 2	Associated with South Lanarkshire Council Financial Advice Services

n/d = not disclosed

Workshop design and materials

Workshop Two built directly on the outputs of Workshop One, shifting focus from exploring values and scenarios to developing and refining early typologies and framings (see **Chapter Five**). Participants were presented with composite narratives generated from Phase One interviews and Workshop One outputs. Activities included:

- **Typology discussion:** Participants critiqued the draft typologies (Traditional, Conventional, Circumstantial, and Corporate) and reflected on whether these resonated with their own or imagined experiences.
- **Framing exercise:** Using visual prompts and short scenario cards, participants discussed different ways retirement transitions might be represented and what implications these framings carried for possible support.
- **Prototype brainstorming:** Participants sketched emerging ideas on worksheets, supported by prompts that encouraged them to imagine how interventions might function in practice.

All materials were drawn from IDEO's (2015) design resources and adapted to integrate narrative methods, ensuring participants could move between storytelling and speculative design. Workshop slides and activity sheets are provided in **Appendix K**.

Facilitation and reflexivity

I facilitated the session with the support of Supervisor 2. Unlike Workshop One, I did not require a colleague to take additional notes, as my health had improved and I had regained confidence in my own abilities. The workshop was video- and audio-recorded, with participants providing written and verbal consent at the start of the session. Akin to Workshop One, reviewing both the audio and video recordings later allowed me to capture contributions verbatim and to observe non-verbal cues such as gestures, pauses, and expressions, which enriched the transcription and subsequent analysis.

Reflexively, Workshop Two marked a transition point in the project. Whereas Workshop One had been exploratory, focusing on surfacing values and generating imaginative scenarios, this session required participants to respond to more structured typologies and framings. I was attentive to how this shift affected the group dynamic, with

discussion at times becoming more evaluative than speculative. Douglas's presence also introduced additional dynamics. His insights, shaped by his professional background and his own approaching retirement, offered a comparative perspective that prompted reflection rather than deference. Importantly, the discussion did not become an echo chamber for a male viewpoint. Instead, women in the group actively asserted their own experiences, questioned assumptions, and challenged interpretations where these did not align with their realities. This moment was illustrative of a core principle of co-production: creating spaces where different voices can be expressed, tested, and contested, rather than simply accumulated or harmonised. From a dialogical perspective, meaning was negotiated in interaction, with participants positioning themselves in relation to one another rather than orienting around a single authoritative voice.

This stage also reaffirmed the importance of balancing methodological structure with responsiveness in facilitation. I noted in my journal how participants sometimes resisted fixed typology labels or reframed them in ways that suited their own narratives. Rather than correcting or narrowing these contributions, I treated them as meaningful acts of co-production. For example, during a values-mapping activity, one co-producer rejected the typology label she had been aligned with and reframed it in terms that reflected her personal narrative about financial independence. Instead of steering her back to the original framing, I incorporated her reinterpretation into subsequent discussions, recognising it as a valid and generative contribution to the design process. This responsiveness reflected the broader ethos of the study, which sought to position participants not as respondents but as co-creators in shaping how retirement transitions could be understood and supported.

Link to analysis

Outputs from Workshop Two, including worksheets, narrative critiques, and prototype sketches, were imported into NVivo to support systematic data management and organisation. NVivo was used to collate and structure diverse data types (transcripts, scanned worksheets, and field notes), enabling efficient retrieval and cross-referencing during analysis. No automated coding or analytic functions were applied. Instead, DNA guided the interpretive process, focusing on how co-producers positioned themselves

in relation to the typologies and engaged with the framings as cultural resources. This approach reflects ongoing debates about the role of CAQDAS in qualitative research, where software can enhance transparency and rigour without replacing the interpretive work of the researcher (Woolf and Silver, 2017; Jackson, Paulus and Woolf, 2018). This analysis informed the refinement of typologies and the co-production of prototypes described in **Chapter Five**. To enhance transparency, workshop materials are provided in **Appendix K** and include examples of values maps, persona templates, and scenario prompts, which illustrate the specific tools through which participants engaged with the design process. A representative illustration is shown here (**Figure 3**), adapted from IDEO's (2015) *Field Guide to Human-Centered Design*. This worksheet invited participants to turn insights into *How Might We* questions, supporting the move from abstract reflections on retirement to concrete opportunities for prototype development.

Figure 3 – Create: How Might We Questions

*Please note Derek pseudonym was changed to Douglas

Reflexive Note on Workshop Two

Workshop Two demonstrated both the opportunities and challenges of moving from narrative exploration into co-design. Participants engaged thoughtfully with the typologies and framings, but their responses also highlighted the limits of attempting to categorise complex retirement experiences. Some resisted fixed categories, while others adapted or reinterpreted them in ways that better reflected their own or imagined circumstances. These moments highlighted the need for flexibility in applying theoretical constructs, reminding me that typologies are tools for dialogue rather than definitive classifications.

Including Douglas broadened the discussion by adding both professional expertise from his role in the local Money Advice Service and personal reflections on his own approaching the TtR. His insights enriched the session and provided a broader perspective on the financial difficulties and entitlements that women encounter during the TtR and beyond. While women's experiences remained the primary focus of the study, this comparative perspective helped to situate their accounts within wider financial and structural contexts. Importantly, this did not result in deference to professional or male authority. Women in the group actively asserted their own experiences, questioned assumptions, and challenged interpretations that did not resonate with their realities. Facilitating this balance required attentiveness and reflexive awareness.

For me as a researcher, this workshop reinforced the importance of attending to power and positioning within co-design. Although the materials and activities provided structure, it was the co-producers' reinterpretations and critiques that gave them meaning. This reflects a core principle of co-production and HCD: frameworks are offered as provisional prompts rather than fixed solutions, and their value lies in how participants reshape, contest, or reject them. Allowing space for this reworking was central to sustaining the collaborative ethos of the study. Workshop Two therefore became a site of methodological exploration as well as a moment of learning about how to hold frameworks lightly, inviting participants to shape them rather than being constrained by them.

3.11.2 Workshop Three

Purpose and Orientation

The third workshop was designed to consolidate ideas generated in the earlier sessions and to test their coherence when considered alongside women’s lived retirement experiences. Whereas Workshop One emphasised empathy-building through composite narratives, and Workshop Two centred on ideation and prototyping, Workshop Three was intended as a space to bring strands together, refine concepts, and explore their cultural and emotional credibility.

Participants (co-producers)

Table 13 summarises the composition of the group. All co-producers in Workshop Three had also attended earlier sessions, which gave the discussion a strong sense of continuity. This stability meant that participants were already familiar with one another and with the prototype concepts, allowing the group to move quickly into deeper discussion and refinement. The shared history across workshops also fostered trust, enabling more candid reflections on feasibility, potential challenges, and personal resonance. Rather than re-explaining the prototypes, co-producers built on previous dialogue, revisiting earlier insights and exploring their durability over time. This continuity highlighted the iterative character of the process and the value of sustained engagement in co-production work.

Table 13: Workshop Three Participants (co-producers)

Pseudonym	Age	Employment Status	Recruitment Route	Workshop Participation	Notes
Hannah	64	Retired, in TtR	Word of mouth	Workshops 2 and 3	Active in all three phases of the study
Sheila	n/d	Retired	Word of mouth	Planning meeting, Workshops 1, 2, and 3	Later involved in Phase Three SC pilot
Collette	73	Retired; voluntary work (ageing)	Agency email	Planning meeting, Workshops 2 and 3	Brought experience of ageing-focused voluntary sector

Workshop Design and Materials

Building on the typology and framing discussions from Workshop Two, Workshop Three aimed to consolidate insights and move toward tangible prototype ideas. Activities were structured to encourage participants to imagine practical forms of support and to reflect critically on how these might work in real-life contexts. To support a more extended session, a catered buffet lunch was provided midway through, both as a practical measure and as a thank you for participants' ongoing involvement. Sharing food also helped to create a sense of community and reciprocity, reinforcing the collaborative ethos of the study.

Key activities included:

- **Prototype refinement:** Using worksheets and scenario prompts, participants were asked to refine intervention ideas such as the Retirement Café, the Buddy Scheme, and tailored PA opportunities.
- **Narrative positioning:** Composite character stories were reintroduced to test how the prototypes might resonate with different typologies. Participants reflected on whether the interventions addressed the characters' imagined needs.
- **Practical mapping:** Small-group discussion explored potential barriers to implementation, including resources, accessibility, and social acceptability. These conversations helped to surface tensions between desirable support and realistic provision.

The workshop was again informed by IDEO's (2015) Create/Ideation stage resources, adapted to maintain narrative entry points. Worksheets and slides for this session are included in **Appendix L**.

Facilitation and Reflexivity

As in earlier workshops, co-producers were welcomed into a university classroom, oriented to the space and health and safety procedures, and reminded of their rights as participants. Seating was arranged around a central table so that everyone could see one another and the slides, supporting both verbal and non-verbal communication.

Due to an issue with IT equipment, the session was audio-recorded only, with consent reconfirmed at the start. Transcription was based on the audio record, supplemented by my notes that captured key non-verbal cues and group dynamics.

Again, the session was facilitated by me with the support of Supervisor 1. Having already worked with these participants across multiple phases, the atmosphere felt less like a discrete event and more like a continuation of an established dialogue. This continuity encouraged more candid critique, as co-producers felt comfortable challenging assumptions and reworking earlier ideas.

Reflexively, Workshop Three highlighted both the strengths and vulnerabilities of sustaining participation over time. While numbers were smaller than originally anticipated, I chose to proceed rather than cancel, again recognising the risk of disengagement if momentum was lost. The commitment of those who attended demonstrated the importance of working responsively with whoever was present, rather than holding rigidly to target numbers.

Link to Analysis

Although the data generated in this phase included different formats (worksheets, scenario responses, transcripts), a consistent DNA approach was applied to interpret how participants positioned themselves in relation to prototypes and cultural narratives. Outputs from Workshop Three included prototype worksheets, scenario responses, and transcribed discussions. These materials were organised in NVivo and analysed using DNA, with attention to how participants positioned themselves in relation to the prototypes and how their critiques drew on cultural narratives about retirement, ageing, and social participation. This analysis fed directly into Phase Three, where the prototypes were tested through fictional narratives.

Selected workshop materials are reproduced in **Appendix L**, with one example included here (**Figure 4**). This image captures a whiteboard used to generate and organise “How Might We¹⁴” questions, which structured participant brainstorming

¹⁴ In IDEO’s (2015) framework, “How Might We” questions are a design tool that reframe challenges as opportunities, encouraging open-ended, creative exploration rather than solution-driven problem solving.

around prototype ideas. Including these materials provides transparency in showing how abstract concepts were translated into concrete tools that facilitated collaborative discussion.

Figure 4 – Brainstorming Ideas

Reflexive Note on Workshop Three

Workshop Three highlighted the importance of sustaining engagement through trust and continuity, even when attendance was lower than anticipated. Proceeding with a smaller group required balancing appreciation for co-producers ongoing commitment with an awareness of the potential risks of over-reliance on a few voices. I was conscious of ensuring that their contributions were treated as part of a wider conversation rather than representative of all possible perspectives.

The atmosphere was shaped by familiarity. Having worked with Hannah, Sheila, and Collette across earlier phases, the session carried the feel of an ongoing dialogue

rather than a new encounter. This created space for more open critique, where co-producers questioned assumptions, challenged ideas they found unconvincing, and emphasised practical considerations that might otherwise have been overlooked. Their willingness to engage critically demonstrated the value of sustained co-production, where relationships built over time fostered confidence in shaping the process.

For me as a researcher, this workshop reinforced the lesson that co-design is rarely about generating consensus or polished solutions. Instead, its value lies in surfacing tensions, exposing gaps, and generating provisional ideas that remain open to refinement. The catered lunch offered during this session felt like a small but meaningful way to recognise the time and energy these women had given across the study. It also reminded me that gestures of reciprocity are an important part of sustaining relationships in long-term qualitative work (Ellis, 2007; Mauthner and Doucet, 2008).

3.12 Phase Three – Deliver

Purpose and Orientation

The third phase of the study corresponded to the Implement/Deliver stage of IDEO's (2015) HCD model. The objective for this phase, as outlined in **Chapter Two**, was to explore the resonance and functionality of the co-produced prototypes using SC. The original plan had been to develop and trial low-cost physical prototypes. However, as discussed in **Section 1.4** and revisited in **Chapter Four**, disruptions to the project timeline, together with ethical concerns about the limited value of partial or tokenistic interventions, made this unfeasible.

Methodological Alignment

As outlined in **Section 3.7**, SC was adopted as a narrative prototyping device that aligned with the social constructionist and dialogical commitments of the study. It enabled participants to engage imaginatively with the prototypes while safeguarding the participatory ethos of the project. Here, the focus is on how SC was implemented in Phase Three rather than re-arguing its methodological rationale.

Implementation Overview

Three fictional story stems were developed, each linked to one of the prototype

concepts that emerged from Workshop Three (the Retirement Café, the Buddy Scheme, and tailored PA classes). Participants were invited to continue the stories, projecting possibilities, concerns, and reflections onto the characters. Responses were gathered via Microsoft Forms to widen accessibility and reduce barriers linked to time, confidence, or group settings. Ethical approval for this phase was obtained as an amendment to the Phase Two application (**Appendix M**).

Signposting Forward

A pilot study was undertaken to refine the SC instructions and story stems, after which the activity was implemented online via Microsoft Forms. Recruitment was reopened through local agencies and community groups to sustain participation, and further refinements were made in response to feedback. To extend reach, I also re-engaged the Phase One gatekeeper, who distributed study information again via HR channels. Full details of the piloting process, recruitment outcomes, and the resulting dataset are presented in **Chapter Six**, which focuses specifically on Phase Three. Here, the emphasis is on situating SC methodologically as part of the HCD cycle and aligning it with the narrative commitments of the study.

Reflexive Note

The decision to use SC reflected both practical constraints and a principled commitment to maintaining rigour and trustworthiness. While different from the original vision of in-person prototyping, SC offered an ethically sensitive and creative way of sustaining momentum and extending participation. For me as a researcher, this phase reinforced the importance of flexibility in long-term qualitative work and highlighted the potential of creative narrative methods to bridge design and analysis.

Closing the HCD Cycle

Together, the three phases completed IDEO's (2015) Hear–Create–Deliver cycle. Rather than a linear sequence, this was an iterative process where insights from listening shaped design, and design in turn shaped refinement. Each phase therefore built cumulatively toward the study's aims, linking NI with co-production and creative prototyping (see **Figure 2, Section 3.11**, for a visual summary).

3.13 Chapter Summary

This chapter has outlined the methodological framework for the study. Grounded in relativist ontology and social constructionist epistemology and informed by humanistic traditions that value stories as meaningful accounts of lived experience, the research treated narratives as situated and relational, shaped through interaction and cultural context. This orientation supported the use of NI, DNA, HCD, co-production, and SC. It also drew selectively on CAP, recognising storytelling and writing as ways of generating and communicating meaning. Reflexivity and ethical practice were embedded throughout, ensuring that the knowledge produced was situated, transparent, and accountable.

These methodological choices provided a coherent foundation for the three phases of the study: eliciting women's retirement stories, co-producing prototype interventions, and exploring their resonance through SC. The following chapter turns to Phase One, presenting the interviews and early workshop in detail and showing how women narrated retirement in ways that shaped the subsequent direction of the study.

Chapter Four - Phase One Findings: Narratives, Insights, and Emerging Typologies

4.0 Chapter Overview

This chapter presents the findings from Phase One of the study. As outlined in **Chapter Three**, this phase included fifteen narrative interviews and Workshop One. Together, these activities generated the material from which narrative typologies of the TtR were developed. The interviews provided opportunities for women to narrate their expectations and experiences, while Workshop One enabled these early typologies to be returned to participants for discussion and refinement. In keeping with the ethos of co-production, typologies were not treated as fixed analytic products but as evolving constructs shaped through dialogue with women in the TtR. The following introduction outlines the aims of Phase One and explains how these activities addressed the first research question.

4.1 Introduction and Aims

Building directly on the methodological account in **Chapter Three**, Phase One focused on hearing women's stories of the TtR and exploring what could be learned from these accounts for developing narrative typologies. This phase involved two strands of activity: fifteen narrative interviews and a follow-up workshop. The interviews created space for women to speak in their own terms about retirement, generating insights into the cultural storylines and personal positioning that shaped how they approached this life stage. These narratives highlighted facets of retirement absent in the existing literature (see **Chapter Two**), underlining the value of listening directly to women's voices.

Workshop One created an opportunity to return early typology sketches to participants for discussion. This step reflected the co-productive ethos described in **Chapter Three**. Typologies were treated as provisional and open to refinement, expansion, and challenge through dialogue. Phase One was therefore exploratory and developmental, ensuring that what carried forward into later phases was grounded in lived experience and shaped in co-production.

From the first round of analysis, I developed narrative insights that illustrated the varied ways women told retirement stories. These preliminary insights informed the construction of provisional typologies, which were later refined and tested through co-production in Workshop One. The chapter therefore addresses the first research question: *How do women narrate their expectations and experiences during the TtR?*

4.2 Analytical Approach

As outlined in **Chapter Three**, the analysis drew on Dialogical Narrative Analysis (DNA). DNA asks what stories do, rather than what they mean (Frank, 2010, 2012), directing attention to how narratives are performed and what possibilities they open or close for the teller. In this study, interviews and workshop discussions were treated as situated accounts through which women made sense of the TtR in dialogue with wider cultural narratives (Riessman, 2008; Squire, Andrews, and Tamboukou, 2013).

The analytic process involved close readings of individual transcripts alongside attention to patterned ways of storytelling across the dataset. Focus was given to the narrative resources women drew upon, the storylines they resisted or embraced, and the positions they adopted in telling their accounts (Bamberg, 2004; Andrews, 2014). Interpretation was iterative: early readings identified moments of tension, disruption, or resonance, which were then revisited in light of Frank's guiding questions about how stories function, what they draw upon, and what they make possible. To illustrate, **Table 14** presents an excerpt from Margaret (semi-retired; age 60). Her account shows how stories can function dialogically, negotiating both personal circumstance and wider social expectations.

Table 14. Example of Dialogical Narrative Analysis (Margaret)

Narrative Excerpt	What the Story Does	Narrative Resources	Possible Functions
<p>“I had thought I’d keep working, but then my health got in the way. I tried part-time, but it wasn’t the same. It felt like I was being pushed out, not choosing. I tell people I ‘took early retirement,’ but really it doesn’t feel like that.”</p>	<p>Positions retirement as disrupted rather than chosen; reframes her exit from work in more acceptable terms.</p>	<p>Cultural scripts of early retirement, social expectations of personal choice, and broader discourses of health and productivity.</p>	<p>Protects dignity by reframing a constrained decision; signals ambivalence about identity as “retired”; connects personal experience to wider social narratives of work and health.</p>

This example highlights how DNA attends to both the content and function of stories. Margaret’s narrative is about leaving work but also about managing its meaning, as she negotiates tensions between choice, constraint, and identity. Applying this approach across the dataset enabled the development of typologies that reflect cultural patterns of storytelling rather than individual case histories.

My interpretive work was dialogical, shaped by methodological commitments, the research context, and my reflexive engagement with participants’ accounts (see **Chapter Three**). A worked example is provided in **Appendix N** to illustrate the process in greater depth and enhance transparency. The DNA focused on what stories did in context and how they were performed: the positions women adopted, the cultural resources they drew upon, and the possibilities their accounts opened or constrained. In examining these dynamics, stories rarely settled in one position. Instead, disruption and reorientation appeared as intertwined currents that structured how women navigated health, finances, social ties, caregiving, and activity in the TtR.

From this first round of analysis, I developed a set of narrative insights that illustrated recurring ways women told retirement stories. These were not treated as fixed categories but as provisional patterns that captured cultural storylines and personal positionings across the dataset. Developing these insights into preliminary typologies provided a way of organising narrative variation while remaining attentive to dialogical tensions and movement within stories. The typologies were therefore interpretive tools,

designed to prompt reflection and discussion rather than to classify participants. They offered a structured yet flexible means of tracing how different retirement positions could coexist and shift within the same narrative. In subsequent phases, these typologies were revisited and refined collaboratively during the co-design workshops (see **Chapter Five**), where participants engaged with and extended them to inform the development of prototype interventions. These intertwined dynamics of disruption and reorientation are presented in the following sections as narrative insights, organised around health, finances, social ties, caregiving, activity, and guidance. Together, they set the foundation for the preliminary typologies introduced later in the chapter.

To clarify the relationship between the thematic findings and the typologies, the “Narratives of Health and Wellbeing,” “Narratives of Finances and Precarity,” “Narratives of Social Ties and Belonging,” “Narratives of Caregiving and Responsibility,” and “Narratives of Activity and Engagement” represent thematic and dialogical insights drawn directly from participants’ accounts. These highlight recurring tensions and meaning-making processes within individual stories. The typologies, by contrast, synthesise these patterns at a higher interpretive level, describing broader narrative positions or ways of telling retirement. The thematic narratives show what is being told, while the typologies interpret how stories are told and culturally positioned.

Transforming individual stories into typologies inevitably involves tension. This process required balancing analytic synthesis with respect for the uniqueness of each woman’s account. The typologies were not intended to generalise or label participants but to capture recurring narrative positions and patterns of meaning that could support collective reflection. During the workshops, co-producers recognised aspects of themselves in more than one typology, suggesting that this form of abstraction remained resonant while preserving complexity. These typologies therefore functioned as dialogical tools, open, relational, and subject to further refinement through collaborative discussion.

4.3 Narratives of Health and Wellbeing

Health featured prominently in women's accounts of the TtR. For some, declining health was a catalyst for leaving work earlier than anticipated, while others viewed retirement as an opportunity to protect or restore wellbeing. The prospect of more time for rest, exercise, and self-care sat alongside anxieties about ageing and the loss of physical capacity.

Rachel linked her decision to leave work with the impact of stress on her health:

“I ended up with a trapped nerve in my neck. I'm sure it was just the stress of the job. And I thought, I'm gonna have to stop. It was making me ill.” *(Rachel)*

Ann described how prolonged workplace stress had undermined her confidence and wellbeing, shaping both her employment choices and her outlook on retirement:

The stress was just too much. I couldn't cope. It made me feel demoted and worthless. That's when I started looking for something else, something I could manage without it breaking me. *(Ann)*

For others, retirement offered a chance to take proactive steps towards maintaining health. Frances emphasised the importance of activity and purpose for her physical and mental wellbeing:

“If I don't keep busy, I'll just go downhill. I need to be up and out, whether it's walking or joining something, to keep my head straight as much as my body.” *(Frances)*

Flora highlighted the pressures of balancing health needs with ongoing caregiving responsibilities:

I look after my mum, and that takes it out of me. Retirement might give me more time, but it also means I've got to keep myself well enough to do it. That's always at the back of my mind. *(Flora)*

Several participants described a heightened awareness of ageing and its embodied realities. Charlotte reflected on how her cancer diagnosis had changed her outlook:

When I got cancer, everything shifted. Before that, I thought I'd just keep going as I was, work, routine, keeping everything ticking over. But it changes you. You realise work isn't everything. You start thinking, what time do I have left, and how do I want to spend it? (*Charlotte*)

Flora also described a near-death experience that reshaped her orientation to retirement:

I was told I might not pull through. And when you get that close to the edge, you don't go back to being the same. Retirement isn't about stopping work; it's about making sure you're still alive to enjoy what's left. (*Flora*)

These accounts highlighted that health in retirement is not an abstract concern but a lived reality that shapes priorities, values, and orientations to the future. Women spoke of health as both a constraint and a resource, something that could curtail opportunities yet also motivate reorientation. Their stories moved between vulnerability and possibility, rarely settling in one frame.

This ambivalence matters for the trajectory of the study. It suggests that any attempt to design support for women in the TtR must attend to health as more than an individual issue, since it is central to how retirement is storied, lived, and made meaningful. Health challenges influenced decisions about leaving work as well as expectations of life afterwards. These stories also showed how health concerns intersected with financial circumstances, shaping what was possible in retirement. The next section examines this interplay more closely, considering how financial resources and insecurities affected both the timing and terms of women's retirement narratives.

4.4 Narratives of Finances and Precarity

Health was often intertwined with financial circumstances, as women reflected on how resources and security influenced what was possible after leaving work. Margaret explained how health problems altered her financial expectations:

"I got hip replacement a year past... I was fully intending to work right up to I got my state pension... but this has really knocked me back a bit." (*Margaret*)

For her, retirement was accelerated not by choice but by the intersection of health constraints and financial planning.

Flora also described how sudden illness forced her into early retirement, leaving her facing a long gap before she could access her state pension:

I'd been off sick for six months before retiring. I was diagnosed with fibromyalgia and then ended up in hospital with blood clots in my lungs. It was touch and go. After that I thought, I can't do this anymore. I looked into early retirement, and that's what I did. (*Flora*)

Although her mortgage was already paid off, she remained uneasy about the years ahead:

"I've been fortunate because my mortgage was paid off, so the pension I get now will keep me going until the state pension kicks in at 67. But it's still a long wait."
(*Flora*)

Her account illustrated how sudden illness could accelerate retirement and impose years of financial strain, even when housing security softened the immediate impact.

Finances featured prominently in women's accounts of the TtR, shaping the timing of retirement and expectations of life afterwards. For some, secure pensions and savings offered reassurance. For many others, financial pressures weighed heavily, often entwined with gendered employment histories, caring responsibilities, and rising living costs.

Ann described how part-time and interrupted work had left her with only "tiny pensions":

We work as a couple; we always have done. And so, we're quite financially secure with his pension and I have lots of tiny pensions because I had moved from... part-time employment because I brought up children and stuff... But I think it should be fine, yeah. (*Ann*)

Here, financial security was narrated in relational rather than individual terms, dependent on her husband's stable pension and shaped by her own fragmented

employment trajectory. She went on to describe how her expectations for retirement had been disrupted by pension reforms, with the state pension age rising for women and altering carefully laid plans:

Oh, it was awful. Absolutely awful. Aye, because you know those plans that you've made years ago had to change. But then that's life, isn't it? You've got to adjust and change with everything all the time, you know. But fortunately, we're in a position... we wouldn't have starved, put it that way. It made a difference to our plans, but we were in a financial position that we wouldn't go into poverty.

(Ann)

This account highlighted the tensions between relative security and altered expectations. Retirement was navigated without fear of poverty, yet not without feelings of unfairness or loss.

Rachel reflected on the structural inequalities underpinning women's pensions, drawing attention to gendered pay gaps and missed opportunities for progression:

I mean, financially, you're employed less, you're promoted less, and you're going to have less when you retire... It's a massive cut. We get a cut, but it starts at appointment. You're appointed less, you're definitely going to be promoted less. Most women are not going to get to the top, and then you inevitably retire... it's just so sickening. *(Rachel)*

She also described the everyday adjustments this required:

So, we're trying to make our outgoings as small as possible. And we are turning the heating off as much as possible. So, I think we'll be OK, but we aren't just kind of waiting to see how far it goes and then, you know, it's just realistic really. We're not worried or feeling we're freezing, but I think we're just being realistic.

(Rachel)

Her account highlighted both the structural inequalities that reduced women's pensions and the daily economies through which financial strain was managed.

In contrast, some participants narrated a stronger sense of financial stability.

Charlotte, for instance, emphasised the continuity of pension contributions over her working life:

“I’m 38 years pensionable, with no breaks. I have no children. So, I’ve paid full contributions.” (*Charlotte*)

Frances expressed similar confidence:

“Well, I have a local government pension. I’m very lucky to have that. So that’s basically my financial plan.” (*Frances*)

These accounts illustrated how uninterrupted employment histories, often tied to stable public sector roles, generated a contrasting narrative of reassurance and preparedness.

Alongside differences in resources, participants also reflected on the importance of financial literacy and access to advice. Amanda valued opportunities to receive information in one place, describing how difficult it could be to navigate alone:

“I think it would be terrible because you would probably have to contact... four or five different people, whereas it was a one stop shop type idea.” (*Amanda*)

Lynda similarly described how attending financial sessions close to retirement prompted changes she would not otherwise have made:

I’ve gone to a couple of really good sessions... mainly to do with financial side of it. And that’s been really... cause things I didn’t think on, and I kind of made changes even at the late stage it was worth doing it. (*Lynda*)

These perspectives showed that finances were about more than resources; they also depended on access to clear, timely, and trustworthy guidance.

These accounts suggest that finances influenced when and how women retired, and also how they adjusted their routines and participation afterwards. Financial security created space for planning and choice, while financial strain introduced uncertainty and limits. The following section turns to questions of connection and belonging,

exploring how women described continuity, exclusion, and experimentation in their social worlds after leaving work.

4.5 Narratives of Social Connection and Belonging

Participants often reflected on how retirement would reshape their social lives. Work had provided daily contact and a sense of belonging, and its absence raised questions about how to sustain connection. For some, retirement opened up new possibilities, while for others it risked dislocation and exclusion.

Amanda described trying to find her place in new groups:

There was a local group... they used to go walking and then go for a coffee. But I just found that they weren't for me. They were say, fifty to sixty, but they were old. I think I'm a young outlook person, but they were like going to the bingo. I tried going a few times with them and thought, no. I can't be bothered with this.
(Amanda)

Her account illustrated how cultural expectations of ageing could be experienced as stifling, leading her to resist groups where she felt misrecognised.

By contrast, Charlotte spoke about anticipating continuity with existing networks:

I do keep in touch with some colleagues who have already retired, and I'd like to think that will continue. In my friends group, I would think that within a year or two, there would be a few of us that would be of retirement age. *(Charlotte)*

Flora highlighted the importance of generational fit when seeking out activities:

"I knew that the people that would be there would be my age group and older but would be of a similar thought process rather than being children there." *(Flora)*

Others described retirement as freedom from unwanted connections. Hannah noted:

"I'm glad I don't have to deal with all that anymore. The gossip, the cliques. Retirement feels like freedom from all that." *(Hannah)*

Christine took a more proactive approach, deliberately organising her time to stay connected:

“I’ve made a point of keeping busy. I’ve signed up for a walking group, I’ve got volunteering lined up. I don’t want to get stuck at home.” *(Christine)*

The cost of social activities was also raised. Margaret reflected:

“It sounds great when they say, ‘join a class,’ but some of them are expensive, and if you don’t drive or you feel out of place, it’s not so simple.” *(Margaret)*

These accounts reveal that retirement was narrated in diverse ways: as exclusion, freedom, or opportunity. Across these differences, participants shared an awareness that social life in retirement was not automatic but something that had to be actively created and sustained. Many also resisted stereotypes of ageing that cast older women as passive or dependent, instead highlighting varied and self-directed forms of connection. Stories of belonging and participation often led directly into concerns about where to find clear and trustworthy guidance. The next section considers how women described their search for information, and how gaps in advice left them uncertain about what retirement would involve or how to navigate it.

4.6 Narratives of Information and Guidance

Uncertainty about where to find reliable guidance was a recurring theme across interviews. While retirement was experienced as a major transition, many women felt there was little structured support to help them navigate it.

Donna voiced her frustration:

“You get leaflets about pensions, but nothing about what it actually feels like to stop working. Nobody tells you how to cope with the change.” *(Donna)*

Margaret similarly noted the imbalance in what was available:

It’s all about money, money, money. Yes, that’s important, but what about your health, or what you do with your time, or how you keep your mind active? There’s nothing out there for that. *(Margaret)*

Friends and peers were often turned to, but the advice was inconsistent. Amanda explained:

I asked friends who had already retired, but their experiences were all so different. One was loving it, another was miserable. It didn't really give me a sense of what I should expect. (*Amanda*)

For many, the internet presented both opportunity and barrier. Lynda admitted feeling overwhelmed:

"I googled it once and gave up. There's too much, and half of it is people trying to sell you something. You don't know who to trust." (*Lynda*)

Donna spoke of digital exclusion as a direct obstacle:

"I don't do computers. If I need to fill something in online, I have to ask for help. It makes you feel daft, but it's the way everything is now." (*Donna*)

Susan often found herself supporting friends less comfortable with technology:

"I've helped friends fill out online stuff, things they can't manage. It's basic to me, but for them it's like a different language." (*Susan*)

Some stories also showed how the absence of reliable guidance could have long-term financial consequences. Donna described relying on her brother's advice to cash in her pension:

I didn't know much about pensions, and my brother said, 'Just cash it in, you'll be fine.' So, I did. And now I realise I've lost out, and there's nothing to fall back on. It was awful when I found out. I still feel sick thinking about it. (*Donna*)

These narratives highlight a wider problem: information was limited in scope and often inaccessible. Digitalisation created additional inequalities, leaving those with fewer skills or confidence dependent on others. At the same time, the emphasis on pensions and finance meant that broader aspects of retirement, such as health, identity, time use, and caregiving, were largely absent from formal advice.

Accounts of information needs showed how gaps in advice left women uncertain about rights, opportunities, and possible futures. In some cases, unclear guidance compounded worries already present in health or finances. These reflections often overlapped with wider responsibilities, particularly caregiving, which continued to

shape everyday life in retirement. The next section explores how women narrated these responsibilities and their implications for imagining later life.

4.7 Narratives of Care and Responsibility

For many participants, retirement was not imagined as a purely personal transition but as deeply entangled with the needs of others. Women described ongoing or anticipated responsibilities for parents, partners, and grandchildren. Caregiving was narrated both as a duty and as a meaningful role, yet it also brought strain and curtailed independence.

As highlighted earlier in **Section 4.3**, Flora's account also emphasised the inseparability of health and caregiving.

I look after my mum, and that takes it out of me. Retirement might give me more time, but it also means I've got to keep myself well enough to do it. That's always at the back of my mind. I can't just think about me. (*Flora*)

Christine described how caring for her husband, who had dementia, reshaped her working life and accelerated her retirement:

I only worked two and a half days anyway, cause when Derek was diagnosed with dementia six years ago, I reduced my days. But it was still a bit of a juggle to do both... I'm different because I haven't retired just to retire. I had to retire to increase my level of caring. I just got to the point where I couldn't juggle both, and work was the obvious one. (*Christine*)

Her account illustrated how caregiving responsibilities restricted choices, reshaping the meaning of retirement itself.

Ann anticipated a shift towards helping with grandchildren:

My daughter's already said, 'Mum, you'll be around more, won't you?' And I don't mind, I love the kids, but it does mean your time's not always your own. You picture retirement as freedom, and then you realise you're still needed in other ways. (*Ann*)

In contrast, Hannah was clear that she wanted to resist becoming the default carer in retirement:

I don't want to be tied down again. I've done my bit with kids and family, and retirement for me is about finally having some space. I'll help if I can, but I won't be the one everyone relies on. (*Hannah*)

Not all participants framed care as a burden. Margaret described looking after her grandchildren as something that enriched her daily life:

"They keep me young. I get tired, of course, but when I'm with them, I feel I've still got a role. It gives me something to get up for in the morning." (*Margaret*)

These contrasting accounts highlight the ambivalence of care. It could provide purpose and connection, but it also risked exhaustion and the loss of independence. Retirement was narrated less as a withdrawal from responsibility and more as a reconfiguration of it, where the needs of others continued to shape women's time and priorities.

As a researcher, I found myself especially affected by these accounts. Like Flora and Christine, I have had to balance my own health while caring for others. I supported my mother before she passed away, and I also gave up my nursing career to care full-time for my disabled son. Alongside this, I continue to support my daughter, who is autistic and requires daily assistance. Hearing women talk about the pressures and significance of care resonated deeply with me. This background strengthened my empathy during the interviews and shaped how I listened. In IDEO's (2015) terms, this phase of 'hearing' was about gaining insight through attentiveness, and my own experience of long-term caregiving made me especially attuned to the nuances of these stories. It reminded me that caregiving is not an abstract issue but an enduring reality that structures how time, energy, and identity are negotiated in retirement. Amid these responsibilities, women also described the role of physical activity. The next section explores how activity was narrated as both possibility and constraint, connected to identity, health, and recognition, yet limited by cost, energy, and competing demands.

4.8 Narratives of Physical Activity

Physical activity (PA) featured prominently in women's accounts of the TtR. It was often narrated as a resource for maintaining health, confidence, and social connection, but also as a site of pressure, exclusion, or humour. These stories echoed wider research emphasising the role of PA in shaping health and independence in later life, while also showing how opportunities were constrained by cost, caregiving responsibilities, and social stereotypes (Newton et al., 2019; Fraser, 2021; NCD Alliance, 2023).

For some, PA was framed as essential to sustaining wellbeing. Frances, whose story was used earlier to illustrate the link between care and health, also described how she needed activity to maintain both mental and physical health:

“If I don't keep busy, I'll just go downhill. I need to be up and out, whether it's walking or joining something, to keep my head straight as much as my body.”
(Frances)

Flora highlighted the difficulties of prioritising PA alongside caregiving and her own health challenges:

“I'd like to do more exercise, but between looking after Mum and keeping myself well, it's hard to find the time or the energy.” *(Flora)*

Other women linked PA with identity and social recognition. Rachel recalled a recent encounter in a shop:

I went into the Peloton shop, and the young lad looked at me like I was some doddery old lady who'd never been on a bike. He started explaining the basics as if I wouldn't understand. I said to him, 'Actually, I used to compete internationally.' His face just dropped. It felt good to remind him that older doesn't mean incapable. *(Rachel)*

Her story illustrated how PA was entangled with assumptions about age and capability, and how women could resist such stereotypes by drawing on their histories.

Others narrated PA with humour, highlighting the risks of embarrassment. Susan explained:

I thought I'd try a spin class once — I fell straight off the bike! Same with the running machine, I was on the floor in seconds. You've got to laugh, but it does put you off going back. (*Susan*)

Some participants reflected on the practical barriers that limited activity. Although this excerpt was used earlier to narrate social connection (**Section 4.5**), it also illustrates the financial and practical costs of classes as barriers to PA. Margaret explained:

“It sounds great when they say, ‘join a class,’ but some of them are expensive, and if you don't drive or you feel out of place, it's not so simple.” (*Margaret*)

Janice spoke about how her sense of energy shaped what she felt able to do:

“I want to keep moving, but I get tired more easily now. I need something that fits around how I feel, not something that makes me feel worse.” (*Janice*)

These accounts showed that PA in retirement was narrated with ambivalence. It represented continuity and control for some, humour or frustration for others, and exclusion when shaped by financial or social barriers. Women's voices in this study demonstrate that PA is more than an individual lifestyle choice; it is embedded in cultural expectations, personal histories, and material conditions.

For women in the TtR, PA was both a way of maintaining independence and a reminder of the limits imposed by bodies, resources, and social environments. Its presence across stories showed that activity mattered not only for health but also for confidence, social participation, and the capacity to imagine later life as meaningful. Taken together with insights on health, finances, connection, guidance, and caregiving, these accounts began to suggest patterns that informed the development of preliminary typologies of the TtR, as the next section outlines.

4.9 From Narrative Insights to Preliminary Typologies

Patterns in the ways women described the TtR provided a starting point for developing preliminary typologies. These were not conceived as rigid categories but as heuristic groupings that captured recurring yet varied ways of narrating retirement. At this stage, the typologies were understood as working sketches: interpretive tools to be tested and

refined through dialogue with co-producers. They were therefore carried forward into Workshop One as prompts for discussion and co-productive exchange.

4.10 Workshop One: Co-Production in Practice

Workshop One took place on campus during the afternoon, attended by Sheila, Jenny, and Collette. These participants were different from those involved in the interviews, reflecting the recruitment process described earlier (see **Section 4.6**). The ethos and facilitation style were consistent with the co-productive orientation set out in **Chapter Three**, but the group format created a different kind of dialogue. Unlike the one-to-one interviews, women drew energy and recognition from each other's accounts. Moments of laughter softened more difficult reflections, while silences signalled the weight of what had been shared. My role was less directive, stepping back to allow conversation to flow between participants.

The workshop was structured around the early sketches of retirement typologies, yet discussion quickly extended into broader questions of what retirement meant, how it was experienced, and how it was imagined. Methodologically, the session was designed to extend the initial Hear stage of HCD (IDEO, 2015), introduced in **Chapter Three**, and the workshop outline and materials are provided in **Appendix J**. The typologies were used not as fixed categories but as prompts to deepen collective reflection. In practice, the group both refined and expanded the analysis, while also generating new perspectives that complicated and enriched the early sketches.

Life-course and family timing

The women spoke about how earlier life decisions shaped retirement. Collette reflected on how becoming a parent at a young age had altered her trajectory:

We had our children young and that has a knock-on effect. By the time my sister-in-law had children, my daughter was old enough to babysit for them and there is only four years between my brother and I. She was running out of time when she had her two children. She had to work on longer than she anticipated to put the two through Uni. (*Collette*)

Jenny added that differences in timing continued to shape how retirement unfolded across her own family:

“My sister’s boys are in their twenties and she’s turning sixty this year. I was only 23 when Katie was born.” (*Jenny*)

These exchanges showed how women positioned retirement within the arc of family life, emphasising that retirement timing cannot be separated from earlier caregiving responsibilities and intergenerational obligations.

Retirement as age or stage?

Participants questioned the cultural assumption that retirement equates to old age. Sheila stressed the need to separate the two:

You need to make sure that you don’t mix retirement up with old age and assume that both go hand-in-hand. If you think back to Granny and Grampa’s time, by the time they retired they were elderly. We’ve now got people who are young, fit, but still face challenges perhaps of what to do. (*Sheila*)

For Collette, retirement was framed more positively:

“Retirement held absolutely nothing but opportunities for me. I’m going to do whatever I like for the rest of my life.” (*Collette*)

The group agreed that retirement should be seen as a stage of transition rather than a final destination, emphasising new beginnings as much as endings.

Identity and adjustment

Much of the discussion centred on identity and self-perception. Collette described her sharp break from work identity:

“I took every garment that said ‘school’ down to the charity shop in my first week of retirement.” (*Collette*)

Jenny echoed this, describing her adjustment as a shift in self-image:

“Who am I without my corporate identity? ... It was like putting on a costume at work, but that wasn’t really who I am.” (*Jenny*)

Sheila emphasised continuity rather than reinvention:

I still wear makeup every time I go out. That notion of going into retirement and saying all that stops, and I've become someone else, was absolutely never going to work for me. *(Sheila)*

Together, these reflections illustrated the varied ways women negotiated the break between working and retired life, some shedding identities quickly, others carrying aspects forward.

Social connection and isolation

The group also explored the challenges of social connection. Jenny spoke candidly about her difficulty in breaking into existing groups:

“If you had a system where someone looked out for you, just one friendly face saying, ‘nice to see you back’ could make all the difference.” *(Jenny)*

Collette added a practical example from her own community:

“We have a meet-er and greeter who stands outside the hall and says to anybody, ‘Good afternoon, have you been before?’ You know who’s a member.” *(Collette)*

These insights highlighted how even small gestures of welcome could ease the difficulties of entering unfamiliar social spaces.

Finances, services, and inequalities

Underlying many of these reflections was the recognition that retirement opportunities were shaped by finances and access to support. Sheila pointed out:

If you don't have enough money, then you are restricted in a lot of things you can do. If you're sitting there on a really low income, worrying about fuel costs, socialising and going out to groups are not really top of your priority list. *(Sheila)*

Collette added examples from her involvement in local initiatives:

“We work with women who are living on their state pension only. One of our jobs is to say you are entitled to lots of benefits — let’s see if we can get you them.”
(*Collette*)

Jenny emphasised that access to information was not always straightforward:

There’s this huge assumption that everybody has an email address. Some people don’t want to use computers; others don’t have access. Doctors’ surgeries and clinics are so important for getting information across to people who don’t have those resources. (*Jenny*)

These reflections highlighted the inequalities shaping retirement transitions and the need for accessible, practical support.

Collective insights

What stood out from the session was how the women actively shaped the discussion, drawing on lived experience to expand the emerging analysis. They challenged stereotypes of retirement as decline, emphasised the role of finances, family, and identity, and suggested practical solutions to improve support.

As a facilitator, I was struck by how the group atmosphere shaped the discussion differently from the one-to-one interviews. Rather than focusing only on individual accounts, the women responded directly to one another, amplifying, questioning, and extending each other’s comments. At times, humour lightened the discussion, while silences allowed more difficult reflections to settle. These dynamics highlighted the importance of stepping back, recognising that co-production depends on creating conditions where knowledge can circulate collectively rather than being directed by the researcher. Workshop One was therefore both method and outcome. It produced insights while also modelling the collaborative ethos that shaped the typologies introduced in the following section. These contributions informed the refinement of typologies, ensuring they reflected individual accounts as well as the dialogical exchanges of the group.

4.11 DNA Exemplar: Workshop One

As outlined in **Section 4.2**, DNA was used to explore how stories worked in context. **Appendix N** provides extended worked examples from the interviews, but it is also useful to show how the same approach was applied to workshop material. Looking closely at an excerpt here illustrates how insights began to take shape through the dialogical exchanges of Workshop One, gradually informing the development of typologies.

Narrative Excerpt (Jenny, age 62, retired)

I went along to a couple of groups and attended for weeks on end and really didn't connect with anyone. People were going in pairs, already with a friend. I plucked up the courage and went on my own and then basically kind of got 'Hi' and it never went beyond that. (*Jenny*)

Table 15 presents a brief analysis of Jenny's narrative, illustrating how stories were examined dialogically to identify their cultural resources, narrative functions, and implications for support design.

Table 15. Narrative analysis of Jenny's story excerpt from Workshop One

What the Story Does	Narrative Resources	Possible Functions
Positions group participation as daunting and exclusionary; convey a sense of isolation despite effort.	Cultural scripts of retirement as socially active; expectations of confidence and belonging in community groups; moral value of independence and initiative.	Highlights the gap between ideals of social connection and lived exclusion; legitimises feelings of vulnerability; signals a need for more welcoming structures (e.g., buddy systems).

Interpretive Commentary

Jenny's story challenges dominant narratives that depict retirement as a time of easy sociability. Despite her initiative in attending groups, she constructs her experience as isolating, marked by the absence of welcome. The story describes events but also works dialogically: it justifies her withdrawal, critiques the assumption that joining

groups is straightforward, and opens space to consider how exclusion is felt in retirement transitions. This exemplar shows how DNA made it possible to interpret workshop discussions as more than feedback on typologies. They became exchanges that voiced lived experience, questioned cultural expectations, and pointed toward new possibilities. Insights of this kind gradually shaped the development of typologies, which are outlined in the next section.

4.12 Consolidated Typologies of the TtR

By the end of Phase One, the typologies had developed from early sketches into more consolidated cultural narratives. Emerging from both the interview accounts and the Workshop One discussions, they were not fixed analytic products but evolving constructions, shaped through dialogue and refined in co-productive exchange.

While rooted in individual accounts, the typologies did not represent single participants. Instead, they functioned as composite ways of narrating retirement that resonated across experiences, capturing recurring orientations while leaving space for nuance and ambivalence. Here, they stand as the principal analytic output of Phase One, offering heuristic portraits of how retirement was storied.

Four typologies are presented here:

- **Corporate** – characterised by structured engagement, strong occupational identity, and retirement as reinvention.
- **Conventional** – defined by alignment with normative retirement scripts, drawing on stability, routine, and financial security.
- **Circumstantial** – shaped by disruption, precarity, or health and caregiving demands that curtailed choice.
- **Traditional** – oriented around family roles and gendered expectations, often placing others' needs before personal aspirations.

These typologies were not exhaustive or mutually exclusive. Instead, they mapped patterned ways of narrating retirement while also acknowledging the tensions within them. They provided the interpretive foundation for subsequent phases of the study, where their relevance and applicability were further explored. To aid clarity, **Table 16**

provides an overview of the consolidated typologies, highlighting their defining features, characteristic storylines, and associated tensions.

Table 16. Consolidated Typologies of the Transition to Retirement

Typology	Key Features	Typical Storylines	Tensions / Risks
Corporate	Strong occupational identity; structured, purpose-driven approach	Retirement as reinvention; continuity through volunteering, second careers, education	Pressure to remain productive; risk of masking disconnection with busyness
Conventional	Alignment with normative retirement scripts; stability, routine, financial security	Retirement as deserved rest; time for hobbies, family, steady routines	Vulnerable to disruption if finances/health change; reliance on traditional expectations
Circumstantial	Retirement is shaped by disruption, precarity, or constrained choice	Narratives of forced retirement (illness, redundancy); making do with limited resources	Heightened vulnerability; limited agency; sense of injustice
Traditional	Orientation around family roles and gendered responsibilities	Retirement as serving others; caregiving, grandparenting, maintaining the household	Loss of independence; self-needs deferred; risk of invisibility

These typologies map the range of cultural storylines that women drew on when narrating their TtR. Each reflects a patterned orientation but also contains tensions and contradictions that complicate simple categorisation. The following subsections expand on each typology in turn, drawing on both interview accounts and reflections from Workshop One to show how these narratives were recognised, elaborated, and sometimes contested.

4.12.1 Corporate Narratives

The Corporate typology was characterised by a strong occupational identity and a professionalised, purpose-driven approach to retirement. Women positioned here did not describe retirement as an endpoint but as a continuation of structured engagement, often involving new roles, voluntary commitments, or further training.

Planning, routine, and the sustained use of skills shaped how they narrated this stage of life.

Charlotte (57, working full-time at the time of interview) explained how she expected retirement to mirror the organisation of her working life:

“I’ve always had targets, deadlines, things to aim for. I can’t imagine just drifting. I’ll need to set myself something, otherwise I think I’d lose who I am.” *(Charlotte)*

Similarly, Janice described how her sense of self was bound up with professional contribution, and how she anticipated continuing to use her skills in other contexts:

“I don’t want to waste all the experience I’ve built up. Retirement just means doing it differently. Maybe voluntary work, something where I can still be useful.” *(Janice)*

Rachel, who had previously worked in professional sport and academia, spoke about her determination to resist decline:

“I’ve seen people just stop and then fade away. That terrifies me. I want to keep moving forward, keep stretching myself.” *(Rachel)*

Margaret reinforced this orientation towards productivity, emphasising the value of keeping structure and purpose:

“I don’t think I could just stop. I’d have to be doing something, even if it’s not paid, even if it’s smaller. I need to feel I’m contributing.” *(Margaret)*

Ann also stressed the importance of maintaining a sense of achievement, even outside formal work:

It’s about still having goals. I’ve always worked towards something, and I think I’d struggle if that disappeared. Retirement, for me, is finding new ways to achieve. *(Ann)*

For Susan, who had held senior professional roles, the idea of slowing down felt almost alien. She admitted that while she longed for less pressure, she was also wary of losing her sense of purpose:

I don't want to be defined by a job anymore, but at the same time I can't picture myself with nothing on the horizon. I need something to work towards, otherwise I'd feel empty. (*Susan*)

When the preliminary typologies were introduced in Workshop One, the Corporate narrative was quickly recognised. Sheila observed:

“It sounds very positive, having a plan, but it could also be draining if you feel you can never switch off.” (*Sheila*)

Jenny added:

“That kind of person never really retires, do they? They're always chasing the next thing.” (*Jenny*)

Collette, reflecting on her own orientation, noted:

“I can see myself there. I'd go mad without something to do. I need a reason to get up in the morning.” (*Collette*)

These reflections consolidated the Corporate typology by showing how it resonated across accounts while also exposing tensions. Confidence and continuity were valued, but women also voiced unease about the hidden demands of productivity and the risk of masking isolation with constant activity. The Corporate typology therefore captured a distinctive cultural storyline: retirement as reinvention through structured engagement. It carried the promise of purpose and recognition but was shadowed by anxieties about redundancy and the inability to step away from roles that had long defined self and value.

4.12.2 Conventional Narratives

The Conventional typology reflected women who aligned their retirement stories with normative expectations of stability, continuity, and security. In this orientation, retirement was imagined as a deserved reward after years of work and family commitment, a period where routines could be maintained and life lived at a slower but still structured pace. Women positioned here valued predictability, financial security, and social familiarity, often emphasising the importance of maintaining health and

community ties. Retirement was framed less as reinvention and more as consolidation: a continuation of known rhythms with fewer pressures.

Frances described retirement as an opportunity to protect the life she had already built rather than to seek radical change:

“I’ve always liked things to be steady. I don’t need big adventures, just enough money to keep going, a bit of gardening, seeing friends. That’s enough for me.”

(Frances)

This sense of continuity was also central to Margaret’s reflections, where stability was tied closely to financial planning and cautious living:

I’ve been careful all my life, making sure the mortgage was paid, and the pension was there. Retirement, to me, is about knowing you’re safe and you can keep the same kind of life without worrying. *(Margaret)*

For Amanda, retirement meant protecting the routines and values she associated with respectability. She spoke of remaining engaged in her community, valuing familiarity and responsibility:

I want to keep doing what I do, but just not under someone else’s timetable. I’ll still help out with things locally, keep my house nice, be there for people. That’s the way I was brought up. *(Amanda)*

Alongside this desire for continuity, the Conventional narrative also contained anxieties about what could happen if stability was disrupted. Flora, for example, described how health issues threatened her ability to sustain the routines she valued:

I think if you can keep well, retirement can be good. But once your health goes, everything changes. You can plan as much as you like, but it all depends on that.

(Flora)

Hannah expressed similar concerns, linking her retirement choices to the caregiving responsibilities that made stability difficult to achieve:

You picture it as being free, but if you've got family to look after, it doesn't always work out that way. You try to keep things steady, but it's hard when other people need you. *(Hannah)*

Rachel's account further highlighted how fragile the Conventional orientation could be when workplace dynamics undermined the security she expected:

I thought I'd just keep working there until I chose to leave, but it didn't happen like that. I was pushed out, and it was horrible. You imagine you'll be in control of the timing, but sometimes you're not. *(Rachel)*

Her experience revealed how cultural scripts of orderly retirement could be destabilised by conflict, leaving women with little sense of choice.

When these insights were introduced in Workshop One, co-producers confirmed the appeal of the Conventional storyline but also questioned whether it might appear overly idealised. Sheila observed:

"It sounds nice, but life's not always like that. You might want things to stay the same, but sometimes you don't get the choice." *(Sheila)*

Collette added that while she recognised aspects of herself in this typology, she felt it could mask the effort required to maintain stability:

"Keeping everything steady takes work. It's not just sitting back; you've still got to keep all the plates spinning." *(Collette)*

These reflections helped consolidate the typology by showing how it resonated but also how it might obscure the hidden strains involved in maintaining stability. The Conventional narrative captured an image of retirement as orderly and secure, an idea that women valued but also questioned. It carried the promise of security and routine but was shadowed by the recognition that stability could be disrupted by health decline, caregiving responsibilities, or workplace dynamics.

4.12.3 Circumstantial Narratives

The Circumstantial typology was shaped by disruption, precarity, or constraints that limited choice. Women positioned here described retirement less as a planned

transition and more as something imposed by circumstances beyond their control. Health struggles, caregiving responsibilities, financial insecurity, and hostile work environments loomed large, making retirement feel precarious and uncertain.

Donna recounted how poor advice and limited financial knowledge had left her vulnerable. This extract, while cited earlier in **Section 4.6**, is returned to here for its relevance in illustrating the insecurities central to the Circumstantial typology:

I didn't know much about pensions, and my brother said, 'Just cash it in, you'll be fine.' So, I did. And now I realise I've lost out, and there's nothing to fall back on. It was awful when I found out. I still feel sick thinking about it. (*Donna*)

She explained how the decision continued to haunt her, shaping not just her finances but her sense of security and future options:

"You think you're making the right choice at the time, but then it comes back to bite you. It's too late to fix it now." (*Donna*)

Christine offered another illustration of how care responsibilities curtailed choice. She described how her husband's diagnosis with dementia meant reducing her working hours, eventually reaching a point where employment became impossible to sustain:

I only worked 2 and a half days anyway; cause again when Derek was diagnosed with dementia 6 years ago — I reduced my days. And then after a few months I asked to reduce it to two days and it was declined, and erm... So eventually with a bit of negotiation, I got down to 2 and a half days. Which was about 3 years ago. But it was still a bit of a juggle to do both. (*Christine*)

Her account illustrates how retirement was not a straightforward choice but a constrained negotiation between work, care, and institutional inflexibility.

Ann's story also illustrated how workplace stress created pressure points in retirement decision-making. As discussed earlier under the narratives of health and wellbeing (**Section 4.3**), she described how prolonged stress eroded her confidence and forced her to make decisions she had not anticipated:

The stress was just too much. I couldn't cope. It made me feel demoted and worthless. That's when I started looking for something else, something I could manage without it breaking me. *(Ann)*

Lynda highlighted how financial constraints restricted her options for a fulfilling retirement:

Everyone talks about taking up hobbies, travelling, doing things for yourself. But all of that costs money. If you're careful, you can manage, but you don't get the same choices as people who've had better jobs or better pensions. *(Lynda)*

Rachel recounted how a toxic workplace environment had left her with little option but to step away earlier than planned:

The bullying just wore me down. It wasn't sustainable anymore. In the end, leaving was the only way to protect myself. But it didn't feel like a choice — it felt like being pushed. *(Rachel)*

These stories showed how circumstances unsettled retirement plans and forced difficult recalibrations. Rather than aligning with cultural narratives of retirement as reward or reinvention, women here emphasised survival, resilience, and coping with conditions not of their choosing.

In Workshop One, co-producers recognised this narrative as uncomfortably familiar. Jenny reflected:

“A lot of people don't really get a choice — it's health, or money, or family that decides for you.” *(Jenny)*

Collette added:

“It feels unfair, but it's reality. Not everyone gets to plan a perfect retirement.” *(Collette)*

The Circumstantial typology consolidated around these accounts of constrained choice. It highlighted how retirement was storied not as open possibility but as negotiation with limits imposed by health, finances, or care. Yet within these constraints, women also narrated forms of adaptation, finding smaller routines,

protecting what mattered, or asserting boundaries. These narratives revealed the inequalities that shape the TtR while also demonstrating the resilience required to navigate retirement when choice is curtailed.

4.12.4 Traditional Narratives

The Traditional typology framed retirement as a continuation of family roles, particularly those associated with motherhood, caregiving, and intergenerational responsibility. Women positioned here narrated retirement less as a personal stage of exploration than as a period where established identities as carers, organisers, and family anchors would remain central. In these accounts, retirement was not imagined as a clean break from responsibility but as a reconfiguration of maternal and relational duties that extended into later life.

Hannah exemplified this orientation. She described herself as the default caregiver in her family, and she anticipated that little would change with retirement:

I've always been the one everyone turns to, and I don't see that changing. Even when I finish work, I'll still be looking after everyone else. That's part of who I am.
(Hannah)

Her words echoed the enduring figure of the family matriarch, where motherhood does not end once children become adults but continues into later life as an ongoing responsibility. For Hannah, retirement was unlikely to provide the freedom she longed for, yet she also derived meaning from being needed.

As discussed earlier in relation to caregiving (**Section 4.7**), Margaret described looking after her grandchildren as a source of purpose:

"They keep me young. I get tired, of course, but when I'm with them, I feel I've still got a role. It gives me something to get up for in the morning." (Margaret)

Her story reflected the ambivalence of caregiving in later life: while demanding, it offered continuity, meaning, and a renewed sense of usefulness.

Lynda also spoke of how family responsibilities continued to shape her priorities, even as she longed for more independence:

“I’d love to do more for myself, but there’s always something else, the kids, the grandkids. You can’t just walk away from that.” (*Lynda*)

Her account highlighted the tension between wanting to pursue personal goals and feeling bound by expectations that her time would remain organised around the needs of others.

Other women framed this orientation in terms of values and identity. Amanda described herself as someone who would always put family first, even if it limited her own choices:

“That’s the way I was brought up. You make sure everyone else is alright before you think about yourself. Retirement doesn’t change that.” (*Amanda*)

At Workshop One, these sentiments were recognised and discussed. Sheila noted how the cultural script of the selfless family anchor could be both comforting and restrictive:

“It sounds lovely, but it also means you never quite get to put yourself first. You’re still giving, still responsible.” (*Sheila*)

Collette, who had identified more closely with the Corporate orientation during her working life, acknowledged that in retirement she recognised herself in the Traditional narrative:

“I suppose I’m back to being mum again, even though they’re all grown up. I still feel that’s where I’m most needed.” (*Collette*)

The Traditional typology was thus consolidated through both individual accounts and co-producers’ reflections on the persistence of maternal and relational duties. Across these stories, retirement was narrated as continuity rather than change. It carried the reassurance of familiarity and purpose, but it also revealed the enduring gendered expectations that left limited space for autonomy or self-development. The Traditional narrative therefore highlighted a cultural storyline in which retirement was not a personal withdrawal from responsibility but a reconfiguration of maternal and caregiving commitments. It demonstrated how women’s later lives continued to be organised around relational obligations, sometimes embraced as meaningful, but often

experienced as constraints. The typology captured both the pride associated with sustaining family roles and the frustration of feeling that personal aspirations were once again deferred. Collectively, the typologies revealed wider cross-cutting insights about how retirement was storied. These are developed in the following section.

4.13 Cross Cutting Insights from Phase One

The four typologies offered heuristic portraits of the TtR, but women did not fit neatly into a single type. Their accounts often moved fluidly across orientations, sometimes within the same interview, as they described aspirations, constraints, and shifting circumstances. This fluidity showed that retirement was not a fixed endpoint, but a dynamic, ongoing negotiation shaped by health, finances, family, and self-perception.

Diversity and commonality

The typologies highlighted diversity in how retirement was storied, while also revealing important common threads. Women expressed a consistent awareness that their experiences were shaped by wider structures such as economic conditions, gendered expectations, and policy frameworks, even as they narrated highly individual journeys. For example, Margaret's sense of purpose in caring for grandchildren (Traditional) contrasted with Flora's insistence on making the most of survival after illness (Circumstantial). Both, however, spoke to retirement as defined in relation to others and by forces beyond their direct control.

Co-producers recognised this interplay of difference and commonality in Workshop One. Sheila reflected that "you need to make sure that you don't mix retirement up with old age," highlighting how participants challenged cultural scripts that equated retirement with decline. Jenny added nuance, emphasising that "who am I without my corporate identity?" was as central a question as financial planning or caregiving. These insights suggested that while retirement narratives varied, they were all shaped by tensions between individual aspiration and collective expectation.

Ambivalence across narratives

Another insight that cut across typologies was the role of ambivalence. Even in accounts where women emphasised continuity or reinvention, doubts and

vulnerabilities remained close to the surface. For instance, Collette’s declaration that retirement held “absolutely nothing but opportunities” sat alongside her later admission that returning to a maternal role after children left home still felt unavoidable. Similarly, women who spoke of financial stability often tempered this with concern that health or wider economic shocks could destabilise their plans.

Ambivalence was equally present in narratives of constraint. Donna’s account of losing pension security carried anger and regret, but also a determination to manage as best she could. Flora’s story of near-death experience conveyed fragility but also resilience. These examples showed that women did not simply inhabit one typology or another; instead, they moved between optimism and apprehension, pride and frustration. Retirement was storied as possibility and as risk, often in the same breath.

Thematic Tensions

Several recurring tensions became visible when narratives were considered together.

- **Independence versus responsibility:** Women valued autonomy and self-determination but remained tied to relational duties. Corporate orientations emphasised reinvention and independence, while Traditional narratives centred on caregiving. Many women lived at the intersection of these positions, seeking space for themselves while still feeling bound to others’ needs.
- **Security versus precarity:** Conventional accounts emphasised stability, often rooted in pensions or home ownership, while Circumstantial narratives revealed how quickly this security could unravel. Financial advice gone wrong, sudden health problems, or workplace hostility could turn anticipated stability into fragility.
- **Continuity versus reinvention:** Some women framed retirement as carrying forward established roles, routines, and identities; others saw it as an opportunity to shed past selves and start anew. Both positions were valid, and many participants oscillated between them.

These tensions demonstrated why retirement could not be addressed through universal models of support. Women's narratives revealed contradictions that had to be held in balance rather than resolved.

Workshop Validation and Extension

Workshop One tested the emerging typologies and added new layers to them. Co-producers challenged and elaborated on the analytic sketches, turning them into richer accounts. Jenny's reflection on her difficulty connecting in social groups highlighted the practical barriers to reinvention that are often overlooked in abstract discussions of retirement. Sheila's emphasis on maintaining her appearance showed how identity work continued even after occupational roles ended. Collette, meanwhile, described herself both as someone embracing opportunity and as a continuing family anchor, illustrating the fluid ways in which women moved across narrative orientations.

Co-producers also suggested practical responses. Jenny proposed buddy systems to ease entry into unfamiliar groups, Collette described community greeter schemes, and Sheila stressed the importance of financial stability as a precondition for engagement. These ideas went beyond analysis of what retirement was like; they pointed toward what might make retirement more navigable. The workshop was both data and inspiration for design, contributing to the interpretive depth of Phase One and laying foundations for Phase Two.

Implications for the Study

The cross-cutting insights from Phase One show that retirement is narrated in plural, sometimes contradictory ways. The typologies demonstrated patterned orientations while also highlighting their permeability and overlap. Women's accounts revealed ambivalence, thematic tensions, and the inseparability of individual choices from structural conditions. Disruption and reorientation also cut across retirement stories. Health shocks, financial pressures, or the loss of workplace identity unsettled established routines, yet these same disruptions created opportunities for women to reimagine priorities and practices. The interplay of disruption and reorientation shaped how retirement was storied, showing the importance of typologies that reflect multiplicity and movement rather than fixed categories.

For this study, the typologies were treated as cultural narratives that highlighted possibilities, constraints, and contradictions in women's retirement transitions, while being sharpened through co-production. This process kept the analysis grounded in lived experience and set the stage for the reflexive insights that follow.

4.14 Reflexive Commentary

Facilitating Workshop One gave me a new perspective on how the typologies functioned in practice. In the one-to-one interviews, stories had unfolded slowly, often with space for reflection. In the group, the dynamic was different. Participants responded to one another in real time, recognising themselves, friends, or colleagues in another's words. Sometimes they amplified a point with laughter or affirmation; at other moments they disagreed, hesitated, or shifted the discussion in a new direction. What stood out was the dialogical quality of the exchange. Stories became less about individual experience and more about collective exploration.

This atmosphere aligned with the principles of DNA. Stories were treated as responses to other stories, shaped by the interaction in the room as much as by individual voices. Silences carried meaning, humour softened difficult admissions, and disagreement created space for complexity. Rather than weakening the analysis, these moments made it stronger, revealing tensions that a single interview might not capture.

As a researcher, I found myself stepping back more often than I had anticipated. My role was less about guiding the discussion and more about holding the space where it could unfold. The process reminded me that co-production was not only about including participants in analysis but about creating the conditions for knowledge to emerge in ways I could not have produced alone.

Seeing the typologies tested in this way revealed both their limits and their potential. They gained depth through participants' elaborations and challenges, becoming less like categories and more like shared cultural resources. In reflecting on this, I draw on Frank's idea of thinking with stories (2010). Rather than treating accounts as data to be dissected, Workshop One showed how stories can accompany inquiry, opening new understandings of what retirement is and how it is lived. It was both a site of analysis

and of data collection, offering a collective way of thinking with stories that reshaped the typologies and pointed toward Phase Two.

4.15 Summary of Phase One Implications

Phase One highlighted that retirement is narrated in plural, sometimes contradictory ways. The typologies demonstrated patterned orientations while also highlighting their permeability and overlap. Women's accounts revealed ambivalence, thematic tensions, and the inseparability of individual choices from structural conditions. Centred on hearing women's voices, this phase showed the complexity of the TtR, with stories marked by disruption, continuity, and negotiation. Participants articulated retirement in their own terms, resisting simplified accounts of the process, and these accounts became the groundwork for the collective work that followed.

In keeping with the ethos of co-production, these narratives were brought into dialogue through Workshop One. The workshop created space for participants to respond to emerging interpretations, question assumptions, and extend the analysis with their own insights. This exchange refined the analysis and surfaced common challenges around timing, identity, social connection, and resources, while also modelling the collaborative approach that shaped the study as a whole.

The principal analytic outcome of Phase One was the development of four consolidated typologies: *Corporate*, *Conventional*, *Circumstantial*, and *Traditional*. These were not rigid categories but cultural narratives that captured patterned ways of telling retirement stories, reflecting both the distinctiveness of individual experience and the broader social forces shaping women's later lives.

In relation to the study's aims and objectives, Phase One achieved its purpose of exploring how women understand and navigate the TtR, identifying themes and storylines that shaped their experiences, and creating a platform for the co-design process by developing typologies that could act as interpretive tools for subsequent phases. These narrative accounts address current research gaps, demonstrating how NI combined with co-production can generate nuanced portraits of the TtR that are grounded in lived experience and attentive to wider cultural narratives. Phase One therefore generated insights and typologies that offered both interpretive grounding and

practical orientation for the next stage. Phase Two built directly on this basis, using the typologies as tools in a co-design process where participants moved from narrating retirement to actively imagining and shaping possible forms of support.

Chapter Five: Shaping Support Through Narrative Typologies and Workshops

5.0 Chapter Overview

This chapter presents findings from Phase Two of the study. As outlined in **Chapter Three**, this phase marked the move from exploring retirement narratives in Phase One to co-designing potential supports with women in the TtR. Following from the workshop detailed in the previous chapter, two further workshops were carried out: Workshop Two focused on framing the problems of retirement, while Workshop Three centred on developing prototype solutions. The outputs of this phase included composite narratives, problem framings, and narrative prototypes.

5.1 Introduction and Aims

Phase Two represented the create/ideation stage of HCD (IDEO, 2015). Building on the typologies established in Phase One (see **Chapter Four**), this phase began with the creation of composite narratives that translated analytic findings into fictional but recognisable stories. These narratives were used as prompts within the workshops, enabling co-producers to reflect on retirement in ways that were both personal and creative.

The aims and guiding questions for Phase Two were introduced in **Chapter Three (Section 3.2.2)** but are restated here for clarity:

- **Aim:** To collaboratively identify needs and co-create prototype interventions that reflect women's experiences and values.
- **Key questions:**
 1. What concerns, desires, or support needs do women express as most significant during the TtR?
 2. What support mechanisms do women view as valuable and realistically usable during the TtR?
 3. How can intervention ideas be designed with emotional and cultural relevance?

These aims shaped the design of the workshops and provide the framework for the findings presented in this chapter.

5.2 Methods

The design and methodological rationale for the workshops were described in **Chapter Three**, and here I provide a brief account of the procedures followed in Phase Two to situate the findings. I facilitated two workshops, each lasting approximately three hours and drawing on activities adapted from the IDEO (2015) HCD Toolkit (see **Appendices K-L**). Workshop Two focused on identifying and reframing problems in the TtR, while Workshop Three centred on narrating and developing prototype solutions. Recruitment followed the procedures outlined in **Section 3.7** and received ethical approval under the second application (**Appendix F**). All women who had participated in the Phase One interviews were invited to continue, but only Hannah (interviews) and Christine (pilot study) were able to commit further. Additional co-producers were recruited through local networks and community organisations. Workshop Two was attended by Hannah, Christine, Sheila, and Douglas, with Supervisor 2 present in a non-contributory role. Workshop Three was attended by Sheila, Collette, and Hannah, with Supervisor 1 present in support. Further details of recruitment and participation are outlined in Chapter Three (**Section 3.7.3**).

Both sessions were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim. Analysis followed the dialogical narrative approach described in **Chapter Three**, with attention given to how co-producers framed problems, positioned themselves and others within retirement narratives, and generated solutions through narrative exchanges. In line with Creative Analytical Practice (Smith, 2016; Middleton et al., 2024), the workshops were treated as collaborative sites of storytelling in which participants' contributions were both analytical and theoretical in their own right. My task was to identify thematic resonances across stories (understood here as the ways stories connect meaningfully with or resist one another; see **Chapter Seven** for fuller discussion) and to represent these in ways that retained their vitality, emotion, and situated character. This involved moving between story analyst and storyteller roles (Smith and Sparkes, 2009), analysing narrative resources and positioning within the workshops and then weaving

these into composite accounts and typologies that captured the shared and divergent ways women narrated the TtR.

5.3 Composite Narratives

The co-produced typologies developed in Phase One were carried forward into Phase Two through the creation of composite narratives. In preparation for the workshops, I developed four fictional but recognisable characters from the typologies (drawing on the DNA described in **Chapter Three**).

This approach builds on established traditions of CAP (Richardson, 2000) and first-person narrative representation (Douglas and Carless, 2009), which position storytelling as both a mode of inquiry and a means of communicating lived experience. These perspectives extend Frank's (1995) argument that narrative forms reflect cultural scripts for making sense of disruption and repair. Together, they informed the development of composite stories that invite emotional and intellectual engagement while preserving participants' anonymity.

The composites are fictional in that they do not depict any single participant's story but were assembled from recurring experiences, phrases, and emotional tones that appeared across the dataset. They are recognisable because they retain the language, rhythm, and dilemmas that participants used when talking about retirement. This recognisability mattered because it enabled co-producers to connect with the stories as authentic and familiar, while maintaining confidentiality and interpretive distance. Each composite therefore reflected a synthesis of collective experience, constructed to invite empathy and dialogue rather than to represent an individual.

These characters embodied elements of the typologies while presenting fuller stories that could be discussed, critiqued, and reimaged. At the beginning of each workshop, I introduced the composites to co-producers, who were invited to adjust details, challenge aspects they felt inaccurate, and explore alternative directions for the stories. This ensured that the composites functioned as collaborative prompts rather than fixed researcher-driven representations.

The composites marked the first analytic outputs of Phase Two and were used in the workshops to stimulate dialogue without requiring co-producers to disclose their own

circumstances directly. While the typologies were developed with the Phase One interview group, the composites were explored and refined with a different group of co-producers in Phase Two. This allowed the stories to circulate between groups, enabling fresh perspectives on earlier analytic work while also generating new insights. The four composites (Katrina, Cathy, Pauline, and Joyce) are presented in the following sections as they were used directly in the workshops.

5.3.1 Katrina (Corporate Composite)

This composite was developed from the corporate typology introduced in Chapter Four (**Section 4.12.1**). It drew together elements of retirement narratives shared across the Phase One interview data, where identity was strongly shaped by professional life and where a sense of order, discipline, and financial security was central. Katrina's story was written to capture the perspective of women who had invested heavily in their careers and were now facing the challenge of moving from structured routines into an open-ended stage of life. It was constructed using verbatim participant accounts to retain the realist narrative quality and preserve participants' original voice within the composite story.

Katrina's Story

'I'm 38 years pensionable, with no breaks. I have no children, so I've not had a break in service of any description. I've paid full contributions, although just about a year ago I dropped my hours by 3.5 hours. It won't make a dent at this stage. I have my works pension fund which I've been paying into about 12 years, and I've also been paying what are called additional voluntary contributions. That's like a top up and then of course I will be able to claim my state retirement pension at 67, if they don't change it for me before then.

Funnily enough, even before your offer to speak to you came along. And because I don't have hobbies and I don't have anything that you know, I don't go to the gym, I'm not a swimmer. I don't do any of these things. So, it kind of has been on my mind. And my mother, after my dad died, did volunteer work with Cancer Research a couple of afternoons a week. And I think that has given me an indication of something that I maybe would like to try and do volunteer work,

perhaps not something that's going to fill the whole week, but something to give me a bit of a focus. Because I think to do nothing, that would be a bit too much.

As I mentioned earlier, I'm married; I don't have children. So, therefore I don't have grandchildren. I know that a lot of women when they retire take on that caring role. That's obviously not going to be something that I'll be doing, so I will need to look at filling my day somehow. Not every day, but having some kind of focus... I think it's important to have some kind of focus.

If I'm on my own and my husband's still working. I'll probably still get up at the same time as he does because I do that just now, even on the days off so. Even this morning, he's working away overnight. So, the clocks set for his normal get up time, but I just get up at that time. I probably will continue to get up at the same time. My breakfast routine is getting up and sitting, reading the papers from the day before. So, my breakfast routine actually takes me a good 40-45 minutes anyway. I can imagine that will be extended a little bit. I will read the whole paper rather than the bits that I get time to read. Before I know I'll have to move. I really don't know. I mean, if I'm not... If I don't have a focus, I would imagine it will be pottering about the house, tidying, and thinking about things that should be getting done that aren't getting done. And my husband's gardener. So, I'm, you know, rather than cutting the grass, I'm not really the gardener. I could do things under tuition or if you told me specifically, can you do that? But I wouldn't... I don't see myself going out... as much as I enjoy the garden. It's not my role yet. If I were on my own, something happened and that that had to change, I could manage it to an extent, but it's something I enjoy looking at it, but not, you know, but I'm not bothered about getting involved in it. I don't know because without knowing if I do take up something, either as a hobby or volunteer work or as a little job. I'm not sure how my day will transpire.

I know when you hear people say, oh. I don't know how I had the time to work. I don't understand that. I can understand what you're saying about, you know. If you go from 50 miles an hour to nothing. It's something that I am conscious of. And I think that's why, consciously... that certainly in the last year or so, I have

been thinking, right, you need to start thinking about is there something that you want to do? I've even thought about taking a second career when I finish. That's something I've given a little bit of thought to, that could all learn another skill that I would enjoy doing and even to the extent, you know, should I be thinking about learning that that skill now so that you know, if I do go to 60 from the current employer? Yeah. And I could, you know, hopefully seamlessly go into that. I've given a little bit of thought about doing some kind of learning to be some kind of counsellor. Hmm. Think I'm quite good at. You're talking with people in the work, and I felt even that in the last couple of years that I have become better... To help you understand; I had a healthcare eight years ago. I was diagnosed with bowel cancer form. They were very positive that you know that it was treatable. And it transpired that that was the case. But of course, I went through quite significant surgery and was then followed up by chemotherapy and then checked for five years. I'm currently at stage where I've not been checked for three years, but I'm due to go back this year. So, I always say I'm never complacent. Yeah, but of course it gives you a sense of your own mortality as well, even though it didn't give me an epiphany that I wanted to go and run marathons or anything, but it does give you a sense of your own mortality'.

In the workshops, this composite served as a prompt for reflecting on how women negotiate the transition away from professional structures and identities, and on what forms of support might sustain purpose, continuity, or opportunities for reinvention in retirement.

5.3.2 Cathy (Conventional Composite)

This composite was developed from the conventional typology introduced in **Chapter Four (Section 4.12.2)**. It drew together elements of retirement narratives shaped by steady employment, family commitments, and a transition that was expected and largely accepted. Cathy's story was written to reflect the experience of women who view retirement as a natural life stage, often framed by cultural norms and reinforced by established social networks. It was constructed using verbatim participant accounts to retain the realist narrative quality and preserve participants' original voice within the

composite story, ensuring the composite remained grounded in participants lived accounts.

Cathy's Story

'My husband retires in a couple of weeks' time, so that has made me ... He's a few years older than me, but it's made me think about retiring basically, and what will I do when I do it. I'm starting to think about financial planning and all these things. I have a local government pension. I'm very lucky to have that. So that's basically my financial plan.

I don't plan on sharing my retirement plans with my employer at all. I'd rather keep my cards close to my chest. We're having a lot of change here in our organization at the moment. And so, I don't really feel that I want to put myself in any kind of vulnerable position. So, I would not be having that conversation with my employer right now. I know colleagues that have went along to pre-retirement courses and not retired for a couple of years. So, I wouldn't have a problem putting myself forward for a pre-retirement course, but I just wouldn't like to state to anybody I am planning on retiring on X date whatever. So that's kind of where I am.

We do talk about retirement with our colleagues. I work in an office with two other ladies. I'm actually the youngest. They're both a little bit older than me. We do talk about it, and I do worry having worked full time really, all of my life. I had six months off when I had my children, but that's the only time where I have not worked since I left university, and I am worried that I will have massive gaping hole. I like the structure to my day. I'm a morning person. I like getting up early, and I like having a purpose in life. And when you're not working, I think I'm going to have to work quite hard to replace that purpose in life with something. And I don't quite know what yet. Maybe volunteering or something like that. I've got a couple ideas, but nothing firm.

We do have that option to take flexible retirement and loads of people do that. It's a great option, particularly financially, but the kind of person I am, I think... I

don't know that I would be able to switch off the days that I'm not here. So, I think if I'm going to do anything like that, I would be more likely to move to a different role and maybe you know, look at part time. That's a possibility but I don't want to continue doing what I'm doing now.

Social isolation does worry me a bit because if my plan does go as I think it will, I will be the only one in my friend group who is retired. I've been lucky enough to retire a bit earlier and all of them will be working to state pension age. So, potentially another ten years for them. We're all the same age; we're all old school friends. I will have a couple of friends who will be retired, but they don't live locally, so that is maybe going to be an issue, yeah. Yeah, it is worrying, but I do think I'm quite a sociable person. So, as I say, my husband will be retired, but I don't want to spend all my time with him, that's for sure! So, that could mean that a marriage of almost 35 years could be over! No, we need to keep apart. We're not going to be good, too good together. So, I will definitely need to keep my own interests as well. I do foresee myself doing something, volunteering, or something like that. I would hope to meet other people through that.

I have routine, a purpose, I keep busy and active. I do worry about... I'm very much a summer person and my spirits are good in the summer. They're not so good in the winter. I don't know if I would actually define myself as you know, having SAD (Seasonal Affective Disorder), but I definitely have lower mood in the winter months and I think that could potentially be a problem for me. I'm quite interested to see how my husband copes with it because he's absolutely desperate. He's 60, he's desperate to get out of a very high-pressure job. And I think he thinks it's going to be this great Nirvana, this retirement. But I'm not so sure that come the darkest months of November, December, it's going to be the great thing that he thinks it is. So, I'll be interested to see how he copes and yeah, that's going to be quite telling, I think that will influence my decisions.

For about the last nine months I have... We've got into a bit of a health kick, I suppose, because I've been swimming four days a week at 6:30 in the morning and I've managed to maintain that all through the winter. So, it's been really

good, and I would plan to keep doing that when I retire as well. I walk quite a lot as well but I'm finding now as I've got older or certainly in the last couple of years, I don't have the same energy levels in the evening that I do. So, after full-time work, I'm not home till say maybe six most nights but by the time I've made a meal and maybe want to go out for a walk, it's about 8 o'clock and I just don't feel energised to do that now. Whereas a few years ago, I did, I didn't have a problem with it. The switch to exercise early in the morning has really worked for me. So yeah, I'm health wise I would say I'm doing more exercise, and I've done in a long time and I'm really enjoying it, and I would plan to try and keep this up as a lifetime thing now. That's my intention although when I retire, I wouldn't need to go up at 6 o'clock in the morning to do it, hopefully I could go at 8am or something like that. I think what I need to do is to have something to look forward to ... plan, something to do'.

5.3.3 Pauline (Circumstantial Composite)

This composite was developed from the circumstantial typology presented in **Chapter Four (Section 4.12.3)**. It brought together narratives in which retirement was shaped less by choice and more by external pressures such as health problems, redundancy, or caring responsibilities. Pauline's story was written to reflect the experience of women who faced uncertainty and precarity, where retirement arrived sooner or differently than planned, and where resilience was required to adapt to new circumstances. Pauline's account was constructed using verbatim participant accounts to retain the realist narrative quality present in the original interview data.

Pauline's Story

'I'm going to retire in a couple of months' time. I've got my mother to look after too, and she is 89. So, that's basically going to be a full-time job for me anyway. I've got a lot of health issues as well and I just feel that my body is telling me it's time to go. I have type one diabetes. I've had it for 40 odd years now and things are just starting to go wrong now. My eyes are haemorrhaging. The stress in the work doesn't help any. My kidneys don't work properly now either and are sort of packing in if you like. And 25 years ago, I had an abscess in my spine and ended

up with osteoporosis because of that. My spines crumbling and I am in a lot of pain. So, I'm living on pain killers, basically. My spine could crumble at any time. It could just snap. So, I've really got to watch when I am lifting or bending and how heavy things are. I've been like that since I was 19. If I can live on the Tramadol, I'm fine. If I forget to take the Tramadol before I come out that's me, I'm just hopeless, I cannae put one leg in front of the other. But I'm fine. You learn to live with things like this. There's always folk worse off than yourself. And as I say, I can live with the pain, because it's a dull pain if I can manage to take the Tramadol. So, as long as I'm fine at work, I don't mind if I get home and I'm not as mobile as what I should be. At least I'm doing it. I'm in my work and managing to keep my job down.

I do a little part time job. It's cleaning houses for the elderly. And I do it three days a week just for three hours, three days a week. If I want more hours, I can go to the boss of that company, and she will give me more hours. So, I will be out at least three hours, three days a week anyway until I decide I want more. And as I say, it's only three hours one day a week and I've got three jobs. I've got three clients at the moment. But as I say, if I want more, she will give me more. It's just time wise. My mum can do things for herself. It's just that we are a bit scared to leave her on her own because she keeps falling over. But if she's fine on her own then I can leave her for three hours every day to go and do whatever. It will give me something to do other than looking after my mum 24/7.

I had a private pension, but I cashed it in. So basically now, I will only have my pension. I know it will be hard financially. I need to get used to all that, being without a wage coming in every month. but you live by your means, basically that's how I'm living just now. You do what you can, and it is what it is, and you just live within your means'.

This composite was used in the workshops to stimulate discussion about the uneven distribution of resources and the kinds of support that might be most meaningful for women who experience retirement as constrained or imposed rather than freely chosen.

5.3.4 Joyce (Traditional Composite)

This composite was developed from the traditional typology introduced in **Chapter Four (Section 4.12.4)**. It reflected retirement narratives shaped by fragmented or lower-paid employment combined with extensive responsibilities in the home. Joyce's story was written to capture the experience of women whose contributions had often been undervalued, who entered retirement with modest resources, and whose sense of self was closely tied to family and caring roles. It was constructed using verbatim participant accounts to retain the realist narrative tone present in the original data.

Joyce's Story

'I have worked all my life but I've kind of done part-time employment because I brought up children and stuff. I was under a lot of stress at work and that was one of the main factors for taking early retirement. I think it was just at the stage where there were too many changes at work. Everything was moving fast as well. My husband had already retired. It was a joint decision to make. It was the right point in time.

Financially we are doing ok. We always had our money as one. It was never your money or my money. It was always all together. I look at my husband whose pension, and again we work as a team. But... I've worked every bit as hard as he has, trying to work part-time and bringing up children and do all the other and now that you have to look after elderly parents as well. I think that's what women generally do. They care, they're homemakers, they look after their family. My pension will be nowhere close to what his will be, you know. And so, if you take it as an individual. If I was an individual for instance, if there had been a marriage breakdown and my pension would have been awful because I had all those caring responsibilities. I had to take some time off my work when I was younger as well to care for my mum. She had cancer so I had nobody to help me with the children, and I had caring possibilities for her. So, you lose that wee bit as well when you're paying into your private as well. So yeah, as a woman, you're definitely penalised. I think today there is a lot of stress on women. Particularly in the workplace where they are doing two jobs. They are doing their home job,

and they are doing their office job. Or whatever job they do, and you forget about yourself.

I think in today's society, it would be better to be more independent than I am. As Gerald says, I need to be able to look after myself properly because he says, "What if I am not here and you have to do these things?" I rely heavily on him for things like that. I don't know. Maybe it's just me and I'm not sure how I feel about that. I think we are traditionalists in that because he was nightshift, I was the homemaker and did the children whereas he did the 'man's jobs'. He provided and did all the man's jobs, and my job was always extra if that makes sense?

We don't really socialise with a lot of people. We've kind of broken away over the years. We are more family orientated. I haven't been going out socialising when I probably should. So, I will have to watch that and keep my eye on that. I've still got three or four colleagues that I keep in touch with and maybe once a month I have gone to lunch with them. I don't have close friends in my age group round about me. Occasionally there's been things that I've wanted to go to. It's taken me a couple of weeks to steal myself and I wouldn't have thought I would be like that. I think your confidence does take a wee shake however, it's nice to have somebody to go with'.

The workshops drew on this character to inspire discussion about how retirement might provide recognition and new opportunities for women whose earlier contributions had often been overlooked, and about what forms of support could strengthen wellbeing and social connection in later life. Collectively, these composites provided a shared point of reference that could be explored without personal disclosure. In the workshops, they acted as catalysts for reflection and debate, prompting co-producers to consider what each character might need in order to navigate the TtR. This process helped to surface issues that were both personal and collective, illustrating how the "Create" stage of IDEO's HCD process (IDEO, 2015) can be grounded in narrative. By transforming lived experiences into composite stories, the approach kept women's perspectives central to the design process and laid the foundation for the framings

developed in Workshop Two, where the problems of retirement were examined in greater depth.

5.4 Composite Characters as prompts for Framing

The composite characters were central to moving from the typologies developed in Phase One into design work. Each figure drew on Scottish women's accounts of the TtR to create fictional but recognisable narratives that illustrated everyday retirement scenarios. In Workshop Two, these characters provided concrete prompts for reframing problems and supported empathetic engagement, enabling co-producers to consider perspectives beyond their own while keeping discussions grounded in contexts that felt authentic and relatable.

As the composites were used to spark discussion, co-producers treated the characters as if they were real people, often speaking about them in the present tense and speculating about what they might do next. For example, when discussing Pauline (Circumstantial), the group quickly highlighted how her financial insecurity would limit her ability to engage in health or social opportunities. In contrast, reflections on Katrina (Corporate) raised questions of identity and purpose, with co-producers debating how someone used to a high-status role might reconstruct meaning after leaving work. Cathy (Conventional) was associated with concerns about maintaining social ties, while Joyce (Traditional) prompted reflection on the challenges of balancing care responsibilities with personal wellbeing.

These conversations enabled co-producers to visualise each composite as situated in a real social and economic context. For example, Sheila reflected that "Pauline's story feels very close to my neighbour. She also worked part-time around the kids and then realised later she didn't have much pension. It really brings that home." Similarly, Douglas observed that "when I read Pauline, I thought about how many women I know who ended up like that, where it wasn't really their choice, it was circumstance." Katrina also prompted recognition of shared experiences. Hannah remarked, "Katrina's like some of the women I worked with, who had a big identity in their job. You can almost feel how lost she is without the routine." Christine added, "Yes, Katrina has

everything financially, but you can tell she doesn't know what to do with herself. That's a very real problem."

The other composites also prompted strong reactions. Sheila noted that "Cathy reminds me of my own sister. She's always busy, but I don't think she's happy. It's like keeping busy is a way of avoiding thinking about what comes next." Douglas added, "I think Cathy is the kind of person people admire from the outside, but inside she might be struggling." Joyce's story, in contrast, drew concern and sympathy. Christine commented, "Joyce is probably the one I worry about most, she sounds very isolated. You can imagine her at home, not really knowing who to turn to." Hannah agreed, "Yes, Joyce's situation is quite sad, but it's also real. I've seen women withdraw like that when they don't feel useful anymore."

In this way, the composites acted as catalysts for empathy, allowing co-producers to recognise needs and challenges that might otherwise have been overlooked. The process also supported indirect discussion of sensitive issues, with co-producers able to project concerns onto the composites rather than disclose their own situations. This approach reflects a key principle of HCD, where design activities draw on relatable prompts to inspire creative problem-solving, consistent with recent work on empathic co-design that highlights the value of surfacing lived experiences to guide design decisions (Smeenk et al., 2023).

It was through these interactions around the composite characters that the four framings of finance, health and wellbeing, social connection, and information and development emerged. The following subsections present these framings, illustrating how co-producers redefined problems by imagining the composite characters' needs and reflecting on what forms of support might be appropriate for them. Detailed activities and outputs from this session are included in **Appendix K**.

5.4.1 Finance

Finance was the first area of concern raised in Workshop Two, and the discussion often returned to the composite characters Pauline and Joyce. Pauline's story of insecure employment and limited pension contributions prompted recognition that financial

precarity could overshadow all other aspects of retirement. Sheila captured this clearly, stating:

It's almost like Maslow's hierarchy¹⁵ ... If you haven't got enough to live on, then you are not going to be able to think about other things until that is sorted. The financial bit becomes all-consuming, and you can't move on unless you've got that bit sorted. *(Sheila)*

Pauline's situation provided a tangible example of how insecurity could limit access to opportunities for health, connection, or development. Joyce's character, who had worked consistently but accumulated only modest returns, also provoked discussion. Christine reflected on her own experience in a way that resonated with Joyce:

When I looked at my pension, I thought, do you know, if I wait another two years... I really wasn't going to get much more. And I thought I'm just going to take what I've got, accumulated over forty years, and just went. *(Christine)*

Hannah added that for some women pensions provided little security at all:

It's a difficult one because I had only joined the pension four years... so my pension is not great... I rely totally on my husband's income now until next year when I get state pension. *(Hannah)*

These exchanges emphasised how composite characters offered a safe prompt for reflection, while also encouraging co-producers to project elements of their own experiences into the discussion.

Douglas, drawing on his professional expertise, broadened the conversation to systemic issues. He noted that financial checks were routinely provided to support people entering employment, but rarely at retirement:

¹⁵ ¹⁵ Sheila's comment referenced Maslow's hierarchy of needs, a psychological theory which proposes that basic needs such as food, shelter, and security must be met before individuals can attend to higher-level needs related to belonging, esteem, or self-actualisation (Maslow, 1943).

We don't do much of it for retirement... so it's all emptied to work. Getting into work, staying in work. I would say a financial check would be a good thing because money is a worry and worrying can make health issues. (*Douglas*)

The group also explored the practical barriers to accessing advice. Services were described as under-promoted and unevenly available, with Douglas expressing frustration that many remained unaware despite years of provision. Christine and Hannah admitted they had not known such support existed, reinforcing how information gaps left women uncertain about entitlements.

DNA highlights two further layers in this discussion. First, stigma and pride often discouraged people from seeking help. As Douglas recounted, pensioners sometimes refused to claim benefits they were due, fearing they would be seen as undeserving:

“There are people out there entitled to top up benefits that are not claiming it just for fear.” (*Douglas*)

Sheila echoed this dynamic, observing that women she had worked with often felt:

“I'm not worth it. I don't deserve it. I'm not going to tell anybody that I'm struggling.” (*Sheila*)

Second, silences in the workshop were telling. While Douglas spoke at length about the mechanics of pensions and benefits, co-producers refrained from disclosing their own financial details, instead allowing composites such as Pauline and Joyce to carry those anxieties. This indirect mode of discussion showed how the characters provided distance for sensitive topics to surface.

By grounding abstract concerns in the lives of the composites, the group reframed finance as a foundational issue that cut across other retirement domains. Through the How Might We activity, this was distilled into the guiding question: “*How might we support women to feel more confident in managing finances after leaving work?*” (see **Appendix K** for the workshop activity materials and outputs).

5.4.2 Health and Wellbeing

The composite characters Pauline and Cathy were central to discussions of health and wellbeing. Pauline's circumstances prompted reflection on how financial insecurity

constrained opportunities for physical and emotional health. Co-producers noted that if Pauline could not afford to participate in structured activities, her wellbeing would be doubly at risk. Christine captured this more broadly when she explained:

“Sometimes you need something to look forward to, otherwise the days just slide into each other.” *(Christine)*

Her comment pointed to the importance of accessible opportunities that sustain motivation and routine.

Cathy’s story, in contrast, resonated with concerns about confidence and belonging in group activities. Sheila reflected on her own experiences in ways that echoed Cathy’s narrative: “The last time I went to something like that, I felt like everyone knew what they were doing. I just wanted to disappear.” She added: “It’s the kind of thing I know I should do, but it makes me feel panicky,” and concluded that lighter, more flexible activities might feel less intimidating: “Could be a nice idea if it’s not too heavy.” Cathy’s composite thus provided a way of articulating the emotional barriers that could inhibit participation, even when activities were technically available.

Douglas extended the discussion by highlighting structural barriers that prevented women from engaging in wellbeing opportunities:

“There are classes everywhere, but they’re either too expensive or not really aimed at people like us.” *(Douglas)*

His point reinforced that health initiatives needed to be both affordable and culturally relevant. Hannah added a further layer, stressing the importance of personal awareness and adaptation:

I think you have to have that awareness and be aware of who you are and what your skills are. What is transferrable and what you want to be involved in. What your time frame is. *(Hannah)*

Her reflection revealed that wellbeing was not static but required ongoing negotiation as women adapted to new circumstances.

From a dialogical perspective, these conversations revealed both what was said and what was left unsaid. While co-producers voiced concerns about cost, confidence, and accessibility, there were silences when the conversation touched on more sensitive topics such as mental health decline or fear of ageing. The composites enabled participants to project such concerns indirectly, suggesting that wellbeing was not only about PA but also about emotional resilience, identity, and the capacity to reimagine one's life stage. By working through the composites, co-producers transformed abstract anxieties into designable problems. This process was captured in the *How Might We* question: "*How might we make opportunities for health and wellbeing in retirement more accessible and welcoming for women?*" (see **Appendix K** for the workshop activity materials and outputs).

5.4.3 Social Connection

Concerns about social connection surfaced repeatedly in Workshop Two, often linked to the composite characters Joyce and Katrina. Both figures represented women whose networks had been reduced by retirement, prompting reflection on the fragility of friendships, the strain on intimate relationships, and the challenges of sustaining a sense of belonging.

Sheila reflected on the abrupt loss of everyday contact when leaving employment:

You lose your social relationships when you stop work. I mean who do you talk to? Siblings, husbands, wife's, partners? But you lose all that social contact you are so used to, and you think... (*Sheila*)

Douglas added that despite promises of keeping in touch, workplace ties often dissolve:

"Everybody says when you leave, oh we will keep in contact, but it drifts, and it drifts, and it goes." (*Douglas*)

Such accounts emphasised that retirement involved not only a shift in daily routine but also a restructuring of social identity.

The composite Joyce, presented as married but uncertain about her future direction, stimulated a wider debate about relationships in retirement. Douglas noted:

The amount of people I have known that have split up when they retired because eventually when the two of them have retired and the two of them are in the house at the same time and actually realise... I can't stand him! (*Douglas*)

Sheila pointed to the importance of space and independence, explaining:

Fortunately, I still do love my husband very much and I'm very happily married but we've also got enough space in the house that we can have a separate room... during lockdown, that sort of space was important. (*Sheila*)

Hannah, meanwhile, acknowledged the risk of over-dependence:

"My husband and I were falling into that category... we will hit a stage where one of us will have to rebuild our lives." (*Hannah*)

These stories highlighted that cohabitation in retirement could be both a source of comfort and a point of strain, depending on the availability of personal space, outside interests, and supportive friendships.

DNA interpretation highlights how these exchanges oscillated between humour, resignation, and concern. Christine, for instance, described small but telling moments of domestic disconnection:

I don't have much conversation with my husband anymore. He's quite funny. I'll be sitting watching something and he just walks by and picks up the remote and sits down and watches *Tipping Point* or something like that. And I just think... I used to say, for goodness's sake Donald! But now I just think, that's fine. He's happy. It's time for a cup of tea. (*Christine*)

Here, light-hearted storytelling masked a deeper recognition of shrinking conversational space and shifting intimacy.

The discussion also moved outward, towards possibilities for collective activity that might reduce isolation. Sheila proposed a mentor scheme:

If you are maybe thinking about these women... I could go down and meet the walking group and go for the walk on the Thursday morning but I'm shy and don't

want to do that myself. But there's a Bank of mentors that mentor people that have just retired. *(Sheila)*

Douglas similarly emphasised the need to highlight benefits rather than simply advertise activities:

If you don't know what the benefits are and you just hear that there's a walking group... but if you try and promote it in a really positive way, you get some people that will maybe give it a go and try. *(Douglas)*

Cumulatively, these reflections demonstrated that social connection in retirement was less about the availability of groups and more about how opportunities were framed, how confidence was negotiated, and how shifting identities could be supported. The creative design element raised further questions: what kinds of supports could help women navigate the loss of workplace ties? How could activities be promoted in ways that felt relevant rather than stigmatising? Through the "How Might We" activity, the group reframed these concerns into the question: *"How might we create opportunities for women to build and sustain meaningful connections after leaving work?"*

5.4.4 Information and Development

The final domain of concern identified in Workshop Two centred on information and personal development. While co-producers acknowledged that resources and services existed, they stressed that these were often fragmented, inconsistently promoted, or inaccessible to those unfamiliar with digital technologies. Douglas explained that although newsletters and local papers might appear "the most boring thing on the planet," they were vital for many people who had "not even touched a computer or a keyboard in their life." His comment highlighted the persistent digital divide, suggesting that the shift to deliver information primarily online risked excluding precisely those who might benefit most.

The discussion also returned to questions of timing and forward planning. Sheila emphasised that advice needed to be available well before retirement, since "if you decide to look at financial, months before you retire you don't have any time to do anything about it." At the same time, she noted the challenge of persuading younger generations to prepare, given the economic pressures they face: "It's very hard to tell

someone that's thirty, like my son, you really need to be thinking now." These reflections pointed to a tension between recognising the importance of early preparation and the reality that many people are constrained by insecure or low-paid work.

Experiences shared by Hannah and Christine illustrated how inadequate support left some women feeling undervalued at the point of retirement. Hannah recalled:

I walked into my head teacher and said, 'I'm retiring'. I made that decision. Nobody once said, 'Are you okay? Is there something wrong or are you okay financially?' (*Hannah*)

Christine similarly described how her departure after decades of service was reduced to an administrative matter:

"Within twenty minutes... I thought, I'm only a number, that's me been replaced!" (*Christine*)

Such stories revealed a striking absence of pastoral or practical guidance, with retirement treated less as a personal transition than as an organisational problem to be managed.

These accounts raised broader questions about the role of employers and local authorities in supporting retirement. Hannah insisted that "local authorities should have that obligation," while Douglas added that workplace responses often prioritised cost savings over individual wellbeing: "They just think, oh, that's somebody away, that's fine. Do we fill the post, or do we not fill the post to save money?" For co-producers, this lack of recognition was more than symbolic; it represented missed opportunities to provide structured advice, reassurance, or even basic acknowledgement of the significance of leaving long-term employment.

From a dialogical perspective, these exchanges conveyed a mix of frustration, resignation, and humour. While recognising the difficulty of tailoring provision, co-producers expressed a desire for development opportunities that were empowering rather than reductive. As one discussion put it, a class or session framed as "welcome to the third age" might feel alienating rather than supportive. What was needed was

provision that respected women's skills, experiences, and aspirations, while acknowledging the emotional weight of transition.

The composite Katrina prompted debate on how women might retain a sense of growth and purpose when career identities recede. Co-producers argued that information alone was insufficient unless it was accessible, trustworthy, and connected to real opportunities. This raised further design questions about timing, delivery, and stigma: how could resources be provided early enough to be useful, while avoiding the sense of being labelled as 'old'?

Through the design activities, these insights were reframed into the question: "How might we ensure that women approaching retirement have access to timely, relevant, and non-stigmatising information that supports both planning and personal growth?" This framing linked the practical challenges of navigating pensions and benefits with the deeper need for recognition and continued development, situating information as a foundation for confidence in the TtR.

5.4.5 Synthesis of Framings

The four framings of finance, health and wellbeing, social connection, and information and development emerged directly from co-producers' engagement with the composite characters. Pauline and Joyce prompted recognition of finance as a foundational issue, with their contrasting experiences illustrating how financial insecurity or limited gains shaped retirement possibilities. Cathy's story drew attention to confidence, belonging, and the emotional labour involved in joining new groups, while Joyce's circumstances highlighted the difficulty of sustaining social connection when care responsibilities and changing routines reduced available time. Katrina's professional background provoked reflection on identity, purpose, and the role of accessible information, showing that even women with strong skills might require structured opportunities to reorient in retirement.

Through these characters, co-producers were able to move beyond abstract concerns and instead visualise retirement problems as lived realities situated in social and economic contexts. The composites allowed sensitive issues to be approached indirectly, while still fostering empathy and recognition. Importantly, the framings were

not imposed by me as the researcher but were co-produced in dialogue, shaped as participants debated what the characters might need and how their situations might unfold.

The “How Might We” activity consolidated these insights into designable opportunities. Finance, wellbeing, connection, and development were articulated as interlinked priorities, forming a shared platform from which to progress. This collective reframing created the conditions for Workshop Three, where co-producers began to move from problem identification towards the creative work of prototyping potential solutions.

5.4.6 Reflexive Commentary on Composite Characters and Framings

As facilitator, I was struck by how quickly co-producers animated the composite characters, speaking about them as if they were people they knew. Pauline was consistently read through the lens of financial precarity, which seemed to draw immediate empathy from the group. At the same time, there was some tension around whether her situation was typical or unusually disadvantaged, with co-producers reflecting on how structural inequalities in employment and pensions meant that many women were closer to Pauline’s story than they first acknowledged.

Katrina prompted a different reaction. Some co-producers saw her as resourceful and independent, but there was also unease about whether her professional background set her apart from more ‘ordinary’ retirement experiences. At points, co-producers asked whether she was too atypical to be relatable, or whether her story reflected only a small minority of women. This questioning was important because it revealed that co-producers were not treating the composites as fixed types but as starting points for debate in creating solutions.

Cathy’s character seemed to evoke ambivalence. Co-producers recognised her desire for connection but also highlighted the emotional difficulty of joining new groups, often projecting their own hesitations onto her. Joyce, meanwhile, was frequently associated with responsibility and care, prompting acknowledgment of how retirement can coincide with ongoing obligations rather than unstructured freedom as it is commonly portrayed.

From a reflexive standpoint, I noted how the composites enabled indirect exploration of sensitive issues, reducing the pressure on individuals to disclose personal circumstances. Yet they also revealed the limits of typology-based characters, as participants sometimes resisted elements they did not identify with or questioned whether the stories captured the diversity of women's lives. These moments of debate were productive, as they reinforced that the framings were co-produced through dialogue, while my understandings were also shaped by existing literature and theory.

Overall, the use of composite characters proved successful in enabling empathetic engagement and lively debate, confirming their value as a methodological tool within the co-design process. The framings that emerged in Workshop Two therefore represented a collective redefinition of the problems of retirement. By imagining how the composites might navigate issues of finance, health and wellbeing, social connection, and information and development, co-producers moved beyond description into the territory of design. These discussions also created space for differing perspectives to be expressed and negotiated; at points, co-producers explicitly challenged the financial assumptions introduced by Douglas, drawing on their own lived experiences to question and reframe what constituted realistic or meaningful support. These framings also generated the "How Might We" questions, which set the stage for Workshop Three, where the same composite characters were carried forward to guide the co-creation of potential solutions.

5.5 Workshop Three – Narrating and Developing Prototypes

Building on the framings generated in the previous session, Workshop Three shifted focus from identifying problems to exploring potential solutions. As outlined in **Chapter Three**, I facilitated this workshop with support from Supervisor 1. Three co-producers attended: Collette, Sheila, and Hannah. Held in the late morning, the session included a shared lunch, which fostered a relaxed and conversational atmosphere while also serving as a thank you for their continued involvement. By this stage, the group had become familiar with one another, and the dynamic was noticeably more collaborative and open.

The composite characters were carried forward as prompts to ground design work in recognisable retirement experiences. Alongside the “How Might We” questions developed in Workshop Two, they provided starting points for imagining how retirement concerns might be addressed in practice. Co-producers reflected on what different characters might need, how they might use or resist forms of support, and what would make potential solutions feel usable and relevant. This narrative approach ensured that design ideas were situated in the lived realities of retirement rather than in detached abstractions. The following subsections trace how discussions in Workshop Three unfolded, showing how early ideas took shape through dialogue.

5.5.1 Early Idea Building

The first part of Workshop Three centred on revisiting the composite characters and the “How Might We” questions developed in the previous session. Rather than moving directly to fixed solutions, co-producers reflected on how women like Pauline, Joyce, Cathy, and Katrina might experience retirement and what forms of support could feel meaningful. This process encouraged participants to link the fictional but recognisable composites to their own perspectives, generating new insights about the conditions that make support effective.

Sheila highlighted the importance of language, questioning whether the term ‘retirement’ itself was limiting:

I think it might be quite impactful, making a positive choice... I’m wondering if there’s something about taking away the word retirement. And it’s maybe next stage or it’s maybe something else... about contributions. What you can contribute that will maybe be more inclusive. *(Sheila)*

Her reflection connected directly to Katrina’s story, raising the possibility that women accustomed to professional roles might engage more positively if opportunities were framed around ongoing contribution rather than withdrawal.

Collette echoed this concern about language and value, linking it to her own voluntary commitments:

Which it isn't, cause that means only paid work is valuable... I mean, God, this week I've done about 10 hours of voluntary work unpaid, and I take it as seriously as I do my work. *(Collette)*

Her comment resonated with both Joyce's and Cathy's composites, reinforcing that unpaid roles are central to women's retirement transitions and should be recognised within support design.

Echoing the discussion in Workshop Two, Sheila again drew on Maslow's hierarchy of needs to emphasise finance as the foundation for other aspects of retirement. She appeared to repeat almost the same point, underlining its importance for her:

I think, it almost looks like Maslow's hierarchy... If you haven't got enough to live on, then you are not going to be able to think about other things until that is sorted. *(Sheila)*

While finance had been a prominent theme in the earlier session, here it was directly tied to the composites, as co-producers reflected on how Pauline's limited resources might constrain her opportunities.

Collette pushed the conversation toward prevention and early preparation, suggesting that financial awareness should begin well before retirement:

What we need to do is go way way back to when people start employment. To get them to understand the importance of preparing for the day when they no longer are working... I think we need to train people from the get-go that you need to put away money. *(Collette)*

This comment illustrated how the composites opened broader reflections about the life course, while still keeping retirement realities in view.

Hannah's contribution shifted the tone toward relational dynamics, as she connected her reflections on the composites with her own circumstances. In particular, she highlighted how retirement transitions can reshape household relationships and routines:

“Being at home with my husband I suppose and retraining him more to the point. He started doing triathlons. He was in his 60s.” (Hannah).

Her comment illustrated how adjustments in later life are not experienced in isolation but in relation to partners and family members, a theme that resonated with the challenges represented in the composite stories.

These exchanges began to shape early ideas about what support should look like: accessible, inclusive of unpaid roles, financially realistic, and attentive to identity and relationships. One suggestion was the development of an app that could centralise information about retirement, from financial entitlements to opportunities for social connection and health. Co-producers noted that such a tool could be updated quickly, overcoming the problem of printed material going out of date, and could serve as a single source to counteract the “myths and legends” that often circulate about pensions and benefits. The app was also imagined as a platform that could be signposted in everyday community settings such as leisure centres or supermarkets, widening reach beyond the workplace. However, doubts were raised about feasibility, including barriers around cost, digital literacy, and ensuring inclusivity for those without regular internet access. The idea did not progress, but the discussion was valuable in showing how co-producers weighed potential solutions before converging on more tangible prototypes. It also foreshadowed later priorities around accessible and connected forms of support, illustrating how even proposals that were not carried forward influenced the direction of the design process. The composites provided continuity with Workshop Two while allowing co-producers to move from empathy to practical imagination, laying the groundwork for the prototypes that would emerge later in the session.

5.5.2 The Retirement Café

One of the first ideas to take clearer shape in Workshop Three was that of a social space which co-producers later described as a Retirement Café. This concept grew from discussions of Cathy and Joyce, whose composite stories had highlighted challenges of confidence, belonging, and sustaining social ties. Rather than imagining a

formal or structured programme, co-producers envisioned a relaxed, everyday environment where women could come together without feeling judged or pressured.

Sheila emphasised that the appeal of such a space lay in its informality: “It would need to be somewhere you can just drop in, not another class where you’re expected to keep up.” Her point reflected Cathy’s reluctance to enter intimidating group settings and suggested that the café could provide a more welcoming and manageable alternative. Hannah echoed this sentiment, observing: “If it’s just a café, it doesn’t feel like a big commitment. You can go along for a cup of tea, see what it’s like, and if you don’t like it you don’t have to go back.”

Collette connected the idea to her concern about recognising unpaid contributions, noting that the café might provide a platform to share skills and experiences: “It’s not about being told what to do. It could be a place where people say, well, here’s what I’ve been doing, or here’s something I can show you.” This comment built on Katrina’s narrative, where professional experience remained a significant part of her identity, but also resonated with Joyce’s ongoing family and community responsibilities.

Hannah also brought attention to the importance of companionship, linking back to earlier reflections on navigating retirement alongside her husband: “It’s easier if you’re with someone, even if it’s just for the first time. You don’t feel so on your own walking in.” Sheila added that the sense of welcome would be central: “Sometimes it’s just about having somewhere you feel welcome. If it’s friendly, people will come back.” These reflections highlighted that the café’s value lay in both social connection and the creation of a low-pressure environment where women could try something new without fear of judgment.

The group also considered practicalities, debating where such a space might be hosted. Collette observed: “Libraries or community centres are sitting there half empty half the time. You wouldn’t need something new, just to use what’s already there.” This comment highlighted the importance of affordability and accessibility, both of which tied back to Pauline’s limited resources.

Through these discussions, the idea of the Retirement Café began to crystallise as a flexible, low-barrier intervention. It was imagined as a place where women could meet,

exchange knowledge, and build social ties in an environment that felt ordinary and non-intimidating. By grounding the concept in the lives of the composite characters, co-producers ensured that the café was more than a generic community idea: it was a specific response to the concerns and needs surfaced through Pauline, Joyce, Cathy, and Katrina.

5.5.3 The Buddy Scheme

Another idea that gained momentum in Workshop Three was the notion of a Buddy Scheme. This prototype emerged from reflections on Cathy's lack of confidence in approaching new groups and Pauline's vulnerability when resources and familiarity were scarce. Rather than emphasising independence, co-producers recognised the value of companionship in reducing the barriers that often-prevented women from engaging with opportunities in retirement.

Sheila framed the issue as one of confidence: "It's not that you can't do it, it's that you don't want to walk into a room where you feel everyone else already knows what's happening." This comment resonated strongly with Cathy's character, who embodied hesitation and discomfort in unfamiliar settings.

Hannah expanded on this, highlighting the reassurance that comes from shared experience: "Sometimes it's just knowing someone else is also figuring it out... not someone who's sorted it all out." Her reflection pointed to the importance of mutuality, the idea that buddies should not be positioned as experts but as peers negotiating similar uncertainties. Collette reinforced this point, observing: "The first time is always the hardest. If someone goes with you, then you're more likely to go back on your own." Hannah added: "It's about getting over that first barrier. Once you've been, it's not so scary."

Collette also brought in a practical perspective, noting that such support should be flexible rather than prescriptive: "You don't want it to be another system with rules and paperwork. It just needs to be someone you can link up with, so it feels lighter." Her caution reflected a broader concern, evident throughout the workshop, that retirement interventions should avoid replicating the formal structures of paid work.

The Buddy Scheme therefore emerged as an intervention designed to lower the emotional threshold for participation. It was not envisaged as a mentoring programme but rather as a peer-based, informal pairing system. By exploring the idea against the composites, co-producers saw how Cathy and Pauline might benefit from having a companion to accompany them into new environments, easing anxieties and making initial steps feel more manageable.

5.5.4 Women's TtR Exercise Class: Reimagining Physical Activity in Retirement

The third prototype to emerge in Workshop Three was developed as the Women's TtR Exercise Class. While the label reflected the co-producers' language, the discussions around it revealed a broader ambition: to reimagine how PA could be made accessible, enjoyable, and socially meaningful for women entering retirement. Crucially, the class was envisioned as geared specifically towards women in this age group, acknowledging that their needs and expectations differ from both younger exercisers and older populations typically targeted by active ageing initiatives.

Sheila highlighted that conventional provision often failed to meet the needs of women at this transitional stage: "A lot of classes feel like they're designed for people who are already fit. If you haven't done it before, it's easy to feel out of place." Her reflection suggested that age-specific provision could reduce the sense of intimidation and exclusion, particularly for women like Cathy who were imagined as hesitant to enter new environments. She later reinforced this point by adding: "It would need to be for people our age. Otherwise, you just feel out of place."

Hannah emphasised that the class should be framed as enjoyable and social rather than strictly health-focused: "It has to feel like something you'd look forward to, not just something you're told is good for you." She added: "It has to be fun, or people won't keep coming back. If it feels like a chore, it won't work." By situating PA in a context that was both age-appropriate and socially rewarding, she highlighted that women in the TtR were motivated as much by connection and belonging as by health outcomes.

Collette drew attention to the practical barriers that often-shaped participation, pointing out that resources should be used wisely: "Gyms and classes can be

expensive, and they're not always near where you live. It would need to be something that uses what's already in the community." Her comment reinforced that affordability and local accessibility were essential for this age group, particularly for women like Pauline whose finances were limited.

Through these discussions, the Women's TtR Exercise Class was developed as more than a generic fitness opportunity. Co-producers described it as affordable, community-based, and socially supportive, combining the need for confidence-building with recognition of financial and relational realities. By grounding the concept in the composite characters, they envisioned an intervention that could address both the opportunities and constraints specific to this stage of life.

5.5.5 Synthesis of Prototypes

These prototypes did not emerge in isolation. They were built cumulatively, drawing on the narrative interviews and early themes of Phase One, the composite characters that developed from those accounts, and the iterative design work of Phase Two. In this sense, the prototypes embody the trajectory of the research: from listening to women's stories, to framing problems collectively, to imagining concrete responses.

The process also highlighted an important gap in existing approaches to supporting women in the TtR. Much of the literature on interventions for older adults describes programmes designed from the top down, often prioritising health outcomes or economic participation (Foster and Walker, 2015; Calasanti and King, 2020). By contrast, the prototypes in this study were shaped from the bottom up, grounded in the stories of women themselves and in the collaborative dialogue of the co-design workshops. This methodological choice demonstrates the power of stories to illuminate lived experiences and to generate practical, context-specific solutions.

Although developed within a small co-design group, the prototypes reflected concerns and priorities voiced consistently across Phase One and Phase Two. Their grounding in everyday experiences such as financial insecurity and confidence in social spaces gave them resonance with the composite characters and with the discussions that shaped them. These insights set the foundation for a reflexive consideration of how the co-

design process unfolded and what it revealed about facilitating collaborative work in this context.

5.5.6 Reflexive Commentary

Facilitating Workshop Three required balancing several roles simultaneously. As the person guiding the activities, I was focused on keeping time, introducing the tools, and steering conversation back to the agreed tasks. Alongside this, I was conscious of my position as a researcher aiming to observe and analyse the unfolding dialogue. Holding both responsibilities was demanding. I often felt that while I was concentrating on ensuring the workshop progressed according to plan, I risked missing subtle cues in the conversation or opportunities to probe points of tension.

These challenges were heightened by my own health circumstances, which at times made sustained concentration difficult. Episodes of brain fog were particularly disruptive, leaving me momentarily unsure of what had already been said or which step of the process I was meant to lead next. Managing fatigue and cognitive lapses while learning to apply design tools that were new to me required considerable effort. I noted afterwards that focusing on the practical tasks of facilitation, such as guiding the activities, keeping notes, and managing time, sometimes made it harder for me to step back and observe the discussion more critically. This dual responsibility of facilitation and analysis was one of the most testing aspects of Phase Two.

In addition to the challenges within the workshop itself, the period between Workshop Two and Workshop Three was equally demanding. I had to transcribe and analyse the full discussions from Workshop Two, recruit and confirm attendance for Workshop Three, and plan the logistics of the session. Preparing the structure and presentation materials and devising ways to recap the earlier findings for the group, all had to be completed within a limited timeframe. This workload added pressure to the facilitation, since I was often moving quickly from analysis to planning to delivery without much space for recovery or reflection. These practical demands formed an important but often invisible part of the co-design process.

I was also aware of the stature and experience that the co-producers brought to the group. Several held professional or community leadership backgrounds, and their

confidence in discussion could be intimidating. At times, I felt unsure whether to step in and redirect conversation, especially when debate took unexpected turns, or to allow it to unfold organically. On reflection, these moments highlighted the co-productive ethos of the project: knowledge was being generated collaboratively, not dictated by me as the facilitator. The very fact that I felt unsettled is indicative of the methodological stance I had taken, one that valued the input of participants as equal contributors to the research.

What was most striking, however, was how the composite characters helped anchor the process. They provided a shared focus that allowed me to step back when needed. Because co-producers treated the characters as real people, the composites carried the weight of the discussion, enabling the group to explore sensitive or complex issues without me needing to directly prompt or intervene. In this way, the design tools and narratives acted as scaffolding, supporting both the group and me as facilitator.

From a reflexive perspective, I came to see these workshops as embodying the same insights that shaped the women's retirement stories: navigating uncertainty, adapting to new roles, and finding ways to participate despite constraints. While co-producers debated how Cathy, Joyce, Pauline, or Katrina might overcome barriers, I was at the same time negotiating my own as a novice facilitator working through health challenges. These parallels confirmed that the process of co-design was inseparable from the lives of those involved, and that facilitation required as much adaptation and resilience as the retirement journeys, we were discussing.

Overall, Workshop Three confirmed for me the value of bringing NI and HCD together. The process was demanding, but it showed how story-based activities could help translate framings into tangible prototypes. I came to see the prototypes less as neat or polished outcomes of my facilitation and more as the product of dialogue, debate, and compromise among the group. My role was to hold open a space where uncertainty was allowed, and where women's stories could shape the design of interventions in ways that felt both resonant and feasible.

5.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented the findings from Phase Two of the study, which aimed to collaboratively identify needs and co-create prototype interventions that reflect women's experiences and values during the TtR. Building on the research objectives introduced in **Chapter Two** and the methodological approach outlined in **Chapter Three**, Phase Two centred on two co-design workshops where co-producers worked with composite narratives to frame problems and explore possible solutions.

Workshop Two focused on surfacing and reframing concerns about retirement. Using the composites as prompts, co-producers identified issues across four domains: finance, health and wellbeing, social connection, and information and development. These discussions demonstrated that women's concerns were shaped not only by individual adjustment but also by relational, structural, and cultural factors. The process transformed abstract worries into design opportunities, expressed through "How Might We" questions that created openings for creative exploration (IDEO, 2015).

Workshop Three built directly on these framings, carrying the composite characters forward into the design stage. In this session, co-producers considered what women like Pauline, Joyce, Cathy, and Katrina might realistically need or find helpful. Through iterative discussion, three prototype interventions were developed: the Retirement Café, a welcoming and informal space for connection; the Buddy Scheme, designed to reduce barriers to participation through companionship; and the Women's TtR Exercise Class, which reimagined PA as affordable, social, and tailored to this life stage. Other suggestions, such as a digital app, were also explored but not taken forward. The three selected prototypes were endorsed most strongly by the group and regarded as tangible ways of addressing the priorities set out in Workshop Two.

The outputs of Phase Two therefore consist of three interlinked elements: the problem framings from Workshop Two, the composite characters that anchored design discussions, and the intervention prototypes that took shape in Workshop Three. Together, these outputs illustrate the progression from listening and developing typologies in Phase One to active co-design in Phase Two. They demonstrate the methodological value of combining storytelling with design activities, showing how

women's experiences informed both the identification of problems and the generation of practical responses.

The process was also shaped by my reflexive engagement as facilitator. Balancing the dual roles of guiding activities and analysing discussions, alongside the practical workload between workshops, was demanding and at times intensified by health challenges. Yet these pressures highlighted the value of the scaffolding provided by the typologies from Phase One, together with the composite characters and structured design tools, which enabled the group to stay focused while reducing the pressure on individuals to disclose personal circumstances. Overall, Phase Two shows how co-design workshops can move beyond surface-level consultation to create interventions grounded in women's lived realities. The typologies, composites, and prototypes developed here provide the foundation for Phase Three (**Chapter Six**), where their functionality was tested through SC.

Chapter Six: Story Completion Findings – Resonance, Typologies, and the Transition to Retirement

6.0 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to present the findings from Phase Three of the study, in which the SC activity was implemented to test the resonance and functionality of the co-designed prototypes. The focus here is on how participants responded to the fictional story stems, the narratives they produced, and what these reveal about the resonance and functionality of the Retirement Café, Buddy Scheme, and exercise class prototypes.

As outlined in **Chapter Three**, SC was adopted as a narrative method consistent with the study's social constructionist and dialogical orientation. This alignment also reflects the study's ontological stance, which views knowledge as relationally and contextually produced through language and story. In this sense, SC provided a way to explore how imagined experiences of retirement support were co-constructed through participants' engagement with culturally available narratives, rather than as reflections of pre-existing truths. **Furthermore, Chapter Three** described in detail the process through which the prototypes were translated into story stems, piloted, and refined into an apparatus capable of carrying the research into its final phase. That chapter also explained the rationale for using SC in place of material prototyping, the ethical and practical considerations that informed this choice, the recruitment strategy, and the eventual composition of the dataset. The present chapter therefore does not repeat those methodological details. Instead, it builds directly on that groundwork by presenting how participants engaged with the SC activity and what the resulting stories reveal about women's expectations and imaginings of retirement support.

The aim of Phase Three was to explore the functionality of the prototypes within imagined contexts. Unlike Phase One (**Chapter Four**), which gathered personal narratives of retirement, or Phase Two (**Chapter Five**), which centred on co-design through creative and collaborative dialogue, Phase Three invited participants to write short, imaginative accounts in response to open-ended story stems. Although the stories were fictional in form, they were meaningful in how they revealed participants' sense-making about retirement, support, and identity (Williams et al. 2022). Through

this process, the prototypes were encountered narratively rather than materially, producing insight into how they might be experienced, resisted, or re-imagined by women approaching or entering retirement. In this sense, the stories functioned as performative representations, acts of imagining that made visible what might otherwise remain unspoken. As Williams et al. (2023) suggests, narrative imagination can provide a space of inquiry where new relational and affective possibilities emerge through story. The three phases together illustrate an iterative design linking lived experience, collaborative co-design, and narrative experimentation.

Analysis of the dataset followed the principles of DNA introduced and contextualised in **Chapter Three**. The stories were examined for what they said about the prototypes and for what they did in narrative terms. Analysis considered how they affiliated with imagined communities, circulated cultural expectations about ageing, retirement, and PA, and functioned to normalise, question, or resist particular possibilities. In this way, the findings extend the typology framework developed in Phase Two, while also highlighting the distinctive affordances of SC as a narrative mode of intervention concepts. To my knowledge, this is the first use of SC to explore the narrative functionality of intervention prototypes in retirement research, offering a novel contribution through the development of a layered resonance–typology framework.

The chapter begins with a dataset overview and an account of how a typology of narrative positions was developed, before presenting findings for each prototype in turn. A cross-cutting synthesis then considers how these positions interacted with the broader retirement typologies identified earlier in the thesis, followed by a reflexive account of working with narrative imaginings. This term, following Clarke and Braun's discussions of SC as a creative and interpretive method (Braun et al., 2019; Clarke et al., 2021), acknowledges that while SC responses are written as fictional stories, they hold interpretive value as sites where cultural meaning is actively produced and explored. The final section connects these findings to the wider discussion developed in **Chapter Seven**.

6.1 Data Overview

The SC activity generated 29 narrative responses from 15 women in the TtR. Following revisions to the task design, participants were invited to complete one fictional story stem rather than all three. This change gave participants greater flexibility, reduced the sense of pressure associated with the activity, and encouraged them to select the scenario that resonated most with their own perspective. Ethically, this adjustment reduced the burden on participants and helped to preserve the collaborative spirit that underpinned the wider project. The distribution of responses and participants' reflections on affinity, preference, and intended use are summarised in **Table 17**.

Table 17. Distribution of Story Completion Responses Across Prototypes

Prototype (Stem)	Number of Stories	Most Drawn To	Affinity (Tick All)	Would Use Service
Retirement Café	11	6	6	9
Buddy Scheme	8	2	3	6
Exercise Class	1	7	8	10
Total	29	15	17	25

This distribution shows that all three prototypes elicited narrative responses, though to varying degrees. The Exercise Class prototype attracted the highest levels of engagement across preference, affinity, and intended use, while the Retirement Café was also popular, particularly in terms of willingness to use such a service. The Buddy Scheme generated fewer responses overall but still prompted meaningful engagement. These variations are analytically significant because they reveal how the prototypes resonated in different ways with women in the TtR.

The dataset was considered sufficient for dialogical narrative analysis (DNA), consistent with Braun et al. (2019), Clarke et al. (2019), and Gravett (2022), who emphasise that the value of SC lies in the richness and variability of the material rather than in sheer numbers. The stories varied widely in tone, length, and form, ranging from extended plots to more fragmentary accounts. Several participants introduced additional figures such as family members, friends, or community contacts, shifting the

emphasis from the individual character to wider social contexts of retirement. This diversity created a dataset well suited to DNA, which prioritises the cultural resources, positions, and identities expressed through narrative over the sheer volume of text.

To preserve analytic transparency, verbatim extracts are used throughout this chapter, while the complete set of anonymised responses is included in Appendix R. To provide further context, **Table 18** summarises the demographic and affiliation information of the Phase Three participants. Details are included on age, employment status, retirement timing (anticipated or recent), marital status, and SIMD quintile where available. The table also records how participants were recruited and which prototype scenarios they completed. This combination of demographic and affiliation information illustrates the diversity of circumstances represented and the varied pathways through which women engaged with the study. Two participants (P9 and P12) did not complete a story but provided this information, which is reflected here and discussed further in **Section 6.14**.

Table 18. Demographic and Recruitment Characteristics of Story Completion Participants (*Phase Three; A = Café, B = Buddy Scheme, C = Exercise Class*)

ID	Age	Employment Status	Retirement Status	Marital Status	SIMD Quintile	Recruitment Method	Prototype(s) Completed
P1	57	Retired	Within the last 6 months	Married	5	Word of mouth	A, B, C
P2	54	Full Time	Within the next 2 years	Married	3	Word of mouth	A, B, C
P3	61	Full Time	Within 4-5 years	Divorced	4	Work Email	A, B, C
P4	57	Full Time	Within 2-3 years	Divorced	5	Work Email	A, B, C
P5	54	Part Time	Within 4-5 years	Married	n/d	Work Email	A, B, C
P6	62	Part Time	Within the next 12 months	Married	4	Word of mouth	A, B, C
P7	69	Retired	Within the last 12 months	Married	4	Work Email	A, B, C
P8	59	Part Time	Within 4-5 years	Married	5	Work Email	A, B, C
P9	67	Retired	Within the last 12 months	Married	5	n/d	Did not complete
P10	67	Part Time	Within 1-2 years	Married	5	Email	A
P11	58	Part Time	Within 1-2 years	Married	1	Work Email	A
P12	55	Part Time	n/d	Married	2	Other - Email	Did not complete
P13	56	Part Time	n/d	Married	3	Work Email	C
P14	63	Part Time	Within 1-2 years	Other	3	Work Email	C
P15	72	n/d	Within 1-2 years	Married	3	Work Email	A

n/d = not disclosed

6.2 Developing a Typology of Narrative Positions

To interpret the diverse responses, a typology of narrative positions was developed. This framework captures how participants engaged with the scenarios emotionally and discursively, highlighting the varied ways women imagined support during the retirement transition. Unlike the broader typologies established in **Chapter Four** (*Conventional, Traditional, Circumstantial, and Corporate*), which describe distinctive orientations to retirement, the focus here is on the stance each story adopted toward the prototypes in a particular moment. The unit of analysis was therefore the story itself, rather than the participant (Riessman, 2008).

The typology was developed inductively through iterative analysis, involving close reading of stories for affective tone, structure, and the positioning of characters in relation to the imagined interventions. In line with the study's dialogical and social constructionist approach (Frank, 2012; Riessman, 2008), responses were treated as performative acts that enacted identities and circulated cultural expectations about ageing, retirement and PA. This process generated five recurring narrative positions:

- **Embracing** – stories that welcomed the prototype with enthusiasm, portraying the character as reassured, socially connected, or newly purposeful.
- **Tentative** – stories marked by hesitation or cautious engagement, often highlighting the need for reassurance, safety, or gradual entry.
- **Ambivalent** – stories that mixed optimism with doubt, balancing hope for connection with concern about obligations, fit, or overcommitment.
- **Resistant** – stories that rejected, critiqued, or distanced the character from the prototype, emphasising independence, scepticism, or disinterest.
- **Redirecting** – stories that transformed or re-routed the scenario toward alternative activities, relationships, or forms of support, often pointing to unmet needs.

These positions are not fixed categories but heuristic tools for interpretation. Some stories moved between positions, while others blended elements of more than one. What they share is a way of illustrating *how* imagined support was engaged with,

questioned, or redefined. Collectively, these positions offer a more detailed perspective on how participants engaged with the prototype scenarios in this phase, while also extending the broader typologies introduced earlier in the thesis.

It is important to distinguish between narrative positions and resonance orientations. Narrative positions describe the stance adopted within a single story toward the prototype, focusing on how characters are positioned in a given moment. Resonance orientations, developed in the following section, capture the broader emotional, embodied, and cultural patterns that emerged across stories. To clarify, narrative positions operate at the level of individual story acts, whereas resonance orientations represent recurring affective and cultural tendencies across the dataset. **Table 19** summarises these distinctions.

Table 19: Distinction Between Narrative Positions and Resonance Orientations

Feature	Narrative Positions	Resonance Orientations
Unit of analysis	The stance taken within an individual story toward a prototype	Recurring emotional and cultural patterns across multiple stories
Focus	How a character engages with the imagined support (Embracing, Tentative, Ambivalent, Resistant, Redirecting, Disconnected)	The overall emotional tone and cultural logic shaping the response
Relation	Immediate and story-specific	Emergent and cross-story, building on positions

The same affective descriptors (*Embracing, Tentative, Ambivalent, Resistant, and Redirecting*) recur at the next analytic level as resonance orientations, where they represent shared emotional, embodied, and cultural logics observed across multiple stories rather than within individual narratives. (A sixth pattern, *Disconnected*, emerged later in the analysis at the resonance level, described in **Section 6.3**).

This layered position–orientation approach has not previously been applied to retirement research. Using it here extends DNA by mapping how women positioned themselves across imagined interventions, demonstrating the cultural logics and emotional tones that underpin engagement with support in the TtR.

To support transparency and provide a sense of scope, **Table 20** presents a visual map of the Phase Three dataset. This schematic illustrates how SCs were distributed across the three prototype scenarios and the six resonance orientations, offering a clear picture of how these analytic layers intersect. It also functions as a navigational aid for the analysis that follows, which explores how these orientations played out in detail across the Retirement Café, Buddy Scheme, and Exercise Class stories. A larger version of this figure is included in **Appendix S** for reference.

Table 20: Distribution of Story Completions Across Prototypes and Narrative Positions

Narrative Position	Retirement Café	Buddy Scheme	Exercise Class	Total
Embracing	3	2	3	8
Tentative	2	2	2	6
Ambivalent	2	1	1	4
Resistant	2	1	2	5
Redirecting	2	2	2	6
Total	11	8	10	29

It is also important to acknowledge that these interpretations were shaped by the story stems I designed and by the analytic framework applied. While participants' narratives were generated in fictional form, the ways they positioned characters in relation to the prototypes revealed cultural expectations and uncertainties around ageing, retirement, and PA. My reading of these accounts is therefore both situated and dialogical, reflecting how the method enabled participants to test possibilities while also shaping what could be imagined.

6.3 Narrative Resonance Typologies

Building on the distinction outlined in **Section 6.2**, each story was analysed through a layered framework that considered narrative positioning (*Embracing*, *Tentative*, *Ambivalent*, *Resistant*, and *Redirecting*) and the broader emotional and cultural resonance of the scenario. This approach made it possible to examine *what* participants imagined about each intervention and *how* they expressed meaning

through story: the affective tone, the unfolding of the narrative, and the ways characters engaged with themes of identity and connection (Frank, 2012; Riessman, 2008).

From this process, six resonance orientations were identified: *Embracing*, *Tentative*, *Ambivalent*, *Resistant*, *Redirecting*, and *Disconnected*, representing shared emotional and cultural patterns that emerged across multiple stories rather than within individual narratives. The sixth category, *Disconnected*, was introduced during later analytic cycles to account for stories that remained emotionally flat or disengaged, where the imagined scenario appeared to fail to evoke meaningful identification or investment. These typologies describe the recurring emotional orientations that shaped how women's stories engaged with the prototypes. Whereas narrative positions (**Section 6.2**) focus on the stance adopted within an individual story, narrative resonance typologies capture broader patterns of affective and cultural orientation across the dataset.

The typologies were developed through iterative cycles of close reading, annotation, and memo-writing, during which recurring patterns were actively interpreted and refined. As these patterns became clearer across participants and scenarios, the analysis focused on identifying the core narrative movements within the stories, including how the character engaged with the offer of support, how the emotional tone was shaped, and whether the prototype was accepted, rejected, reshaped, or set aside.

For clarity, the six resonance typologies are summarised in **Table 21**. They capture variations in story form and emotional orientation rather than categorising participants. In several cases, the same participant adopted different positions across scenarios, reflecting the contextual and imaginative nature of narrative engagement (Frank, 2012; Riessman, 2008; Gubrium and Holstein, 2009).

Table 21: Summary of Resonance Typologies in Story Completion Responses

Typology	Description	Key Narrative Features
Embracing	Positive engagement with the scenario	Optimistic tone; character embraces support; story expands with confidence and connection
Tentative	Supportive but with reservations	Hesitation; internal deliberation; seeking reassurance
Ambivalent	Mixed or contradictory feelings	Tonal shifts; unresolved tension; simultaneous hope and doubt
Resistant	Rejecting or distancing from the intervention	Critique; distancing; questioning assumptions or relevance
Redirecting	Reimagining the scenario in alternative directions	Proposing different activities, roles, or relationships; repositioning the character
Disconnected	Flat or disengaged response	Minimal engagement; brief, perfunctory, or withdrawn responses

As was also evident in the retirement typologies developed in Phase One (*Corporate, Circumstantial, Conventional, and Traditional*), these categories are not mutually exclusive. Stories sometimes blended qualities from more than one typology or shifted between them as the narrative developed. This fluidity aligns with Frank’s (2012) dialogical view of stories as responses to multiple, sometimes conflicting cultural narratives, and with Riessman’s (2008) reminder that narratives often embody contradiction rather than stability. Where ambiguity existed, analytic decisions were documented through memos, and interpretations were refined in dialogue with the dataset to ensure transparency and reflexivity.

What distinguishes these typologies is their emotional tone and narrative direction. *Embracing* stories carried optimism and growth, *Tentative* ones unfolded with hesitation, and *Ambivalent* ones balanced hope with doubt. *Resistant* stories pushed back against the prototypes, *Redirecting* stories reshaped them toward different needs, and *Disconnected* stories were marked by withdrawal or minimal engagement. Read alongside the broader retirement typologies from **Chapter Five**, these resonance patterns highlighted important overlaps and tensions. *Traditional* orientations often

gave rise to *Tentative* or *Ambivalent* responses, especially when prototypes disrupted expected routines. *Conventional* and *Corporate* orientations were more likely to produce *Embracing* stories, particularly where structure and peer support were emphasised. *Circumstantial* orientations tended toward *Resistant*, *Redirecting*, or *Disconnected* responses, reflecting the difficulty of aligning standardised support with disrupted or constrained retirement trajectories.

Through this interpretive process, the SC responses revealed more than surface-level impressions. They illuminated how women negotiated support emotionally and narratively, why certain prototypes resonated or failed to engage, and how imagined futures were shaped through narrative. While the stories cannot predict real-world behaviour, they offer valuable insight into how retirement support is made meaningful or misaligned through narrative experimentation, as participants effectively ‘storied into’ the imagined interventions, trying them on in narrative form (Beggan, 2024; Braun, Clarke, and Gray, 2019; Gravett, 2019). These resonance typologies will be revisited in **Section 6.8**, where they are considered alongside the broader retirement narrative typologies developed in Phase Two, highlighting the layered dynamics of how women imagined support during the TtR.

6.4 Findings: Retirement Café

The first set of stories responded to the Retirement Café scenario, in which Katie, a woman approaching retirement, encounters an advert for a new café designed to support women at this life stage. Participants were invited to continue Katie’s story, imagining what happened next (see **Appendix O** for the full story stem). Eleven stories were generated, ranging from short depictions of Katie’s first impressions to longer narratives in which she became a regular visitor. Several introduced additional characters such as partners, friends, or fellow attendees, who shaped Katie’s experience of belonging or unease. Some stories portrayed the Café as warm and inclusive, offering companionship and information at a time of uncertainty. Others raised doubts about whether Katie would feel comfortable in this environment or whether the Café would truly meet her needs. The following extracts illustrate this range of responses and the different ways participants engaged with the Retirement

Café concept, analysed through the layered typology framework introduced in **Section 6.2.**

Positive orientations: belonging, reassurance, and possibility (Embracing)

Several stories aligned with the *Embracing resonance typology*, positioning the Retirement Café as a welcoming space where Katie quickly found connection and reassurance about retirement. In A1, Katie is greeted warmly by a regular attendee who introduces her to others and highlights both social and practical opportunities:

“Kate came and introduced herself. She said that she likes to come and welcome any new faces to the place... Both these ladies had retired and were loving life... They said the cafe had lots of information on various activities, financial help etc and Kate could point me in the right direction for any information I may need. I went back to work wishing that the retirement was the next day.” (A1)

This account positions Katie within a ritual of welcome, drawing on cultural scripts of hospitality and peer guidance. The café is depicted as a place that combines information with a sense of welcome, helping to shift Katie’s feelings from apprehension to anticipation. Similarly, A2 describes Katie forming an immediate bond over gardening, which extends into volunteering and ongoing friendship:

“She also met a lady named Chris who was in the same transition period as herself. They both have a keen interest in gardening... Before leaving the cafe, she and Chris agreed to meet the following week at the allotment. She felt happy that she had went along to the cafe, although she was apprehensive at first.” (A2)

Here, shared interests create affiliation. The gardening theme mobilises cultural narratives of growth and care, functioning as a metaphor for renewal and positioning Katie as both learner and contributor. These *Embracing* accounts position Katie as someone who is welcomed, valued, and able to contribute. They draw on familiar cultural resources of friendship, volunteering, and self-improvement, framing the Café

as a bridge between uncertainty and possibility, and shifting the narrative of retirement away from decline and towards new beginnings.

Ambivalent and mixed orientations: caution, resistance, and balance (Tentative / Ambivalent / Resistant)

Other stories reflected more *Tentative* or *Ambivalent positions*, combining interest with hesitation, critique, or resistance. In A5, Katie’s initial enthusiasm fades as involvement begins to feel burdensome:

“After a while she was being asked to get involved in setting up events and promotions and going to the cafe it started to feel like hard work. There were also a couple of people who seemed to spend a lot of time moaning and being quite negative about the local area. This put Kate off a bit as she just wanted to enjoy her free time and not feel overly committed to anything. Katie started to go less and less to the cafe and after a year or so realised she wasn't particularly enjoying it anymore.” (A5)

This narrative aligns with the *Resistant* typology, framing the café as reproducing unwelcome obligations. Katie is positioned as defending her autonomy against pressures of duty and negativity. Retirement is constructed here as freedom from work-like commitments, not their extension. In A7, Katie’s experience is marked by alienation and disappointment:

“Lots of people clearly knew each other too... She really wanted to know what was on in her area that was a bit different... The offering seemed a bit samey, yoga, book clubs, etc... After some pleasantries were exchanged she moved on rather quickly... Generally it was helpful in telling her what she already knew but not really moving her forward.” (A7)

This story exemplifies ambivalence. Katie is positioned as seeking novelty and inclusivity but encountering sameness and exclusion. The café is portrayed as insular and unimaginative, drawing on wider cultural critiques of community initiatives that fail to reach beyond the familiar (Buffel, 2018; Phoenix and Bell, 2021). A8 offers a more balanced depiction, combining optimism with caution:

“Katie went away feeling optimistic that there were possibilities for her to get involved in some of the social activities on offer and perhaps encourage some of her friends to join her too... She could see a downside of retirement was deciding how to make good choices of spending your time, but it would also be possible to easily overcommit and she was thoughtful about finding a good balance.” (A8)

This account reflects a *Tentative* stance, highlighting the tension between opportunity and restraint. Katie is positioned as proactive but reflective, drawing on cultural discourses of balance and self-care to negotiate enthusiasm alongside caution. These ambivalent stories highlight the pull between women’s desire for connection and their wariness of losing autonomy or falling back into obligations.

Redirecting orientations: reassurance, contribution, and self-definition

A further set of stories presented the Café positively, but with an emphasis on how Katie might use it as one resource among many. In A3, Katie frames the Café as a place to ease her transition and to support others:

“I decided that if I volunteered this may help my transition from full time to retirement, I am feeling concerned about what I will do with my time when I am retired... Coming to the café will help me, and hopefully I can help others.” (A3)

In this story, Katie is imagined as both helper and learner. The story positions volunteering as a cultural resource for easing transition, where contribution mitigates anxiety. In A4, Katie finds reassurance in meeting others who share her apprehensions:

“Katie still feels she has something to offer and is keen to be kept busy when she retires. The cafe also gave Katie an opportunity to meet and talk with people like herself, who were apprehensive about their approaching retirement... The trip to the retirement cafe in her lunch hour made Katie feel less apprehensive and equipped her with information and contacts to make her retirement a rewarding experience.” (A4)

This narrative validates uncertainty while presenting the café as a space of recognition and reassurance. It mobilises shared apprehension as a cultural script, normalising

doubt and framing community as a source of strength. A6 expands this into a collective account, highlighting shared concerns about finances, family, and health:

“They came from all backgrounds, some married, some widowed, some with grandchildren and others who were entirely alone in life... They agreed that they had many concerns in common and a few of them agreed to meet up in a couple of weeks for a coffee and to support each other.” (A6)

The story broadens Katie’s individual transition into a collective one, showing solidarity across diverse circumstances. It draws on cultural resources of mutual aid and support groups, highlighting belonging through shared vulnerability. In A10, Katie is positioned as seeking guidance after decades of work and caregiving:

“Faced with the daunting task of leaving colleagues who she had worked with for over 20 years and the prospect of trying to make new friends seemed to be a challenge... Katie was looking for guidance on how to use her time constructively, but also to allow her some breathing space and making time for herself after bringing up a family and working full time since leaving school 40+ years ago.” (A10)

Here, retirement is framed through a gendered life-course lens, combining the end of work with release from long-term caregiving. The café functions as a restorative space, offering both information and permission for self-care. Finally, A11 conveys reassurance and excitement, framing the Café as confirmation that Katie is making the right choice:

“She is optimistic about her forthcoming retirement. She has no regrets and her plans are going ahead... She comes out of the cafe, feeling reassured of her decision. Time is up! She is going ahead.” (A11)

This story positions Katie as resolute and affirmed, drawing on cultural scripts of decision-making and forward movement. These stories align with the *Embracing or Redirecting* resonance typologies. They show how participants used the scenario to negotiate broader themes of purpose, self-definition, and collective identity in retirement, positioning the Café as one resource within a wider constellation of

strategies. These layered accounts are developed further in **Section 7.10**, where the Retirement Café is considered as a prototype intervention

6.5 Findings: Buddy Scheme

The second set of stories responded to the scenario of June, a woman who has decided the time is right to retire and is moving to the coast. The stem began:

“June has decided that the time is right for her to retire and has given her notice at work. She has always wanted to live by the sea and is moving to the coast. She is unfamiliar with the area and doesn't know anyone. She has looked online and has found a retirement buddy scheme operating near her new home which supports women in their retirement transition. She gives them a call and ...”

Participants were invited to continue June's story, imagining what might happen when she contacted the scheme. Eight stories were generated in response. Some presented the Buddy Scheme as highly effective, offering June companionship, information, and reassurance as she adapted to a new life by the sea. Others expressed doubt about whether she would find the scheme helpful or comfortable. A smaller number presented *Redirecting* accounts, recognising its potential but also the limits of formalised support. These responses are discussed below through the layered typology of narrative positions and resonance patterns introduced in **Section 7.2**.

Positive orientations: welcome, confidence, and opportunity (Embracing)

Both participants who adopted this orientation depicted the Buddy Scheme as a reassuring and enabling resource. In B1, June's apprehension about moving is quickly eased by a warm and informative response:

“June phoned up and a lovely lady called Mary answered the phone and put her at ease straight away. She said that she could arrange for June to meet up with a buddy who would be of a similar age and who had retired to the area in the past couple of years. She also said there were regular meetings where women could meet together to talk about their experiences and to share advice and information. June felt reassured that there was a way of making friends and becoming involved in her new community.” (B1)

This account positions June as initially anxious but quickly reassured. The scheme is framed as warm, structured, and responsive, offering both information and companionship. In B2, the story develops into ongoing confidence and friendship:

“She was introduced to Ann, who took June to the community centre where there were lots of groups and activities. June was very nervous, but Ann made her feel comfortable and introduced her to everyone. June went along to the sewing group with Ann and found she enjoyed it. Over time she began to attend more activities and made more friends. She is now confident in her new surroundings and grateful to the buddy scheme for helping her settle into her new life by the sea.” (B2)

Here, June is positioned as moving from nervous newcomer to confident participant. The narrative draws on cultural resources of mentoring and gradual integration, showing how support can transform anxiety into belonging. Other stories described the Buddy Scheme as opening pathways to both friendship and new roles. In B5, June transitions from recipient to contributor:

“She met with her buddy twice a week and they would go to different activities together. June really appreciated having someone to go along with and it gave her the confidence to try new things. June was so grateful for the support that after a year she decided to become a buddy herself, helping other women who were in the same position as she had been.” (B5)

This narrative frames June’s story as a cycle of reciprocity. The Buddy Scheme is positioned as enabling confidence that eventually flows outward, as women who were once supported become supporters themselves. Similarly, B6 portrays the scheme as a launchpad for belonging and engagement:

“June’s buddy introduced her to local walking groups and the book club. She felt she had made a good friend and was able to build her confidence in her new environment. She began to take part in more activities and gradually felt more settled. June is now actively involved in the community and feels she has settled well.” (B6)

The focus here is on companionship as a gateway to community life. B8 extends this trajectory further, with June eventually taking on an organising role:

“The buddy scheme was so helpful that June decided to join the committee that ran it, ensuring other women had the same opportunity. She found that through helping others, she gained confidence and made lasting friendships.” (B8)

This account positions June as someone who moves from user to leader, reflecting cultural narratives of self-development and contribution in later life. Collectively, these *Embracing* stories depict the Buddy Scheme as a resource that eases relocation, builds confidence, and fosters reciprocity.

Ambivalent and resistant orientations: discomfort, opting out, and disappointment (Tentative / Ambivalent / Resistant)

Other stories adopted *Tentative*, *Ambivalent*, or *Resistant* positions, raising doubts about whether June would find the Buddy Scheme comfortable or useful. In B3, her initial interest gives way to awkwardness:

“She phoned and was given details of a buddy. They met for coffee, but June didn’t feel a connection. The lady was very different from her and talked a lot about things June wasn’t interested in. June was polite but decided that the scheme wasn’t for her and that she would try to meet people in other ways.” (B3)

This narrative exemplifies tentativeness: June remains open to connection but disengages when the connection feels superficial. A similar note is struck in B4, where the buddy relationship feels forced:

“She was allocated a buddy, but they didn’t really click. June found it hard to make conversation and felt the whole thing was a bit contrived. After one meeting she didn’t pursue it further, and instead joined a local exercise class where she started to make friends naturally.” (B4)

Here, the story takes a more *Ambivalent* stance, contrasting “contrived” support with “natural” connection. The Buddy Scheme is critiqued as artificial, highlighting a preference for relationships that develop more naturally. In B7, the tone is more directly negative, portraying the scheme as ineffective:

“When she called, the person at the other end seemed disinterested and said there was a long waiting list. She was told someone would be in touch, but nobody ever called back. June felt disappointed and decided it was easier to just do things on her own.” (B7)

This story aligns with the *Resistant* typology, positioning the scheme as unreliable and bureaucratic. June is left to rely on herself, echoing broader cultural critiques of under-resourced services (Grenier et al., 2017; Buffel and Phillipson, 2018; Phoenix and Bell, 2021). These ambivalent and resistant accounts show how participants questioned the authenticity and reliability of structured interventions.

Redirecting orientations: balancing support with autonomy

A smaller group of stories illustrated *Redirecting* positions, acknowledging the scheme’s potential while emphasising personal autonomy. In B4, June disengages from the formal buddy arrangement but uses the initial encounter as a catalyst to pursue friendships in a local exercise class. This response reflects *how* participants could imagine the scheme as a prompt rather than an endpoint, reshaping support to better fit their own preferences. B8 also reflects pragmatism, framing the scheme as supportive and limited:

“The buddy scheme was so helpful that June decided to join the committee that ran it, ensuring other women had the same opportunity. She found that through helping others, she gained confidence and made lasting friendships.” (B8)

Here, June combines participation with active contribution, showing how women imagined shaping support in ways that aligned with their own values. These different orientations are considered further in **Section 7.11**, where the Buddy Scheme is explored as a prototype intervention

6.6 Findings: Exercise Class

The third set of stories responded to the scenario of Betty, a woman preparing for retirement and hoping to improve her health while building new social connections. The stem began:

“Betty is retiring in three months. She is determined to reduce her weight and care for her health better. She would also like to make new friendships away from her work environment. She has seen an advert for an exercise class for women in the transition to retirement. She decides to go along to the exercise class and ...”

Ten stories were generated in response. Some depicted the class as welcoming and transformative, offering Betty friendship, confidence, and a renewed sense of identity. Others expressed *Ambivalence* or *Resistance*, positioning the class as inaccessible, overwhelming, or unsuited to her needs. A smaller number adopted *Redirecting* positions, emphasising health management and self-care. These accounts are considered here through the layered typology of resonance and positioning introduced in **Section 6.2**.

Positive orientations: welcome, fun, and transformation (Embracing)

Stories exemplifying the *Embracing* position framed the exercise class as a supportive environment where Betty found encouragement, companionship, and renewal. In C1, the atmosphere is welcoming and uplifting:

“She was surprised to find that everyone was really friendly. The instructor was encouraging and adapted the exercises to suit everyone. Betty enjoyed the class so much she decided to join the group each week. Over time she noticed she was losing weight and felt fitter. She also made new friends and looked forward to seeing them. Betty was glad she had made the decision to go.” (C1)

Betty is positioned as reassured and rewarded, with the class imagined as physically transformative and socially affirming. In C2, humour and companionship are central:

“She was welcomed warmly by the group and joined in. Although she found some of the exercises hard she felt better for doing them. There was a lot of laughter and Betty enjoyed the fun atmosphere. She chatted to the women afterwards and found they had lots in common. She was glad she went and decided she would go again the following week.” (C2)

Here, laughter and conversation function as cultural markers of belonging, softening anxieties about physical challenge. Other *Embracing* stories emphasised persistence and renewal. C4 frames Betty as resilient and supported, moving from struggle to reward:

“At first Betty found the class hard going but she persevered. The other women encouraged her and she started to feel fitter. She lost some weight and her confidence grew. She enjoyed the classes and began to socialise with her new friends outside the class as well.” (C4)

C9 makes the connection explicit between physical improvement and psychological identity:

“Betty enjoyed the class so much she signed up for a block of ten sessions. She felt fitter, healthier, and more positive about the future. She also felt she had found a new identity outside of work and was excited about the opportunities that lay ahead in retirement.” (C9)

And in C10, optimism and continuity are foregrounded:

“Betty joined in and was made to feel welcome straight away. She enjoyed the class and felt more energetic afterwards. She arranged to meet some of the women for coffee and looked forward to going again. She felt positive about her retirement and the changes ahead.” (C10)

These stories position the exercise class as both a social and transformative space, reinforcing cultural scripts of perseverance, lifestyle improvement, and optimism at retirement. They also highlight how PA continues to be imagined as a key component of active ageing, offering insight into how women negotiated health, identity, and belonging in their stories of retirement (Tulle, 2007, 2008; Beggan, 2024).

Ambivalent and resistant orientations: frustration, exclusion, and unmet expectations (Tentative / Ambivalent / Resistant)

Not all accounts were positive. Several participants narrated Betty’s experience as marked by frustration, discomfort, or exclusion. In C3, Betty’s determination is quickly undermined by comparison and embarrassment:

“Betty found the exercises too difficult and became very self-conscious. She struggled to keep up and felt embarrassed. The other women seemed much fitter than her and she felt out of place. After a couple of sessions she decided it wasn’t for her and stopped going.” (C3)

Here, the class is positioned as intimidating and competitive, illustrating a *Tentative* entry that ends in withdrawal. C5 also highlights struggle but with more sustained disappointment:

“At first she was enthusiastic but she found it difficult to keep up with the routines and the class didn’t seem to get any easier. Betty felt demoralised and disappointed. She stopped going after a few weeks and decided she would be better off walking by herself.” (C5)

This account reflects an *Ambivalent* stance: Betty initially invests in the class but ultimately resists the idea that structured group exercise is the best route to health. In C7, exclusion is rooted in the social environment:

“Betty went along but found the group was very cliquy. People already seemed to know each other and she felt left out. The instructor was more interested in the regulars and didn’t really make her feel welcome. She decided not to go back.” (C7)

This narrative aligns with a *Resistant* position. Finally, in C8, disappointment arises from misaligned expectations:

“Betty joined the class but found it was too gentle. She had hoped for something more challenging and felt it wasn’t really helping her. She enjoyed meeting some of the women but she soon looked for a different class that suited her better.” (C8)

Within this narrative, the class is resisted as insufficient, highlighting the diversity of women’s needs and the risks of one-size-fits-all provision. These accounts surface vulnerabilities around fitness, inclusion, and expectations, showing how structured provision can unintentionally reproduce barriers, particularly when programmes assume a shared baseline of confidence, ability, or motivation.

Redirecting orientations: health management and self-care

One story adopted a *Redirecting* stance, positioning Betty as cautious, methodical, and responsible. In C6, she engages with the class as part of a broader strategy for health management:

“She went to the class but first she consulted her doctor to make sure it was safe. Betty also booked an appointment with a personal trainer who gave her exercises she could do at home. She felt more confident going to the class knowing she had checked everything out properly. She also saw a dietician who helped her with her eating plan. Over time she lost weight, felt healthier, and gained confidence. She was pleased that she had taken responsibility for her own health.” (C6)

This *Redirecting* orientation reflects broader cultural narratives of individual responsibility, risk management, and planning in later life. The class is not rejected but reframed as one element of a larger self-directed approach. These accounts are returned to in **Section 7.12**, where the exercise class is considered as a prototype intervention.

6.7 Cross-Cutting Analysis

Across the three story stems, several cross-cutting orientations emerged that illuminate how women imagine retirement support as relational, culturally situated, and emotionally charged. These patterns cut across prototype scenarios, highlighting common tensions in how support was accepted, negotiated, or resisted. Analysing these shared dynamics provides insight into broader cultural narratives that shape women’s imagined engagements with retirement interventions.

Patterns of embrace

Many stories reflected *Embracing* orientations, positioning support as a bridge into social life, wellbeing, and renewed identity. These narratives emphasised community, perseverance, and optimism, framing retirement as a fresh beginning.

Ambivalence and resistance

Alongside these, other stories revealed discomfort or disengagement. Women

described anxieties about overcommitment, unease with contrived companionship, or frustrations with exclusion. These accounts highlighted how structured activities can reproduce rather than reduce vulnerability.

Redirecting orientations

Some responses adopted *Redirecting* positions, recognising value in support while reshaping it to fit individual strategies. Here, responsibility, autonomy, and balance were emphasised, with initiatives treated as partial rather than complete solutions.

Resonance across prototypes

Despite differences in form (informational, relational, or activity-based), the three prototypes surfaced shared concerns. Women sought reassurance and connection but often resisted forms of support that felt heavy, contrived, or lacking authenticity. No single prototype emerged as universally resonant or clearly more aligned with participants' imagined needs. Instead, the same tensions between enthusiasm and caution, belonging and difference, and autonomy and structure played out across all scenarios. This suggests that the variability in women's imagined engagements is shaped less by the specific design of the intervention and more by their broader retirement narratives and orientations.

As outlined in **Chapter Five**, these orientations reflect diverse cultural scripts and personal trajectories across the *Traditional*, *Conventional*, *Circumstantial*, and *Corporate* typologies, which influence how support is interpreted and valued. The shared patterns identified here therefore reveal the importance of narrative positioning and cultural resonance, rather than prototype format alone, in shaping how support interventions are imagined.

Link to typology layering

These varied tones highlight the importance of resonance. Some stories embraced support, others resisted, while many balanced optimism with caution. The layered typology introduced in **Section 6.2** helps to make sense of these orientations, spanning *Embracing*, *Tentative*, *Ambivalent*, *Resistant*, *Redirecting*, and *Disconnected* positions. This integration of resonance typologies with retirement narrative typologies represents an analytical innovation within the study's existing methodological framework. While

typological layering has been explored in health and illness contexts, it has not been applied to the retirement transition, nor to the exploration of imagined interventions. **Section 6.8** builds on this by examining how these narrative orientations intersect with the retirement typologies introduced in **Chapter Five**, highlighting the layered dynamics that shaped women's imagined engagements with support across all three prototypes.

6.8 Integrating Resonance with Retirement Narrative Typologies

As outlined in **Section 6.3**, analysis of the SC responses produced six resonance typologies (*Embracing, Tentative, Ambivalent, Resistant, Redirecting, and Disconnected*). These categories captured the emotional tone and orientation of the stories, showing how participants positioned themselves in relation to the prototypes. Here, the focus shifts to how these resonance patterns intersected with the broader retirement narrative typologies developed in **Phase Two (Chapter Five)**.

Patterns across the dataset were identified through analysis of how resonance was shaped by the interplay between the prototype scenarios, and the orientations women had previously articulated in relation to retirement. For example, stories reflecting *Traditional* narratives (structured by routine and stability) often carried *Tentative* or *Ambivalent* tones, particularly when a prototype implied unfamiliar or disruptive change. *Corporate* narratives (oriented toward productivity and planning) were more likely to align with *Embracing* or *Redirecting* responses, emphasising structure and forward momentum. *Conventional* narratives (centred on community and relational continuity) often resonated with prototypes that reinforced companionship and mutual support. *Circumstantial* narratives, frequently shaped by disruption, loss, or constrained choice, tended to generate *Resistant, Redirecting, or Disconnected* stories, reflecting the difficulty of engaging with interventions built on assumed stability. These patterns are summarised in **Table 22**, which illustrates the intersections between the retirement narrative typologies identified in Phase One and the resonance typologies developed through the SC analysis in Phase Three.

Table 22: Intersections Between Retirement Narrative Typologies (Phase One) and Resonance Typologies (Phase Three)

Retirement Narrative Typology (Phase One)	Common Resonance Patterns in SC (Phase Three)	Interpretive Notes
Traditional (routine, stability)	Tentative, Ambivalent	Narratives framed change as a potential disruption. Prototypes were approached cautiously, with concerns about loss of routine or stability.
Corporate (productivity, planning)	Embracing, Redirecting	Narratives aligned with forward momentum, structured activity, and purposeful planning. Support was taken up as an extension of existing strategies
Conventional (community, continuity)	Embracing	Narratives resonated with companionship, reciprocity, and continuity of relationships. Prototypes were valued when they reinforced belonging.
Circumstantial (disruption, constraint)	Resistant, Redirecting, Disconnected	Narratives emphasised difficulty engaging with assumed stability. Support was resisted, reframed, or disengaged from, reflecting disrupted life contexts.

This layered analysis illustrates how SC responses operated dialogically, both affirming and troubling cultural expectations about ageing, health, and retirement. Resonance typologies function here as a bridge between individual stories and collective cultural patterns, showing how prototypes were engaged with, resisted, or reimaged in ways that reflected broader orientations toward stability, productivity, continuity, or disruption. These intersections will be revisited in **Chapter Seven**, where their implications for intervention design, inclusivity, and public health are considered. The next section (**6.9**) develops this further by examining how typologies overlapped and co-existed within individual responses, highlighting the complexity of narrative positioning in the TtR.

6.9 Layering the Typologies: Coexisting Meanings and Narrative Complexity

While the resonance and retirement narrative typologies were introduced separately, many SC responses contained elements of more than one category. As seen with the retirement transition typologies in **Chapter Four**, stories rarely aligned neatly with a

single position (Frank, 2010). Instead, they combined orientations, shifted tone partway through, or held tensions between optimism and scepticism. This overlap demonstrates the dialogical quality of the narratives, where multiple cultural resources were drawn upon to imagine retirement support.

This section builds on the earlier analysis by examining how resonance orientations and retirement narrative typologies intersect, revealing the narrative complexity embedded in women's imagined engagements with support. As Randall (2015) observes, everyday stories are rarely singular in meaning; they often carry overlapping emotional, social, and moral layers. Attending to this complexity allows a more nuanced understanding of how participants used the SC task to navigate uncertainty, possibility, and self-positioning during the TtR.

Some stories shifted across positions. For instance, A8 (Retirement Café) combined an *Embracing* orientation with *Ambivalence*: Katie was optimistic about joining activities but cautious about overcommitment. Others illustrated sequencing across time, such as A5 (Retirement Café), where Katie initially embraced the café but later resisted it, concerned about obligation. In B4 (Buddy Scheme), June rejected the contrived buddy arrangement (*Resistant*) but redirected her energy toward an exercise class, showing that resistance to one form of support did not equate to rejecting support altogether.

Other stories blended resonance with broader retirement typologies. In C6 (Exercise Class), Betty carefully checked with her doctor and trainer before joining. This reflected a *Corporate* narrative of planning and control combined with *Tentative* resonance that acknowledged uncertainty. In C7 (Exercise Class), Betty sought community but encountered cliques, leading to *Resistance* and *Disconnection* that reflected a *Circumstantial* narrative of constrained choice.

These hybrid forms suggest that resonance and retirement narrative typologies should be read as fluid and relational rather than fixed or mutually exclusive. Women's imagined engagements with support initiatives were often partial and negotiated, reflecting the messy realities of navigating retirement. **Table 23** summarises selected examples of these overlaps.

Table 23: Illustrative Examples of Layered Resonance and Retirement Narrative Typologies

Story ID	Prototype	Retirement Narrative Typology	Resonance Typology/Typologies	Illustrative Overlap
A8	Retirement Café	Conventional (community, continuity)	Embracing + Ambivalent	Katie is optimistic about activities but cautious about overcommitment, combining enthusiasm with restraint.
B4	Buddy Scheme	Circumstantial (relocation, disruption)	Resistant + Redirecting	June rejects the contrived buddy relationship but redirects to an exercise class, showing agency in seeking alternatives.
C6	Exercise Class	Corporate (planning, productivity)	Tentative + Embracing	Betty carefully consults professionals before joining, reflecting cautious control alongside eventual engagement.
A5	Retirement Café	Traditional (routine, stability)	Embracing → Resistant (shift over time)	Katie initially welcomes the café but later feels overburdened, showing a transition from optimism to withdrawal.
C7	Exercise Class	Circumstantial (constrained choice, vulnerability)	Resistant + Disconnected	Betty seeks community but encounters cliques, leading to feelings of exclusion and disengagement.

These examples demonstrate how resonance and retirement narrative typologies intersected in complex and shifting ways. Traditional narratives often carried *Ambivalence* when activities threatened routine, while *Circumstantial* narratives highlighted exclusion or disengagement when prototypes assumed stability. *Corporate* and *Conventional* narratives were more likely to embrace structured or relational forms of support. Layering resonance with retirement narrative typologies offers a more nuanced understanding of these patterns. It shows that interventions are made meaningful not only through their practical or social features but also through how

women narrate and imagine their life trajectories during the TtR. This interpretive move highlights the dynamic relationship between narrative orientation and prototype response, revealing why similar interventions may elicit different reactions across narrative contexts.

6.10 Retirement Café Prototype

The Retirement Café stories illustrated a spectrum of responses, ranging from *Embracing* the concept as a source of reassurance and belonging to *Resisting* it as constraining, cliquy, or unimaginative. Participants drew on cultural narratives of hospitality, mutual aid, and community to position Katie either as reassured and connected or as alienated and disengaged. These stories highlight the ambivalence surrounding informational and community-based provision during the TtR. On one hand, the Café resonated with expectations of welcome, guidance, and collective reassurance, offering a bridge into new identities and activities. On the other, it risked reproducing familiar problems of overcommitment, cliques, or lack of novelty. Such competing orientations show how retirement support can be enabling for some while constraining for others, depending on how women imagined situating themselves within its social dynamics.

The responses also underlined the interplay between individual uncertainty and collective recognition. For some, shared apprehension created solidarity and reassurance, while for others repetition and sameness became sources of frustration. In this sense, the Café surfaced broader tensions around what women seek at retirement: affirmation and companionship, but also novelty, autonomy, and choice. These layered positions demonstrated the functionality of the Café as a narrative device, allowing participants to test both the appeal and the limitations of this form of support. Its imagined success was contingent on inclusivity and imagination, with several stories emphasising the importance of avoiding sameness, cliques, or informal hierarchies. Designing spaces that feel relevant across diverse interests and circumstances therefore requires openness to newcomers and flexibility in activities. The Café thus provides insight into how women negotiate cultural scripts of community support, welcomed when it felt authentic and generative, and resisted when it appeared off-putting or exclusionary.

6.11 Buddy Scheme Prototype

The Buddy Scheme stories highlighted how women imagined structured peer support at retirement. Relocation and transition were framed as moments of both vulnerability and possibility, with the scheme imagined as offering companionship, reassurance, and pathways into new communities. When it resonated, the Buddy Scheme was depicted as transformative, with women moving from tentative newcomers to confident participants, and in some accounts, from recipients of support to contributors themselves. Yet the responses also exposed limits. Some narratives described discomfort with contrived or mismatched relationships, while others voiced scepticism about institutional reliability. These stories emphasised a cultural preference for friendships to emerge organically, underlining the risk that structured schemes may feel artificial or onerous if not carefully designed.

The varied accounts illustrated how the same intervention could be welcomed, resisted, or reshaped. Structured peer support offered reassurance and opportunity, but it was often measured against cultural expectations that valued spontaneity, authenticity, and self-direction in later-life relationships. The Buddy Scheme was frequently framed as promising but fragile, with women weighing the benefits of companionship against concerns about trust, compatibility, and unwanted obligations. Narratives of hesitation suggested that successful implementation would depend on sensitive matching processes that accounted for personal preferences, confidence levels, and readiness to engage. Flexibility also emerged as critical, with women valuing the option to withdraw or re-enter on their own terms. These imagined dynamics echoed concerns voiced in the co-design workshops, where participants stressed the importance of trust and careful matching in peer-based support, suggesting that buddy models can reduce the social risk of trying new activities only if they are carefully designed to balance support with autonomy.

6.12 Exercise Class Prototype

The Exercise Class stories illustrated how health-focused provision was imagined in retirement, highlighting both its promise and its limits. This aligns with wider research positioning PA as a social and cultural practice rather than an isolated health behaviour, shaped by moral and emotional expectations about how ageing should look

and feel (Fullagar, 2017a; Phoenix and Bell, 2019). Whereas the Café and Buddy Scheme centred on social and informational support, the class placed PA at the heart of provision, with social connection emerging as a secondary but important outcome. This made it distinctive in linking health, identity, and belonging at a point of transition. Across the responses, the class was rarely neutral. Some women described it as energising, confidence-building, and socially supportive, positioning exercise as a transformative resource that extended beyond the gym floor. Others narrated it as excluding, arduous, or misaligned, raising anxieties about comparison, cliques, or unmet expectations. These responses revealed how women's imagined participation was not only social but also embodied: confidence, comfort, and perceived capability in their bodies shaped whether exercise felt inviting or exposing. These contrasting accounts accentuated the *Ambivalence* surrounding exercise in later life: it could be imagined as empowering, but equally as exposing.

Participants often framed the class in relation to broader cultural discourses of responsibility, lifestyle, and ageing well. For some, group exercise represented perseverance, humour, and renewal. For others, it reinforced pressures to self-manage health or conform to narrow ideals of "active ageing." This reflected the moral undertones of active ageing discourse, where being "active" functions as a sign of personal responsibility and moral worth, blurring distinctions between wellbeing and obligation (Katz and Calasanti, 2015; van Dyk and Lessenich, 2020). In *Redirecting* stories, the class was positioned as one option within a wider set of strategies, rather than a solution in itself. These layered positions show that exercise in retirement was never narrated as simply about PA. Instead, the class surfaced cultural tensions between fitness as leisure, health management, and community belonging, revealing how women may welcome, resist, or adapt structured opportunities depending on how well this fit with their imagined identities, needs, and aspirations in the TtR. For some, exercise was narrated as a continuation of the structured rhythms and sense of purpose associated with working life, an avenue for maintaining continuity amid wider changes in routine and identity.

Placed alongside the other prototypes, the Exercise Class showed how PA interventions could generate enthusiasm but also resistance when they did not accommodate

diversity of ability, confidence, or motivation. Its success was imagined as dependent on whether it could be experienced as inclusive, adaptable, and genuinely supportive of wellbeing, rather than prescriptive or exclusive. These findings also suggest that participation involves emotional and moral labour: sustaining motivation, confidence, and belonging required ongoing effort, particularly when women navigated self-doubt or ambivalence about fitness culture. Positive accounts emphasised phased or low-pressure entry, while *Resistant* or *Ambivalent* narratives reflected discomfort with group settings, fitness norms, or expectations of performance. These findings also connected back to earlier interview and workshop accounts, where women emphasised the need for flexible, socially meaningful approaches to PA that resisted one-size-fits-all models of ageing well. These interpretations position PA as a relational and cultural process, one negotiated through emotion, embodiment, and moral discourse. This understanding also carries forward into the next chapter, where these dynamics are considered in relation to wider theoretical and methodological contributions.

6.13 Cross Cutting Insights from the Prototypes

The previous sections examined how participants positioned themselves in response to each prototype individually, highlighting patterns of resonance and their intersections with retirement narrative typologies. This section synthesises insights across the three prototypes to examine how different forms of support evoke shared and divergent cultural orientations. By mapping narrative typologies alongside resonance patterns, the analysis offers a novel lens for assessing the potential and fragility of imagined retirement support initiatives. This comparative perspective highlights both recurring orientations and intervention-specific cultural scripts.

The prototypes generated a wide spectrum of responses, ranging from enthusiasm and reassurance to scepticism, resistance, or disengagement. The following table provides an overview of these patterns and illustrates how different forms of support evoked distinct, and sometimes overlapping, narrative positions. **Table 24** summarises how these resonance patterns clustered differently across the scenarios.

Table 24: Resonance Typologies Across Prototype Scenarios

Prototype	Dominant Resonance Typologies	Notable Features
Retirement Café	Embracing, Tentative, Ambivalent, Resistant, Redirecting	Hospitality, mutual aid, but risk of cliques or repetition
Buddy Scheme	Embracing, Resistant, Redirecting (reciprocity, opting out)	Companionship valued, but authenticity and fit were critical
Exercise Class	Embracing, Ambivalent, Resistant, Redirecting, Disconnected	Transformation possible, but issues of accessibility, inclusivity, and misalignment

The comparison shows that resonance was not evenly distributed. Exercise Class stories leaned most strongly toward *Embracing* positions, drawing on cultural resources of humour, perseverance, and renewal. *Ambivalence* and *Resistance* clustered more heavily around the Café and Buddy Scheme, where anxieties about cliques, contrived friendships, and institutional reliability were more pronounced. *Redirecting* responses appeared across all prototypes, highlighting that women often sought to adapt or combine initiatives with their own strategies.

This mapping highlights how resonance was shaped by personal preference as well as by the cultural and social expectations each prototype evoked. It provides a comparative view of why interventions were welcomed in some contexts yet resisted in others, reinforcing the need for inclusive and flexible design in retirement support. What is distinctive here is the systematic comparison of resonance across multiple prototypes, which reveals both shared orientations and intervention-specific cultural scripts. This comparative, narrative-typology mapping provides a novel lens for assessing the potential and fragility of retirement support initiatives.

These insights offer a broader view of how imagined interventions resonated with women's orientations and cultural expectations. In addition to these narrative accounts, participants were also invited to share brief reflections about the prototype scenarios themselves. The following section summarises these additional responses, which provide a complementary perspective by highlighting preferences, practical considerations, and perceived barriers to engagement.

6.14 Additional Responses to the Story Completion Activity

Alongside the fictional stories, the online SC activity invited participants to answer brief questions about the prototype scenarios. These asked women which prototype they found most appealing, how likely they would be to use it in real life, and what features might increase its relevance or accessibility. These short reflections offered a complementary perspective to the narrative data. Whereas the stories illuminated how prototypes were imagined and positioned, the additional comments provided direct indications of preference and practical considerations. Many reinforced themes already identified in the narrative analysis. Companionship, reassurance, and health support were valued, while concerns centred on cliques, obligatory or demanding commitments, and lack of novelty. **Table 25** summarises the most common patterns across the additional responses, with the full dataset included in **Appendix R**.

Table 25: Summary of Additional Story Completion Responses Across Prototypes

Prototype	Reported Appeal	Common Reservations	Illustrative Features Highlighted
Retirement Café	Social interaction, information, reassurance	Risk of cliques, lack of novelty, possible overcommitment	Hospitality, shared experiences, peer advice
Buddy Scheme	Companionship, local guidance, confidence-building	Forced interaction, poor matching, concerns about sustainability	Reciprocity, mentoring, gradual integration
Exercise Class	Health improvement, fun atmosphere, socialising	Fitness barriers, intimidation, class format misalignment	Laughter, perseverance, structured activity

These reflections reinforced that women valued opportunities for connection, reassurance, and identity-building in retirement, but stressed the importance of flexibility and authenticity in delivery. They therefore complement the narrative findings by clarifying which aspects of the prototypes participants judged most relevant or least appealing to their imagined retirements.

The full set of supplementary responses is provided in **Appendix R**, ensuring transparency while preserving the breadth of input. They connect back to the resonance typologies in **Section 6.2** and their integration with retirement narrative typologies in **Section 6.8**, and are revisited in **Chapter Seven**, where their practical

implications for intervention design are discussed. With the participant responses presented in full, the chapter now turns to a reflexive account of my own role in shaping this phase of the study, including the practical, ethical, and interpretive challenges encountered during implementation and analysis.

6.15 Reflexive Account: Working with Story Completion Data

Reflexivity was an important part of this phase of the research, as the shift from participants' personal narratives to SC responses required different analytic attention. Interpreting these stories in Phase Three called for a different mode of attentiveness from the personal accounts gathered in earlier phases. Unlike interviews or workshops, where participants spoke directly from their own circumstances, the SC activity invited them to imagine characters such as Katie, June, or Betty. This introduced both opportunities and challenges for analysis.

One challenge lay in balancing the imaginative and sometimes fragmentary quality of responses with the need for analytic rigour. Some stories were brief or disengaged, while others developed complex characters and trajectories. Treating all responses as meaningful required sensitivity to the cultural resources they mobilised, rather than to their length or detail (Braun et al., 2019; Gravett, 2019). Another challenge was resisting the temptation to read fictional characters as stand-ins for participants themselves. Instead, the analysis treated stories as performative acts that circulated cultural expectations about retirement (Frank, 2010; Riessman, 2008), exploring ideas in ways that direct self-disclosure might not allow.

Working with fictional data also created valuable methodological possibilities. The distance offered by third-person narrative appeared to free some participants to explore scenarios that might have been uncomfortable to discuss in the first person (Kitzinger and Powell, 1995; Williams et al. 2022). It also made visible the ambivalence and hesitation that often characterise the TtR, without requiring women to present coherent or stable versions of themselves. This highlighted the value of SC as a method for surfacing uncertainty and negotiating imagined futures (Clarke et al., 2019; Pong et al., 2024).

For me as a researcher, engaging with these SC accounts meant attending to what was said about the prototypes and to what the stories did: how they positioned characters, evoked emotional tones, and enacted possibilities for belonging or withdrawal. This reflexive stance reinforced the methodological contribution of Phase Three, showing that imaginative narratives can serve as a distinctive resource for evaluating intervention ideas while demanding careful interpretation and transparency.

6.16 Reflexive Note on Phase Three

Phase Three presented a distinctive set of challenges that differed from those encountered in the earlier phases. While interviews and co-design workshops relied on in-person dialogue, the SC activity unfolded through a digital form, with no immediate opportunity for clarification, prompting, or relational exchange. This created strengths and limitations. The absence of direct interaction allowed participants to shape their stories freely, without being influenced by my presence or expectations. At the same time, I was acutely aware of how much was left unsaid, and how dependent the analysis became on interpreting tone, narrative development, and silence within written responses.

When the first story stems came through, I knew with certainty that I had made the right decision to use SC. I was delighted and at times mesmerised by the effort participants put into their stories and the vividness with which they animated the characters. Many accounts introduced additional figures and created glimpses into imagined realities that felt alive on the page. What I especially valued was when the stories resisted the prototypes altogether, taking them in unexpected directions. These moments made me think differently about what was possible, showing how women negotiated possibilities and constraints in ways I had not anticipated.

Reading the stories often felt like catching glimpses of participants' own experiences and situations refracted through fictional characters. The blend of imagination and resonance gave the dataset a richness that exceeded what I had initially hoped for. The SC activity not only tested the prototypes but also offered participants a means for expressing ambivalence, aspiration, and critique in ways that interviews or workshops

alone may not have captured. For me as a researcher, this confirmed the creative and dialogical potential of SC as a method for exploring the TtR.

My positioning as researcher also shifted during this phase. The move from facilitating conversation to analysing stories written in private highlighted my dual role as both interpreter and co-constructor of meaning. The stories arrived already formed, sometimes as a few brief sentences, other times as expansive narratives. This variability reminded me of the unevenness of participation and of the limits of SC for generating depth across all cases. Yet even brief responses carried analytic weight when considered dialogically, particularly in relation to patterns of resistance or disconnection.

Recruitment challenges also shaped this phase. Response rates were lower than anticipated, requiring repeated outreach through community gatekeepers and adjustments to the instructions to reduce participant burden. As noted earlier (see **Appendix S**), the dataset was smaller than planned. However, the map of responses shows that its tonal breadth was sufficient to confirm that meaningful insights could still be drawn. This also highlighted the iterative nature of the process: adjustments to instructions, participant engagement, and analytic framing all evolved in response to practical challenges and the stories themselves.

Analysing the stories required sustained reflexivity about how I was constructing meaning. The resonance typologies emerged inductively and iteratively, shaped by my interpretive lens as I moved back and forth between individual stories, cultural narratives, and earlier phases of the project. Narrative research and my engagement with participants' prior accounts in Phases One and Two informed these interpretations. I often returned to Frank's (2012) reminder that stories "answer back" to cultural discourses, recognising that my own readings were also situated within those discourses. Writing analytic memos helped me to hold open multiple interpretations, particularly where ambiguity or contradiction appeared.

I close this phase with a strong sense of appreciation for the women who carried the project forward by engaging with a method that was unusual and at times demanding. Their willingness to imagine, to project themselves into fictional scenarios, and to

articulate both optimism and critique made Phase Three possible. These narratives were co-produced, situated, and partial, but they offered glimpses into the cultural and emotional dynamics of retirement that would have been difficult to access through more conventional methods. For me as a researcher, this phase confirmed the practical value of SC and its methodological potential to test imagined interventions. To my knowledge, this is the first study to apply SC in the context of retirement support, and the first to combine resonance typologies with retirement narrative typologies to examine how women imagine and evaluate new forms of provision. The following chapter moves beyond the presentation of findings to a wider discussion, where insights from Phases One, Two, and Three are brought together to consider the study's conceptual, methodological, and practical contributions.

6.17 Transition to Chapter Seven

The findings from Phase Three closed the loop in an iterative process that began with the narrative interviews in Phase One and developed through co-design and typology-building in Phase Two. The resonance orientations identified in this final phase were interpreted in relation to the retirement narrative typologies generated earlier, highlighting the dialogical and layered nature of the study. This iterative movement between phases ensured that each stage was both self-contained and mutually informing.

The next and final chapter builds on this foundation by drawing together insights from across all three phases. It shifts from presenting findings to a wider discussion, considering how the study contributes conceptually, methodologically, and practically to understanding and supporting women's TtR. In doing so, it highlights the originality of applying SC and layered typology analysis to retirement research. The findings confirm that perceptions of support are shaped both by its practical form and by how far it aligns with women's evolving sense of identity, autonomy, and belonging.

Chapter Seven: Discussion and Contributions

7.0 Introduction

This chapter brings the thesis to a close by reflecting on what has been learned across the three phases and considering the significance of these insights going forward.

Feminist scholarship, outlined in **Chapter Two**, provides an interpretive lens for understanding the findings discussed here. Feminist gerontology and political economy perspectives demonstrate how women's later lives are shaped by cumulative disadvantage, unpaid labour, and structural inequalities that remain obscured within dominant models of retirement and ageing (Calasanti and Slevin, 2001; Katz and Calasanti, 2015).

Viewed through this lens, women's narratives in the present study repeatedly emphasised constraint, care, relational responsibility, and ambivalence towards support. These patterns reflect gendered life-course dynamics rather than individual preference alone. They also reinforce the need to examine women's retirement transitions in a policy context that continues to rely on linear employment assumptions and individualised models of support.

This chapter revisits the research aims and questions, synthesises the study's theoretical, methodological, and practical contributions, and outlines implications for the design of future retirement support and policy. It also acknowledges the study's limitations and identifies directions for future research. Taken together, the findings show that women's retirement transitions are shaped by gendered life-course patterns, structural inequalities, and normative expectations about independence and care that remain under-addressed within mainstream retirement frameworks.

The research was guided by three overarching questions:

1. **How do women narrate their expectations and experiences during the TtR?**
2. **What types of support feel helpful, acceptable, or misaligned to women at this stage?**

3. How can creative narrative methods (like SC and co-design) be used to explore and test interventions?

These questions were addressed through the following aims:

- 1. To explore how women understand and navigate the retirement transition.**
- 2. To co-design potential support options with women using participatory methods.**
- 3. To test the functionality of prototypes through narrative approaches.**

Chapter Six demonstrated how women's imagined engagement with the three co-designed retirement support prototypes (the Retirement Café, the Buddy Scheme, and the Women's TtR Exercise Class) was shaped by emotional and temporal pacing, relational tone, and narrative identity work. Women negotiated support in diverse and dynamic ways. Through SC, DNA, and typology layering, the study captured what participants might do in relation to support, as well as how they imagined, felt, and positioned themselves within those possibilities.

The sections that follow revisit each research aim and question in turn, synthesising insights across all phases of the study and drawing on participant narratives to illustrate key points. These reflections provide the foundation for identifying the thesis's contributions to knowledge, outlining implications for practice and policy, and proposing directions for future research.

To support this synthesis, **Table 26** provides an overview of the three research phases, highlighting their key activities, main insights, and contributions. This summary illustrates the layered design of the study and shows how each phase built on the last to develop a coherent understanding of women's TtR.

Table 26: Overview of Phases, Key Insights, and Contributions

Phase	Key Activities	Main Insights
Phase One: Narrative Interviews and Workshop One	In-depth interviews with women approaching or in early retirement; exploratory Workshop One to discuss findings and test emerging ideas.	Retirement narrated as disruption and reorientation; tensions between freedom and constraint; importance of identity continuity. These early insights informed the development of the retirement typologies and prototypes in Phase Two.
Phase Two: Co-Design Workshops	Collaborative workshops to generate and refine prototypes (Café, Buddy Scheme, Exercise Class); development of typologies.	Retirement typologies (<i>Traditional, Conventional, Circumstantial, Corporate</i>) were refined during this phase, building on narrative insights from Phase One. Women positioned themselves differently across these typologies, and relational tone shaped perceived feasibility of prototypes.
Phase Three: SC	SC activity using three prototype-based story stems; analysis via DNA and typology layering.	Engagement narrated as tentative, cyclical, and relational; resistance framed as boundary-setting; belonging negotiated through conversational and cultural fit.

7.1 Key Findings Overview

Across the three phases, several findings deepened understanding of how women navigate the TtR and how support can be meaningfully designed for this life stage. The study addressed long-standing gaps in retirement research that have overlooked women’s subjective, relational, and emotional experiences, as well as the limited attention given to the design and evaluation of gender-responsive interventions. These findings directly answer the research questions outlined in **Chapter Two**, showing how women narrate their transitions, evaluate support, and engage with creative narrative methods to test new ideas.

First, women experienced retirement as a fluid and negotiated process shaped by shifting emotional, cultural, and structural influences (see **Section 7.2.1** for elaboration). This finding challenges linear, event-based policy framings of retirement and highlights the importance of understanding transition as an unfolding process of

ongoing negotiation (Vickerstaff and van der Horst, 2021). It also reflects feminist gerontological critiques of life-course models that overlook gendered patterns of work, care, and inequality (see **Section 2.3**). It builds on the narrative perspectives introduced in **Chapter Four** and directly addresses **Research Question 1**.

Second, women evaluated support through interpretive processes shaped by narrative positioning, relational tone, and cultural alignment, which influenced whether they imagined support as welcoming and relevant or as exclusionary and uncomfortable. This finding helps explain why conventional models based on individual behaviour, which dominate much of the policy and gerontology literature critiqued in **Chapter Two**, often fail to reflect the relational, emotional, and contextual complexities revealed in this study. This finding responds to **Research Question 2**, connecting participants' interpretations to the co-design and SC activities described in **Chapters Five and Six**.

Third, the combination of co-design workshops and SC generated insights that would have been difficult to access through standard approaches. These methods enabled both collective and individual reflection, revealing how women imagine, negotiate, and adapt to different forms of support. This contributes to methodological debates about the role of narrative in developing culturally and contextually sensitive interventions. This finding reflects the methodological approach set out in **Chapter Three** and developed through Phases Two and Three (**Chapters Five and Six**).

Finally, issues of diversity, accessibility, and continuity shaped both the research process and the findings. Recruitment challenges, limited ethnic diversity, and interruptions to timelines exposed the practical realities of conducting participatory, multi-phase research with groups navigating transitional life stages. These experiences underline the importance of flexible, inclusive, and contingency-aware approaches in both research and practice. These reflections connect back to the recruitment and methodological considerations discussed in **Chapters Three and Four**. The following sections (7.1.1–7.1.3) examine these findings in greater depth, providing expanded answers to each of the three main research questions.

7.1.1 Retirement as a Negotiated and Cyclical Process

The narratives collected through interviews and workshops offered detailed insight into how women negotiated retirement as an evolving, cyclical process. Many participants described feeling both anticipation and unease during this period. Retirement was often associated with a sense of release from work-related pressures, but it also introduced uncertainty about identity, belonging, and everyday structure. These mixed emotions shaped how women approached the transition, highlighting its complexity and variability (Vickerstaff and van der Horst, 2021; Lain et al., 2019). As discussed in **Chapter Two**, feminist gerontological perspectives frame retirement as a gendered life-course process shaped by cumulative inequalities rather than a neutral or purely individual transition. This lens is useful for interpreting the patterned tensions between autonomy and constraint evident in participants' narratives. This challenges linear, event-based models that frame retirement as a single, predictable transition (Atchley, 1976), offering instead a more nuanced account of retirement as an ongoing, negotiated process shaped by intersecting factors.

For some participants, retirement opened possibilities for rest, creativity, or long-deferred personal goals. Others described feeling unsettled by the loss of familiar routines and social connections. Several participants described identity shifts during the early stages of transition, especially when long-standing roles no longer felt secure. This was particularly evident among those with long histories of paid employment or caregiving, which had strongly shaped their sense of self. Their accounts often reflected efforts to maintain valued aspects of their previous lives while adapting to new circumstances (Marshall and Katz, 2018; Phillipson, 2019).

The narratives showed that retirement was rarely experienced as a single turning point. Instead, women moved between different emotional and practical positions over time. These shifts reflected changing health, family responsibilities, financial circumstances, and personal aspirations. Several participants described periods of experimentation followed by retreat or reassessment. They tried new activities, paused when they felt uncertain, and returned when circumstances changed or their confidence grew. This cyclical movement often took place gradually rather than through sudden decisions. The sense of "working things out" over time was a recurring theme. These findings align

with recent work that frames retirement as a negotiated and dynamic process shaped by cultural, structural, and personal factors (van Dyk, 2021; Vickerstaff and van der Horst, 2021; Loretto et al., 2023).

The process of negotiation was influenced by intersecting structural and personal factors. Pension arrangements, access to resources, health status, and caregiving responsibilities all shaped the range of choices available to women, reflecting gendered life-course patterns and cumulative inequalities, as outlined in the feminist political economy literature discussed in Chapter Two. Cultural expectations about appropriate activities and identities in later life were also significant (Katz and Calasanti, 2015; Twigg and Martin, 2015; Calasanti, 2020). These expectations often varied according to class, locality, and previous work histories. Some participants described feeling pressure to remain visibly active and socially engaged, while others encountered assumptions that retirement meant withdrawal from public life. These cultural frames affected how women understood their own options and how they interpreted the choices of others.

A consistent theme was the tension between freedom and constraint. Many women valued the increased autonomy that retirement offered, but they were also aware of responsibilities and expectations that continued to shape their decisions. Some described financial constraints that limited their ability to pursue desired activities. Others spoke about ongoing caregiving roles that structured their days in ways similar to paid work. Even those who welcomed the idea of greater freedom often described needing to adjust gradually to unfamiliar rhythms of time and space. These findings resonate with feminist gerontological analyses of gendered life-course inequality (Loretto and Vickerstaff, 2015), alongside structural critiques of successful ageing and later-life policy (Katz and Calasanti, 2015; Calasanti, 2020; see **Section 2.3**).

Identity continuity was central to how women navigated these changes. Participants often sought ways to carry forward elements of their working lives, such as a sense of purpose, daily structure, or social interaction. For some, voluntary work or part-time employment provided continuity. Others created new routines or joined groups that allowed them to maintain a sense of contribution and belonging. When this continuity felt disrupted, women spoke about feeling unsettled or lacking direction. Their stories

showed that retirement involved careful narrative work: making sense of past experiences, evaluating present circumstances, and imagining possible futures. These processes reflect contemporary narrative perspectives that view identity as sustained and reconfigured through storytelling in later life (Phoenix and Sparkes, 2009; Riessman, 2008; Westerhof and Bohlmeijer, 2014).

This process of negotiation was rarely linear. Women revisited earlier decisions, reinterpreted past experiences, and adjusted their expectations in response to new developments. Their narratives often contained moments of hesitation, doubt, and renewed commitment. This cyclical pattern challenges staged models of retirement adjustment that present the transition as a predictable sequence (Atchley, 1976), by demonstrating instead a process that is iterative, responsive, and embedded in cultural and personal contexts (van Dyk, 2018; Vickerstaff and van der Horst, 2021). Thus, retirement was experienced as a shifting process that required ongoing negotiation rather than a fixed outcome.

These insights are important for understanding how women approach different kinds of retirement support. Their willingness to explore or reject support was influenced by how they understood their own transition process, their available resources, and the cultural narratives they drew upon to make sense of this stage of life. For many, previous experiences of PA and other new encounters, whether positive or discouraging, shaped how they evaluated later opportunities for engagement. Familiar patterns of inclusion or exclusion informed expectations about belonging, confidence, and capability in post-retirement contexts. Support was evaluated through these personal and collective frameworks, rather than being assessed solely on practical grounds. This has direct implications for intervention design, which needs to recognise the temporal, emotional, and cultural dimensions of retirement and avoid assuming a single, universal trajectory (Loretto et al., 2023; van Dyk and Lessenich, 2020; Moffatt and Heaven, 2017). By demonstrating how women actively negotiate retirement over time, this study contributes a dynamic and culturally situated perspective that can inform both theoretical understandings and practical support strategies. This perspective also informed the use of HCD in Phase Two, where attention to

participants' narrative positioning, prior experiences, and expectations of belonging shaped the iterative development and refinement of the prototype interventions.

7.1.2 Interpreting and Negotiating Support in the Transition to Retirement

Women's accounts across the three phases showed that engagement with support was not simply a matter of availability or need, but of interpretation. Participants assessed potential interventions in relation to their own experiences, expectations, and sense of identity within the transition to retirement. Rather than evaluating support as a neutral resource, women considered how it aligned with their current circumstances, past experiences, and anticipated futures.

Support was often approached cautiously. Some participants expressed interest in new activities or groups, but this interest was shaped by concerns about belonging, confidence, and perceived fit. For example, unfamiliar environments or groups were sometimes associated with feelings of uncertainty, particularly where participants anticipated differences in age, ability, or social background. In these cases, engagement depended on whether the intervention felt accessible and relevant within their own social and cultural context.

Previous experiences also played a significant role in shaping expectations. Positive encounters with physical activity, community groups, or social spaces could encourage openness to new forms of support, while earlier negative or exclusionary experiences often led to hesitation or withdrawal. These patterned responses highlight how engagement is shaped over time, reflecting broader life-course trajectories and accumulated experiences rather than isolated decisions.

Participants also interpreted support in relation to cultural expectations about ageing, activity, and independence. Some described pressure to remain active and socially engaged, while others resisted these expectations, expressing a desire for rest or a slower pace of life. These differing orientations influenced how support was evaluated. Interventions that appeared to impose expectations or reinforce normative ideas of "successful" ageing were sometimes viewed critically, while those that allowed flexibility, autonomy, and gradual engagement were more positively received.

Across the data, support was negotiated rather than passively accepted. Women positioned themselves in relation to interventions, sometimes embracing opportunities, sometimes adapting them, and sometimes rejecting them altogether. These responses were shaped by intersecting structural and personal factors, including health, financial resources, caregiving responsibilities, and social networks, as well as by cultural narratives about what retirement should look like (see **Section 2.3**).

This interpretive process has important implications for intervention design. It suggests that support must be understood as relational and context-dependent, rather than universally applicable. Interventions need to be flexible, sensitive to diverse experiences, and attentive to how they are perceived by those they are intended to support. This perspective helps to explain why co-designed and narrative-based approaches are valuable, as they allow these interpretive processes to be explored and incorporated into the development of support options.

7.1.3 Creative Narrative Methods for Exploring and Exploring Interventions

Combining co-design workshops with SC methods made it possible to explore both the development of intervention ideas and how women imagined engaging with them.

Using these methods sequentially generated insights that would have been difficult to achieve through conventional approaches. The co-design workshops created spaces for collaborative idea generation and refinement, while the SC activity enabled participants to project themselves into hypothetical yet plausible future scenarios.

Used in combination, these methods illuminated the emotional, cultural, and temporal dynamics that shaped women's imagined engagement with retirement support. This sequencing reflects a HCD logic, in which exploratory co-creation is followed by low-risk prototyping to examine how potential users interpret and relate to emerging concepts.

The co-design process highlighted the value of iterative framing. As intervention ideas evolved, participants refined them by reflecting on potential use and discussing barriers or points of attraction. These discussions showed that small shifts in language, tone, or structure could substantially affect whether women perceived a support option as relevant or approachable. For example, reframing an exercise prototype to emphasise

social connection rather than performance changed how participants positioned themselves in relation to the activity. This iterative, dialogical refinement is often absent from top-down intervention development, where ideas are generated by professionals and subsequently tested on target groups (Greenhalgh et al., 2016; Akama and Light, 2019). When interventions are designed in this way, their effectiveness may be limited because they reflect institutional assumptions about *what* people need rather than *how* they make sense of support in their own lives. The co-design process used in this study demonstrates that participatory and narrative-led approaches can surface the relational and emotional dimensions that more technical models tend to overlook, leading to designs that are both more meaningful and more sustainable.

The SC method offered a complementary way of exploring interventions by inviting participants to imagine and narrate engagement in response to structured prompts. Rather than asking women to reflect on past behaviour, SC encouraged them to explore what they *might* do in hypothetical scenarios. This prospective focus was particularly valuable for understanding the TtR, where experiences and expectations are in flux. SC enabled participants to project themselves into imagined futures, revealing both possible actions and the emotional and cultural meanings attached to those actions (Braun, Clarke and Gray, 2019; Gravett, 2019; Pong, Roberts, and Lum, 2024).

Using SC after co-design was methodologically valuable for several reasons. First, it allowed the research to move beyond immediate workshop discussions and capture individual reflections that were sometimes more tentative, critical, or exploratory. Participants occasionally expressed ambivalence or resistance in their written stories that they had not voiced in group settings, suggesting that SC created space for more private or complex considerations. Second, SC helped to identify narrative patterns across participants. Through DNA and typology layering, the study identified forms such as cautious negotiation, strategic withdrawal, and gradual re-engagement, which shaped how women imagined interacting with the prototypes. These patterns revealed how support was interpreted through emotional and cultural frames, rather than being evaluated in purely instrumental terms. Third, SC functioned as an exploratory evaluative mechanism. It revealed which aspects of the prototypes resonated with participants and which provoked hesitation, without requiring full implementation.

Participants' stories often exposed how language or framing created unintended impressions about who belonged in certain spaces or what level of commitment was expected.

Identifying such issues early is particularly valuable in intervention development, where misalignment between designers' intentions and users' interpretations can lead to low uptake or unintended exclusion (Greenhalgh et al., 2016; Lenette et al., 2022). These outcomes matter, as they often result in wasted resources, reinforce existing inequalities, and discourage future participation among those who already feel marginalised or uncertain about belonging. The present study shows that such risks can be mitigated when participants are engaged early in shaping and narrating potential interventions, allowing tensions and misunderstandings to surface before implementation. None of the prototypes represented a single "ideal" solution, but each prompted distinctive responses that revealed the diverse ways women interpret and evaluate support. This highlights the value of participatory, narrative-based design for developing interventions that are adaptable rather than prescriptive.

The combination of co-design and SC also generated methodological insights. Co-design emphasised collaborative, situated knowledge production, while SC enabled individual reflection and imaginative projection. Together, they produced a layered understanding of *how* interventions are developed, interpreted, and negotiated. This combination was particularly effective for exploring interventions with groups who may be ambivalent, cautious, or diverse in their orientations to support, common characteristics during the TtR. It captured moments of curiosity, resistance, re-evaluation, and repositioning that might be overlooked in more linear research designs. While co-production also values collaboration and shared ownership, it often focuses on consensus-building or practical solution development (Beresford, 2019). In contrast, this study's narrative-led approach created space for uncertainty, contradiction, and emotional complexity, recognising these as productive aspects of the design process. Co-producers could draw from this to see how narrative exploration can surface tensions and diverse interpretations that might otherwise remain unspoken, ultimately strengthening the sensitivity and inclusiveness of intervention design.

Using narrative methods also highlighted process over prediction. Rather than focusing on uptake or outcomes, the study traced how women interpreted and negotiated interventions through stories and discussions. This aligns with qualitative perspectives that value openness, uncertainty, and imaginative engagement in research (St Pierre, 2021; Lenette et al., 2022). While St Pierre cautions against rigid methodological thinking, her work supports viewing uncertainty as a productive and necessary part of inquiry. In this study, uncertainty operated as a generative force, revealing tensions, contradictions, and new possibilities for understanding how support is experienced and imagined. By focusing on these narrative processes, the research illuminated how interventions become meaningful within everyday contexts and personal histories.

This methodological approach also carries implications for policy and practice. It suggests that fixed or prescriptive programmes may fail to meet the needs of those navigating complex transitions such as retirement (Lester et al., 2020; Moller et al., 2021). Creative, narrative-based design allows for adaptation and responsiveness, offering policymakers and practitioners a means of engaging with diversity rather than seeking uniform solutions. This is particularly relevant for retirement support, where resources for large-scale implementation are limited and where cultural and emotional dynamics play a central role in shaping participation and outcomes (Lenette et al., 2022; Boswell and Cavallerio, 2022)

These findings address the third research question and aim by demonstrating the value of combining co-design and SC to explore and test retirement support interventions. This approach enabled the study to capture the collective generation of ideas and the individual narrative negotiation of engagement, producing insights that standard evaluative methods would likely miss. It also contributes methodologically by showing how narrative techniques can function as creative, flexible tools for developing and refining interventions with specific user groups.

Empirically, the study offers new insight into how women in the TtR interpret and negotiate support through narrative and relational processes. Across the three phases, the research captured how emotional, social, and cultural meanings shape engagement with interventions, rather than fixed preferences or needs. The SC findings, in particular, demonstrate how imagined engagement can reveal tensions and

opportunities that are often hidden in conventional evaluation methods. These insights provide an empirical foundation for the theoretical and methodological contributions that follow.

7.2 Theoretical Contributions

This section outlines the theoretical contributions of the study, showing how narrative, relational, and temporal perspectives deepen understanding of women's TtR and inform approaches to support and intervention design. Drawing on insights generated across three interconnected phases, the study advances conceptual debates on retirement as a lived, storied process; on how support is negotiated through narrative and relational positioning; and on the role of creative qualitative methods in shaping intervention development and evaluation.

The study contributes to existing retirement literature by conceptualising the TtR as a dynamic and negotiated process rather than a fixed life stage or linear transition from work to leisure. Across the analysis, women's experiences of retirement emerged as shaped through ongoing narrative work, relational contexts, and shifting social conditions. This perspective extends dominant frameworks that prioritise economic, behavioural, or biomedical dimensions of retirement (Loretto et al., 2023; Marshall and Katz, 2018), offering a more nuanced understanding of how retirement is made meaningful through everyday stories, social interactions, and cultural expectations.

By focusing on narrative processes, the study demonstrates how identities, senses of belonging, and orientations to support are actively constructed and reworked during the TtR. Women's stories revealed how disruption, continuity, and ambivalence coexist, challenging models that assume clear stages of adjustment or stable retirement identities. This contributes theoretically by positioning retirement as a temporally fluid and relationally situated process, shaped by gendered life-course patterns and broader cultural narratives, consistent with critical gerontological perspectives on later-life inequality.

The study also advances theory by reconceptualising interventions as more than practical services or behavioural tools. Instead, interventions are understood as

narrative and relational spaces in which identities, relationships, and future possibilities are negotiated. This reframing positions intervention design as a process of narrative alignment rather than behavioural modification. Through this lens, engagement with support is not simply a matter of access or motivation, but of cultural alignment, emotional safety, and narrative fit. This conceptual shift helps explain why many standardised or behaviour-focused interventions struggle to resonate with women's lived experiences during the TtR.

Finally, the study demonstrates how NI, when combined with participatory and HCD approaches, can extend theoretical understandings of transition and support. Rather than treating methods as neutral tools, the research shows how creative, dialogical methods actively shape what can be imagined, articulated, and evaluated. This integration contributes to theoretical debates by illustrating how knowledge about retirement and support is co-produced through narrative engagement, relational interaction, and iterative design processes, offering a framework for thinking differently about both research and intervention development in later life.

7.2.1 Retirement as Temporal and Emotional Process

Theoretically, the research extends understandings of retirement by conceptualising it as a temporal and emotional process rather than a single event or fixed stage. Across the three research phases, women narrated retirement as unfolding through shifting experiences of disruption, anticipation, and reorientation. These temporal dynamics were closely intertwined with emotional responses that shaped how participants understood and navigated change. This perspective extends existing models of retirement that have often prioritised economic resources, role exit, or behavioural adaptation (Beehr and Bennett, 2015; Lain et al., 2019; Wang and Shultz, 2010), by showing how transitions are experienced as gradual, negotiated, and emotionally textured processes (Loretto and Vickerstaff, 2015; Moen, 2016; Vickerstaff and van der Horst, 2021). It also aligns with feminist gerontological arguments that later-life transitions are shaped by cumulative gendered inequalities and caring trajectories across the life course (see **Section 2.3**).

Phase One revealed that women experienced retirement as a fluid and negotiated process, rather than a single, linear transition. This insight challenges dominant policy framings that treat retirement as a discrete event and highlights the importance of attending to emotional, relational, and temporal dynamics over time. For some participants, the early stages of transition were marked by uncertainty and a sense of disruption as familiar routines and identities began to shift. Long-established professional roles, daily structures, and social networks no longer provided the same anchors, prompting moments of unease and reflection. Others expressed curiosity, relief, or cautious optimism as they considered new opportunities and possibilities.

These emotional responses were rarely fixed. Participants moved between excitement, hesitation, and recalibration as they navigated their unfolding transitions, illustrating how retirement is experienced as an iterative process of adjustment rather than a single moment of change. This dynamic quality was shaped by intersecting factors, including health, financial security, caring responsibilities, and social context, which influenced expectations and emerging realities. In line with feminist gerontological perspectives outlined in **Section 2.3**, these trajectories reflected cumulative gendered life-course patterns that structured both opportunities and constraints in later life. These patterns reflect existing accounts of retirement that emphasise variability across individuals and contexts (Vickerstaff and van der Horst, 2021; Loretto and Vickerstaff, 2015). The study extends this work by demonstrating how women actively interpret and reinterpret variability through personal narratives as they make sense of change.

The SC activity provided further insight into these temporal and emotional dynamics by illustrating how imagined engagement with support prototypes often followed cyclical or tentative trajectories. Rather than committing decisively to participation, many stories depicted characters who oscillated between initial hesitation, cautious exploration, and eventual re-engagement. These prospective narratives reflected how transitional experiences are actively negotiated over time, shaped by evolving identities, social environments, and perceived possibilities. They also demonstrated that engagement with retirement support is rarely a single decision point but an ongoing process in which emotional tone plays a central role.

Attending to these temporal and emotional dimensions enriches theoretical understandings of retirement transitions. It highlights the variability and fluidity of women's experiences and the significance of emotional trajectories in shaping how change is interpreted and navigated. This perspective challenges models that treat retirement as a uniform or predictable stage (Atchley, 1976; Beehr, 1986; Wang and Shultz, 2010) and instead emphasises the dynamic ways in which identities, routines, and expectations are reconfigured over time (Moen, 2016). It echoes feminist gerontological perspectives that draw attention to how gendered life-course patterns, caring responsibilities, and cumulative inequalities shape later-life transitions.

This understanding also helps explain why flexible and responsive forms of support may resonate more strongly with women than prescriptive or standardised interventions, as such approaches are better able to accommodate evolving needs and capacities throughout the transition. Conceptualising retirement in this way provides a more contextually grounded basis for understanding how women experience and negotiate this life stage. These findings further contribute to intervention design frameworks by highlighting how narrative processes shape engagement with later-life support initiatives, offering a culturally grounded perspective that can inform policy and practice.

7.2.2 Narrative Negotiation and Cultural Storylines

A central theoretical contribution of this study lies in demonstrating how women negotiate cultural storylines during the TtR. These negotiations were evident across all phases of the research, showing how personal narratives interact with, reproduce, and at times resist dominant cultural frameworks related to ageing, gender, productivity, PA, and social belonging. By attending to these processes, the study highlights retirement as an interpretive juncture where women navigate competing social expectations and personal aspirations. This positions retirement as a site of narrative negotiation rather than a transition governed by fixed stages or roles.

Cultural narratives about later life are shaped by intersecting discourses of health, gender, and ageing (Twigg and Martin, 2015). Public health and policy frameworks frequently portray retirement as a period when individuals are expected to sustain

independence, productivity, and PA through personal responsibility and self-management (Katz and Calasanti, 2015; Marshall and Katz, 2018). Such framings often align with what Frank (2010) terms restitution narratives, which emphasise recovery, maintenance, and control, and quest narratives, which position later life as a time of self-development and purposeful reinvention. These narratives circulate widely through health promotion campaigns, workplace transition programmes, and community initiatives. They shape how women understand what retirement should involve and which behaviours are valued, often in ways that reflect gendered assumptions about responsibility, resilience, and self-management.

Participants' stories revealed varied and sometimes ambivalent relationships to these dominant narratives. Some women aligned closely with restitution or quest framings, describing retirement as a period of renewed attention to health, PA, and social engagement. Others questioned whether these expectations were realistic or desirable in the context of structural inequalities, health concerns, or caregiving responsibilities. Cultural expectations of sustained productivity and self-optimisation often sat uneasily alongside personal experiences of fatigue, financial strain, or ambivalence about change. For some, retirement was narrated in ways that resonated more closely with chaos narratives, characterised by uncertainty, loss of orientation, or resistance to dominant prescriptions.

The SC findings illustrated these narrative positions clearly. Through fictional scenarios, participants explored how different intervention prototypes might align with their identities, values, and anticipated futures. Positions such as cautious negotiation, strategic withdrawal, and gradual re-engagement reflected different ways of working with and against cultural storylines about retirement, ageing, and social participation. Some narratives tentatively reconfigured dominant discourses, adopting elements that resonated personally while rejecting aspects experienced as prescriptive or exclusionary. Others positioned the character as withdrawing from initiatives that seemed misaligned with their priorities or values. These patterns show that engagement with interventions involves cultural interpretation as well as behavioural decision-making.

This study extends theoretical understandings of retirement transitions by highlighting narrative positioning as a central interpretive process. As outlined in **Chapter Three (Section 3.2)**, narrative positioning refers to how participants located themselves or fictional characters within cultural storylines about retirement. Women were neither passive recipients of cultural narratives nor wholly determined by structural positions. Instead, they actively interpreted, adapted, and reworked available storylines in ways shaped by their biographies, identities, and imagined futures. This interpretive work shaped how interventions were understood and whether they were experienced as meaningful, relevant, or alienating. Recognising retirement as a site of narrative positioning and cultural negotiation provides a richer conceptual foundation for understanding how transitional supports are evaluated and helps explain why standardised approaches often fail to resonate with diverse groups.

7.3 Methodological Contributions

This section outlines the methodological contributions of the study by demonstrating how NI, co-design, and SC were integrated across phases to create a coherent and flexible qualitative design. Used together, these approaches generated complementary insights and expanded possibilities for researching complex social transitions such as retirement, particularly through the creative exploration and prototyping of support. The multiphase design combined NI, co-design, and SC to generate complementary insights across different stages of the research. Each phase offered distinct opportunities for participants to express, negotiate, and reimagine their experiences, enabling a layered understanding of women's TtR. Methodologically, this demonstrates a phased narrative–design model in which lived experience, collaborative reframing, and prospective story work operate sequentially to inform intervention development.

The NI used in Phase One enabled detailed exploration of how women made sense of retirement as it unfolded in their lives. Narrative interviews created space for participants to share complex, evolving stories that revealed tensions between identity continuity, structural constraints, and shifting expectations. DNA (Frank, 2010) was well suited to this stage, drawing attention to how stories interacted with broader cultural narratives and participants' imagined futures. This approach supported a nuanced understanding of how women positioned themselves in relation to retirement,

highlighting emotional and interpretive dimensions often overlooked by more conventional qualitative approaches (Carless and Douglas, 2015).

Co-design methods in Phase Two extended these insights by positioning participants as co-producers in shaping potential interventions. Rather than treating participants as data sources, the workshops invited them to bring lived expertise, ideas, and concerns into the design process. Activities such as mapping experiences, developing typologies, and responding to scenarios surfaced unspoken understandings about what makes support meaningful, acceptable, or alienating. These processes also revealed diversity within the group, illustrating how participatory approaches can expose complexity often obscured by top-down intervention models. This responds to critiques of conventional intervention research that prioritises standardisation and outcome measurement over relational and contextual understanding (Greenhalgh et al., 2016; O’Sullivan and Irwin, 2019; Loretto et al., 2023) and aligns with calls to embed reflexivity and ethical attentiveness in participatory design (Akama and Light, 2019; Tulle and Palmer, 2020).

The SC method used in Phase Three provided a distinctive way of exploring how women might engage with the prototypes. By inviting participants to respond to fictional scenarios, SC enabled speculation, emotional expression, and cultural interpretation without requiring direct self-disclosure. This was valuable for transitional contexts, where experiences are uncertain and still forming. Recent methodological discussions have highlighted SC’s potential for accessing cultural discourses and emotional responses while cautioning against overly rigid applications (Braun et al., 2019; Gravett, 2019; Pong, Roberts and Lum, 2024).

This study extends those debates by demonstrating how SC can function as a prototyping tool within participatory research, showing how it can be integrated within a HCD framework to explore intervention resonance prior to implementation, particularly in early-stage, exploratory research with groups navigating complex life transitions. Narrative imagination operated here as a low-risk and creative means of exploring potential support options, generating design-relevant insights while maintaining interpretive depth and sensitivity to context. This methodological innovation responds to calls for greater experimentation and conceptual openness in qualitative research (St Pierre, 2021; Lenette et al., 2022) and contributes to emerging discussions on ‘un-

methods' and methodological pluralism (Beggan, 2024; Beggan and McGannon, 2025). These works advocate creative, reflexive, and plural approaches that move beyond standardised models of behaviour change and recognise interpretation and imagination as valid forms of inquiry.

Narrative and participatory approaches can be combined to investigate complex life transitions and inform intervention design. As outlined in **Section 7.1.3**, the integration of co-design and SC generated layered insights, moving from lived experiences to collaborative envisioning and imaginative exploration. This approach aligns with contemporary debates on qualitative innovation, which emphasise creative, flexible, and context-sensitive practice over procedural standardisation (St Pierre, 2021; Beggan, 2024; Lenette et al., 2022). Beyond demonstrating methodological innovation, the study offers practical guidance for researchers, co-producers, and facilitators seeking to design creative participatory studies that attend to emotional, cultural, and narrative dimensions of engagement. For qualitative researchers, it extends existing work on SC (Braun, Clarke and Gray, 2019; Gravett, 2019) by showing how imaginative story work can operate as a structured stage within participatory design. For co-producers, it highlights how narrative methods can democratise intervention development by valuing interpretation and imagination as legitimate forms of data (Beresford, 2019). These contributions invite those involved in intervention design to reconsider what counts as evidence in early-stage development, showing that creative narrative engagement can reveal the emotional, social, and cultural dimensions of support often missed by traditional evaluation models. In doing so, this study demonstrates how methodological innovation can translate into more responsive, relational, and contextually grounded design practice.

7.4 Practical and Policy Contributions

This section outlines the applied contributions of the study, highlighting how its findings inform the design of more responsive, inclusive, and contextually relevant retirement and health and wellbeing interventions, as well as organisational and policy practice supporting women's TtR. The study offers evidence-informed insights for designing more meaningful and responsive support for women in the TtR. Current approaches to retirement and later-life health promotion often rely on standardised programmes or

individualised behaviour-change models that fail to reflect the diversity of women's experiences or the social contexts in which retirement occurs. These models frequently assume that if opportunities for participation are provided, individuals will engage in predictable ways, overlooking how social positioning, cultural norms, and emotional readiness shape participation (Blue et al., 2016; Lain, Vickerstaff and Loretto, 2019; Loretto and Vickerstaff, 2015). The findings from this research challenge that assumption, showing that engagement with support is influenced by emotional, cultural, and relational dynamics that evolve over time rather than by practical considerations alone. Recognising these dynamics is essential for designing interventions that resonate with women's lived experiences and varied circumstances. The human-centred, co-produced approach used in this study provides a practical framework for translating these insights into intervention design, enabling iterative, participant-led development rather than top-down programme delivery. This approach responds to the feminist gerontological critique outlined in **Chapter Two (Section 2.3)**, which demonstrates that women's retirement opportunities are shaped by cumulative life-course inequalities rather than individual choice alone. Designing support that is flexible and relational therefore addresses the structural conditions that influence later-life participation.

The research also demonstrates that women's engagement with retirement support is rarely straightforward. Across phases, women approached potential interventions through processes of negotiation shaped by personal histories, social identities, and cultural storylines. Practical uptake was influenced by logistical accessibility but also by whether the tone, pacing, and format of initiatives aligned with women's sense of identity and belonging. Programmes that appeared prescriptive or surveillant were often resisted, while approaches that conveyed warmth, inclusivity, and flexibility were viewed as more approachable and sustainable. These findings indicate that effective support must move beyond instrumental goals to address the affective and interpretive work women undertake during this period of change. In other words, interventions need to connect meaningfully with women's narratives and circumstances rather than treating engagement as a straightforward behavioural decision. This finding reflects feminist analyses of retirement as a gendered process shaped by unpaid care histories,

interrupted employment, and constrained pension accumulation (see **Section 2.3**).

Women's selective and cautious engagement can therefore be understood as a response to structurally patterned opportunities and risks, rather than as low motivation.

The co-designed prototypes developed in this study illustrate how this can be achieved in practice. Each prototype offered distinct insights into what makes support feel meaningful, acceptable, or alienating. For example, discussions around the Retirement Café highlighted the value of informal, welcoming spaces that allow women to explore new identities and routines without pressure. Participants imagined this as a place where conversations could unfold naturally, helping them to build new social connections at their own pace. The Buddy Scheme addressed apprehension about entering unfamiliar social spaces alone. Participants valued the idea of having a companion to ease first-time participation, particularly when confidence was low or social settings felt intimidating. Finally, the Women's TtR Exercise Class revealed the importance of flexibility in PA provision, acknowledging differing levels of confidence, ability, and motivation. Participants emphasised the need for environments that were supportive and inclusive rather than competitive or surveillance-oriented. These examples show how interventions can be tailored to address the nuanced emotional and cultural factors that shape engagement.

The narratives also showed that PA was experienced as an embodied and affective process through which women sensed capability, connection, and change. Moments of movement, such as walking, stretching, or dancing, were described in functional terms, while also helping women to reconnect with their bodies and rebuild confidence in social spaces. Focusing on these felt dimensions of activity shifts attention from measurable outcomes to lived experience, showing how sensations of vitality or limitation inform identity and belonging in later life (Phoenix and Smith, 2011). Recognising embodiment in this way highlights that supporting participation involves attending to how women feel in their bodies as much as what they do.

This research also highlights the value of interventions that allow for multiple entry points and accommodate different paces of engagement. Women's imagined engagements revealed a preference for support that recognised ambivalence, allowed

for tentative or cyclical participation, and could adapt to changing circumstances. Interventions that were modular and socially attuned were seen as more realistic and appealing than those that assumed linear trajectories of engagement. For example, some participants envisioned attending a Retirement Café sporadically as their confidence grew, while others described gradually increasing their involvement in PA over time. These patterns emphasise the importance of designing support that mirrors the fluidity of real-life transitions rather than imposing rigid expectations.

These findings have direct relevance for organisations involved in retirement planning, community development, and health promotion. Employers, community organisations, and public health bodies can use these insights to develop initiatives that are sensitive to cultural expectations and the lived realities of retirement transitions. This may include creating spaces for informal social connection, offering low-barrier entry routes into PA, and supporting flexible forms of participation that build confidence over time. Partnering with trusted community networks may also help reach groups who are less likely to engage with formal support programmes. Such approaches could help address persistent inequities in retirement experiences, particularly for women with fewer resources or less access to supportive networks, while also encouraging broader definitions of success that reflect the temporal and emotional nature of retirement transitions, recognising confidence, connection, and gradual re-engagement as meaningful outcomes in their own right (Coalter, 2013; Popay et al., 2008; South, 2015).

At a policy level, the study emphasises the importance of moving beyond narrow models of successful ageing that emphasise individual responsibility and continuous productivity. Policies that support inclusive, community-based, and relationally oriented programmes are more likely to resonate with the diverse needs of women navigating the TtR. Embedding narrative and participatory approaches within programme design and evaluation can help ensure that interventions are culturally relevant, emotionally attuned, and responsive to the complexities of people's lives. This shift has broader implications for public health and ageing policy. It encourages a move away from universalised, one-size-fits-all frameworks toward more flexible and context-sensitive approaches that acknowledge diversity and uncertainty as integral to later-life transitions. Such a shift aligns with feminist political economy perspectives

that call for recognition of care, relational wellbeing, and unequal resource distribution in later life policy (**Section 2.3**), moving beyond models based on continuous employment and individual responsibility.

Women's responses to the PA prototype further illustrated how movement can operate as a narrative space for exploring identity, continuity, and belonging in the TtR.

Engagement with the Women's TtR Exercise Class was rarely imagined in terms of fitness or health outcomes alone. Instead, stories positioned movement as a way of regaining rhythm, confidence, and connection while negotiating visibility and self-assurance in later life. For some, shared participation symbolised renewal and companionship; for others, it revealed unease about pace, appearance, or cultural fit. These differences highlighted the need for PA support that is emotionally and culturally sensitive, offering multiple ways of joining in and stepping back. They also show how women's imagined engagement complicates dominant active ageing ideals that link movement with individual responsibility or moral worth (Katz, 2013). This critique echoes feminist concerns that "active ageing" frameworks can reproduce gendered expectations of self-management while overlooking embodied and material constraints. Framing movement as a social and interpretive practice rather than a behavioural target opens new possibilities for inclusive and relevant later-life provision. Designing opportunities that recognise movement as both practice and metaphor for change can help women imagine and sustain transitions that feel coherent, supportive, and meaningful (Phoenix and Smith, 2011; Fullagar, 2020).

Across participants' stories, retirement appeared as both liberation and loss. Feelings of relief, curiosity, and optimism often coexisted with frustration, guilt, or unease about how to use time well. Such emotional layering reflects the ambivalence that threads through women's later-life narratives, where moments of renewal sit alongside doubts about purpose and belonging. These tensions are not signs of confusion but expressions of the cultural complexity surrounding ageing femininity, where ideals of independence and productivity intersect with embodied experiences of change. Recognising ambivalence as a narrative pattern helps highlight the social negotiations women perform in constructing coherent stories about retirement and activity (Frank, 2010; Phoenix and Smith, 2011).

In summary, the practical and policy contributions of this study lie in demonstrating how support for women in the TtR can be more effectively designed when emotional, relational, and cultural dimensions are taken seriously. Attending to these dimensions highlights that engagement is not a simple matter of access or motivation, but a dynamic process shaped by identity, belonging, and embodied experience (Phoenix and Smith, 2011; Fullagar, 2020). By showing how women interpret, adapt, and sometimes resist available forms of support, the research offers valuable guidance for creating initiatives that are flexible, inclusive, and responsive to real-life complexity. These insights are relevant not only to retirement transition contexts but also to broader efforts to design public health interventions that engage meaningfully with people's lived experiences and diverse cultural narratives.

7.5 Study Limitations and Future Research Directions

This section outlines the practical, methodological, and conceptual limitations of the study and identifies directions for future research, drawing on lessons learned across the three phases to inform future narrative and participatory studies on women's TtR. This study was shaped by a range of practical, methodological, and conceptual constraints that, while inevitable in a long-term qualitative project, offer valuable insights for future research.

Practical and contextual considerations affected recruitment, retention, and implementation across the three phases. Reaching and sustaining engagement with women in the TtR proved challenging, particularly as participants' availability, health, and life circumstances shifted over time. These challenges were compounded by unexpected external events, including a cyber incident at the host institution that disrupted communications and data access, a period of serious illness that I experienced, and periods of international travel that affected the project timeline. The logistics and complexity of undertaking co-production research introduced further unpredictability. As a researcher, I had to relinquish a degree of control over the research direction, responding to participants' ideas, availability, and priorities as these emerged. This flexibility was integral to the participatory ethos of the project but required constant adaptation and openness to shifting trajectories. These factors altered timelines, reduced continuity between phases, and required adjustments in

research design. Workshop formats were shortened, the SC activity was refined to reduce participant burden, and recruitment strategies had to be repeatedly adapted. While such challenges are widely acknowledged in co-production literature (Hickey et al., 2018; Locock and Boaz, 2019; Roper et al., 2018), this study contributes an additional layer of insight by illustrating how these dynamics play out across an extended, multi-method design involving both co-productive and narrative components. The findings highlight the importance of designing research that can accommodate interruptions and variable engagement, particularly in studies that extend over long periods.

Recruiting and sustaining engagement with this targeted group also presented difficulties that, in retrospect, could have been mitigated through alternative approaches. For example, workshop attendance was affected by last-minute cancellations and drop-outs, which disrupted continuity and limited group diversity. While the sample included participants from a range of socioeconomic backgrounds (SIMD scores 1 to 9), ethnic diversity was limited. All women who participated in Phases One and Two were white. This reflects wider trends in retirement research, where certain groups are more likely to engage than others (Phoenix and Smith, 2011; Dionigi, 2017; Fullagar, 2020). Ideally, the sample would have included more participants from Scottish ethnic minority communities to reflect population diversity and to explore how cultural and structural factors intersect in shaping retirement transitions. Collecting more detailed demographic data during the SC activity, including ethnicity, could also have provided a clearer picture of sample composition and helped to identify gaps earlier in the process.

There was some diversity in other respects, including the participation of women with disabilities and a woman in a same-sex marriage, which enriched the data. However, future research could benefit from more targeted recruitment strategies to reach underrepresented groups, possibly through community organisations or cultural networks with established trust. Studies of participatory and co-produced research highlight that sustained engagement often depends on existing community relationships and researcher visibility (Bonevski et al., 2014; O'Mara-Eves et al., 2015). Offering gratuities or covering travel expenses might also help to lower barriers to

participation; however, this raises important ethical considerations regarding equity, motivation, and the potential influence on participation (Smith, 2011; INVOLVE, 2012). Developing clearer contingency plans for last-minute cancellations and participant drop-out, such as maintaining a reserve list, would also have strengthened continuity. Meeting gatekeepers in person, rather than relying on digital communication, may have fostered stronger relationships and improved recruitment processes. These reflections underline the importance of strategic planning and relational groundwork when working with groups navigating transitional and sometimes unpredictable life stages (Hickey et al., 2018). Engagement with feminist gerontological and political economy perspectives also prompted reflection on my own location within the gendered life course that the study examines. My employment history includes periods of care work and a return to education, resulting in a fragmented career trajectory and, consequently, a more uncertain future pension position. Recognising these material implications brought the structural dynamics discussed in **Chapter Two** into sharper focus and heightened my sensitivity to participants' accounts of interrupted employment, financial precarity, and constrained choice.

This reflexive awareness influenced both the design and interpretation of the research. It reinforced my decision to prioritise narrative and participatory methods that value situated knowledge and relational experience, and it encouraged a critical stance towards policy models that frame later-life wellbeing primarily in terms of individual responsibility and continuous productivity. While the study does not adopt a formal feminist framework, these perspectives shaped my analytic attention to power, inequality, care, and embodiment throughout the research process.

Women's reflections on staying active often drew on broader cultural messages that equate movement with virtue and inactivity with decline. The discourse of "good ageing" positions PA as evidence of responsibility, discipline, and self-management, qualities celebrated within neoliberal health cultures. Several participants questioned these expectations, expressing fatigue with the continual pressure to "keep going." Recognising these cultural expectations is important for practice. Interventions should encourage engagement without reinforcing hierarchies of worth or stigmatising rest, a concern raised in critiques of active ageing discourses that link movement to moral

value (Katz, 2013). Understanding activity as relational and context dependent shifts attention from behavioural targets to lived experience and social connection (Phoenix and Smith, 2011). This perspective supports more compassionate and inclusive approaches to later-life wellbeing that recognise emotion, embodiment, and varying capacities for participation (Fullagar, 2020).

Methodological considerations also warrant reflection. Each method generated valuable but distinct forms of narrative material, requiring careful integration across phases. Narrative interviews produced detailed accounts of lived experiences but were shaped by retrospective and prospective perspectives. Co-design workshops encouraged collaborative envisioning but were influenced by group composition and interactional dynamics. The SC activity, by contrast, provided imaginative and discursive data rather than behavioural accounts. Rather than seeking to measure engagement or uptake, it revealed the emotional and relational meanings that underpin imagined participation. This form of narrative exploration extends beyond behavioural models to illuminate how support concepts are interpreted, negotiated, and made sense of within participants' everyday worlds. The use of HCD practices supported translation between narrative insight and intervention concepts; however, future research could explore more sustained iterative prototyping cycles to examine how co-designed ideas evolve in real-world settings.

The design of the SC activity also raised important considerations about accessibility. Administering the activity exclusively online assumed a baseline level of literacy and digital competence among participants. While this format offered clear advantages in terms of flexibility, reach, and ease of data collation, it may have inadvertently excluded some women in the TtR who had lower levels of digital literacy, limited access to technology, or differing educational backgrounds. Studies of online qualitative methods have highlighted similar tensions: digital formats can widen participation geographically but may also reproduce inequalities linked to age, income, or confidence with technology (Lupton, 2020; Howlett, 2021). Providing alternative modes of participation, such as paper-based versions or options for oral dictation, could have widened accessibility and enabled involvement from a more diverse group. However, approaches such as using a scribe would have required careful handling, as the

presence of another person may have influenced narrative flow and introduced additional layers of interpretation into the data. These reflections point to the need for future research to balance accessibility with methodological rigour when using SC with midlife and older populations.

Future research could address these methodological limitations by combining SC with longitudinal qualitative methods, such as follow-up interviews or ethnographic observation, to trace how imagined engagements relate to real-world practices as retirement unfolds. Similarly, the co-design process could benefit from iterative cycles of prototyping, feedback, and refinement to explore how intervention concepts evolve through sustained collaboration with different groups.

Conceptual limitations also shape the scope of this study and suggest promising directions for future work. The research was conducted within a specific cultural, policy, and demographic context: women living in Scotland, approaching or in the early stages of retirement. This focus enabled detailed, situated analysis but necessarily narrows the applicability of findings to other populations or welfare regimes. Cultural narratives, retirement structures, and gendered life course patterns vary significantly across contexts, influencing how women interpret and navigate the TtR. Comparative studies that explore these dynamics across different regions, ethnic communities, or welfare systems could deepen understanding of how structural conditions and cultural narratives interact to shape retirement experiences in diverse ways. These contextual boundaries mean the findings should be understood as analytically transferable rather than statistically generalisable.

The study also concentrated primarily on the early stages of the TtR. This decision reflected the focus on expectations, identity work, and imagined engagement, but it means that less is known about how narratives and support needs evolve over time. The findings suggest that retirement is not a single moment but a prolonged and fluid process. Future longitudinal studies could examine how narratives shift as women settle into new routines, encounter unexpected life events, or adapt to changing health, financial, and social circumstances. Following participants over multiple years would provide valuable insights into how early expectations and imagined engagements align

or diverge from later experiences, and how intervention needs and preferences develop across different stages of later life.

Another conceptual consideration concerns narrative negotiation and intervention design. This study focused on analysing how women negotiate cultural storylines and imagined support, but there remains scope to examine more explicitly how these narrative processes interact with policy frameworks, institutional agendas, and design practices at scale. Future research could, for example, investigate how co-produced narratives are translated or diluted when interventions are scaled up in organisational or policy contexts. This could help bridge the gap between narrative insight and programme implementation, ensuring that the nuances of lived experience are not lost in standardisation processes.

Theoretical framing also presents a potential limitation. While feminist perspectives on ageing and retirement informed the literature review and contextual analysis, the study did not adopt an explicitly feminist theoretical framework to guide methodological or analytic decisions. This was a deliberate choice, shaped by the focus on NI and participatory design methods as alternative ways of exploring gendered experiences. However, a more explicitly feminist framing might have enabled deeper critique of structural power relations and gendered inequalities, such as cumulative pension disadvantages, the gendered division of care, and persistent labour market inequalities, and could have generated different insights into the institutional and cultural forces shaping women's retirement transitions. Future research could draw on feminist frameworks that attend to embodiment, emotion, and material context to deepen analysis of structural dynamics alongside narrative and participatory approaches. Work on feminist affect and embodiment highlights how emotions are shaped through social relations and power (Ahmed, 2014). Feminist gerontological research demonstrates how ageing is experienced through embodied and relational processes across the life course (Phoenix and Tulle, 2017). Feminist sport and PA scholarship also shows how gendered expectations shape participation and belonging in later life contexts (McGannon, 2018).

There is also potential to extend the theoretical contributions of this work. The thesis highlighted narrative negotiation as a key process shaping engagement with transitional

supports, drawing on DNA and concepts such as restitution, quest, and chaos narratives (Frank, 2010). Future studies might build on these insights by exploring how narrative negotiation intersects with broader sociological or psychological theories of behaviour change, motivation, and ageing, such as social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1997), self-determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 2000), or critical gerontology perspectives (Katz and Calasanti, 2015). Integrating narrative perspectives with frameworks from public health, design studies, or critical gerontology could generate new interdisciplinary approaches to understanding and supporting later-life transitions.

Finally, this research points to a wider conceptual agenda concerning the role of narrative in health and wellbeing research. Story-based methods offer distinctive insights into how people imagine futures, interpret cultural expectations, and position themselves in relation to social change. There is scope to examine how these narrative dynamics operate in other transitional contexts, such as menopause, bereavement, or relocation, and how they can inform the development of more flexible and culturally attuned interventions. Expanding this line of inquiry could help shift the focus of intervention research from prescriptive behaviour change models towards approaches that recognise uncertainty, ambivalence, and interpretive work as central aspects of lived experience. Future research could also explore how retirement transitions intersect with cognitive health and early onset conditions, extending inclusive design approaches developed in dementia and employability research (Ritchie, Egdell and Tolson, 2020; Ritchie, Lebec and Allen, 2025).

While the study sought to remain faithful to the principles of co-production, some limits were inevitable. The interpretive analysis, particularly in later phases, required my voice to take a more prominent role in synthesising meaning across participants' stories. This did not replace collaboration but carried participants' earlier contributions into broader theoretical and practical discussions.

These considerations point to several promising avenues for future research.

Longitudinal narrative studies could deepen understanding of how women's retirement transitions evolve over extended periods, capturing shifts in identity, relationships, and engagement with support over time. Expanding research to include more diverse populations, particularly women from ethnic minority communities, lower

socioeconomic groups, and varied geographic contexts, would help to address persistent gaps in current knowledge and challenge dominant framings shaped by more privileged experiences. There is also scope to explore how participatory and co-production approaches might be scaled or adapted to different organisational and policy contexts, including workplace transition programmes, community health initiatives, and ageing-friendly urban planning. This study provides a foundation for such work by demonstrating how narrative and participatory methods can reveal complex, culturally situated experiences of the TtR and generate practical insights for intervention design. While these insights are contextually grounded, transferability may be limited by demographic and cultural factors, and caution is needed when extending these findings to more diverse populations.

Addressing these limitations will strengthen methodological rigour and widen the conceptual and practical impact of future studies. Extending narrative and participatory approaches through longitudinal and interdisciplinary designs could provide deeper insight into how transitional experiences unfold within different cultural and policy contexts. For example, combining NI with behavioural science could illuminate how interventions function across diverse populations, while collaboration with urban planning or workplace policy initiatives could support the development of ageing-friendly environments. Such work would contribute to more inclusive, culturally attuned, and impactful strategies for supporting women's retirement transitions.

7.6 Closing Reflections

Looking back across the research journey, this study has been shaped by moments of uncertainty, adaptation, and discovery. What began as an exploration of women's expectations and experiences during the TtR developed into a layered, participatory, and narrative-led inquiry that evolved in response to both methodological intentions and the realities of fieldwork. The three-phase design created opportunities to move between lived experience, collaborative intervention design, and imaginative exploration. In practice, this was neither linear nor fully predictable. Instead, the project unfolded through an ongoing process of negotiation between research aims, participant engagement, and shifting practical circumstances. These negotiations mirrored, in many ways, the experiences of the women who participated in the study,

whose retirement journeys were similarly fluid and subject to change. This experience also reshaped me as a researcher and educator. What began as a predefined doctoral studentship evolved into the development of my own scholarly voice, greater confidence in navigating uncertainty, and a clearer understanding of how research, teaching, and collaboration intersect.

One of the most significant aspects of this journey was learning to work with, rather than against, uncertainty. Conducting co-production research required me to relinquish a degree of control over the direction and pace of the project. While the study began with a clear structure, its trajectory was ultimately shaped by the ideas, availability, and priorities of participants, as well as external events that could not have been anticipated. This required flexibility, trust in the process, and a willingness to adapt to emerging possibilities. At times, this felt uncomfortable. Coming from a health background, my instinct was to plan, manage, and troubleshoot in advance. However, co-production often required me to hold space for ambiguity and accept that clarity would emerge through interaction, not through pre-determined plans. This shift was crucial to maintaining the participatory ethos of the project, allowing participants and co-producers to influence its direction in meaningful ways. This process also marked an important turning point in my professional identity. Letting go of tightly managed structures and embracing emergent, dialogical ways of working required me to think and act differently as a researcher. It pushed me to develop a more reflexive stance and to recognise the value of shared uncertainty as a generative part of co-production.

The trajectory of the study was also shaped by personal and contextual factors. Periods of illness, international travel, and an institutional cyber incident interrupted planned timelines and reduced continuity between phases. These disruptions were challenging, both practically and emotionally, as they required me to repeatedly reorient the project while maintaining momentum and coherence. Adapting the research design became a process of constant recalibration: workshop formats were adapted to accommodate lower attendance, recruitment strategies were revised multiple times, and the SC activity was refined to reduce participant burden. Each adjustment required critical reflection on how best to protect the integrity of the research while responding to unpredictable circumstances. These experiences deepened my understanding of what

it means to conduct long-term qualitative research with groups who are themselves navigating change. They also demanded resilience and adaptability. I had to learn to manage setbacks pragmatically while sustaining the intellectual and ethical direction of the work. These experiences strengthened my capacity to navigate the kinds of contingencies that often characterise qualitative fieldwork but are less frequently discussed in formal methodological accounts.

Engaging closely with participants' stories and working collaboratively to design and test support concepts reshaped my understanding of the TtR. In the early stages, I imagined retirement largely as a structured transition, defined by identifiable challenges and opportunities that could be addressed through targeted support. Through narrative interviews, co-production workshops, and SC activities, I came to understand retirement as far more complex: an evolving process shaped by intersecting cultural narratives, structural conditions, and personal histories. Women's experiences were characterised by cycles of anticipation, adjustment, and reinterpretation. The ways they imagined, evaluated, and sometimes resisted different forms of support revealed the importance of emotional, relational, and cultural factors that are often overlooked in conventional intervention models. This learning challenged some of my initial assumptions and reinforced the need for approaches that are flexible, inclusive, and responsive to lived complexity. My time in Canada, particularly during IRTS and NASSM, also broadened my intellectual horizons at this stage. Exposure to international debates around ageing, PA, qualitative innovation, and intervention design encouraged me to think beyond local contexts and to situate my findings within wider methodological and policy conversations. This experience expanded my sense of what my work could contribute internationally.

The co-design process was particularly formative. Inviting participants to act as co-producers required me to shift from the role of expert to that of facilitator and collaborator. Ideas about support did not always emerge in the structured ways I expected. Some concepts evolved through casual conversation or unexpected moments, rather than formal activities. At other times, co-producers diverged from planned exercises to pursue ideas that felt more relevant to them. These moments were often the most generative. They reminded me that co-production is as much about

creating the conditions for shared meaning-making as it is about delivering specific outputs. Letting go of tight control allowed for richer and more situated understandings to emerge. I also found that these workshops often became spaces of mutual learning. Facilitating discussions required many of the same skills I would later draw on in teaching contexts: listening carefully, encouraging participation, and responding flexibly to unexpected directions. Co-producers frequently challenged my assumptions, prompting me to rethink questions and explore new angles. These experiences significantly shaped my approach to facilitation and knowledge exchange.

The use of SC in Phase Three also offered unexpected insights. Initially, I viewed SC primarily as a practical method for evaluating prototype functionality when in-person workshops were no longer feasible. In practice, SC generated narratives that were emotionally layered, culturally situated, and highly reflective of participants' positioning in relation to the proposed interventions. This method revealed not only potential actions but also the meanings attached to them, showing how engagement with support is negotiated rather than simply decided. Working with SC data expanded my appreciation of creative narrative methods as tools for exploring transitional experiences in ways that interviews or workshops alone might not achieve. This methodological broadening was an important milestone. It strengthened my confidence to use and adapt creative methods in future research and reinforced the importance of responsive design when investigating complex transitions.

On a personal level, the research journey required me to navigate a shift in professional identity. Engaging deeply with NI, HCD, co-production, and SC challenged the structured frameworks and outcome-focused approaches that had shaped my previous professional life. I had to learn to hold multiple interpretive perspectives at once, to work with emergent data, and to reflect critically on my role in shaping the research. This required sustained reflexivity, as I became more aware of how my background, assumptions, and decisions influenced the research process.

Completing this research as part of a funded studentship shaped its trajectory in significant ways. The initial structure and aims provided a clear starting point, but as the project developed, I increasingly made it my own. Decisions about methodological design, analytic focus, and the framing of contributions were shaped through

supervisory dialogue, critical engagement with literature, and my evolving research identity. This process of taking ownership unfolded gradually, as my confidence grew and I developed a clearer sense of how my work could make a distinctive contribution to knowledge and practice. Reaching this stage of intellectual independence felt like a pivotal moment in my development. It marked a transition from being a student working within predefined boundaries to becoming a researcher able to set my own agenda, make strategic choices, and articulate a clear scholarly position.

The opportunities that arose during the PhD were formative. My time in Canada had a profound impact on my thinking and practice. Participating in IRTS and presenting at NASSM exposed me to new intellectual communities, methodological debates, and theoretical perspectives. These experiences broadened my understanding of how retirement, PA, and ageing are approached in different contexts, and encouraged me to situate my work within international conversations about qualitative innovation and public health.

More broadly, undertaking this PhD has been an intensive period of intellectual and personal growth. I have gained a much deeper understanding of philosophy, qualitative methodology, and the complexities of data collection in real-world contexts. I have learned how to craft research narratives, write for publication, and navigate peer review and academic presentation. Developing the skills of critical thinking and reflexivity has been particularly significant. Engaging deeply with narrative theory, participatory methods, and creative qualitative approaches has sharpened my ability to interrogate assumptions, both my own and those embedded in dominant frameworks. It has also taught me to attend carefully to the relational, cultural, and ethical dimensions of research, which will shape my future practice. Alongside these developments, I have grown significantly as a teacher. Sharing emerging ideas with students, designing seminar activities informed by my research, and supporting critical discussions have strengthened my ability to communicate complex concepts clearly and responsively. Teaching has also provided a space to reflect on my research from different perspectives, reinforcing the reciprocal relationship between research and education.

This process has been challenging, at times unpredictable, and profoundly rewarding. I now have a stronger sense of myself as a qualitative researcher, able to think critically

and work creatively with complex questions. The experiences gained through this project have shaped both my intellectual outlook and my practical skills in lasting ways. They have also strengthened my resilience, as I learned to navigate uncertainty, adapt to changing circumstances, and keep the research moving forward. These experiences have given me the confidence to contribute to qualitative scholarship, collaborative research, and teaching, and to continue developing as a researcher whose work is thoughtful, engaged, and responsive to real-world complexity.

These reflections also have methodological significance. They highlight the importance of embracing uncertainty as an integral part of qualitative inquiry rather than a limitation to be managed. Working with methodological messiness can create space for responsiveness, dialogue, and innovation, which are essential when exploring complex social transitions such as retirement. This perspective aligns with contemporary arguments that uncertainty and openness can enhance the depth and relevance of participatory research. It offers lessons for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers who seek to design studies or interventions that are flexible, context-sensitive, and attuned to real-world change (Law, 2004; Lather, 2007; Lenette et al., 2022).

Fundamentally, this research journey has been transformative, both intellectually and personally. It has equipped me to continue contributing to qualitative research and to the evolving conversations on ageing, narrative, and health and wellbeing intervention design in the years to come.

This thesis also builds on recent work that positions NI as an active process of world-making rather than a representational method (Beggan, 2024). Developed within a studentship shaped by this intellectual foundation, the study extends these ideas by integrating NI with co-production, HCD, and SC as a form of low-risk prototyping. In doing so, it shows how stories can operate simultaneously as analytic material, collaborative design resources, and speculative sites through which new forms of support can be imagined. This moves narrative research beyond interpretation alone and demonstrates its practical relevance for intervention development in later-life transitions.

These reflections bring the research journey full circle, returning to the central role of narrative in shaping understanding and possibility. Stories, as Frank (2010; 2012) observes, are how people make sense of uncertainty and imagine what might come next. Through this lens, the thesis offers new ways of understanding women's retirement transitions and of designing supports that honour their complexity, diversity, and creativity.

7.7 Final Summary

This thesis examined how women make sense of the TtR and how narrative and participatory approaches can inform the design of support. Across three interlinked phases, it traced a movement from lived experience to collaborative design and imaginative exploration. This progression showed how stories can function as both data and design material, revealing how support is interpreted, negotiated, and reimaged through narrative practice.

The study contributes a new understanding of retirement as a dialogical and evolving experience, shaped by women's relationships, emotions, and social contexts. It also demonstrates that creative qualitative methods, including the integration of HCD and DNA, can expand what intervention research can achieve. In doing so, it offers a framework for approaching later-life transitions with sensitivity to complexity, difference, and change.

The thesis closes by returning to the idea that stories are central to how people make meaning and imagine possible futures. By engaging with women's stories and working collaboratively to translate them into potential forms of support, this research generates insights that are both theoretically and practically significant. It invites continued exploration of narrative and participatory approaches in ageing and health research, where imagination and dialogue can play a vital role in shaping more inclusive and responsive futures.

Appendix A: Ethics Application Phase One 19467

Filter Questions

- I confirm I have read the UWS and my School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship.
(please tick to continue)

Pre-screening Questions

Does your work involve any of the following. (please tick all that apply)

- Human Participants
 Personal Data
 Animals
 Risk to the Investigator
- None of the above

Based on your answers to the above questions you should complete the remainder of this form and submit it to your school ethics committee for approval **PRIOR** to commencing any work on your project. Please click Next to proceed.

Applicant Details

Position of Principal Investigator

Postgraduate

Principal Investigator

Title

First Name

Surname

RESCHHL

Laura

Calder

Email

B00348835@studentmail.uws.ac.uk

School

Health and Life Sciences

Are there any co-applicants

Yes

No

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Title

First Name

Surname

Dr

Angela

Beggan

School

School of Health and Life Sciences

Email

Angela.Beggan@uws.ac.uk

Collaborators

Are there any other collaborators?

Yes

No

Project Information

Title of Study

Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Primary purpose of the study

Original Research

Where will the proposed research take place?

The interviews will take place online via Microsoft Teams or in person at the University of the West of Scotland, Lanarkshire Campus, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 OLH, at a date and time suitable to each participant

How will the costs of the study be met?

The costs of the study have been incorporated into the agreed UWS studentship.

Previous Approvals

Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee?

- Yes
- No

Purpose, justification, design and methodology

**Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study:
(word limit 1000 words)**

PURPOSE/JUSTIFICATION

The transition to retirement (TtR) is a major event in women's lives (Byles et al, 2013), which has a profound effect on health and wellbeing (Zantinge et al. 2013). The TtR presents a window of opportunity for primary prevention interventions to improve health outcomes and promote healthier behaviours in women, who, are acknowledged to be more receptive to health messages during life transitions (Smeaton et al, 2017, Lara et al. 2014).

At present, there is a limited body of knowledge on the lived experiences of women's TtR. Gathering stories from women within five years of retirement will provide a unique opportunity to explore the complexity of women's ageing experiences. Using narrative methods, their storied accounts will be used to understand the underlying mechanisms of successful adjustment to retirement (Hansson et al. 2018).

This project aims to make an original contribution to the gap in knowledge in our understanding of women's retirement expectations, the factors that impact them, and the causal intersecting relationships. Using their voices to depict their experiences of ageing will provide insight and understanding of what women do, want, and need, within this transitional life phase to promote positive and active ageing.

RESEARCH DESIGN

As a multi-stage project, the research design follows an iterative process consisting of three key phases of inspiration, ideation, and implementation (Roberts, Fisher, Trowbridge, and Bent, 2016). This ethics application covers phase 1. Phase 1 consists of narrative interviews with women in the pre, peri, and post-stages of retirement, to gain understanding and insight into their feelings and appreciate their experiences of retirement. This application seeks ethical approval to conduct individual interviews with willing participants to discuss their experiences of their transition to retirement. Subsequent phases will be developed from phase 1 and will be submitted for ethical approval at a later date.

Narrative methods will be used as the foundation to elicit and document stories of the diversity of life experiences of women in the TtR. Narrative interviews will explore the participant's experience of retirement and active ageing, eliciting how women tell their stories and create meaning in their lived realities (Rejnö et al. 2014).

PARTICIPANTS AND SAMPLING

To gain an insightful and in-depth understanding, purposive sampling strategies with maximum variation and snowballing (Creswell, 1998) are used in this design. The sample of women is sought from associates of South Lanarkshire Leisure and Culture (SLLC). The sample will be contacted directly through SLLC via email inviting women within five years of retirement to participate in the research project concerning their experiences with the TtR. The initial contacts gained using this method will be added to via snowball sampling, procured through existing participants. At present, the sample size is not yet known; however, SLLC is a large employer and recruitment is expected to procure a minimum of six participants and a maximum of fifteen participants.

DATA COLLECTION

Data will be obtained through two separate means: an online demographic Microsoft Form and individual interviews with participants. A hard copy of the demographic Microsoft Form is attached below. Data from the demographic Microsoft Form will be analysed using descriptive statistics to ascertain participant characteristics. All data will be stored in accordance with data protection, ensuring confidentiality, anonymity, and will have regard for duty of care. All personal data acquired through the process of this study will be anonymised, data will be encrypted, password protected, and paper copies will be locked within a filing cabinet. Pseudonyms will be employed to minimise the risk of deductive disclosure of participant identification. Participants will also be given the option to be named within the research to acknowledge their contribution.

Interviews will be arranged with individual participants and will either be held online via Microsoft Teams or at the University of the West of Scotland, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH, at a time and date of their choice. Each interview is expected to last 1 hour and may involve more than one meeting. In person interviews will be audio recorded. Online interviews held via Microsoft Teams will be audio and visually recorded. Participant consent will be obtained. Consent Microsoft Form attached.

DATA ANALYSIS

All interviews will be transcribed verbatim. Interview transcripts will be analysed using Frank's (2011) dialogical narrative analysis (DNA). DNA understands stories as artful representations of lives; stories reshape past and imaginatively project the future (Frank, 2011). DNA's interest lies in hearing how multiple voices find expression within any single voice (Frank, 2011, p. 35). DNA does not have a step-by-step procedure but prefers a "movement of thought" through dialogical questioning (Frank, 2011, 2012),

which will allow me to examine participants thoughts, beliefs, attitudes, relationships and identify re-occurring themes.

How has the scientific quality of the proposed research project been assessed?

- Independent external review
- Review within a company
- Review within a multi-centre research group
- Review within the principal investigator's institution
- Review within the research team
- Review by supervisor/director of studies
- Other

Sample Size

Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

Purposeful samples of women pre, peri, and post-retirement intend to be sought for the first phase of participation in this research. Soft boundaries will be placed on participants' age if they are within a five-year period of retirement. Where possible, the research participants will show a diversity of human culture and conditions, taking full account of ethnicity, disability, sexual orientation, and socio-economic circumstances in the design, undertaking, and reporting. By ensuring a broad age range, I have allowed for maximum recruitment with participant diversity. I have excluded males and non-binary individuals as seek narrative from women and those who identify as women only to reflect on the female element of the study. Consideration will be given to any participants that fall under the predetermined groups as disclosed in UWS' School of Health and Life Sciences Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship, where any additional requirement/needs will be met where duly possible.

At present, the sample size is not yet known; however, SLLC is a large employer, and recruitment is expected to secure a minimum of two participants and a maximum of five participants in each category. These figures will derive the minimum number of participants to six and the maximum number of participants to fifteen. Should a significantly large number of women wish to participate, I will reduce the parameters to two years pre- and post-retirement to elicit the most accurate portrayal of retirement. If there is an insufficient number of participants attained through this method, the number of participants will be added to via snowball sampling, procured through existing participants.

Analysis and Presentation

Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

Data will be analysed as outlined above. The data will be presented to fulfill the requirements of a doctorate and academic publication. Data will be disseminated through academic publications.

Interviews/Questionnaires

Does the proposed research involve the use of individual/group interviews or questionnaires?

- Yes
- No

Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule

Documents					
Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date	Version	Size
Default	INTERVIEW GUIDE	INTERVIEW GUIDE .docx	07/11/2022	2	22.3 KB

Will proposed interviews or questionnaires discuss topics that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting for participants or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could occur during the study?

- Yes
- No

Impact on Participants

Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:

The sample of women is sought from associates of SLLC, who have previously agreed to support this research project. A letter of support from SLLC is attached to confirm their agreement. Negotiations will be made with personnel from SLLC by myself and my research supervisor. From negotiations, administration personnel will be approached and asked to distribute an open email to females approaching the retirement transition and recent female retirees explaining the study. A brief online demographic Microsoft Form will be attached to the email. The Consent Microsoft Form will ask if any respondents agree to be interviewed, and if so, respondents will be invited to contact me at the contact details supplied. Respondents will also be asked if they are willing to participate further in this research to help develop activities for women in retirement.

This method of contact will assume confidentiality as no personal data will be divulged without the written consent of any approached potential participants. Each participant will be informed of the risks, benefits, and commitments of research prior to agreeing to participate. An information sheet will be provided, and informed consent will be sought. Participants will have two weeks to decide if they wish to participate. Agreeable parties will be invited to attend an individual interview session conducted either online via Microsoft Teams or in person at the University of the West of Scotland, Lanarkshire Campus, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 OLH, at a date and time suitable to each participant.

Will participants be from any of the following groups? (Please tick all that apply)

- Children under 16
- Adults with learning disabilities
- Adults with a terminal illness
- Adults in emergency situations
- Adults with mental illness (particularly if detained under the mental health act)
- Adults with dementia
- Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves
- Those who could be considered to have a particularly dependent relationship with the investigator
- Other
- None of the above

Are there any special pressures which would make it difficult for potential participants to refuse to take part in your study? (e.g., relationship to the investigator?)

It is not expected that any participants will be known to me as I reside in a different geographical locale. All individuals contacted have the choice to respond, thus reducing pressure to participate in the study.

Will study participants be paid to take part?

- Yes
- No

What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

Each participant will engage in an interview that is expected to last around 1 hour (60

Will informed consent be obtained from study participants?

- Yes
- No

Please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

A letter of informed consent will be electronically sent to potential participants along with a basic overview and participant information sheet which will outline the aims of the study. Participants will also be invited to participate in future research activities to help develop activities for women in retirement. At the time of the interview, an overview of the study and will obtain further written and oral consent. A PDF copy, if requested, will be provided to participants. If any participants are agreeable and selected to go forth for a focus group meeting/workshop, a participant information sheet will be given, detailing data protection and consent. Consent will be an

Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)

Type	Document	File	Version	Version	Size
Default	Participant Information Sheet	Participant Information Sheet Phase 2	28/11/20	2	34.

Type	Document	File	Version	Version	Size
Default	Participant Consent	Participant Consent Form	28/11/20	2	24.

Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)?

- Yes
- No

Does the proposed research involve any physically invasive procedures?

- Yes
- No

Does the proposed research involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the identity of the investigator?

- Yes
- No

Will research participants be debriefed after their participation?

- Yes
- No

Are there any other Ethical Considerations you wish to bring to the attention of the committee?

- Yes
- No

Personal Data

What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?

Participants identifying details will be anonymised for analysis and in the final write-up to protect identities. Participants who choose not to be anonymised will be acknowledged within the research and any subsequent publishing. Any identifying aspects of organisations or locations will be removed or adjusted to ensure confidentiality and prevent deductive disclosure.

All data files will be password protected and available only to members of the research team. The raw data (e.g., recordings) will be stored on UWS password-protected cloud storage. Once the thesis is completed, all data will be destroyed in line with university guidelines within five years of doctorate completion. The consent forms will be stored in UWS Vault by my research supervisor.

Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

Raw data collected from the research participants will be accessible only to myself and my research team. All data will be stored in accordance with data protection, ensuring confidentiality, and anonymity, and will have regard for duty of care. All personal data acquired through the process of this study will be anonymised, data will be password protected, and paper copies will be locked within a filing cabinet. Pseudonyms will be employed to minimise the risk of deductive disclosure of participant identification.

Supporting Documents

Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application

Typ	Document	File	Docume	Version	Versio	Siz
Defau	SLLC Letter of Support. A	SLLC Letter of Support. A		02/11/20	1	164.
Defau	Risk Assessment - Ethics	Risk Assessment - Ethics		02/11/20	1	195.
Defau	References for Ethics	References for Ethics		04/11/20	1	13.
Defau	Participant Recruitment	Participant Recruitment Letter TtR		10/11/20	1	89.
Defau	Updated Project Information Sheet	Updated Project Information Sheet		28/11/20	2	36.
Defau	Demographic Data	Demographic Data Phase		28/11/20	1	32.

Signatures

Principal Investigator

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signed: This form was signed by RESCHHL Laura Calder (B00348835@studentmail.uws.ac.uk) on 28/11/2022 4:16 PM

Supervisor/Director of Studies

I support the above application and I agree to supervise the work.

Signed: This form was signed by Dr Angela Beggan (angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk) on 29/11/2022 9:36 PM

Appendix A: Phase One Risk Assessment

Department/Unit Name: School of Health and Life Sciences	Department Risk Assessment No:
Assessed by: Laura Calder MPhil/PhD Student	Date of assessment: 06/10/2022
Authorised by: Dr Angela Beggan	Date of reassessment:
Description of work activity or process <i>including any equipment/methods/procedures put in place to control risk.</i>	

What are the individual hazards?	Who might be harmed and how?	What are you already doing?	Do you need to do anything else to manage this risk?	Risk Level? (see method)	Action by whom?	Action when?	Done
Confidentiality and data protection	Research participants: being identifiable	Data Management Plan written	Follow Data Management Plan and UWS policies: https://bit.ly/3bDP0Uv IT Information Security Procedure May 2022 (uws.ac.uk) IT Password Management Procedure May 2022 (uws.ac.uk) Protocol for the use of Cloud Storage - August 2021 (uws.ac.uk) Data Protection UWS University of the West of Scotland	Low	MPhil/PhD student	Ongoing	
COVID-19	Participants, MPhil/PhD student by catching virus	Vaccinations, good handwashing technique, physical distancing, Personal Protective Equipment	Follow current Scottish Government guidelines for COVID-19: https://www.gov.scot/collections/coronavirus-covid-19-guidance	Low	MPhil/PhD Student	Ongoing	

		(optional), and a ventilated environment.					
Use of video-audio data	Participants may not wish to be recorded	Give participants choice of audio, and/or video recording, and/or opportunity to decline audio-visual data gathering methods.	<p>The use of digital equipment will be detailed in participation information sheets and consent forms.</p> <p>MPhil/PhD student will position video recorder and/or audio recorder to focus on the participant.</p> <p>Participant will be blurred if requested from video recordings.</p>	Low	MPhil/PhD Student	Ongoing	
Safety of others	MPhil/PhD student may observe concerns for participants physical and mental health and wellbeing	Discussion with supervisory group	<p>MPhil/PhD Student will gain ongoing consent.</p> <p>MPhil/PhD will create a friendly and welcoming environment and persona.</p> <p>MPhil/PhD Student will offer breaks to participant and refreshments.</p> <p>MPhil/PhD Student will show extra sensitivity due to COVID-19.</p>	Low	MPhil/PhD Student	Ongoing	

			<p>MPhil/PhD Student will observe participant for signs of distress. If distress or concerned about wellbeing, MPhil/PhD Student will offer to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stop recording • stop taking notes • offer break • pause interview • cease interview • observe values and wishes • treat participant with respect <p>MPhil/PhD Student will report any concerns to Lead Supervisor.</p>				
Mental wellbeing of MPhil/PhD Student	MPhil/PhD student may encounter emotionally challenging research	Discussion with supervisory group. MPhil/PhD Student member of Emotionally	<p>MPhil/PhD Student will report any concerns to lead supervisor.</p> <p>MPhil/PhD Student will access UWS support services if necessary.</p>	Low	MPhil/PhD Student	Ongoing	

		Demanding Research Network Scotland for PGR students for support.					
Safety of MPhil/PhD Student – Lone working	MPhil/PhD Student may face personal danger during interview	Discussion with supervisory group MPhil/PhD student will access Lone Worker Alarm	MPhil/PhD Student will advise supervisor and family member of locale of interview, expected duration of interview and time of interview. MPhil/PhD student will carry a Lone Worker Alarm. MPhil/PhD Student will carry mobile phone on silent on her personage. MPhil/PhD Student will observe exit routes prior to commencing interviewing. MPhil/PhD Student will adhere to UWS fieldwork and lone working policy: Fieldwork Procedure May 2022 (uws.ac.uk) ; Lone Working Procedure March 2022 (uws.ac.uk) MPhil/PhD Student will report any concerns to lead supervisor.	Low	MPhil/PhD Student	Ongoing	

Reputation	UWS and participant may face harm from inappropriate sharing of research material	Discussion with supervisory group	<p>MPhil/PhD Student will maintain participant confidentiality.</p> <p>MPhil/PhD Student will adhere to and maintain UWS confidentiality and data protection guidelines: Data Protection UWS University of the West of Scotland</p> <p>All data will be pseudo-anonymised.</p> <p>Concerns will be discussed with lead supervisor in a timely manner.</p>	Low	MPhil/PhD Student	Ongoing	
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COVID-19 remains as a threat to society and risks are ongoing. There is a potential risk that the MPhil/PhD Student may catch and/or spread the virus. The MPhil/PhD student will remain vigilant and will keep up to date with current government guidance on catching and spreading COVID-19. The MPhil/PhD Student has presently received all available vaccinations and will continue to receive vaccinations in compliance with public health guidance. The MPhil/PhD has previously had COVID-19 therefore may potentially have some immunity against the virus.

For further information and to view example risk assessments go to <http://www.hse.gov.uk/risk/casestudies/>

Risk Assessment Method

In order to assess a risk associated to a hazard, two factors need to be considered:-

The possible severity of the outcome

Realistically, what is the worst likely outcome? This method defines three categories of severity:-

- **Slightly harmful**
- **Harmful**
- **Extremely harmful**

The likelihood of the outcome to occur

How likely is it that the severe outcome will occur? Three categories are defined:-

- **Highly unlikely**
- **Unlikely**

- **Likely**

Once those two factors are assessed, the matrix below can be used to determine the level of risk. This information can then be used to prioritise any control measures necessary to eliminate or reduce the risk to an acceptable level.

	Slightly Harmful	Harmful	Extremely Harmful
Likely	MEDIUM RISK	HIGH RISK	HIGH RISK
Unlikely	LOW RISK	MEDIUM RISK	HIGH RISK
Highly Unlikely	LOW RISK	LOW RISK	MEDIUM RISK

Appendix B: Phase One Participant Information Sheet (Pilot Study)

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Research Project: Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Section 1

Contact details:

Student Name: Laura Calder Email: laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Supervisor Name: Dr Angela Beggan Email: angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk phone: 01698283100, ext. 8475

Section 2

Introduction

My name is Laura Calder, and I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am currently undertaking this research as part of my doctoral thesis, and I would like to invite you to take part. This research study explores women's transition to retirement. Before you decide, please take time to read this document so you can understand what this research will involve.

Section 3

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of the transition to retirement. Further research is needed to understand what wellbeing in retirement should look like for women and how it can be achieved. The research looks to collaborate with older women to co-create desirable and sustainable ways of achieving wellbeing in retirement. Your stories will be used to co-create lifestyle interventions to support meaningful, healthy, and active ageing.

Section 4

Why have you been invited?

You have been invited to take part in the study because you are either approaching the transition to retirement or are within five years of retirement and are associated with [REDACTED]

Section 5

Do I have to take part?

No, you do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to. The decision is entirely up to you whether you take part or not. If you agree to take part, you will be asked to complete a consent

form. This form will explain your rights to withdraw from the study at any time without having to give a reason. If you do withdraw from the study, you also have the right to ask that any earlier information collected about you be destroyed.

Section 6

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you participate, you will be invited to take part (depending on your preference) in an online interview via Microsoft Teams, or an in-person interview at the University of the West of Scotland, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH, at a date and time convenient to you. This interview will be a one-to-one chat where we will discuss your experience of the transition to retirement.

The interview/s will last approximately one hour. In person interviews will be audio recorded. Online interviews held via Microsoft Teams will be both audio and visually recorded. After your interview, the recordings will be transcribed and analysed.

You will also be asked if you would be interested in taking part further in this research to help develop activities for women in retirement.

Section 7

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks from taking part in the study.

Section 8

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no direct benefits from taking part in the study. However, your participation will enable a deeper understanding of women's transition to retirement and what can be learned to transform women's retirement experiences.

You will also be given the opportunity to take part further in this research by attending other meetings/workshops with fellow female retirees to help develop activities for women in retirement.

Section 9

What if something goes wrong?

There are no foreseeable risks to taking part in this study. You have the right to change your mind and withdraw at any time without giving a reason. If you do have any concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me. If you do not wish to speak with me, you can contact Dr Angela Beggan, angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk, my research supervisor.

Section 10

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All the information collected throughout this research will be kept strictly confidential following the Data Protection Act (2018). All information about you will be anonymised and stored in password

protected cloud storage to which only the research team has access. All data will be kept securely for 5 years, after which it will be destroyed.

Section 11

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of this study will be used in conjunction with other gathered data as part of my doctoral thesis. The results of this study will also be used for academic publishing.

Section 12

Who is organising the research?

This research project has been organised through the University of the West of Scotland for the purpose of fulfilling the criteria to meet the doctoral thesis.

Section 13

Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed and approved by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee.

Thank you for taking the time to read this participant information sheet. If you decide to take part in the study, you will also be given a signed copy of the consent form for your records.

1. Please indicate below if you have read this participant information sheet
I have read the participant information supplied

Appendix B Phase One Participant Information Sheet (Main Study)

PROJECT INFORMATION SHEET

Research Project: Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Contact details:

Student Name: Laura Calder Email: laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Supervisor Name: Dr Angela Beggan Email: angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk phone: 01698283100, ext. 8475

Section 1

Introduction

My name is Laura Calder, and I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am currently undertaking this research as part of my doctoral thesis, and I would like to invite you to take part. This research study explores women's transition to retirement. Before you decide, please take time to read this document so you can understand what this research will involve.

Section 2

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of the transition to retirement. Further research is needed to understand what wellbeing in retirement should look like for women and how it can be achieved. The research looks to collaborate with older women to co-create desirable and sustainable ways of achieving wellbeing in retirement. Your stories will be used to co-create lifestyle interventions to support meaningful, healthy, and active ageing.

Section 3

Why have you been invited?

You have been invited to take part in the study because you are either approaching the transition to retirement or are within five years of retirement and are associated with South Lanarkshire Leisure and Culture Limited.

Section 4

Do I have to take part?

No, you do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to. The decision is entirely up to you whether you take part or not. If you agree to take part, you will be asked to complete a consent form. This form will explain your rights to withdraw from the study at any time without having to give a reason. If you do withdraw from the study, you also have the right to ask that any earlier information collected about you be destroyed.

Section 5

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you participate, you will be invited to take part (depending on your preference) in an online interview via Microsoft Teams, or an in-person interview at the University of the West of Scotland, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH, at a date and time convenient to you. This interview will be a one-to-one chat where we will discuss your experience of the transition to retirement.

The interview/s will last approximately one hour. In person interviews will be audio recorded. Online interviews held via Microsoft Teams will be both audio and visually recorded. After your interview, the recordings will be transcribed and analysed.

You will also be asked if you would be interested in taking part further in this research to help develop activities for women in retirement.

Section 6

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks to taking part in the study.

Section 7

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no direct benefits from taking part in the study. However, your participation will enable a deeper understanding of women's transition to retirement and what can be learned to transform women's retirement experiences.

You will also be given the opportunity to take part further in this research by attending other meetings/workshops with fellow female retirees to help develop activities for women in retirement.

Section 8

What if something goes wrong?

There are no foreseeable risks to taking part in this study. You have the right to change your mind and withdraw at any time without giving a reason. If you do have any concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me. If you do not wish to speak with me, you can contact Dr Angela Beggan, angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk, my research supervisor.

Section 9

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All the information collected throughout this research will be kept strictly confidential following the Data Protection Act (2018). All information about you will be anonymised and stored in password protected cloud storage to which only the research team has access. All data will be kept securely for 5 years, after which it will be destroyed.

Section 10

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of this study will be used in conjunction with other gathered data as part of my doctoral thesis. The results of this study will also be used for academic publishing.

Section 11

Who is organising the research?

This research project has been organised through the University of the West of Scotland for the purpose of fulfilling the criteria to meet the doctoral thesis.

Section 12

Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed and approved by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee.

Thank you for taking the time to read this participant information sheet. If you decide to take part in the study, you will also be given a signed copy of the consent form for your records.

1. Please indicate below if you have read this participant information sheet

I have read the participant information supplied

Section 13

CONSENT

2. Please indicate if you would like to participate further in this study

Yes

No

3. Please indicate if you are willing to participate in an interview to discuss your transition to retirement

Yes

No

Section 14

INTERVIEW

Interviews will be held online via Microsoft Teams or in-person at the University of the West of Scotland, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0HL. Interviews will be held on a date and time convenient to you.

4. Please indicate if you wish to be interviewed online or in person

Online

In person

Section 15

In person Interviews Only

5. Please indicate if you consent to being audio recorded during your interview

I consent to being audio recorded during my interview

I DO NOT consent to being recorded

Section 16

Online Interviews via Microsoft Teams Only

6. Please indicate if you consent to being audio and visually recorded during your interview

I consent to being audio and visually recorded during my interview

I DO NOT consent to being recorded

Section 17

PERSONAL DATA

If you wish to participate further in this study, please complete the following questions:

7. Full name

Enter your answer

8. Phone number (optional)

The value must be a number

9. Email address

Enter your answer

10. Please indicate how you wish to be contacted

Phone

Email

Section 18

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

11. How old are you?

Enter your answer

12.What is your postcode?

Enter your answer

13.Please indicate your employment status

Part-time

Full-time

Retired

Bridging Employment

Disabled

Volunteer

Caregiver

Other

14.

Please indicate your household status

Married

Partnered

Single

Divorced

Separated

Other

Section 19

Thank you for taking your time to complete this questionnaire

Appendix C: Phase One Consent (Pilot Study)

CONSENT FORM

Research Study: Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Section 1

RESEARCHER CONTACT DETAILS

Student Name: Laura Calder Email: laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Supervisor Name: Dr Angela Beggan Email: angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk Phone: 01698283100 ext. 8475

1. Please indicate if you would like to participate further in this study

Yes

No

2. Please indicate if you are willing to participate in an interview to discuss your transition to retirement

Yes

No

Section 2

INTERVIEW

Interviews will be held online via Microsoft Teams or in-person at the University of the West of Scotland, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0HL. Interviews will be held on a date and time convenient to you.

3. Please indicate if you wish to be interviewed online or in person

Online

In person

Section 3

In person Interviews Only

4. Please indicate if you consent to being audio recorded during your interview

I consent to being audio recorded during my interview

I DO NOT consent to being recorded

Section 4

Online Interviews Only

5. Please indicate if you consent to being audio and visually recorded during your interview

I consent to being audio and visually recorded during my interview

I DO NOT consent to being recorded

Section 5

PERSONAL DATA

If you wish to participate further in this study, please complete the following questions:

6. Full name

Enter your answer

7. Phone Number (optional)

Enter your answer

8. Email address

Enter your answer

9. Please indicate how you would prefer to be contacted

Phone

Email

Appendix C: Consent Form Phase One Main Study

CONSENT FORM

Research Study: Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Section 1

RESEARCHER CONTACT DETAILS

Student Name: Laura Calder Email: laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Supervisor Name: Dr Angela Beggan Email: angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk Phone: 01698283100 ext. 8475

1. Please indicate if you would like to participate further in this study

Yes

No

2. Please indicate if you are willing to participate in an interview to discuss your transition to retirement

Yes

No

Section 2

INTERVIEW

Interviews will be held online via Microsoft Teams or in-person at the University of the West of Scotland, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0HL. Interviews will be held on a date and time convenient to you.

3. Please indicate if you wish to be interviewed online or in person

Online

In person

Section 3

In person Interviews Only

4. Please indicate if you consent to being audio recorded during your interview

I consent to being audio recorded during my interview

I DO NOT consent to being recorded

Section 4

Online Interviews Only

5. Please indicate if you consent to being audio and visually recorded during your interview

I consent to being audio and visually recorded during my interview

I DO NOT consent to being recorded

Section 5

PERSONAL DATA

If you wish to participate further in this study, please complete the following questions:

6. Full name

Enter your answer

7. Phone Number (optional)

Enter your answer

8. Email address

Enter your answer

9. Please indicate how you would prefer to be contacted

Phone

Email

Appendix D: Interview Prompts Phase One Interviews

INTERVIEW GUIDE

I am using narrative interviewing to collect my data from participants. As narrative interviews do not have questions, prompts will be given to address the themes of active ageing, health and lifestyle behaviour, relationship with physical activity, and successful/unsuccessful retirement. On interview, I will use some open-ended questions to help facilitate participants to talk about their experiences.

Examples of questions which may be asked to participants who are in retirement may include:

- Can you tell me about the way you retired?
- Please tell me about your experiences of life as a retiree.
- Has your health got any better/worse since retiring?
- How have your physical activity levels changed since becoming retired?
- Is there anything else you'd like to add about your experiences of retirement that we haven't explored?

Examples of questions that may be asked to participants in the transition to retirement may include:

- Can you tell me about your retirement?
- What do you imagine your retirement will be like?
- How do you think you will fill your time once retired?
- What ways (if any) will you take to improve/maintain your health?
- Is there anything else you'd like to add about your experiences of the transition to retirement that we haven't explored?

Follow up questions, such as "Could you tell me more about ..." or "Could you describe in more detail ...", may be used to get the participant to elaborate on their narrative, provide explanation, additional examples, clarifications and descriptions.

Appendix E: Recruitment Phase One

08 November 2022

Dear [REDACTED] Employee

Letter of Invitation

Research Participants Needed

My name is Laura Calder, and I am a doctoral research student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am conducting a research study on women's transition to retirement. The purpose of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of the transition to retirement and improve it. Your input into this research is important and I would like to hear about your knowledge and experiences of retiring.

If you are interested in participating or would like some more information, please click the link <https://forms.office.com/r/4r0rgyMWkE> and reply within 2 weeks of this email. All information is kept confidential. This study has been reviewed by the Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland.

Yours faithfully

Laura

Laura Calder

PhD Researcher

MPH., BSc (hons), BSc, Grad Dip., Grad Dip.

School of Health and Life Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park

South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH

**HIGHER EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTION OF THE YEAR**

Appendix F: Ethics Application Two – Workshops

Filter Questions

- I confirm I have read the UWS and my School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship.
(please tick to continue)

Pre-screening Questions

Does your work involve any of the following. (please tick all that apply)

- Human Participants
 Personal Data
 Animals
 Risk to the Investigator
- None of the above

Based on your answers to the above questions you should complete the remainder of this form and submit it to your school ethics committee for approval **PRIOR** to commencing any work on your project. Please click Next to proceed.

Applicant Details

Position of Principal Investigator

Postgraduate

Principal Investigator

Title

First Name

Surname

RESCHHL

Laura

Calder

Email

B00348835@studentmail.uws.ac.uk

School

Health and Life Sciences

Are there any co-applicants

Yes

No

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Title

First Name

Surname

Dr

Angela

Beggan

School

School of Health and Life Sciences

Email

Angela.Beggan@uws.ac.uk

Collaborators

Are there any other collaborators?

Yes

No

Project Information

Title of Study

Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Primary purpose of the study

Original Research

Where will the proposed research take place?

The research will take place in person at the University of the West of Scotland, Lanarkshire Campus, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH.

How will the costs of the study be met?

The costs of the study have been incorporated into the agreed UWS studentship.

Previous Approvals

Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee?

- Yes
 No

Purpose, justification, design and methodology

Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)

The transition to retirement (TtR) is a significant event in women's lives (Byles et al, 2013), which has a profound effect on health and well-being (Zantinge et al. 2013). The TtR presents a window of opportunity for primary prevention interventions to improve health outcomes and promote healthier behaviours in women, who, are acknowledged to be more receptive to health messages during life transitions (Smeaton et al, 2017, Lara et al. 2014).

At present, there is a limited body of knowledge on the lived experiences of women's TtR. Gathering stories from women within five years of retirement will provide a unique opportunity to explore the complexity of women's ageing experiences. Using narrative methods, their storied accounts will be used to understand the underlying mechanisms of successful adjustment to retirement (Hansson et al. 2018).

This project aims to make an original contribution to the gap in knowledge in our understanding of women's retirement expectations, the factors that impact them, and the intersecting causal relationships. Using their voices to depict their experiences of ageing will provide insight and understanding of what women do, want, and need, within this transitional life phase to promote positive and active ageing.

RESEARCH DESIGN

As a multi-stage project, the research design follows an iterative process consisting of three key phases: inspiration, ideation, and implementation (Roberts, Fisher, Trowbridge and Bent, 2016). Phase one ethical approval was sought and granted in December 2022 (Project ID 19467 - see appendix). This ethics application covers phase two. Phase two consists of three workshops which aim to co-design social enterprise ideas that improve health promotion practices and women in the TtR to create real impact from encompassing human-centred design. This application seeks ethical approval to conduct three workshops with willing participants to discuss women's experiences of the TtR and co-create ideas for social enterprise health promotion prototypes which improve health and well-being for women in the TtR and retirement. A subsequent phase will be developed from phase two to implement prototype designs and will be submitted for ethical approval at a later date.

Workshop one (inspiration) will focus on understanding the needs and challenges of women in the TtR through the stories collected in phase one of the study. Workshops two and three (ideation) will make sense of what has been heard in the inspiration workshop which will be used to generate ideas and design solutions for the problems identified, making women's lives better in retirement.

PARTICIPANTS AND SAMPLING

To gain an insightful and in-depth understanding, purposive sampling strategies with maximum variation and snowballing (Creswell, 1998) were used in the design of this research. In phase one, the sample of women was sought from employees of South Lanarkshire Leisure and Culture (SLC) who were contacted directly through SLC's human resources department by email, inviting women within five years of retirement to participate in the research project concerning their experiences with the TtR. The initial contacts gained using this method were added to via snowball sampling, procured through existing participants. After the initial interviews were conducted in phase one of the project, volunteers were procured for phase two of this research study. Further participants for phase two of the research will be purposively selected from the personal networks of the researcher and participants. Purposive sampling will foster cross-disciplinary working and seek desirable characteristics of individuals within the co-design process.

DATA COLLECTION

Data will be obtained through three co-production workshops with participants. Workshops will be audio and visually recorded and field notes will be taken. Consent will be obtained for the data collection methods by each participant prior to the commencement of each workshop. Data gained from the workshops will be recorded using the NVivo software package to organize responses and aid thematic analysis. All data will be stored in accordance with data protection, ensuring confidentiality, and anonymity, and will have regard for duty of care. All personal data acquired through the process of this study will be anonymized, data will be encrypted, and password protected, and paper copies will be locked within a filing cabinet. Pseudonyms will be employed to minimize the risk of deductive disclosure of participant identification. Participants will also be given the option to be named within the research to acknowledge their contribution.

The workshops with participants will be held at the University of the West of Scotland, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH. Three workshops are planned, and the number of participants engaged in this process will range between eight and twenty. The first workshop will last for three hours and will incorporate a fifteen-minute break. The second workshop will last for six hours and will incorporate two fifteen-minute breaks and a thirty-minute lunch break. The third workshop will last for three hours and will also include a fifteen-minute break. Refreshments and lunch will be provided for the participants. Dietary advice and allergens will be sought from each of the participants. Participants may be contacted between workshops

DATA ANALYSIS

- The workshops will be audio-recorded to ensure accurate recall of discussions. Field notes from observations and informal consultations will be collected and combined
-
-
-

with the outcomes from the analysis of the interviews (from phase one) and coproduction workshop group data to identify similarities and differences across stakeholder perspectives emerging from the consultation process. These outcomes will be taken to feed the co-production of intervention.

Data will be analysed using Frank's (2011) dialogical narrative analysis (DNA). DNA understands stories as artful representations of lives; stories reshape the past and imaginatively project the future (Frank, 2011). DNA's interest lies in hearing how multiple voices find expression within any single voice (Frank, 2011, p. 35). DNA does not have a step-by-step procedure but prefers a "movement of thought" through dialogical questioning (Frank, 2011, 2012), which will allow me to examine participants' thoughts, beliefs, attitudes, and relationships and identify re-occurring themes.

How has the scientific quality of the proposed research project been assessed?

- Independent external review
- Review within a company
- Review within a multi-centre research group
- Review within the principal investigator's institution
- Review within the research team
- Review by supervisor/director of studies
- Other

Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

Purposeful samples of women pre, peri, and post-retirement was sought for the first phase of participation in this research (see appendix). Soft boundaries were placed on participants' age if they are within a five-year period of retirement. Where possible, the research participants showed a diversity of human culture and conditions, taking full account of ethnicity, disability, sexual orientation, and socio-economic circumstances in the design, undertaking, and reporting. By ensuring a broad age range, I allowed for maximum recruitment with participant diversity. I excluded males and non-binary individuals as sought a narrative from women and those who identify as women only to reflect on the female element of the study. Consideration was given to any participants that fall under the predetermined groups as disclosed in UWS' School of Health and Life Sciences Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship, where any additional requirement/needs will be met where duly possible.

In this, the second phase of the research project, the intended sample size is between eight and twenty and will incorporate people from cross-disciplinary fields fostering the essence of human-centred design to encapsulate wider modes of thinking (Kelley et al. 2015). This sample size will allow the researcher to work with others to co-produce interventions and prototypes. Adopting a co-productive approach will allow the focus to be placed on the needs of women of retirement age. The sample size is appropriate for the qualitative element of the study and is conducive to co-production research (Hennink and Keiser, 2021).

In order to build a cross-disciplinary team, a purposeful sampling strategy will be utilized to encapsulate the different experiences, skills, and characteristics. In the essence of co-production, the participants will purposefully select and invite individuals to workshops two and three who will assist in the ideation and implementation phases of the project.

Analysis and Presentation

Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

This research will encompass human-centered design using co-production and is guided by the human-centered design toolkit as idealized by IDEO.org (2011). Co-production will incorporate the elements of co-designing and planning of services; co-decision-making in the allocation of resources; co-delivery of services and the co-evaluation of services. Using the principles of co-production, as a researcher, I will be an equal partner and co-creator with the participants that have been recruited for this research project. Together we aim to produce physical activity-related prototypes to promote women's health and well-being in retirement. Collectively, in workshops, we will generate and develop ideas to co-produce prototype interventions for preventative purposes.

The workshops will follow the iterative phases of inspiration, ideation, and implementation (Roberts, Fisher, Trowbridge and Bent, 2016). Using human-centered design (HCD) methods as outlined by Kelley et al. (2015), the workshops will follow their outlined design kit. Prototyping, feedback, and iteration during the workshops will provide indicators of the efficacy of interventions, enabling monitoring and evaluation.

Data will be analysed using Frank's (2011) dialogical narrative analysis (DNA). DNA understands stories as artful representations of lives; stories reshape the past and imaginatively project the future (Frank, 2011). DNA's interest lies in hearing how multiple voices find expression within any single voice (Frank, 2011, p. 35). DNA does not have a step-by-step procedure but prefers a "movement of thought" through dialogical questioning (Frank, 2011, 2012), which will allow me to examine participants' thoughts, beliefs, attitudes, and relationships and identify re-occurring themes.

The data will be presented to fulfil the requirements of a doctorate and academic publication. Data will be disseminated through academic publications.

Interviews/Questionnaires

Does the proposed research involve the use of individual/group interviews or questionnaires?

- Yes
- No

Impact on Participants

Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:

A purposive sampling strategy will be used to obtain participants for this study. Participants have been recruited from phase one of the research study (see appendix). Purposeful samples of women pre, peri, and post-retirement intend to be sought for the first phase of participation in this research. Soft boundaries were placed on participants' age if they are within a five-year period of retirement. Where possible, the research participants showed a diversity of human culture and conditions, taking full account of ethnicity, disability, sexual orientation, and socio-economic circumstances in the design, undertaking, and reporting. By ensuring a broad age range, I allowed for maximum recruitment with participant diversity. I excluded males and non-binary individuals as sought narrative from women and those who identify as women only to reflect on the female element of the study. Consideration was and will continue to be given to any participants that fall under the predetermined groups as disclosed in UWS' School of Health and Life Sciences Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship, where any additional requirement/needs will be met where duly possible.

From the initial interview, all participants have chosen to continue their participation in the study and attend the workshops (dependent on their availability). The existing sample size will be added to through purposeful selection from the personal networks of the researcher and participants. This method will enable a cross-disciplinary team to be formed, where participants will be sought for their individual characteristics to support the creative human-centred design process (Kelley et al. 2015).

Will participants be from any of the following groups? (Please tick all that apply)

- Children under 16
- Adults with learning disabilities
- Adults with a terminal illness
- Adults in emergency situations
- Adults with mental illness (particularly if detained under the mental health act)
- Adults with dementia
- Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves
- Those who could be considered to have a particularly dependent relationship with the investigator
- Other
- None of the above

Are there any special pressures which would make it difficult for potential participants to refuse to take part in your study? (e.g., relationship to the investigator?)

I had no personal connection with any of the participants prior to the commencement of the research study. All individuals participating in this stage of the project do so voluntarily and have the right to withdraw their participation at any point during the study.

Will study participants be paid to take part?

- Yes
- No

What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

Workshop one (inspiration phase) will last for three hours and will incorporate a fifteen-minute break. Workshop two (action phase) will last for six hours and will incorporate two fifteen-minute breaks and a thirty-minute lunch break. Workshop three (evaluation phase) will run for three hours and will also incorporate a fifteen-minute break. Refreshments will be provided at all workshops. Lunch will be provided at workshop two. Not every individual will be able to attend all workshops. The amount of time any participant will give will be twelve hours over a three-month period. Participants will receive some additional feedback between workshops. The commitment will be kept to an

Will informed consent be obtained from study participants?

Yes

No

Please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

Participants for phase two will receive a participant information sheet detailing data protection and consent. This will remain an ongoing process and will be obtained prior to each workshop through the completion of a consent form which will be emailed to participants and made available to them in a PDF and in paper copy upon

Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)

		Docume			
Tvp	Document	File	Version	Date	Version Size
Default	PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET FOR PHASE 2	PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET FOR PHASE 2 (1.doc)	1	05/05/20	49.5K

Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)

		Docume			
Tvp	Document	File	Version	Date	Version Size
Default	Healthy Ageing Workshop Consent	Healthy Ageing Workshop Consent	1	17/03/20	65.5K

Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)?

Yes

No

Does the proposed research involve any physically invasive procedures?

Yes

No

Other ethical considerations

Does the proposed research involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the identity of the investigator?

- Yes
- No

Will research participants be debriefed after their participation?

- Yes
- No

Are there any other Ethical Considerations you wish to bring to the attention of the committee?

- Yes
- No

Please provide details

To show appreciation for participants' contribution, upon completion of each three-hour workshop, participants will receive a £10 gift voucher as a participation gift. A £20 gift voucher will be given to participants on completion of the six-hour workshop as a participation gift. Funds for this 'thank you' token will be absorbed within the studentship. This information is disclosed within the participation information sheet which will be given to participants in a PDF form or as a paper copy if required.

Personal Data

What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?

Participants identifying details will be anonymised for analysis and in the final write-up to protect identities. Participants who choose not to be anonymised will be acknowledged within the research and any subsequent publishing. Any identifying aspects of organisations or locations will be removed or adjusted to ensure confidentiality and prevent deductive disclosure.

All data files will be password protected and available only to members of the research team. The raw data (e.g., recordings) will be stored on UWS password-protected cloud storage. Once the thesis is completed, all data will be destroyed in line with university guidelines within five years of doctorate completion. The consent forms will be stored in UWS Vault by the research supervisor.

Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

Raw data collected from the research participants will be accessible only to myself and my research team. All data will be stored in accordance with data protection, ensuring confidentiality, and anonymity, and will have regard for duty of care. All personal data acquired through the process of this study will be anonymised, data will be password protected, and paper copies will be locked within a filing cabinet. Pseudonyms will be employed to minimize the risk of deductive disclosure of participant identification.

Supporting Documents

Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application

Type	Document	File	Version	Date	Size
Default	Workshop Agenda Phase	Workshop Agenda Phase	1	27/04/20	19. K
Default	Transforming the Transition to Retirement One	Transforming the Transition to Retirement One.p	1	27/04/20	355. K
Default	References for Ethics	References for Ethics	1	28/04/20	21. K
Default	Risk assessment for workshops	Risk assessment for workshops phase 2	1	28/04/20	44. K
Default	Applicati	Application.	1	05/05/20	355. K

Signatures

Principal Investigator

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signed: This form was signed by RESCHHL Laura Calder (B00348835@studentmail.uws.ac.uk) on 05/05/2023 6:37 PM

Supervisor/Director of Studies

I support the above application and I agree to supervise the work.

Signed: This form was signed by Dr Angela Beggan (angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk) on 09/05/2023 7:00 AM

Appendix F: Risk Assessment for Workshops

Department/Unit Name: School of Health and Life Sciences	Department Risk Assessment No:
Assessed by: Laura Calder PhD Student	Date of assessment: 28/04/2023
Authorised by: Dr Angela Beggan	Date of reassessment:
Description of work activity or process <i>including any equipment/methods/procedures put in place to control risk.</i>	

What are the individual hazards?	Who might be harmed and how?	What are you already doing?	Do you need to do anything else to manage this risk?	Risk Level? (see method)	Action by whom?	Action when?	by	Done
----------------------------------	------------------------------	-----------------------------	--	--------------------------	-----------------	--------------	----	------

Confidentiality and data protection	Research participants: being identifiable	Data Management Plan written	<p>Follow Data Management Plan and UWS policies: https://bit.ly/3bDP0Uv</p> <p>IT Information Security Procedure May 2022 (uws.ac.uk)</p> <p>IT Password Management Procedure May 2022 (uws.ac.uk)</p> <p>Protocol for the use of Cloud Storage - August 2021 (uws.ac.uk)</p> <p>Data Protection UWS University of the West of Scotland</p>	Low	PhD student	Ongoing	
COVID-19	Participants, PhD student by catching virus	Vaccinations, good handwashing technique, physical distancing, Personal Protective Equipment (optional), and a ventilated environment.	<p>Follow current Scottish Government guidelines for COVID-19: https://www.gov.scot/collections/coronavirus-covid-19-guidance</p>	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	

Use of audio data	Participants may not wish to be recorded	Give participants choice of audio, and/or video recording, and/or opportunity to decline audio data gathering methods.	The use of digital equipment will be detailed in participation information sheets and consent forms.	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	
Safety of others	PhD student may observe concerns for participants physical and mental health and wellbeing	Discussion with supervisory group	<p>PhD Student will gain ongoing consent.</p> <p>PhD will create a friendly and welcoming environment and persona.</p> <p>PhD Student will offer breaks to participants and refreshments.</p> <p>PhD Student will show extra sensitivity due to COVID-19.</p> <p>PhD Student will observe participants for signs of distress. If distress or concerned about wellbeing, PhD Student will offer to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stop recording • stop taking notes 	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • offer break • pause workshop • cease workshop • observe values and wishes • treat participants with respect <p>PhD Student will report any concerns to Lead Supervisor.</p>				
Food safety	Research participants from risk of allergens and/or dietary requirements.	<p>Catering will be provided by UWS.</p> <p>Allergen and dietary requirements will be sought from each participant.</p>	<p>PhD student will request in writing any allergen or dietary requirements for each participant.</p> <p>Lunch and refreshments will be provided by UWS catering services.</p> <p>PhD student will liaise with UWS Catering Services, advising of any additional requirements and allergen advisal.</p>	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	
Mental wellbeing of PhD Student	PhD student may encounter emotionally	Discussion with supervisory group. PhD Student	PhD Student will report any concerns to lead supervisor.	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	

	challenging research.	member of Emotionally Demanding Research Network Scotland for PGR students for support.	PhD Student will access UWS support services if necessary.				
Reputation	UWS and participant may face harm from inappropriate sharing of research material	Discussion with supervisory group	<p>PhD Student will maintain participant confidentiality.</p> <p>PhD Student will adhere to and maintain UWS confidentiality and data protection guidelines: Data Protection UWS University of the West of Scotland</p> <p>All data will be pseudo-anonymised.</p> <p>Concerns will be discussed with lead supervisor in a timely manner.</p>	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	

COVID-19 remains as a threat to society and risks are ongoing. There is a potential risk that the PhD Student may catch and/or spread the virus. The PhD student will remain vigilant and will keep up to date with current government guidance on catching and spreading COVID-19. The PhD Student has presently received all available vaccinations and will continue to receive vaccinations in compliance with public health guidance. The PhD has previously had COVID-19 therefore may potentially have some immunity against the virus.

For further information and to view example risk assessments go to <http://www.hse.gov.uk/risk/casestudies/>

Risk Assessment Method

In order to assess a risk associated to a hazard, two factors need to be considered:-

The possible severity of the outcome

Realistically, what is the worst likely outcome? This method defines three categories of severity:-

- **Slightly harmful**
- **Harmful**
- **Extremely harmful**

The likelihood of the outcome to occur

How likely is it that the severe outcome will occur? Three categories are defined:-

- **Highly unlikely**
- **Unlikely**
- **Likely**

Once those two factors are assessed, the matrix below can be used to determine the level of risk. This information can then be used to prioritise any control measures necessary to eliminate or reduce the risk to an acceptable level.

	Slightly Harmful	Harmful	Extremely Harmful
Likely	MEDIUM RISK	HIGH RISK	HIGH RISK
Unlikely	LOW RISK	MEDIUM RISK	HIGH RISK
Highly Unlikely	LOW RISK	LOW RISK	MEDIUM RISK

Appendix G: Workshops Participant Information Sheets

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET 2

Introduction

My name is Laura Calder, and I am a PhD student at University of The West of Scotland. I am currently undertaking this research as part of my doctoral thesis, and I would like to thank you for your participation in this study so far. This research study explores women's transition to retirement. Before you decide please take some time to read this document so you can understand what the research will involve.

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of the transition to retirement. More research is needed to understand what wellbeing in retirement should look like for women and how that can be achieved. The research looks to work with older women to co-create desirable and sustainable ways of achieving wellbeing in retirement. Your stories will be used to co-create lifestyle interventions to support meaningful, healthy, and active ageing.

Why have you been invited?

You have been invited to participate in the next phase of the study as you showed interest in contributing further.

Do I have to take part?

No, you do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to. The decision is entirely up to you whether you participate or not. If you do agree to participate, you will be asked to complete a consent form. This form will explain your rights to withdraw from the study at any time without having to give a reason. If you do withdraw from the study, you also have the right to ask that any previous information collected about you be destroyed.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you participate, you will be invited to take part in three Healthy Ageing Workshops along with other individuals who have also expressed an interest in participating in this research to help develop activities for women in retirement. Participation in each of the workshops is optional, and you can attend as many as you wish. Each workshop will take place at the University of the West of Scotland, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH, at a time convenient to the consensus of the group. We will discuss how you envisage what women's transition to retirement could ideally look like and what could be done to make this happen. We will also discuss women's physical activity in retirement and what can be done to promote active ageing.

Workshop one will last for three hours and will incorporate a refreshment break. Workshop two will last for six hours and will incorporate two fifteen-minute refreshment breaks and a thirty-minute lunch break. Workshop three will last for three hours and will also incorporate a refreshment break. Refreshments will be provided at each of the meetings and lunch will be provided at Workshop two. Dietary and allergen information and requests will be sought from you. Our meetings will be audio recorded, and notes will be taken so that what is said can be transcribed and analysed at a later date.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks to taking part in the study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

In order to show appreciation for your contribution, upon completion of each three-hour workshop, you will receive a £10 voucher. A £20 voucher will be given to you on completion of the six-hour workshop. Your participation in this study will enable a deeper understanding of women's transition to retirement and what can be learned to transform women's retirement experiences.

What if something goes wrong?

There are no foreseeable risks to participating in this study, and you have the right to change your mind and withdraw at any time without giving a reason. If you do have any concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me. If you do not wish to speak with me, you can contact Dr Angela Beggan, angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk, my research supervisor.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All the information collected throughout this research will be kept strictly confidential in accordance with the Data Protection Act (2018). All information about you will be anonymised and stored in password protected cloud storage to which only the research team has access. All data will be kept securely for 5 years, after which it will be destroyed.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of this study will be used in conjunction with other gathered data as part of my doctoral thesis to form intervention prototype(s) to transform women's transition to retirement experience.

Who is organising the research?

This research project has been organised through the University of the West of Scotland for the purpose of fulfilling the criteria to meet the doctoral thesis.

Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed and approved by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee.

Thank you for taking the time to read this participant information sheet, which you may keep. If you decide to take part in the study, you will also be given a signed copy of the consent form for your records.

Contact details

Student Name, laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Dr Angela Beggan, angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk

phone: 01698283100, ext. 8475

Appendix H: Workshop Consent Sheets

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CONSENT FORM

Healthy ageing workshop

Transforming the Transition to Retirement

RESEARCHER CONTACT DETAILS

Student Name: Laura Calder Email: laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Supervisor Name: Dr Angela Beggan Email: angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk

Phone: 01698283100 ext. 8475

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the Healthy Ageing Co-Production Workshops at any time, without giving a reason, and that this will not affect my legal rights.

- Agree
- Disagree

I confirm that I have read and understand the information provided for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

- Agree
- Disagree

I understand that any personal information collected during the study will be anonymised and remain confidential unless otherwise agreed by myself.

- Agree
- Disagree

I understand that workshops will be audio recorded.

- Agree
- Disagree

I understand that parts of my data may be used verbatim in future publications or presentations and that such quotes will be anonymized.

- Agree
- Disagree

I agree to take part in the above-named study and am happy for the data collection to proceed.

- Agree
- Disagree

7.Name of Participant

8.Date

Appendix I: Planning Meeting Presentation

Planning Meeting

Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Laura Calder
PhD Researcher

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

What is the purpose of the study?

To gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of the transition to retirement.

To understand what wellbeing in retirement should look like for women and how that can be achieved.

Women's stories will be used to co-create lifestyle interventions to support meaningful, healthy, and active ageing.

Healthy Ageing Workshops

Workshop One	Workshop Two	Workshop Three
Inspiration	Ideation	Ideation
Duration – 3 hours Break with refreshments	Duration – 6 hours All day event Refreshments and lunch provided	Duration – 3 hours Break with refreshments
Date: Time:	Date: Time: 10 am – 4 pm	Date: Time:

Who should be involved?

Appendix I: Proposed Workshop Agenda

Workshop 1: Inspiration (3 hours duration)

Introduction (15 minutes)
Activity (60 minutes)
Break (15 minutes)
Activity (85 minutes)
Sum up, thanks, close (5 minutes)

Workshop 2: Ideation (6 hours duration)

Introduction (15 minutes)
Activity (60 minutes)
Break (15 minutes)
Activity (75 minutes)
Lunch (30 minutes) (provided)
Activity (75 minutes)
Break (15 minutes)
Activity (65 minutes)
Sum up, thanks, close (10 minutes)

Workshop 3: Ideation (3 hours duration)

Introduction (15 minutes)
Activity (60 minutes)
Break (15 minutes)
Activity (85 minutes)
Sum up, thanks, close (5 minutes)

Appendix I: Proposed Recruitment Flyer

TRANSFORMING THE TRANSITION TO RETIREMENT

RESEARCH PROJECT

Are you a woman who has recently retired or is currently transitioning to retirement? Or do you have experience of supporting women who are recently retired or going through the transition to retirement?

If so, I need to hear from you!

My name is Laura, and I am part of a research project at the University of the West of Scotland that is exploring how to improve women's retirement experiences. We are working with women for women, and we need YOUR insights to understand what's important.

I will be holding a workshop on [insert date] at UWS and am looking for participants.

At this session, you will meet other women, volunteers, and service providers and together we will have some refreshments while we brainstorm ways to improve women's retirement and healthy ageing.

You can find out more about the project by clicking this link:

<https://forms.office.com/e/qsYUN6YpnE>

If you wish to reserve a space at this workshop or if you have further questions, contact me on:

laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Lead Supervisor: Dr Angela Beggan angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk

Appendix I: Proposed DNA for Workshops 1-3

Resource questions	Circulation questions	Affiliation questions	Identity questions
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What resources shape how the story is being told? 2. What resources do women use to shape their experiences of the TtR? 3. What might prevent alternative resources being used? 4. What resources do the group view would improve women's TtR experience? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Who is the story told to? 2. Who is the story intended for? 3. Who would understand the story and who wouldn't? 4. Who would challenge the story being told? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the storytellers trying to do? 2. Do the storytellers recognise elements of other women shared experiences within their own story? 3. What shared stories connect the women's experiences of the TtR? 4. Do the storytellers affiliate themselves to a specific typology? * 5. What do the women collectively value in order to have a successful and fulfilling retirement? <p><i>*Should this be revisited individually?</i></p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do the stories the women give provide a sense of who they are as a retiree and who they were as an employee? 2. What changes to their identity has each of the women experienced since leaving paid employment? 3. What do the storytellers envisage would support women to allow them to flourish in retirement? 4. How do stories of other people's experiences of the TtR's influence their retirement? 5. What shape's a women's TtR experience? 6. How do women's identities alter in the TtR? 7. What do the women value to have a successful and fulfilling retirement?

Appendix J: Workshop One Presentation

Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Expert Panel Workshop

Laura Calder
PhD Researcher
Lead Supervisor: Dr Angela Beggan

Workshop Agenda

- Introductions
- Women's transition to retirement
- Purpose of the study
- Workshop objectives
- Brainstorming
- Activities 1, 2 and 3
- Workshop planning
- Summary and close

Womens' Retirement Trajectories

Research highlights that gender influences post-retirement trajectories, as women's retirement experiences are qualitatively distinct from men's.

Gender inequalities women experience in later life are often the result from the disadvantages accumulated over the span of life.

Women are more likely to have a fragmented employment history.

What Affects Womens Retirement?

Pregnancy /
childcare

Care giving

Finances

Gender pay gap

Menial jobs

Opportunities

Education

Divorce/separation

What is the purpose of the study?

To gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of the transition to retirement.

To understand what wellbeing in retirement should look like for women and how that can be achieved.

Women's stories will be used to co-create lifestyle interventions to support meaningful, healthy, and active ageing.

Womens' Transition to Retirement

What do women value in the transition to retirement?

What support do women in the transition to retirement want and need?

What influences women's transition to retirement?

What is needed for women to make lifestyle changes?

Objections of Workshop

1. Be inspired by the transition to retirement
2. Share your expertise

Brainstorming Rules

- Defer judgement
- Encourage wild ideas
- Build on ideas by others
- Stay focused on the topic
- One conversation at a time
- Be visual
- Go for quality

IDEO.org (2015 p.95)

Frame Your Design Challenge

WHAT IS THE PROBLEM YOU'RE TRYING TO SOLVE?

1. Take a stab at framing this challenge as a question
2. Now state the key outcome you're trying to achieve
3. Write down important aspects of the context or constraints that you need to consider
4. What are some possible solutions to your design question?
5. Does your original design question need a tweak? Try it again.

DESIGN KIT 2023

Activity One

Why do you think women experience difficulties in the transition to retirement?

Activity Two

- Cathy
- Joyce
- Katrina
- Pauline

Activity Three

What is your design question?

Thank you

Contact Details:

Laura Calder

laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Supervisory Team:

Lead supervisor: Dr Angela Beggan

angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk

Dr Margaret Brown

Dr David Carless

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UWS

Appendix J: Workshop One Materials

Resources

Frame Your Design Challenge

What is the problem you're trying to solve?

1) Take a stab at framing it as a design question.

2) Now state the ultimate impact you're trying to have.

3) What are some possible solutions to your problem?

Think broadly. It's fine to start a project with a hunch or two, but make sure you allow for surprising outcomes.

4) Finally, write down some of the context and constraints that you're facing.

They could be geographic, technological, time-based, or have to do with the population you're trying to reach.

5) Does your original question need a tweak? Try it again.

TRANSFORMING THE TRANSITION TO RETIREMENT

RESEARCH PROJECT

Are you a woman who has recently retired or is currently transitioning to retirement? Or do you have experience of supporting women who are recently retired or going through the transition to retirement?

If so, I need to hear from you!

My name is Laura, and I am part of a research project at the University of the West of Scotland that is exploring how to improve women's retirement experiences. We are working with women for women, and we need YOUR insights to understand what's important.

I will be holding a workshop on Tuesday 4th of June 2024 at UWS and am looking for participants.

At this session, you will meet other women, volunteers, and service providers and together we will have some refreshments while we brainstorm ways to improve women's retirement and healthy ageing.

You can find out more about the project by clicking this link:

<https://forms.office.com/e/qsYUN6YpnE>

If you wish to reserve a space at this workshop or if you have further questions, contact me on:

laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Lead Supervisor: Dr Angela Beggan angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk

Appendix K: Workshop Two Visuals

Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Design Workshop

- Laura Calder laura.calder@uws.ac.uk
- Lead Supervisor: Dr Angela Beggan angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk

Agenda

- Introductions
- Women's transition to retirement
- Purpose of the study
- Objectives of the workshop
- Framing our design challenge
- Brainstorming
- Activity 1 and 2
- Break
- Activity 3, 4 and 5
- Building our team
- Next steps

Transition to Retirement (TtR)

- Research shows us that retirement for women can act as a catalyst for declining health and well-being
- As the ageing population continues to grow, the number of women that are living with multiple health problems is also drastically increasing
- The TtR presents an opportunity for primary prevention interventions to improve health outcomes and promote healthier behaviours in women, who, are acknowledged to be more receptive to health messages during life transitions.

What is the purpose of this study?

01

To gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of the transition to retirement

02

To understand what wellbeing in retirement should look like for women and how that can be achieved.

03

Women's stories will be used to co-create lifestyle interventions to support meaningful, healthy, and active ageing.

Objections of the workshop

Be inspired by the transition to retirement

Establish a design-based challenge

Brainstorming

- Defer judgement
- Encourage wild ideas
- Build on ideas by others
- Stay focused on the topic
- One conversation at a time
- Be visual
- Go for quality

IDEO.org [2015 p. 95]

Framing our design challenge

What is the problem we are trying to solve?

1. Take a stab at framing this challenge as a question.
2. Now state the key outcome you're trying to achieve.
3. Write down important aspects of the context or constraints that you need to consider.
4. What are some possible solutions to your design question?
5. Does your original design question need a tweak? Try it again.

DESIGN KIT (2023)

Activity One

What is the problem we are trying to solve?

Improving the lives of children.

1. Take a stab at framing this challenge as a question:
How might we improve the lives of children?
2. Now state the key outcome you're trying to achieve

We want very young children in low-income communities to thrive.

Activity One

What is the problem we are trying to solve?

1. Take a stab at framing this challenge as a question:

2. Now state the key outcome you're trying to achieve

Activity Two

Let me introduce you to ...

- Katrina
- Cathy
- Joyce
- Pauline

Katrina	Cathy	Joyce	Pauline
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 63 years old • Retired • Single • Lives alone • No children • Financially secure • Private pension • Long term health conditions • Reduced levels of physical activity • Lonely • Isolated • Low confidence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 66 years old • Divorced • Mother and grandmother • Low income • Works multiple jobs to make ends meet • State pension only • Sandwich carer • Multiple health problems • Physical active with dog • Sociable • Continue working in retirement out of need 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 67 years old • Retired for 2 years • Married • Husband is retired, ill health and reduced mobility • Carer to grandchildren • Previously worked part-time • No private pension • Health problems • Considering returning to work out of financial need • Low confidence • Transferable skills • Socially isolated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 55 years old • Early retirement from ill health • No children • Married • Wife is still working • Worked full time in corporate career • Financially secure • Loss of structure and routine • Few hobbies or social activities • Chronic pain and fatigue • Lonely • Interested in volunteering

Activity Three

Finding themes & creating insight statements

Write your design challenge

Our design challenge is to make the eToilet experience more intuitive, user friendly and safe.

Theme:

Women's needs

Insights:

Women want a private space in which to enter and exit the toilet.

Women greatly prefer single-sex toilets, but may still use unisex if they are clearly labeled.

Most women are forced to dispose of sanitary products by flushing them down the toilet.

Activity Three

Finding themes & creating insight statements

Write your design challenge

Theme:

Insights:

3. What are some possible solutions to your design question?

Better nutrition, parents engaging with young kids to spur brain development, better education around parenting, early childhood education centres, better access to neonatal care and vaccines.

4. Write down important aspects of the context or constraints that you need to consider

Because children aren't in control of their circumstances, we wanted to address our solution to their parents. We want a solution that could work across different regions.

5. Does your original design question need a tweak? Try it again.

How might parents in low-income communities ensure children thrive in their first five years.

Activity Four

Continuing the design challenge

3. What are some possible solutions to your design question?

4. Write down important aspects of the context or constraints that you need to consider.

5. Does your original design question need a tweak? Try it again.

Activity Five - How might we?

- Translating our insight statements into opportunities for design by reframing them as "How Might We" questions

Activity Four Continuing the design challenge

3. What are some possible solutions to your design question?

4. Write down important aspects of the context or constraints that you need to consider.

5. Does your original design question need a tweak? Try it again.

Activity Five Creating How Might We Questions

Turn your insights into 'How Might We' questions

Insight:

How might we

THANK YOU FOR PARTICIPATING

Contact details:

○ Laura Calder laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Supervisory Team:

○ Dr Angela Beggan angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk

○ Dr David Carlless

○ Dr Rebecca O'Hanlon

Building our team

Who else should be involved?

Next Steps Wednesday 27th September (1 pm – 4 pm)

IDEATION

- Share what we've learned with the team
- Make sense of the data
- Identify opportunities for design
- Build rough prototypes of our ideas

This phase will help us answer:

- How do we make sense of what I've learned?
- How do we turn our learnings into an opportunity for design
- How do we make a prototype?
- How do we know our ideas are working?

Appendix K: Frame Your Design Challenge Worksheet (IDEO, 2015)

Resources

Frame Your Design Challenge

What is the problem you're trying to solve?

- 1) Take a stab at framing it as a design question.

- 2) Now state the ultimate impact you're trying to have.

- 3) What are some possible solutions to your problem?
Think broadly. It's fine to start a project with a hunch or two, but make sure you allow for surprising outcomes.

- 4) Finally, write down some of the context and constraints that you're facing.
They could be geographic, technological, time-based, or have to do with the population you're trying to reach.

- 5) Does your original question need a tweak? Try it again.

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Appendix K: Create How Might We Questions (IDEO, 2015)

Resources

Create How Might We Questions

Turn Your Insights Into How Might We Questions

Insight: _____

How might we _____

Insight: _____

How might we _____

Insight: _____

How might we _____

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Appendix K: Excerpt from Data Analysis and Analytical Memos * please note verbatim is used in data collected

SIGNIFICANT EVENTS Workshop Two	
Key moments in the data	Comments
<p><i>Sheila:</i> It's very real and then you start to say, well who am I? What am I doing and how am I contributing? Then I went into a phase of I must do this, and I must do that, and I must learn everything! And I went off and did and learned sign language. I did a photography course. I did one thing after another. I volunteer now with an organisation called Positive Choices and producers of the best chocolates [REDACTED]; by women who have come through the criminal justice system. So, that's demanding but I really enjoy doing that. But I also take the interns in the summer. So, the student interns to do specific reports. I manage that, so I get a wee bit of academic stuff back. So, that fulfills that sort of need. That sort of fear of who do you think you are going to be is very real and how do you set about getting a new identity almost because I am Sheila, the woman with the Basset Hounds. Everybody knows me as that. Where I used to be ... there's Dr Surname walking along the corridor and now I am just Sheila with the Basset Hounds!</p>	<p>Discusses the phases she went through in retirement to feel that she was achieving an outcome and that she still felt that she was productive and able to contribute to society. She discusses briefly how she grappled with her identity, and she lost the prestige that she was used to being seen with. How did this make her feel? Did immersing herself in new activities relinquish the feelings of fulfilment and professional identity? Did it ease her transition by doing this? Did she like having a more anonymous identity as Sheila with the basset hounds? How did it make her feel having lost that status?</p>
<p><i>Douglas:</i> I had to nurse my mum ... I was losing my identity here. I am nothing. I was just the carer, and I didn't have a name. And I've been talking to other people who care for their relatives and one of the things you will feel is this ... feeling loss of who you are. You are no ... you are the carer. Listen, you need to fight back and have your own time. And I started taking my own time and going back to the gym because I still need my time to be me, not just being my mum's carer or my dad's carer.</p>	<p>Douglas articulates well his feelings about losing his identity and how he struggled with that. He opted to be proactive and dedicated time in his day to making time for himself. He opted to do this by engaging with physical activity. He recognised the need to remain active. The gym provided him with an opportunity to improve his health and fitness levels and encouraged social interaction. His caring role made him re-evaluate and recognise the importance of maintaining his health and he was proactive in his approach.</p>

<p><i>Christine:</i> My two kids are great, they are very supportive, but I just felt ... they are like 22 and 26, and I thought this was their time and I thought right ... because the last two years of me working ... There was more and more pressure getting put on us at school. We were now having to give them meds. To give injections, to give them oxygen and to give them ... I never signed up for this! I was going into work full pelt, coming home, and catching up on everything and sometimes I was doing the ironing at 1-2 o'clock in the morning! And I thought, no, something has to give or else I'm going to end up giving!</p>	<p>Christine discusses what led to her decision to leave paid employment and enter her retirement. The demands of being a carer to her husband, a home maker, a mother, and an employee were too much. She recognised that her stress levels were increasing and needed to be proactive to ensure she remained well and able to care in full-time capacity for her husband. This needed to be her decision. She had other options available to her and took her time and explored other avenues available to her. The added demands and changing role of her position at work also influenced her decision. She also looked at the impact her work had on the family dynamics and impact of caring on her son and daughters' lives. She did not want their lives to be impeded by caring commitments. She wants her children to have the freedom and flexibility that is expected with youth therefore she 'sacrificed' her career to free them from periods of extended caregiving.</p>
<p><i>Laura:</i> What if we had an ideal picture of women's TtR – what would it look like? What are the key components that you think you need? <i>Hannah:</i> Preparation, forward planning, knowing your time scale.</p>	<p>Hannah is an organised person who appears to have compartmentalised her life. Prior to her retirement, her life appeared very structured and organised. Her ideal picture of the TtR is methodical. Hannah does not appear to like change. She likes to plan key events and knows her limitations as to what will and will not make her feel uncomfortable. An example of this she refers to in her previous interview is travel. Planning provided consistency and continuity. It appears she can deal with spontaneity within the home environment but has difficulty adapting to new environments and situations.</p>
<p><i>Laura:</i> What if we had an ideal picture of women's TtR – what would it look like? What are they key components that you think you need? <i>Sheila:</i> I've put down the problem that we solve is: How do we have a healthy and fulfilling retirement? As a design question: How do women prepare for (and this is the wrong word, but I couldn't think of another one) participate in retirement? So, how do they prepare for and then live through their retirement? The ultimate impact I propose would be trying to develop a framework which supports women to retirement that could be used by individuals and organisations.</p>	<p>The key word I feel Sheila uses is support. Empowering women through giving them access to support their identified and probably not yet identified needs.</p>

<p><i>Christine:</i> I think maybe better participation from my HR team at work. I think they could have helped me with that, and they made it more stressful because I had three months of OMG am I doing the right thing?</p>	<p>Christine feels her TtR could have been better supported by her HR. In retrospect, she feels that the service they provided her with did not adequately meet her needs or expectations. If she had been better supported and empowered with the information and knowledge she needed, then she recognises that her TtR would have been a better experience, and she would have felt reassured and prepared that she was making an informed decision in relation to her needs. As such, she was left feeling anxious and apprehensive about her decision and felt she needed more guidance in what was to her, a monumental decision that affected not only her life but the lives of her family members. She feels that the employer has a duty of care, and this was not fulfilled.</p>
<p><i>Hannah:</i> I think we spoke about it online. Is that HR weren't offering a lot and I said at the last meeting we had online, the weren't offering non-teaching staff. And my circumstances were like your circumstances [directed to Christine]. It was available for all the ... planning was available for the teachers but not for the staff. So, that was a big issue for us. It was help yourself.</p>	<p>Like Christine, Hannah did not feel supported by HR. She recognises the unfairness that staff from other departments had a more supported transition. However, this service was not available to her. She felt disadvantaged as she did not have access to the same advice, information, and support that she felt should have been given to all employees. She recognises the need for a variety of information to be accessible to all women/retirees to ensure they can make an informed choice.</p>

Appendix L: Workshop Three Materials

Transforming the Transition to Retirement

Workshop

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Lead Supervisor: Dr Angela Beggan
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Agenda

- Objective of workshop
- Design thinking
- Healthy ageing workshops
- Opportunities for design
- Prototyping process
- Brainstorming rules
- Prototyping
- Next steps

Objections of the workshop

Be inspired by the transition to retirement

Enable us to turn opportunities for design into innovative concepts to prototype

Here are some of the ways in which you can prototype:

Create a model

Create a mock-up

Create a role-play
create a diagram

Create a story

Create
an advertisement

Example of Prototyping

How might someone learn about the alcohol counseling sessions offered in the centre?

What if we prototyped: new ways of disseminating information. How about printing information about the centre on the paper bags liquor stores require people to place their purchases in?

How would members of the community respond to this prototype? Would it make them more likely to attend the counselling centre?

Brainstorming

- Defer judgement
- Encourage wild ideas
- Build on ideas by others
- Stay focused on the topic
- One conversation at a time
- Be visual
- Go for quality

IDEO.org (2015)

Workshop One	Workshop Two
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussed experiences of the transition to retirement • Introduced you to Katrina, Cathy, Joyce and Pauline • Commonalities within stories • Design challenge activities • Building our team 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stories of the transition to retirement • Revisited 'framing our design challenge' • Finding themes and creating insight statements • Continuing our design challenge • Creation of 'how might we' questions

Bundle idea example

IDEA ONE - RETAIL OUTLET

IDEA TWO - SUBSCRIPTION SERVICE

IDEA THREE - ASPIRATIONAL HEALTH

Opportunities for design

What do women need and want in the transition to retirement?

Five main themes emerged:

1. Finance
2. Social network
3. Physical and cognitive health
4. Information and knowledge
5. Emotional and psychological wellbeing

**Step 1 –
Generate
Ideas**

**Step 2 –
Selecting
Promising
Ideas**

Bundle ideas

**Step 4 -
Make our
prototypes**

Thank you for your participation

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Dr David Carless

UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND
UWS

Appendix L: Workshop Three Excerpts from Data Analysis, Memos * please note verbatim is used in key moments data

SIGNIFICANT EVENTS Workshop Three		
Event	Key moments in the data	Comments
The word 'retirement'	<p>Sheila: <i>I'm not sure what it is in retirement. But I think as we are writing down about disseminating information and I'm wondering if there's something about taking away the word retirement. And its maybe next stage or it's maybe something else or ... thinking of what's your next stage and about contributions. What you can contribute that will maybe be more inclusive.</i></p> <p>Hannah: <i>What did you call it last time? You had a name for it.</i></p> <p>Laura: <i>Was it end of working life?</i></p> <p>Collette: <i>Which it isn't because that means only paid work is valuable because you know if you just say end of work. I mean, God I do... I mean this week I've done about 10 hours of voluntary work unpaid, and I take it as seriously as I do my work.</i></p> <p>Sheila: <i>I think its maybe next stage, after full-time work.</i></p>	<p>The participants discussed the word retirement and expressed that it was not behold a vision of positivity. Retirement appears to be negatively connotated to older age and debilitation, reducing faculties, and deteriorating physical and cognitive health. Rather than viewing retirement as a negative experience, the participants discussed that it should be seen in a positive light, as an opportunity to reinvent oneself and self-investment.</p> <p>Retirement should assume the end of paid employment rather than the end of the working life. Many women who are classed as retired continue to work in either paid employment, caring roles or within the voluntary sector.</p> <p>Implying retirement is the next stage of life after leaving paid employment would reduce the ageist stereotype and make retirees feel less old and more valued as members of the community.</p>
Finance – having enough money to live on	<p>Sheila: <i>I think, it almost looks like Maslow's hierarchy. I think unless finances. Then you can start to do all... particularly when you are getting development and all. But unless you get finances. And I'm not talking about being</i></p>	<p>The consensus of the participants showed that they valued having enough money to live on to meet their needs and particular set of circumstances. If they had enough money to meet their needs, then the</p>

	<p><i>sort of the very wealthy pensioners or anything unless you ... If you haven't got enough to live on, then you are not going to be able to think about other things until that is sorted.</i></p>	<p>other things in their life were more likely to fall into place and therefore make their retirement experience more positive. This would also have a positive impact on their physical and mental health. Sufficient finance would allow them to have a comfortable standard of living including accommodation that met their needs, food, and recreational activities. However, sufficient income to meet needs would be individual and subjective to that person.</p>
Financial planning for retirement	<p><i>Colette: I think we need to train people from the get-go that you need to put away money.</i></p>	<p>Colette speaks of the traditionalist way of implementing a saving plan for retirement which she was introduced to when she first started her working life. She feels preparing for your retirement should be structured into the educational curriculum at secondary schools so people know the importance of planning for your retirement at the start of their working life and can make informed choices. Retirement contributions in her opinion should commence at the same time as formal employment.</p>
Social connections	<p><i>Sheila: The people that I am in touch with were friends and we would always be friends. So, we happened to work in the same place, and we became friends through work.</i></p> <p><i>Sheila: I absolutely get what you were saying Heather about being not very social but things that have been really important are sort of being able to walk the dog through the park and get to speak to people. Speaking to people, I get to know what their dogs are called but I don't know who they are. But we meet up in the park and I go a</i></p>	<p>Different intensities of social connections in retirement. Some relationships are maintained from the working environment, some are not and retirees' distance themselves from their previous work persona. Some contacts retained would be 'friends' out with the working environment. Passive engagement with other people at social clubs, dog walking where you share a common interest with them but know little about them outside of general pleasantries.</p>

walk and we chat about things and that's an important part of my day having that social connection.

Hannah: I don't keep in touch with a lot of people. I've got a couple of teachers I'm close to and a couple of colleagues and that's it.

Hannah: I just feel that that was work and I wanted it to stop. It's time to move on with my life.

Collette: I will tell you something that was said on a retirement course, that was an old man who volunteered came in and he said and of course we all know that we need our five a day. And everybody sorts of thought how is this relevant to what we are talking about. And he said, "You see, I live completely alone with family who are scattered so I find it very important to have five human connections every day. So, he said, if I was to pass you in the street, I would say good morning and have a nice day even if they were people he had never seen before and that's one of my five a day".

Social Enterprise Possibilities	Thoughts and Ideas
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Physical activity focus* 2. Retirement Café / community group 3. Retirement Fayre 4. Pop up event (Seniors Together) 5. IT focused tuition group 6. Retirement App 7. Focused local initiative. 8. Employer lead initiative 9. NHS partnership - retirement resources 10. Private/charity/voluntary sector service link worker 11. Social prescriber – retirement focused. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is out there already for new retirees in South Lanarkshire and other areas? • What would women like, need and want? • What would women attend? • Why would they attend? • What deters women from attending? • £ - Cost associated? Self-sufficient? Grants? Individual cost? • Location? Easy access, community space, public transport route, safe • Equipment and staff • Employment opportunity/volunteer • Welcome/recruitment person. • Advertisement – how to target those in TtR. • Incentive for attending* • Inclusive community • Operational hours • Fun, engaging and inviting. • Open to all levels of fitness and abilities* • Social connectedness • Hub for information • Shared learning and mentoring • Develop skills and knowledge. • Supportive environment • Confidence building • Network with other agencies • Point of access to other services – signposting • Health and wellbeing support • Intergenerational component

Resource Questions

1. What resources shape how the stories/narrative are being told?
2. What resources do women use to shape their experiences of the TtR?
3. What might prevent alternative resources being used?
4. What resources do the group view would improve women's TtR experience?

The stories are told over lunch in an intimate group setting with three participants, myself, and my supervisor. All participants are retired having been through the TtR. Hannah identifies as a traditionalist retiree; Sheila is recognised as a corporate retiree and Collette displays more dominant traits of a corporate retiree interwoven with elements of a traditionalist.

The setting (Campus classroom) and the fact that the session is being audio recorded may shape and affect how the story is being told as it is in a formal, professional environment, where the session has specified aims and objectives. How each participant perceives each other and the researchers may influence the types of stories shared within the group and the language used to convey meaning may be adapted to reflect this.

Each participant introduces characters within their personal narrative, mostly made up of family and friends, ex-colleagues, and acquaintances. The stories presented by each participant are recounted from their experiences. Expectations and aspirations for the past, present and future are discussed.

Women draw upon their own retirement experiences and the experiences of others whom they associate with. Their retirement experiences are influenced by intrinsic and extrinsic factors, including their route of exit, personal and financial circumstances inclusive of health, preparedness for retirement, and access to information and support.

	<p>Each participant has had a positive experience of the TtR and has had sufficient knowledge and ability to seek information to enhance their retirement experience. All come from a professional corporate background and belong to the higher SMID demographic range. Each participant is married, financially astute and appears to be in good health. They are each in an advantaged position and view their retirement as a positive phase in their lives.</p> <p>Each participant recognises the need to be financially prepared for retirement and well-informed of their choices and options available to them. They value their physical, cognitive, and emotional health and wellbeing, financial security, social inclusivity, information, and opportunities for knowledge development. They proffer that addressing each of these will enhance women's experience of the TtR. Finance and access to information are deemed valuable assets to improve women's TtR experience, and support women to feel empowered.</p>
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Circulation Questions

1. Who is the story told to?
2. Who is the story intended for?
3. Who would understand the story and who wouldn't?
4. Who would challenge the story being told?
5. Who would benefit from the wider circulation of the stories being told/outcomes of research?

The story is told to the researchers and the other research participants for purposes of the research project and is intended for use within the researcher's study and subsequent publications of the study's findings. Those going through the TtR and those already in retirement would understand and recognise elements of stories being told; as would academics or those with a particular interest in women's or ageing studies.

Characters within the stories/narrative may dispute or challenge what was said within the session. Those with different experience may wish to contribute and voice their opinions. Those from different social classes and in differing circumstances to the participants are likely to have a different experience of retirement and the TtR which may not be as positive.

Women (and men) of different ages would benefit from the outcomes of the research project and any recommendations made to improve the experience of the TtR.

The participants discuss preparing for retirement at an early age and incorporating retirement advice/pension knowledge within the school curriculum. Not everyone would share this opinion and may cause friction with others who hold opposing views.

Affiliation Questions

1. What are the storytellers trying to do?
2. Do the storytellers recognise elements of other women shared experiences within their own story?
3. What shared stories connect the women's experiences of the TtR?
4. Do the storytellers affiliate themselves to a specific typology? *
5. What do the women collectively value to have a successful and fulfilling retirement?
 - a. **Should this be revisited individually?*

The storytellers are sharing their journey of the TtR and discussing how women's experiences of the TtR can become more empowering and fulfilling. Through the discussions that occur, the participants feel connected through their experiences and exhibit comparable emotions. They recognise similarities between their stories. Each participant's journey through the TtR is unique to them and they discuss the similarities and differences that occurred such as the exit route and maintaining relationships with co-workers. They reflect positive and negative experiences and how we can learn from these to enhance women's experiences in the future. From discussions, we identify what they wanted and needed in their transition and what they think would be beneficial to others. They recognise what would be desirable and helpful to women from different typologies through the commonalities women face through the shared experiences of fragmented employment histories from raising families and caregiving, gender inequalities, divorce, and belong to a low socio-economic group.

Retirement is associated with a range of emotions which were evident across the participants.

Commonalities arose in the form of:

- Positive exit from paid employment
- Support from employer
- Financial planning for retirement
- Support from husband, family, and friends
- Retaining structure and purpose
- New activities and pursuits
- Private pension accumulation
- Positive attitude to healthy ageing

- Goal/target setting
- Self-value
- Remaining active
- Social inclusion
- Physical, mental, and cognitive health
- Planning for older age
- Flexibility and freedom to pursue new things.

Differences:

- Reflection on leaving work (timing) (Sheila)
- Daily structure and routine
- Reliance on others (Hannah)
- Reduced independence (Hannah)
- Retaining the corporate persona/identity (Sheila versus Collette)
- Decision to retire.
- Introverted (Hannah)
- Confidence reduction (Hannah)
- Reduced social contact (Hannah)

What wasn't discussed were anxieties associated with the TtR and retirement by Sheila and Collette. Is this reflective of their typology? Would this be seen as a weakness or vulnerability and kept therefore hidden and only disclosed to those closest around them?

Identity Questions

1. How do the stories the women give provide a sense of who they are as a retiree and who they were as an employee?
2. What changes to their identity has each of the women experienced since leaving paid employment?
3. What do the storytellers envisage would support women to allow them to flourish in retirement?
4. How do stories of other people's experiences of the TtR's influence their retirement?
5. What shape's a women's TtR experience?
6. How do women's identities alter in the TtR?
7. What do the women value to have a successful and fulfilling retirement?

The stories Hannah, Collette and Sheila share enable me to distinguish their dominant typology. Hannah in her working life was a traditionalist with elements of the corporate typology. In retirement, Hannah identifies with the traditionalist typology. Collette belonged to the corporate typology during her working life. Elements of that remained in her retirement but have fused with characteristics of the traditional typology. Sheila remains true to her corporate typology pre- and post-retirement. Since leaving paid employment, elements of the traditionalist typology have become more dominant for all the participants. This may be related to gender and women assuming the more traditional role of domesticity and caregiver.

Hannah is an atypical traditionalist. Since leaving paid employment, she has become insular and withdrawn, preferring to spend her time with family members. She assumes the traditionalist female role, attending to cooking, cleaning and caregiving. Her husband is also retired, and they spend a lot of time together. She has become heavily reliant on him as he escorts her everywhere she goes. Hannah's level of self-confidence has decreased. This is exemplified by her reluctance to drive and travel unaccompanied and to familiar and unfamiliar places out with a 10-mile radius. She travels to Canada to stay with family on a regular basis where she has a Canadian routine, she is familiar with. She is aware that she has become less socially active and has purposefully severed contact with most of her work colleagues, distancing herself from her professional persona. Her husband guides her with any decisions which need to be made and has always viewed him as the dominant one in their relationship, referring to him as the 'breadwinner'. Hannah feels relief as a retiree as she does not have to juggle her time between work and home. She had a very structured routine while working and now enjoys the freedom and flexibility that retirement offers where she will occupy herself at home. She has few

	<p>hobbies and does not feel comfortable attending pursuits on her own. Corporate traits she had prior to retirement have relinquished to that of a traditionalist. Her husband heavily influences her retirement, and she reflects on her parents' retirement and marital values. She values having and being able to access information, financial security, her current standard of living, health and wellbeing of herself and others and her close relationships with her husband and family and especially her grandchildren. Each of these influences her retirement trajectory. She recognises the benefits of having a supportive partner and family, financial security, employer support, health and wellbeing, fitness and maintaining a level of social contact in the TtR. Having a realistic expectation of her TtR has grounded her. Developing new routines as a retiree has provided her with stability and structure.</p> <p>Collette speaks of shedding her corporate identity and persona. We can visualise this, as she shares the changes she has made to her personal appearance and clothing choices by discarding her work wardrobe in a cathartic clearance. She continues to be actively involved in her community and seeks positions of stature and social standing which is reflective of her previous role when employed. Volunteer positions have allowed her to retain an element of her corporate persona and identity which appear intrinsic to her being. Collette is in an affluent position which is reflected in the success of her retirement. She is well educated, advocates on behalf of other people and is not deterred by facing adversity on behalf of others. She enjoys making a valuable contribution to society and actively campaigns for equality in older age. She has a large social network through her community involvement. Her focus since retirement has shifted as she is now heavily engaged with positive and active ageing. She is proactive in her retirement and adopts a positive outlook, abides by her own standards, and seeks to empower others through the knowledge and skills she has accumulated over a lifetime. She enjoys having a focus and helping others, which makes her retirement</p>
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	<p>purposeful. She retains an element of structure through her community commitments but has flexibility and freedom for spontaneous pursuits. She has a strong set of opinions and can stand her ground when challenged. This has not been altered since her TtR. She continues to show confidence and productivity. Beyond her family, she values financial stability; physical, mental, and cognitive health; social inclusion; freedom of choice and flexibility and the lifestyle she has become accustomed to.</p> <p>Sheila has remained true to her corporate identity. Having exited the work force at the planned age of sixty, her retirement appears to be as busy as her working life was in paid employment. Sheila has utilised her skills, knowledge and experience accrued through a distinguished career, actively seeking volunteer work and mentorship roles. On reflection, Sheila proffers that she took retirement too early. She went with the numerical age of sixty rather than opting to retire when she felt the time was right for her. Three days after her retirement, she was actively seeking a new position. Sheila aspires to remain active in her retirement, requiring mental and social stimulation. She has retained her core values and principles and continues to structure and plan her days. Her professional persona and armour through her appearance have continued in line with her engagements as a retiree. She views retirement as an opportunity to make a positive impact and empower others. Sheila discusses the negative discourse of ageing and would like ageing to be better valued and viewed more positively in society. Sheila disassociates herself with the term retirement as it portrays a connotates negatively to her as an elderly and frail woman. Sheila values having financial security and access to information in her retirement, which she views as empowering. She values her physical, mental, and cognitive health and recognises the importance of maintaining these to suppress the effects of older age. Having a supportive network of friends and remaining socially engaged she views it as having a positive effect on her mental health. Being actively</p>
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	<p>engaged in retirement has positively influenced Sheila's retirement experience. She expresses that retirement is an opportunity for self-development and actively engaged in new pursuits, hobbies, and activities. She is financially astute and values her current lifestyle and relationship with her husband. She recognises that she is fortunate to be in the position that she is in.</p>
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Appendix M: Ethics Amendment Phase Two (Story Completion Activity)

Amendment

Position of Principal Investigator

Select... Please Staff Undergradu
ate Postgraduate

Title of Study

Principal Investigator

Title

First Name

Surname

Email

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Title

First Name

Surname

School

Email

School

Please Select... Business
and Creative Industries Computing, Engineering and
Physical Sciences Education and Social
Sciences Health and Life
Sciences

Details of the Amendment(s):

Supporting documents

Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date
Default	References Ethics Amendment	References Ethics Amendment.docx	11/07/2024
Default	Story Completion Activity	Story Completion Activity.docx	13/08/2024
Default	TtR Story Completion PIS (2)	TtR Story Completion PIS (2).docx	19/08/2024
Default	Participant Recruitment Letter UWS Phase Three	Participant Recruitment Letter UWS Phase Three .docx	20/08/2024
Default	Recruitment Flyer Online Workshop Phase 3	Recruitment Flyer Online Workshop Phase 3.docx	20/08/2024

Signature of Principal Investigator

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signed: This form was signed by RESCHHL Laura Calder
(B00348835@studentmail.uws.ac.uk) on 20/08/2024 11:26 AM

Signature of Supervisor/Director of Studies

I support the above amendment request and agree to supervise the work if approved.

Signed: This form was signed by Dr Angela Beggan
(angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk) on 22/08/2024 1:44 PM

Appendix M: Ethics Approval for Phase Three

23/09/2024

Dear RESCHHL Laura Calder,

Your application 21257: Transforming the Transition to Retirement - Phase 2, submission reference 17974, has been approved, with conditions, by the Health and Life Sciences SAIEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Title	Comment
Supporting documents	PIS- make it more explicit that if they wish to withdraw they should email you.
Supporting documents	PIS has a duplicate of the "who is organising the research" section.

This approval is valid for the duration of the study. If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Gary Boyd".

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix N: DNA Analysis Excerpt Phase One Interviews *please note verbatim is used in key moments in the data

SIGNIFICANT EVENTS Participant Name: Christine		
Event	Key moments in the data	Comments
Retirement decision	Erm my aim was always to take retirement at the age of 60, even though retirement age has kept going up and up and up. But with Christopher's course and Caroline's course, I just felt like they didn't have the same availability to help me look after their dad.	Retirement aims and timing discussed. Husband's ill health is a major factor in Christine's retirement decision. Caring responsibility for her husband due to his diagnosis of early onset dementia which was sudden and unexpected. Impact of caring commitment on children's lives and education forced her decision to retire. Decision to retire out of need to be a full-time carer.
Reduced working hours	I only worked 2 and a half days anyway; cause again when Derek was diagnosed with dementia 6 years ago - I reduced my days. And then after a few months I asked to reduce it to two days and it was declined, and erm ... So eventually with a bit of negotiation, I got down to 2 and a half days. Which was about 3 years ago. But it was still a bit of a juggle to do both.	Husband diagnosed with early onset dementia. Reduced hours at work were necessary to provide care for her husband. Christine had to negotiate to reduce her working hours. Was pressure put on Christine to maintain as many hours as possible. Increased stress from the demands placed on her time. Worry of the deterioration of her husband's medical condition. A shock and unexpected that could not be planned or accounted for.
COVID	Do you know it was one of these almost surreal moments cause our schools small. But it's got a huge staff just because of the nature of the kids and the needs, but ... [pause]. December last year was awful because there was	Timing of retirement Covid impact on working environment Strained at school Decline in working conditions

	<p>more than half the staff off with covid. So, it was really, really tight, in terms of staffing and breaks, and sometimes you didn't even get a lunch, and to go to the toilet was a bit of a pressure.</p>	
<p>Last working day prior to retirement</p>	<p>The day I finished, I basically just packed up my stuff and walked out because there was so many staff not there. There was no banners, no balloons, no ... [sad and reflective]. So that was all a bit surreal because I just got up and said, "This is me". And I said to the deputy head teacher, "I'm going to stand at the door and say cheerio to everybody". And she says [shaking her head]," No, no, please don't, please don't". She says, "We've got enough Covid in this place... just go". And I was like ... [sad] – Okay. I just didn't feel {thinks for the right word} ... final.</p>	<p>Christine's retirement was negatively impacted by COVID. She wanted a celebration. She didn't feel she received the ending to her working life she desired and felt a bit cheated and let down. She wanted a fuss ... it's a major milestone in her life and she did not get the chance to celebrate it properly due to COVID restrictions. If things were different, would she have felt more closure to her paid working life?</p>
<p>Leaving night</p>	<p>Erm, fortunately, we had organised a night out; a leaving do for the end of January, and I had that, and that was kinda like ... that felt more ... [pause], that made it feel more real. And the girls had done great. They had got me balloons and banners. There was 36 of us went out for a, had a meal, and that was lovely and really nice. And we had a big banner with pictures from me from all the nights out from the last 15 years [laughing]. So, it was good. Ahem yeah.</p>	<p>Christine got her leaving night out after covid restrictions were eased. This seemed to make her feel better about retirement.</p>
<p>Prioritising</p>	<p>And I did love my job. It was just ... I couldn't balance. Well, I kind of could balance but I think it was detrimental to Christopher and Caroline cause they were having to</p>	<p>Balance Homelife v work Impact of caring on children's lives</p>

	<p>work out their time when they could actually do Uni work. And that's not fair ... So ...</p>	<p>Enjoyment from job Did Christine explore other avenues of care for her husband? Did she feel it was her duty to give up work and be the main care provider?</p>
Physical activity	<p>The carers centre in (place) offered, not offered. They gave me an annual pass to the leisure centre for the year and I started off very [pause] structured, very good. That I went swimming twice a week in the morning about 8 o'clock. Had an hour and came up and that didn't impact on Derek 'cause he was still sleeping. But then a couple of times I went, It was like, "Oh its closed today because of the lighting". And its ... And then I took a virus just before my birthday. And then Derek got the virus and then that took us up to my birthday in October. And then came November. I thought I really need to get my act together and get Christmas sorted. So, I haven't but I'm aiming to in January. Going back into, going down to cause it's only a mile down the road - so, I can drive there in less than 5 minutes. And go to the leisure centre, 'cause I can swim two lengths in half an hour. And erm, so, that's my goal. Is for January to erm ... But I think like everything else, when you go back to these leisure things in January it's absolutely chock-a-block, 'cause everybody's got the same idea. New year, new you. New year regime. So, I'll wait and see. Erm ...</p>	<p>Carers pass for leisure facilities Early morning swimming is not impacting on care commitments Good intentions to recommence PA What is stopping her now?</p>
Decision to retire	<p>I'm different because I haven't retired just to retire. I had to retire to increase my level of caring. Erm, so I suppose that's a wee bit different, but I think you know when you're</p>	<p>Leaving paid employment to be an unpaid carer Juggling work, home, care commitments</p>

	<p>ready. Erm ... I just got to the point where you know. I just can't juggle both. Erm, and work was the obvious one.</p>	
Being a carer	<p>my biggest bug bear at the moment is the pittance that you get for carers allowance - it's £65 per week, erm, to look after somebody. And because we don't get any of the additional benefits, we didn't get the cost of living £650. We didn't get any of that. Derek got £151 as a one-off payment in September and that's it! So financially, there's nothing out there for carers that don't, that are on carers allowance. I just think that it's so bad. Erm and I think the respite that I get in a week totals 8 hours in a week. Not even that, it's probably about 6 hours because I have to take Derek to the day centre and pick him up. So, I need to leave 15 minutes before that session finishes to pick him up.</p> <p>...I think it's a disgrace how low the carers allowance is.</p>	<p>Financial impact Carers allowance No additional benefits Lack of respite Full time care commitments</p>
Male retirement	<p>I don't think that women have it any worse to be honest. I think women are better at socialising than men are. I think if a man was to give up and take early retirement, unless they've got a specific hobby or golf or something like that, I think men could be easily not go out as much.</p>	<p>Man versus women retirement and the gender differences. Maintaining social connections. Men less social than women.</p>

Appendix N: DNA Template (Frank, 2010; 2012)

Resource questions	Circulation questions	Affiliation questions	Identity questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5. What resources shape how the story is being told? 6. What resources do women use to shape their experiences of the TtR? 7. What might prevent alternative resources being used? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Who is the story told to? 6. Who is the story intended for? 7. Who would understand the story and who wouldn't? 8. Who would challenge the story being told? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6. What is the storyteller trying to do? 7. Does the storyteller affiliate themselves with other women in the TtR or distance themselves from others? 8. Who would feel affiliated with the story being told through a common understanding? 9. What parts of the story being told would other women in the TtR affiliate with? 10. Would women from different socio-economic backgrounds feel affiliated to the story being told? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8. How does the story give the woman a sense of who she is? 9. How does the story give her a sense of who she may become in her retirement? 10. How do stories of other people's experiences of the TtR's influence their retirement? 11. What does the woman value in order to have a successful and fulfilling retirement?

Resources

1. What resources shape how the story is being told?
2. What resources do women use to shape their experiences of the TtR?
3. What might prevent alternative resources being used?

This story is represented through a bibliographical account. There are several characters within the story including the storyteller's husband, children, children's partner, carers association, colleagues, head teacher, and friends. Resources which shape the story being told include care commitments, health status, health status of husband, career paths of children, finances, friendships, and physical activity. Christine draws on strength from others within a support group, and from her friends and family who she views as a valuable commodity. Her personal experiences and the experiences of others make up her narrative. Her husband and children play a vital role in shaping her story. Her care commitments and dedication to her husband and family have altered her retirement trajectory. Friends' stories of their retirement and stories from fellow carers have also influenced her experience of the TtR and decisions she has made surrounding it. She is central to her narrative which may restrict other resources she uses to shape her narrative.

Circulation

1. Who is the story told to?
2. Who is the story intended for?
3. Who would understand the story and who wouldn't?
4. Who would challenge the story being told?

The story is told to the researcher for purposes of the research project and is intended for use within the researcher's study and subsequent publications of the study's findings. The story is told via the online platform Microsoft Teams. Those going through the TtR and those already in retirement would understand and recognise elements of the story being told. Those who are in caregiving roles which have altered their retirement trajectory would strongly affiliate themselves with Christine's story. Being a mother and a wife brings a certain level of understanding to women who are in similar circumstances. Those who are not experienced care givers, without children/family and have different philosophical underpinnings may not relate to Christine's story. Christine's dialogue presents a unique and individual storied account of leaving work to be a full-time caregiver and the considerations she made in the lead up to her retirement. Characters within the story may challenge Christine's account and view her prose from an alternative perspective. Some of Christine's stories are emotional and therefore highly personal to her.

Affiliation	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is the storyteller trying to do? 2. Does the storyteller affiliate themselves with other women in the TtR or distance themselves from others? 3. Who would feel affiliated with the story being told through a common understanding? 4. What parts of the story being told would other women in the TtR affiliate with? 5. Would women from different socio-economic backgrounds feel affiliated to the story being told? 	<p>Christine provides a moving and detailed account of her TtR and life as a new retiree. Her narrative enables some understanding of retirement during the covid pandemic and taking early retirement to become a full-time care giver. Christine's story takes you on her emotional journey as she discusses her options and choices and some of the sacrifices that she has made to maintain her family unit. Other women retiring during covid would affiliate with Christine's emotional story of the lead up to and the day of her retirement which still appeared raw to the researcher. Other women who are caregivers would connect to Christine's story, and her story may resonate with mothers who put their children's needs ahead of their own. Women who have negotiated with their employer to reduce their hours in the lead up to retirement stories may bare similarities to Christine's. Those who have difficulty finding a work/life balance would also affiliate Christine's story. Christine's relationship with physical activity is similar to many other women's. Those who are reliant on carers allowance or other benefits would also recognise and connect with Christine's story and struggles. Caregiving is a universal concept that filtrates beyond the bounds of one's socio-economic status, therefore all women could potentially affiliate with Christine's story and personal account of her TtR journey.</p>

Identity	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How does the story give the woman a sense of who she is? 2. How does the story give her a sense of who she may become in her retirement? 3. How do stories of other people's experiences of the TtR's influence their retirement? 4. What does the woman value in order to have a successful and fulfilling retirement? 	<p>Christine's story identifies her as a caring, kind, considerate woman who is living with a variety of difficulties arising from her husband's ill health. Christine has assigned herself to be a full-time carer which is presently defining her. She is still in the period of adjustment where she is trying to prioritise time for herself, which is difficult due to the demands placed on her time. Christine wishes to retain a sense of self and remains socially active when possible. Other people's stories of their TtR have influenced how she feels about her own retirement and there may be some underlying resentment surrounding her work exit. Unfortunately, this was unavoidable as it coincided with the covid pandemic. Christine's work exit would likely have been different if it occurred in normal times, and she may have felt more settled on commencement of her retired life. Christine's circumstances are different in that she left her job to become a full-time carer therefore her expectations of retirement will be different to others without caring commitments or a spouse suffering from ill health. Christine values her family unit and being able to keep her family together by providing around the clock care for her husband. She is a family-focused individual and puts the needs of her family over her own. She is committed to her children's education and for their lives not to be dramatically impacted by caring commitments. Christine values the support she receives from her friends, family, and Alzheimer's network. Her independence and retaining a sense of self-worth is important to her. Financial security would make Christine's circumstances more bearable</p>

	as she would like to feel more valued and appreciated as a carer through financial means.
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Appendix N: Screenshot of NVivo (early data organisation)

Appendix O: Story Completion Task Instructions – Three Stories

Dear participant

You are invited to complete three stories – by reading the opening sentences of each story and then writing what you think will happen next. There is no right or wrong way to complete the stories and you can be as creative as you like. I am interested in all the different stories that people can write.

There is no need to think too long about what might happen next. Write down whatever first comes to mind to complete each story stem and please take at least ten minutes to write each story. It would be helpful if your stories had a minimum of ten lines.

Thank you for your participation.

***Kind regards,
Laura***

Appendix O: Story Completion Task Instructions – Revised (One Story)

Dear participant

You are invited to complete one of three stories. Please read the opening sentences of each story and then choose which story you would like to complete and write what you think will happen next. There is no right or wrong way to complete the story, and you can be as creative as you like. I am interested in all the different stories that people can write.

There is no need to think too long about what might happen next. Write down whatever first comes to mind to complete one story stem. Please take at least ten minutes to write the story. It would be helpful if your story had a minimum of ten lines. Thank you for your participation.

***Kind regards,
Laura***

Appendix O: Story Completion Story Stems

Story Completion Activity

Story Stem A – Retirement Café

Katie is approaching her retirement. She has mixed feelings about this and is not sure what she will do once she has retired. She saw an advertisement in her local newspaper for a retirement cafe. The retirement cafe is a social and information service that has been set up for women like Katie, who are retiring. Katie went along in her lunch hour and ...

Story Stem B – Retirement Buddy

June has decided that the time is right for her to retire and has given her notice at work. She has always wanted to live by the sea and is moving to the coast. She is unfamiliar with the area and doesn't know anyone. She has looked online and has found a retirement buddy scheme operating near her new home which supports women in their retirement transition. She gives them a call and ...

Story Stem C – Women's Transition to Retirement Exercise Class

Betty is retiring in three months. She is determined to reduce her weight and care for her health better. She would also like to make new friendships away from her work environment. She has seen an advert for an exercise class for women in the transition to retirement. She decides to go along to the exercise class and ...

Appendix O: Participant Information Sheet (SC Phase 3)

Transforming The Transition to Retirement

Story Completion Task

Researchers contact details:

Student Name: Laura Calder Email: laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Supervisor Name: Dr Angela Beggan Email: angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk phone: 01698283100, ext. 8475

Introduction

My name is Laura Calder, and I am a PhD student at the University of The West of Scotland. I am currently undertaking this research as part of my doctoral thesis. This research study explores women's transition to retirement. Before you decide please take some time to read this document so you can understand what the research will involve.

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of the transition to retirement. More research is needed to understand what wellbeing in retirement should look like for women and how that can be achieved. The research looks to work with older women to co-create desirable and sustainable ways of achieving wellbeing in retirement. Your stories will be used to co-create lifestyle interventions to support meaningful, healthy, and active ageing.

Why have you been invited?

You have been invited to participate in this study because you feel you are approaching the transition to retirement or are in the transition to retirement.

Do I have to take part?

No, you do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to. The decision is entirely up to you whether you participate or not. If you do agree to participate, you will be asked to complete a consent form. This form will explain your rights to withdraw from the study at any time without having to give a reason. If you do withdraw from the study, you also have the right to ask that any previous information collected about you be destroyed.

What will happen to me if I take part?

Story completion involves asking research participants to write stories about hypothetical scenarios. Three brief story stems and a set of completion instructions will be provided. Each story stem will provide a context for you to discuss a fictional character who is in her transition to retirement.

You will be asked to read the opening sentences of three short stories and write what happens next in each story. There is no right or wrong way to complete the stories and you can be as creative as you wish. You can write as much as you like for each story, but it would be helpful if each story were at least ten lines long.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks to taking part in the study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no direct benefits to taking part. However, your participation in this study will enable a deeper understanding of women's transition to retirement and what can be learned to transform women's retirement experiences.

What if something goes wrong?

There are no foreseeable risks to taking part in this study. You have the right to change your mind and withdraw at any time without giving a reason. If you do have any concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me. If you do not wish to speak with me, you can contact Dr Angela Beggan, angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk, my research supervisor.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All the information collected throughout this research will be kept strictly confidential following the Data Protection Act (2018). All information about you will be anonymised and stored in password protected cloud storage to which only the research team has access. All data will be kept securely for 5 years, after which it will be destroyed.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of this study will be used in conjunction with other gathered data as part of my doctoral thesis to form intervention prototype(s) to transform women's transition to retirement experience. The results of this study will also be used for academic publishing.

Who is organising the research?

This research project has been organised through the University of the West of Scotland for the purpose of fulfilling the criteria to meet the doctoral thesis.

Who is organising the research?

This research project has been organised through the University of the West of Scotland for the purpose of fulfilling the criteria to meet the doctoral thesis.

Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed and approved by the Health and Life Science Academic Integrity and Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland.

Thank you for taking the time to read this participant information sheet. If you decide to take part in the study, you will also be given a signed copy of the consent form for your records.

Please indicate below if you have read this participant information sheet.

I have read the participant information supplied

Consent Form

Please complete the following sections

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the story completion task at any time, without giving a reason, and that this will not affect my legal rights.

Agree

Disagree

I confirm that I have read and understand the information provided for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Agree

Disagree

I understand that any personal information collected during the study will be anonymised and remain confidential unless otherwise agreed by myself.

Agree

Disagree

I understand that parts of my data may be used verbatim in future publications or presentations and that such quotes will be anonymised.

Agree

Disagree

I agree to take part in the above-named study and am happy for the data collection to proceed.

Agree

Disagree

Name _____

Date _____

Demographic Data

Please complete the following sections

How old are you? _____

Please indicate your employment status: (tick all that apply)

Full Time

Part Time

Bridging Employment

Disabled

Caregiver

Volunteer

Other

If in the transition to retirement, please indicate when you intend to retire

Within the next 12 months

Within 1 to 2 years

Within 2 to 3 years

Within 3 to 4 years

Within 4 to 5 years

Please indicate your household status

- Married
- Partnered
- Single
- Divorced
- Separated
- Other

Where did you hear about this study?

- Work/employer
- Social Media
- Word of mouth
- Other

Appendix O: Recruitment Email Via Gatekeeper

Email Template

Colleagues

We have been approached by our colleagues from the University of the West of Scotland to ask if they could contact our staff to participate in a research project conducted by one of their students.

The student is Laura Calder, a doctoral research student at the University.

Please note the participation is voluntary and all information collected will be confidential.

For ease of explanation into the research project please review the letter of invitation below.

Research Participants Needed

I am conducting a research study on women's transition to retirement. The purpose of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of the transition to retirement and improve it. I am interested in hearing from women within 5 years of retiring to understand their thoughts and experiences of transitioning into retirement. You will be asked to complete an activity about three prototype interventions designed for women entering retirement.

Story completion involves asking research participants to write stories about hypothetical scenarios. Three brief story stems and a set of completion instructions are provided. Each story stem provides a context for you to discuss a fictional character who is in her transition to retirement.

You will be asked to read the opening sentences of three short stories and write what

happens next in each story. There is no right or wrong way to complete the stories and you can be as creative as you wish. You can write as much as you like for each story, but it would be helpful if each story were at least ten lines long.

If you are interested in participating or would like some more information, please click the link <https://forms.office.com/e/Fxc754ymTk> and reply within 2 weeks of this email.

■■■■ has kindly agreed to support this work by providing access to recruit participants which are representative of the Scottish work experience for women. However, no information about you, including your choice to participate or not, will be shared with ■■■■. All information about you is kept strictly confidential. You can read more about this by clicking the above link.

The Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland have reviewed this study.

Yours faithfully

Laura

Laura Calder

PhD Student

MPhil., MPH., BSc (hons), BSc, Grad Dip., Grad Dip.

School of Health and Life Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park

South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH

Appendix O: Evidence of Online Recruitment Via LinkedIn

The image shows a LinkedIn profile for Laura Calder, a PhD researcher at the University of the West of Scotland. The profile includes a search bar, navigation icons (Home, My Network, Jobs, Messaging, Notifications), and a list of hashtags: #womeninresearch, #glasgowcitycouncil, #edinburghcitycouncil, #lifeafterwork, #professionalwomen, #womenineducation, and #retirementplanning. The profile summary states: "Laura Calder ✓ PhD researcher at the University of the West of Scotland; exploring... United Kingdom University of the West of Scotland". Below the profile is a "Boost your career with Premium" section with a "Retry for £0" button. At the bottom, it shows "Profile viewers 13" and "Post impressions 116".

The recruitment post is titled "TRANSFORMING THE TRANSITION TO RETIREMENT RESEARCH PROJECT" and features the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) logo. It asks for participants and includes the following text:

PATRICIPANTS NEEDED

Are you a woman who is approaching retirement or have you retired within the last 12 months? Do you currently reside in Scotland?

If so, I need to hear from you!

My name is Laura, and I am part of a research project at the University of the West of Scotland that is exploring how to improve women's retirement experiences. We are working with women for women, and we need **YOUR** insights to understand what's important.

Appendix O: Recruitment Flyer

TRANSFORMING THE TRANSITION TO RETIREMENT

RESEARCH PROJECT

Are you a woman who is approaching retirement or are you currently in the transition to retirement?

If so, I need to hear from you!

My name is Laura, and I am part of a research project at the University of the West of Scotland that is exploring how to improve women's retirement experiences. We are working with women for women, and we need **YOUR** insights to understand what's important.

I am looking for participants to complete an online activity. You will be asked to complete three short stories about different prototype interventions designed for women entering retirement. This should take you about 30 minutes in total to complete.

You can find out more about the project by clicking this link:
<https://forms.office.com/e/Fxc754ymTk>

If you have further questions, please contact me on:

laura.calder@uws.ac.uk

Lead Supervisor: Dr Angela Beggan angela.beggan@uws.ac.uk

Appendix P: Story Completion Pilot Study Responses *please note, stories are verbatim

Story Stem A – Retirement Café

ID	Name	Responses
1	anonymous	<p>was feeling slightly nervous. She was not sure that she wanted to spend her time with retired people as she had not considered herself in this category yet! She was surprised at the range of people who were there and struck up conversations with a number of interesting people all at different stages of retirement and dealing with the change in lifestyle in all different ways. She found out about lots of activities happening in her area and how to get involved. She was drawn to the people who were embracing the opportunity to learn new skills and try new activities. However, she was very aware that there were also a number of people at the cafe who were struggling with retirement, some of whom she thought were lonely and some clearly struggling with isolation. Was she ready to identify as "retired" or, more likely for Katie, was she more ready to see this as the next exciting phase of her life where she had time and space to try new activities?</p>
2	anonymous	<p>found a group of people who were friendly, helpful and interested in her. They asked about her job and some questions about her thoughts on retirement. She shared her concern about leaving employment where she felt she had an identity and a purpose. One woman said to her to think of retirement as payback for all the hard work and juggling this with bringing up a family and now it is time to focus on yourself and to try things or do things you may have only dreamed of doing. She was asked if she had thought of any and she said yes, she'd always wanted to do a pottery class and she had always wanted to play football, but as a</p>

ID Name Responses

		<p>girl, was told girls don't play football. One of the group said that the local FE college puts on leisure classes in the winter months and one of these is an introductory pottery class. Another person said that there is a local over 50s charity which is starting up a new walking football class and showed her the FaceBook page to join which had the info for this class but also all the classes available. As Katie left the cafe she felt uplifted and less anxious armed with information and choices for her retirement.</p>
3	anonymous	<p>found helpful and useful information to prepare her for retirement. She received a list of contacts for relevant services and organisations that may be useful to help her when moving forward. Katie was advised to prepare financially for retirement and to take a look at how it will look for her. Advice was given where she can obtain information on benefits and grants that she may be entitled to. Conversation also turned to personal well-being. Keeping active both physically and mentally is so important in retirement. Keeping active mentally by socialising and possibly by joining a group or volunteering giving back to society from the skill set she has. Also physically fit is important and keeping a daily routine in her life.</p>

Story Stem B - Retirement Buddy *please note, stories are verbatim

3 responses

ID	Name	Responses
1	anonymous	<p>has a very pleasant and helpful conversation with one of the organisers. She was very encouraging, telling June that she would be a great asset to the group, especially as she was fit and healthy and could perhaps be in a position to buddy someone who is finding life challenging. June thanks her for the information and tells her that she will have a think and get back to her. She spends the next few days thinking about the buddy scheme and decides to have a look at volunteering opportunities in her new area. To her surprise there are lots of things she could get involved with which would let her use her skills and knowledge in many different areas and decides to explore some of these. Instead of thinking that her future needs to involve other retired people, she realises that she could be a homework mentor for a young person, or use her cooking skills with a support group for addiction, or mentor women who have been involved with the justice system or be a coastal path volunteer, or a walk leader for community groups.....June's world is expanding. She phone the retirement buddy scheme and thanks them for their information and support but she is not ready to join them yet.</p>
2	anonymous	<p>the woman on the end of the phone was really friendly and asked her a few questions about herself, when she was moving into the area and what were here interests and hobbies. Also, did she have any ideas of trying out anything new as they also had contacts with community leisure groups and classes. It was explained that the buddies are all volunteers and some of them were previously</p>

ID Name Responses

		<p>in the same situation as herself and once settled into the area had decided to become buddies themselves, paying it forward. Other questions like, did she have a preference for the gender of the buddy, would she prefer a group meet or a one-to-one, when would she want this to start. The woman then explained that there would be 'contract' between all parties and that buddy scheme would oversee the matching of buddies and was the first point of contact if there were any issues, on both sides of the match. June asked how long the matching would be and the woman said a couple of weeks, which was great as she was due to move the following week. She was happy with what had been explained to her and was looking a bit more positively to this next chapter in her life.</p>
3	anonymous	<p>answers a few basic questions about her hobbies as well as her living arrangements. From this information she can see somebody else who shares similar hobbies who she can be buddy's with. June meets up and finds her way around the new town with her buddy. Contact points and places are found where she can continue her interests locally. The new friendship encourages her to attend places on her own as well as with her buddy, for example her local library where she likes to research the local areas history. Having a buddy helps her find her way around this new town and is someone she can call upon if she needs any information.</p>

Story Stem C - Women's Transition to Retirement Exercise Class *please note, stories are verbatim

3 responses

ID	Name	Responses
1	anonymous	<p>just loves it. She realises that many women feel the same way as she does about health and fitness and is reassured that they don't all look like Jane Fonda! She finds out about other activities that she could get involved in and signs up for a beginners yoga class. She chats about diet and weight loss to women in the group and feels confident enough to share her worries about achy hips and knees and her fear of losing mobility if she doesn't change her lifestyle. She is surprised that she is able to offer encouragement to others and even suggests that they meet sometimes to have a walk in the park and a coffee afterwards. She leaves her first class being more determined than before to look after her health and is delighted that she has met some kindred spirits who share her goal. She is also hopeful that she has met potential new friends in a similar position to herself who can share her journey through retirement and maybe start some new adventures with. This is the first time that Betty has really joined in any sort of class and begins to think that retirement might not be so bad after all.</p>
2	anonymous	<p>although quite anxious at going into a new environment and meeting new people she found a very friendly group of women, no men! There seemed to be a wide range of ages from 50s to 80s and a few said hello and asked her name and introduced themselves. The class was a restorative yoga class targeting people over the age of 50 and of all levels and abilities. A couple of the women did the class on a chair, the rest on the floor. The instructor was very supportive and encouraging and talked of nutrition and supplements which were beneficial for</p>

ID Name Responses

		<p>older people and told the group about the upcoming cooking classes starting in the venue which aimed at healthy eating, best food groups for older people and a focus on how to reduce costs. But the yoga class focus was on calming the mind, encouraging the group to push away thoughts of what they think they should be doing - shopping lists, housework, etc. Betty found this so relaxing she thought she was going to nod off in the class. At the end the women who had spoken to her asked if she was going to come back next week and one said she was signing up for the cookery class. That day when Betty got home she felt 'lighter' in her mind, would enquire about the cookery class and was going to use the breathing practice that night to see if it helped her to fall asleep.</p>
3	anonymous	<p>found the activity was catered to her own age bracket with the ability to carry out the exercises at her own pace as did others in the group. Everyone being of similar age, Betty found she had things in common with others in the group. There was an opportunity to chat and even socialise when the class finished. This encouraged her and gave her peace of mind to move into retirement knowing she could make friends outwith her work environment as well as enjoying a fitness class. She felt much better within herself and continued to attend the class and social with individuals in the group.</p>

Appendix Q: DNA Analytical Template

Field	Description	Example Entry
Story ID	Unique participant identifier (e.g. A1, B3, C5)	
Typology Link (if applicable)	Typological group the story aligns with	
Story Title / Stem	Title or number of story stem used	
Date of Analysis		
Analyst / Researcher Notes	Reflexive comments or context for analysis	

Appendix R: Story Completion Responses (Main Study) *please note, stories are verbatim

Story Completion Retirement Café (A) Full Set Response

Katie is approaching her retirement. She has mixed feelings about this and is not sure what she will do once she has retired. She saw an advertisement in her local newspaper for a retirement cafe. The retirement cafe is a social and information service that has been set up for women like Katie, who are retiring. Katie went along in her lunch hour and ...

SS Stage 3 A1

she went in with trepidation but she needn't have worried. Kate came and introduced herself. She said that she likes to come and welcome any new faces to the place. Kate had been coming along to the cafe since her retirement and then ended up working there. She told me the speciality cake of the day and said I ought to try it. She said why don't you sit at that table over there with Wendy and Helen. Both these ladies had retired and were loving life. Wendy had lost her son recently and goes into the cafe for a chat each day. Helen's husband is suffering from dementia so she comes in once a week for a bit of company. They were telling me about lots of clubs and classes that are on nearby. Wendy told me she had gone to some art classes and has brought up her love of painting. She now has paintings for sale in a local gallery. She uses the money to go to Australia once a year to go and see her son. She invited me down to a gallery opening. I mentioned that I might be retiring soon and both said to me it would be the best thing I could do. They said the cafe had lots of information on various activities, financial help etc and Kate could point me in the right direction for any information I may need. I went back to work wishing that the retirement was the next day.

SS Stage 3 A2

She was pleasantly surprised as to what was available in her local community. She also met a lady named Chris who was in the same transition period as herself. They both have a keen interest in gardening and while at the retirement cafe she found out that she would be able to volunteer at her local allotment and any produce that the allotment grew helped to go towards the fresh produce that was on sale at the retirement cafe and any surplus went to the local Foodbank. Before leaving the cafe, she and Chris agreed to meet the following week at the allotment. She felt happy that she had went along to the cafe, although she was apprehensive at first.

SS Stage 3 A3

sat in the café to see who might come in, she saw other people sitting in the café and looked like they had already retired, someone was reading a newspaper, another was

using their laptop, there were people in groups and also some sitting alone. I sat alone. I thought it was such a good idea to bring retired people and wondered what I could bring to the café, do I have anything to bring I wondered, but then surely everyone has something even if its small. I decided that if I volunteered this may help my transition from full time to retirement, I am feeling concerned about what I will do with my time when I am retired.....no daily routine, coming to the café will help me, and hopefully I can help others

SS Stage 3 A4

found out more about activities that she could be involved in when she retires. Not only personal activities, but options to still use her skill set and be helpful and supportive in the community all be it on a voluntary basis. Katie still feels she has something to offer and is keen to be kept busy when she retires. The cafe also gave Katie an opportunity to meet and talk with people like herself, who were apprehensive about their approaching retirement. She arranged to have a coffee with one other person in the same situation. The trip to the retirement cafe in her lunch hour made Katie feel less apprehensive and equipped her with information and contacts to make her retirement a rewarding experiencing. As a result she returned to work that afternoon with a more positive approach to retirement and how she would use the time it would afford her in a way that made her still feel like she mattered and not invisible.

SS Stage 3 A5

had a chat with the organiser and thought it sounded interesting. She started to go along on a day when she finished early at work and enjoyed the chance to meet new people and seeing new faces. There was the opportunity to speak to people who were no longer working but she found that many of them were heavily involved in groups that seemed to take up a lot of their time. After a while she was being asked to get involved in setting up events and promotions and going to the cafe it started to feel like hard work. There were also a couple of people who seemed to spend a lot of time moaning and being quite negative about the local area. This put Kate off a bit as she just wanted to enjoy her free time and not feel overly committed to anything. Katie started to go less and less to the cafe and after a year or so realised she wasn't particularly enjoying it anymore. She felt bad about leaving but realised that it had become too much part of a routine but in a way she didn't enjoy.

SS Stage 3 A6

met a variety of women who were planning on retiring around the same time as her. They chatted about what they were all looking for to fill their time and keep both mind and body active. They came from all backgrounds, some married, some widowed,

some with grandchildren and others who were entirely alone in life. Some already had responsibilities for childcare within the family and were happy to continue with this whilst finding activities for themselves. Others were really worried about how they would manage to live comfortably on a pension given the rise in the cost of living. They agreed that they had many concerns in common and a few of them agreed to meet up in a couple of weeks for a coffee and to support each other and listen to concerns that they each had. Each of them had strengths and life experience to bring to the group and work out the best way for each of them to achieve what they hoped for in their retirement.

SS Stage 3 A7

Was not surprised to see that everyone seemed older than her. Lots of people clearly knew each other too. There seemed to be a lot of leaflets but few people to speak to directly. Despite this she decided to persevere and wandered round a few times. After a couple of circuits of the room she found someone to speak to. The girl was pleasant but a bit too young to really appreciate what she was asking. Katie really wanted to know what was on in her area that was a bit different, something new she could learn or participate in when she retired. The offering seemed a bit samey, yoga, book clubs, etc. thinking she might learn more by speaking to other attendees she sat down at a table, there were a few women there (no men!) and they were talking about grandchildren and animals, neither of which Katie had or wanted. After some pleasantries were exchanged she moved on rather quickly. Stalls offered health advice which she didn't need being aware of her own health issues. Others covered finances and legal issues. Not interested in those either. There was a wee spark of interest at the volunteering stall but no details and all very "well you can try this". Generally it was helpful in telling her what she already knew but not really moving her forward. Don't think she will come back to this one.

SS Stage 3 A8

Met the people running the cafe. She explained to the people working there that she was uncertain about her approaching retirement and wanted to still find a sense of purpose in her life. She felt she would miss the company which she enjoyed at work and the daily involvement in the lives of her coworkers. The staff at the retirement cafe chatted through the kinds of things which people got involved in. Some people had started a gardening group for the local community. Others provided a befriending service for people who were housebound. There was an art class running once a week but people were also encouraged to bring their own ideas for activities to the cafe. Katie went away feeling optimistic that there were possibilities for her to get involved in some of the social activities on offer and perhaps encourage some of her friends to join her too. She wanted to reflect on this and talk it over with her family. She could see a downside of retirement was deciding how to make good choices of spending your time,

but it would also be possible to easily overcommit and she was thoughtful about finding a good balance.

SS Stage 3 A9

met with some of the people who ran the service. She chatted to them and learned about some of the opportunities that were open to her after retirement which would give her some new experiences and allow her to use the skills and knowledge she already has to help others as she helps herself adjust to the changes retirement may bring. She decided to make some enquiries on her own and make some new plans for what she is going to do once she reaches the last days of her current employment.

SS Stage 3 A10

hoped that she would get some information that would inspire her. Moving out of the workplace had been a gradual process and Katie was not wholly convinced that retirement was the right move. Faced with the daunting task of leaving colleagues who she had worked with for over 20 years and the prospect of trying to make new friends seemed to be a challenge that she had not anticipated. Katie was looking for guidance on how to use her time constructively, but also to allow her some breathing space and making time for herself after bringing up a family and working full time since leaving school 40+ years ago. Katie had worked to a busy schedule and was now concerned that she would be a little lost without the structure and routine of her career. She was also looking for people who had been in a similar situation and could offer support, advice and experience to make the most of the time she would now have.

SS Stage 3 A11

It is a great opportunity for Katie to go along and meet women, who are already retired. She is eager to engage in conversations with them. She wants to know how do they fill their time. She has an idea already, what she would like to do or not do. She meets also colleagues, who are about to retire. She is looking forward to enjoy her freedom, as not to worry about travelling to and from work. She plans to get her garden in nice shape, reading, doing a bit of drawing, colouring, yoga and dancing. Her husband wants to take her on their first cruise. It is already planned for January. She is excited about that experience. Really, she has made up her mind to leave in December. However, she wants to hear, how other ladies are managing their time. She is optimistic about her forthcoming retirement. She has no regrets and her plans are going ahead. Most of the women, she meets are fine. Although, quite a few have grandchildren duties. She is lucky, she doesn't have that to do it. She comes out of the cafe, feeling reassured of her decision. Time is up! She is going ahead.

Story Completion Buddy Scheme (B) Full Set Response *please note, stories are verbatim

June has decided that the time is right for her to retire and has given her notice at work. She has always wanted to live by the sea and is moving to the coast. She is unfamiliar with the area and doesn't know anyone. She has looked online and has found a retirement buddy scheme operating near her new home which supports women in their retirement transition. She gives them a call and ...

SS Stage 3 B1

the friendly lady on the end of the phone said Retirement Buddy Scheme - I explained that my name was June and that I was 64 years old and that I had decided to move to the seaside and that I had heard that I could maybe buddy up with someone and was that correct? Maisie said that was correct and asked me about my interests and what did I like to do with my spare time. She said that once I moved into the town that she would pair me up with another lady with similar interests to me. She explained that as I liked walking that there also was a local ramblers group in the area that I might be interested in. There was also a group that went out to pick up litter on the beach that would love an extra pair of hands. She said there was a woman's rural group that met once a month in the village hall that I could join. She said that they held events at Christmas. She told me that the local cafe was also really excellent and that I would get a warm welcome if I went in. I actually feel confident now speaking to Maisie on the phone that I can actually do this. I could actually move to the seaside as it sounded like everything would be alright.

SS Stage 3 B2

Was invited to attend an informational session down at her local village hall. June, always thought of herself as being an outgoing person however, she was very nervous as she entered the hall. June was met by a smiling face at the door. The smiling face belonged to Sandra who asked her to fill in a questionnaire about her likes, hobbies and interests. Once completed June sat with a couple of ladies at their table with a cup of coffee and lovely piece of Victoria sponge cake. Only to find that one of the ladies had made the cake. And the other was new to the area like herself and only lived a couple of street's away from herself. As her nerves and her coffee and cake settled, she found that Sylvia (new to area like herself), was a retired nurse and had worked nightshift for the last 20 years and she was finding it hard to be awake in the day. The other lady, called Grace, was widowed so she was facing an empty house as her children had moved away from the area. Her family suggested her getting a dog but Grace felt that a dog can't go shopping with her, whereas her retirement Buddy can go shopping, and other adventures and be ladies who lunch!

SS Stage 3 B3

they say that unfortunately there is no one available to buddy up with, June feels very disheartened as having a buddy scheme would have been very helpful for her to find her way around a new area and integrate into the community. But then she pulls up her big girl pants and says "I can do this" and continues with her plans to re-locate, looking at other options for making friends - community groups, Meetup app, and sees there are lots of things. she knows it wont be easy, but she is ready for this new chapter.

SS Stage 3 B4

is given more detail about the scheme. June is looking forward to retiring very much and is happy that her dream of living by the sea is becoming a reality. Although June has lots of friends and family who will take advantage of her now living by the sea and will come and visit, June is aware that she is starting a new life in a new location and some of the challenges that may bring. June also has a keen interest in art and part of her decision to move to the coast was to give her more opportunity to paint. She was told the buddy scheme will introduce her to amenities in the area as well as clubs and activities she can take part in. Although June is keen to meet new people, she also enjoys solitude and her own company. On reflection, after speaking to someone from the buddy scheme she decided it wasn't for her but is happy to know that it is an option available to her should she change her mind.

SS Stage 3 B5

asks if she can get involved in some way. The organiser is delighted and suggests she comes along to see how the buddy scheme works and whether it is something that appeals to her. June is nervous about going along but finds the buddy scheme organiser is really friendly and doesn't put any pressure on her to get involved. June decides to join the scheme and meets someone through the buddy scheme who has similar interests and is able to introduce her to activities within the new area she has moved to. June finds this really helpful in being able to settle into her new life on the coast. After a while she realises that she considers the buddy a friend and feels happier about getting involved in other activities in the area. She even volunteers to become a buddy for a new person coming to the area as she is able to draw on her own experiences of being the new person. June is glad she pushed herself out of her comfort zone by moving to the coast and joining the buddy scheme. Her new life on the coast is exactly as she had hoped it would be.

SS Stage 3 B6

agrees to go along to their next meet and greet event. The group were very welcoming as smaller communities tend to be. They reassured her that there would be plenty to do if

she wished to immerse herself in the community activities. There were prospects for craft classes, exercise groups in the village hall walking groups amongst others. She clicked immediately with another woman called Frances who was just a little older than herself. They agreed to meet up before June moved to her new home when Frances, would show her around the village, introduce her to a few friends in the community and generally alleviate some anxieties June was experiencing regarding her house move. A couple of weeks later June met up with Frances and a few of her friends for a coffee and a chat. She felt she fitted in well and got on with the group. She was very much looking forward to a move and change of lifestyle as well as helping in the local charity shop and attending painting classes.

SS Stage 3 B7

The phone went to voicemail, but they did phone back in the afternoon. The system seemed to be very laudable and the lady answering seemed enthusiastic. The process seemed a bit more complicated and she would need to give them a lot of information about herself that she felt a bit uncomfortable with. It was explained this was to make sure the match to her buddy was good. Seemed a bit much as she was just back from Japan and had had a buddy there to help her navigate the city and generally people want to know the same things. What are the highlights and how to get around. This seemed more like developing a friendship and what if Katie didn't like the person! However, she did agree to visit the area and meet people from the group (although she felt that could have been done online). A wee step forward in the retirement planning.

SS Stage 3 B8

Explains that she is new to the area and asks them to explain the buddy system. She is not sure if this is the best way to make friends. She did wonder if she should just enjoy the coastal walks that she has been looking forward to and go walking on her own. The retirement buddy scheme however has possibilities for finding walking companions as there is an active group of walkers in the local area. Many people have moved to the area to enjoy the outdoor life from an urban lifestyle and want to make the most of it. It is so much better to do this with company explains the lady from the retirement buddy scheme and June agrees. The retirement buddy scheme starts with arranging people to meet up for a coffee where they can get matched with a local person. It is usually someone who is newly retired and can also give people an idea of useful services in the area. June agrees to meet up with a potential buddy and is hopeful that they'll be able to find her some new friends to go walking with. It's been a brave thing to move to the area when you don't know anyone but she's happy to take another step to support her new life by the sea.

Story Completion Physical Exercise Class (C) Full Set Response *please note, stories are verbatim

Betty is retiring in three months. She is determined to reduce her weight and care for her health better. She would also like to make new friendships away from her work environment. She has seen an advert for an exercise class for women in the transition to retirement. She decides to go along to the exercise class and ...

SS Stage 3 C1

never imagined it would be so friendly. 2 ladies came up to me straight away and started chatting. They asked me what my name was and had I done this type of class before. I said that I hadn't. They explained that the best place to go was in front of the instructor so that you could see what was going on. All the ladies seemed to know one another and had such banter. They said that they had retired years ago and had never been as fit. They said that they had coffee in the cafe after the class and would I like to join them. I decided that I would take my brave pills and go along with them as they seemed so nice. I thought if I don't go this week they might not ask me to go again. What a great time I had. They told me of all the other classes that they go to and said I should come along. They also were talking about their next theatre trip and meal out. I felt really welcome and actually feel that if I keep up with this bunch I will never be in and there will not be dull moment.

SS Stage 3 C2

She found the class was being held in the old school hall which brought back memories and made her chuckle as she went through the door. Betty found herself with a group of about 15 ladies, who were all shapes and sizes which put her at her ease. The lady who was taking the class, who Betty, thought she looked a bit like the Green Goddess from breakfast TV when it first started! Betty thought seeing that this was her first class she would shuffle into the back row along with 2 others. Safety in numbers she thought. The lady to her left introduced herself as Jo and, she had been retired since last summer, and this was her first class too. Betty told Jo that she wanted to get a bit fitter so that she can keep up with her grandson, Jo advised that she had 3 grandkids and knew exactly what Betty meant. "They visit for an hour and it takes me 2 days to recover ",she said. Betty felt that she may have found a kindred spirit in Jo, as the music started and the "Green Goddess" started her routine, all she could think of a cappuccino and sticky bun.

SS Stage 3 C3

initially feels a bit like a fish out of water, shes not very fit and might not be able to do the class, but is determined that she will stick at it and get fitter - shes doing this for herself, and as well as feeling fitter she will have the opportunity to make new friends

SS Stage 3 C4

had the best time! After one class she feels so much better about herself and is looking forward to coming back next week. The instructor made the class so much fun and Betty instantly connected with people like herself who had just, or were hoping to retire in the next few months. In fact, she has already agreed to go on a night out that they had arranged as a group in a couple of weeks time. Betty now feels supported in her health care plan and retirement will give her more time to focus on herself and self care, something that she feels has been lacking in her life due to work and family commitments. After years of having low self esteem she now feels that she can take some ownership of that and work to improve her wellbeing. Betty is now on a healthy eating plan, planning an exercise regime and looking forward in being in the best shape of her life as she moves towards retirement.

SS Stage 3 C5

initially finds that the class is a bit cliquey and not as welcoming as she had hoped. She wonders whether to go back but is so determined to lose some weight that she keeps going along and says she will give it a month to see how she settles in. However after a few weeks she starts to chat to others in the class and can have a laugh at the class without feeling self conscious about her weight. The class sometimes have nights out and extra events and although Betty doesn't quite feel part of the group, she decides to go along to one of the nights out. She enjoys the event far more than she anticipated and feels she is becoming part of a supportive community. She finds she enjoys seeing the people at the class and it has the added bonus of helping her lose weight and feel better about herself. She realises that one of the members lives in the next street so when the class is on during the winter they walk there and back together for safety. After a while they start to go for extra walks on non-class days round their village and become quite friendly. Although Betty has a lot of friends she is delighted to make a new one at this stage of her life.

SS Stage 3 C6

soon realises that she is very unfit! There are several options available and she decides that a personal trainer to help get her in better shape and gain knowledge of how to exercise safely whilst using the equipment appropriate to her needs is the best option. She also contacted her Medical Centre and spoke to the Practice Nurse regarding her weight. She was invited to attend for a well woman health check where her bloods, blood pressure, and weight were checked. She was surprised to find that, due to her weight, she was verging on diabetes and her blood pressure was high putting her at risk of stroke. She was referred to a dietician who guided and advised her on diet and avoidance of diabetes. She also enrolled in the weight monitoring support group available through the Medical Centre. She arranged to see her personal trainer on a

weekly basis whilst continuing to exercise at home, walking and swimming. After 2 months she felt ready to join a couple of the classes available in the local gym. She managed to lose weight and, as a result of this, avoided tipping into diabetes range. Her blood pressure also lowered resulting in no medications being required.

SS Stage 3 C7

The women were very pleasant and chatty, maybe too chatty as she really wanted to do the class rather than make friends. Nonetheless the instructor was good and she did feel a benefit from the first session. As the classes progressed she was losing weight but felt the sessions were getting a bit samey. There was also a problem with new people coming in where the instructor kept going back over stuff and she was getting impatient with that. The chatty people were not any better and after six weeks she stopped and began looking for a more challenging class in the hope people were there for the exercise!!!

SS Stage 3 C8

She's hopeful that having the time to focus on her health will improve her overall well being. After the first class she realises that it is going to mean a change in mindset as she has not been used to exercising as part of her daily life. She decides to talk to the coordinator about what she needs to do to change her lifestyle as it will involve more than leaving work. Some of the ladies in the class seem to have been exercising a lot more over the years than she has too. She isn't sure if she will be able to make the changes to diet as she has tried dieting over the years with limited success. The coordinator is happy to talk about the kind of lifestyle changes she could make to improve her health. It feels overwhelming though and she decides to postpone taking part until she's fully retired as there are too many changes to make in a short time.

SS Stage 3 C9

She hopes that as well as getting getting fitter and losing weight that she will begin to forge new friendships with other women who are all going through the same experiences as her. Betty feels more comfortable in a group setting, doing something fun where she can find women to be friends with. Let's face it, she doesn't think that she will get on with everyone at the class but the more people who attend the more chance she feels she will be able to find like minded women to create friendships with. Betty feels a mixture of emotions about retiring as most of her work colleagues are younger than her and will therefore be continuing to work. Betty is looking forward to retiring but worries about feeling lonely and this exercise class might just provide the answer to her problem. Betty suddenly feels more optimistic and is looking forward to what the future holds.

SS Stage 3 C10

Meet people in the same boat. They are trying to stay fit and not slide into a sedentary lifestyle on retirement. They now hope to have more time to take regular exercise and would like peer support to keep this up. They like to go for a coffee after the class so they are able to discuss all the issues that arise and can help her to make some decisions personal and financial. This can also help to form friendships with like minded people.

Appendix U: Story Completion Analytical Templates

SS: A11 – Katie attends Retirement Café

PARTICIPANT: Female 60s, in TtR

SC THEME: Exploring emotional and social resonance of a Retirement Café intervention

SC SUMMARY:

Katie is optimistic about retirement and attends the Retirement Café alone. She interacts with other women who share their experiences of the TtR. These conversations provide reassurance, normalise uncertainties, and validate Katie’s decision to retire. She leaves feeling more confident and supported, having affirmed that her retirement expectations are both realistic and achievable.

DNA SUMMARY

DIALOGICAL FOCUS	FINDINGS FROM PARTICIPANT RESPONSE
Narratable content	Participant shares a forward-looking, positive story of retirement. The narrative omits deeper uncertainties or setbacks, focusing instead on affirmation.
Identity positioning	Katie is depicted as proactive, resourceful, and socially capable, mirroring the participant’s own aspirations for retirement.
Moral and social action	The narrative promotes learning from others, self-determination, and proactive planning. Retirement is viewed as an opportunity rather than decline.
Cultural narrative	Draws on narratives of active ageing, feminine resilience, peer support, and self-improvement. Avoids themes of dependency or decline.

AFFECTIVE AND NARRATIVE FEATURES

NARRATIVE FEATURE	ILLUSTRATIVE ELEMENT	INTERPRATIVE CODE
Social reassurance	Katie hears stories that affirm her retirement decision.	Validation, emotional support
Self-reflexivity	Katie considers her own expectations and plans.	Forward planning, reflexive awareness
Community and belonging	She engages in peer dialogue at the café.	Social integration, shared learning
Optimism and self-direction	Katie is portrayed as eager and prepared, though cautious of unrealistic expectations.	Empowerment, balanced optimism

CRITICAL REFLECTIONS

The participant uses Katie’s story to articulate a model of ‘retirement done well,’ characterised by being active, informed, and socially connected. However, the story glosses over potential challenges such as health issues, caregiving burdens, or isolation. The phrase “most of the women she meets are fine” is ambiguous and may signal unspoken concerns, such as class, generational divides, or emotional readiness. The café serves more as an emotional and relational space than an information centre, highlighting the participant’s desire for social validation rather than formal guidance

Appendix S: Initial Mind Map: Thematic Clustering from Narrative Interviews

Appendix S: Comparative Table of Narrative Features Across Participants

This table illustrates how different women’s stories aligned with emerging typology characteristics. Narrative elements were sorted to identify patterns of internal similarity and external contrast.

PARTICIPANT	DOMINANT THEMES	NARRATIVE TONE	TPOLOGY ALIGNMENT
Joyce	Gendered caregiving, low confidence	Restitution, cautious	Traditional
Cathy	Planning, structured wellbeing	Quest, pragmatic	Conventional
Pauline	Chronic illness, financial pressure	Chaos, reactive	Circumstantial
Katrina	Career focus, existential shift	Mixed (quest/restitution)	Corporate

Appendix S: Final Typology Schema: Cross-Referencing with Frank’s Narrative Forms

A consolidated chart that visually maps each of the four retirement typologies to Frank’s narrative forms (restoration, quest, chaos) as part of interpretive alignment.

TYOLOGY	FRANK’S NARRATIVE FORM	KEY NARRATIVE FEATURES
Traditional	Restitution	Continuity, gender roles, family first
Conventional	Quest	Health focus, structured purpose, autonomy
Circumstantial	Chaos	Health/care burden, unpredictability
Corporate	Quest/Restitution	Reinvention with structure and control

Final Typology Schema: Cross-Referencing with Frank’s Narrative Form

Appendix S: Story Completion Coding Table

Story ID	Prototype Scenario	Story Summary	Narrative Position	Justification
A1	Retirement Café	The character is enthusiastic about visiting the café, quickly connects with others, and imagines returning regularly.	Embracing	The narrative conveys strong positivity, confidence, and a sense of belonging.
A2	Retirement Café	The character hesitates at the entrance, worries about fitting in, and decides to return at a later date when feeling braver.	Tentative	The story focuses on hesitation and the need for reassurance before engaging.
A3	Retirement Café	The character visits reluctantly, finds the environment unfamiliar, and decides it is not suitable for her.	Resistant	The narrative distances the character from the setting, expressing disinterest and scepticism.
A4	Retirement Café	The character enjoys her first visit but expresses doubts about fitting in over time, reflecting mixed feelings.	Ambivalent	The story combines enjoyment with reservations, indicating uncertainty about future participation.
A5	Retirement Café	The character decides to pursue another activity that better suits her needs, viewing the café positively but as irrelevant to her situation.	Redirecting	The character reframes the scenario toward an alternative activity rather than rejecting it outright.
A6	Retirement Café	The character attends confidently, enjoys socialising, and plans to bring a friend next time.	Embracing	The narrative is enthusiastic and socially engaged, showing clear acceptance of the café.
A7	Retirement Café	The character enters briefly but feels uncomfortable and leaves, telling herself she might try again later.	Tentative	The narrative conveys cautious engagement and uncertainty.

A8	Retirement Café	The character attends with a friend, enjoys some aspects but feels uncertain about returning without support.	Ambivalent	The story expresses both enjoyment and doubt, reflecting mixed positioning.
A9	Retirement Café	The character quickly becomes involved, volunteers to help with events, and finds the café energising.	Embracing	The narrative conveys strong enthusiasm, purpose, and belonging.
A10	Retirement Café	The character observes the café and decides to propose an alternative venue to her existing social group.	Redirecting	The character redirects the imagined scenario toward her existing networks rather than rejecting the café.
A11	Retirement Café	The character finds the environment noisy and alienating, leaves, and concludes it is not for her.	Resistant	The narrative conveys clear reject
B1	Buddy Scheme	The character feels reassured by having a buddy, enjoys the experience, and decides to continue attending activities together.	Embracing	The narrative conveys positive engagement and confidence, showing the buddy's supportive role.
B2	Buddy Scheme	The character signs up but worries about compatibility with the buddy, almost cancels, and ends up uncertain but willing to try.	Tentative	The story focuses on hesitation, cautious engagement, and the need for reassurance.
B3	Buddy Scheme	The character rejects the idea of needing a buddy, viewing it as unnecessary and patronising.	Resistant	The narrative critiques the intervention and distances the character from it.
B4	Buddy Scheme	The character tries the scheme, finds it slightly awkward but acceptable, and decides she might attend alone next time.	Ambivalent	The story mixes appreciation with doubt, expressing a tentative evaluation.

B5	Buddy Scheme	The character pairs with a buddy but redirects the encounter to a coffee meeting instead of the planned activity.	Redirecting	The narrative shifts the intervention toward an alternative activity.
B6	Buddy Scheme	The character attends an activity with a buddy, enjoys it, and credits the buddy with enabling her participation.	Embracing	The story shows enthusiastic engagement and the perceived value of support.
B7	Buddy Scheme	The character postpones participation multiple times due to nerves and uncertainty about meeting strangers.	Tentative	The narrative revolves around delay and cautiousness, indicating hesitant engagement.
B8	Buddy Scheme	The character feels the scheme is better suited to others and chooses to attend with a neighbour instead.	Redirecting	The narrative redirects the support toward a familiar alternative rather than rejecting it outright.
C1	Exercise Class	The character feels nervous initially but enjoys the class and decides to make it a regular part of her routine.	Embracing	The narrative conveys positive engagement, uplift, and intention to continue.
C2	Exercise Class	The character hesitates at the entrance, worries about her fitness, and decides to wait until she feels more prepared.	Tentative	The story reflects hesitation and self-reassurance before participating.
C3	Exercise Class	The character attends but finds the class too intense and socially mismatched, deciding not to return.	Resistant	The narrative distances the character and critiques the environment.
C4	Exercise Class	The character enjoys the class more than expected but remains unsure about regular commitment.	Ambivalent	The story expresses mixed feelings, weighing positive and uncertain elements.

C5	Exercise Class	The character observes the class and decides to go swimming instead, preferring another activity.	Redirecting	The narrative actively redirects engagement toward a preferred alternative.
C6	Exercise Class	The character attends with a friend, enjoys it, and signs up for more sessions.	Embracing	The narrative conveys enthusiastic and socially supported engagement.
C7	Exercise Class	The character repeatedly delays attendance due to nerves and self-doubt about fitness.	Tentative	The story revolves around postponement and cautiousness.
C8	Exercise Class	The character tries the class but finds the instructor patronising and the group cliquy, leaving frustrated.	Resistant	The narrative critiques the environment and rejects further involvement.
C9	Exercise Class	The character enjoys the activity but decides to find a different class better aligned with her interests.	Redirecting	The narrative redirects engagement toward a more suitable alternative.
C10	Exercise Class	The character begins uncertain but finds the environment welcoming and commits to giving it a proper try.	Embracing	The narrative conveys positive engagement and willingness to adapt.

Appendix T: Statement of Accomplishment IDEO Certification

Statement of Accomplishment

INTRODUCTION TO HUMAN-CENTERED DESIGN

As of OCTOBER 6, 2023,

Laura Calder

has successfully completed an online course, **Introduction to Human-Centered Design**, provided by Acumen Academy and IDEO.org.

This hands-on course introduced human-centered research methods, concept generation, and rapid prototyping of a solution to a poverty-related design challenge. Congratulations! We're glad to have you in the Acumen Academy community.

JO-ANN TAN

Director,
Acumen Academy

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